

SUPPLY CHAIN RESILIENCE IN THE SCOTTISH BEEF SUPPLY CHAIN (SBSC)

USMAN MASOOD

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

Declaration

I DECLARE THAT:

- Except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this thesis is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.
- I have followed data protection and copyright guidance and have obtained written permission to include any copyright or personal material in publication, and/or have agreed with the library the parts of the thesis that need to be redacted before publication.
- As a student of the University of the West of Scotland I will maintain a high standard of personal conduct, co-operate with all members of staff and agree to abide by the University's Regulations.
- My thesis will be made available publicly on the British Library's thesis platform EThOS and may be included in the institutional repository.
- I have followed the University style and standard of presentation of the thesis.
- I confirm that the attached version of my thesis has been submitted to the University's plagiarism software and that I consent to the Doctoral College re-submitting my thesis to the University's plagiarism software.
- I am aware that my similarity report from the University's plagiarism software may be shared with my examining team.

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I am profoundly thankful to Allah Almighty for granting me the strength, patience, and resilience to complete this journey.

I wish to express my deepest gratitude to my Director of Studies, Dr Salman Ahmad, for his invaluable guidance and encouragement; I am equally grateful to my entire supervisory team, especially Daniel Perry, for their ongoing support, which has significantly shaped the outcome of this dissertation.

A special thanks to my former supervisor, Dr. Tom Keegan, whose steadfast support and belief in my potential have been a constant source of motivation. His encouragement and mentorship during the early stages of this journey have left a lasting impact on my academic and personal growth.

I would also like to extend my heartfelt thanks to my wife, whose unwavering support, patience, and understanding have been the foundation of my success. Her belief in me gave me the strength to persevere through the challenges and sacrifices required to reach this goal.

Finally, I express my appreciation to all the participants, colleagues, friends, and family who contributed to this work in various ways. Your encouragement, insights, and support have made this achievement possible. Thank you all

List of Acronyms

AFSC Agri-Food Supply Chain

CCC Climate Change Committee

DCT Dynamic Capabilities Theory

IAAS Institute of Auctioneers and Appraisers Scotland

LFASS Less Favoured Areas Support Scheme

NFUS National Farmers Union Scotland

QMS Quality Meat Scotland

RBV Resource-Based View

SAMW The Scottish Association of Meat Wholesalers

SBSC Scottish Beef Supply Chain

SCDO Supply chain disruption orientation

SCRAM Supply Chain Resilience Assessment and Management

SCRES Supply Chain Resilience

SEPA Scottish Environment Protection Agency

SRUC Scotland's Rural College

SSBSS Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme

Abstract

The Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC) is a cornerstone of the national rural economy, contributing over £1 billion and sustaining a globally recognised brand. However, this critical sector faces an existential threat from persistent challenges, evidenced by a 14.7% decline in national cattle production over the last decade, coupled with chronic labour shortages, succession constraints, and critically low profitability. Safeguarding the viability of the SBSC is therefore a matter of urgent economic and policy importance. While prior agri-food research has addressed resilience in response to acute disruptions (e.g. disease outbreaks and extreme weather events), a significant theoretical gap remains in understanding how resilience functions as a system-level dynamic capability that responds to enduring systemic challenges within decentralised, multi-tier supply chains.

A qualitative, holistic multiple-case study design was adopted, with the supply chain comprising farmers, processors, auction marts, and retailers treated as the unit of analysis. Twenty-five semi-structured interviews were conducted with key supply chain actors, policymakers, and industry bodies. The data were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis.

The findings indicate that SBSC resilience is underpinned by several capability areas, including traceability, inherent resilience, supplier relationship management, supplier selection, supply base diversity, transparency, logistical capabilities, redundancy, and government support. However, the analysis demonstrates that these capabilities are constrained by enduring challenges such as declining herd sizes, labour shortages, succession constraints, low profitability, regulatory uncertainty, limited technological adoption, market volatility, and trust-related issues. Collectively, these challenges weaken the SBSC's ability to identify emerging risks, implement timely responses, and pursue longer-term adaptive change.

The study makes three main contributions. First, it introduces an updated definition of agri-food supply chain resilience that incorporates both acute disruptions and long-term systemic pressures. Second, it extends the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV) by demonstrating that the sequential stages of sensing, seizing, and transforming have limited applicability at the supply chain level; consequently, a collective sensing, seizing, and transforming approach is proposed. Third, it provides empirical evidence of how resilience capabilities manifest within a decentralised, multi-actor agri-food system an area that remains under-represented in the current literature.

Overall, the research offers theoretically grounded insights into supply chain-level resilience and identifies key areas for policy and industry intervention aimed at strengthening the long-term functionality of the SBSC.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	1
1.1	Research Context.....	2
1.2	Research Aim and Objectives.....	4
1.3	Research Questions.....	5
1.4	Research Methodology.....	5
1.5	Research Significance.....	6
1.6	Thesis Outline.....	7
2	Industry Context.....	9
2.1	Scottish Red Meat Industry Profile.....	9
2.2	Scottish Beef Supply Chain.....	10
2.2.1	Livestock Farmers.....	10
2.2.2	Structure of the Livestock Farms.....	11
2.2.3	Classification of Cattle Farms in Scotland.....	12
2.2.4	Classification Based on Hectares.....	12
2.2.5	Cattle output in 2023.....	15
2.3	Processing Sector.....	17
2.3.1	Processing Sector Output.....	17
2.3.2	Major Processing Plants of Scotland.....	17
2.4	Auction Marts.....	18
2.5	Retailers.....	19
3	Literature Review.....	21
3.1	Conceptual foundations of resilience.....	21
3.2	Definitions of Supply Chain Resilience.....	21
3.3	Applicability of Supply Chain Resilience Definitions.....	25
3.4	Supply Chain Resilience Drivers.....	26
3.5	Operational and Structural Drivers.....	26
3.6	Relational and Organisational Drivers.....	30
3.7	Technological, Strategic and Learning Drivers.....	33

3.8	Agri-Food System Resilience	36
3.8.1	Agricultural Food Supply Chain Resilience Drivers	42
3.8.1.1	Collaboration	42
3.8.1.2	Flexibility	43
3.8.1.3	Agility.....	44
3.8.1.4	Redundancy	45
3.8.1.5	Government Support	45
3.8.1.6	Traceability.....	45
3.9	Limitations of Supply Chain Resilience Drivers	46
3.10	Theoretical Frameworks used in Supply Chain Resilience	48
3.10.1	Resource Based View.....	48
3.10.2	Dynamic Capabilities View	49
3.10.3	Contingency Theory.....	50
3.10.4	Complex Adaptive System.....	51
3.11	Gap in Literature.....	54
4	Methodology.....	58
4.1	Research Philosophy.....	58
4.2	Research Design	59
4.2.1	Case Study Protocol.....	60
4.2.1.1.1	Case Study Methodological Rigor.....	61
4.3	Selection and Recruitment of Participants.....	63
4.4	Participant’s Profile	63
4.5	Data Collection	64
4.6	Data Analysis	66
4.7	Ethical Considerations	66
5	Analysis and Discussion	67
5.1	Analysis and Discussion	67
5.2	(CASES).....	68
5.2.1	Academic Expert Research Institute Interview Participant No 1 (IP1).....	68

5.2.1.1	Theme1 Factors Contributing to the Resilience of Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC)	69
5.2.1.1.1	Provenance.....	69
5.2.1.1.2	Production Systems	70
5.2.1.1.3	Resilient to Market Volatility.....	70
5.2.1.2	Theme 2 Challenges faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (Current and Future) ..	71
5.2.1.2.1	Lack of Infrastructure	71
5.2.1.2.2	Lack of Hygiene and Cleanliness of Livestock.....	71
5.2.1.2.3	Lack of Product Quality.....	72
5.2.1.2.3.1	EUROP Grid	72
5.2.1.2.3.2	Misalignment in Production	73
5.2.1.2.3.3	Shorter Shelf Life	73
5.2.1.2.4	Procurement Issues	74
5.2.1.2.5	Limited Use of Modern Farming Practices	74
5.2.1.2.6	Lack of Export Ambition	75
5.2.1.2.7	Market Power Imbalance	75
5.2.1.2.8	Knowledge Transfer.....	76
5.2.1.2.9	Relationship Between Farmers and Retailers	76
5.2.1.3	Theme 3 Future Resilience.....	76
5.2.1.3.1	Improve Farmer Knowledge in Livestock Farming	76
5.2.1.3.2	Carcass Specification as KPI	77
5.2.1.3.3	Follow Global Trends	77
5.2.2	Academic Expert Research Institute Interview Participant No 2 (IP2).....	78
5.2.2.1	Theme 1 Challenges Faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC).....	79
5.2.2.1.1	Critical Mass.....	79
5.2.2.1.1.1	Lack of Financial Returns.....	80
5.2.2.1.1.2	Suckler Herd efficiency	80
5.2.2.1.1.3	Lack of KPIs	80
5.2.2.2	Theme 2 Government Support	81

5.2.2.2.1	Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme	81
5.2.2.2.2	Role of Subsidies	82
5.2.2.2.3	MyHerd Stats	82
5.2.2.3	Theme 3 Recent Disruptions	82
5.2.2.3.1	COVID-19 and the Scottish Beef Supply Chain	82
5.2.2.4	Theme 4 Lack of Communication and Collaboration	83
5.2.2.5	Theme 5 Factors Contributing to the Supply Chain Resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC)	83
5.2.2.5.1	Diversified Income Stream	83
5.2.3	Academia’s Perspective on the Challenges of the SBSC	84
5.2.4	Academia ‘s General Concerns Regarding the SBSC	85
5.2.5	Industry Expert / SAC Consultant Interview Participant (IP) 3	86
5.2.5.1	Theme Challenges Faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain	87
5.2.5.1.1	Lack of Financial Returns.....	87
5.2.5.1.2	Poor Infrastructure	88
5.2.5.1.3	Slow Adoption of Technology	89
5.2.5.1.4	Lack of Supply Chain integration.....	89
5.2.5.1.5	Critical Mass	89
5.2.5.1.6	Lack of Succession and Labour.....	90
5.2.5.1.7	Lack of Product Quality.....	90
5.2.5.2	Theme Factor Contributing to the Supply Chain Resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC)	91
5.2.5.2.1	Traceability	91
5.2.5.2.2	Supplier Relationships	92
5.2.5.2.3	Integrated Business Model	93
5.2.5.3	Theme 3 General Issues Related to the Scottish Beef Supply Chain.....	93
5.2.5.3.1	Lack of Trust.....	93
5.2.5.3.2	Profitability Misrepresentation	94
5.2.5.3.3	Cross Border Trade	94

5.2.5.3.4	Slow Government Response.....	94
5.2.5.3.5	Food Security.....	95
5.2.5.3.6	Uncertainty in Recovery Trends	96
5.2.5.3.7	Group Think.....	96
5.2.6	Interview 4:Cattle Society Official Interview Participant IP4.....	97
5.2.6.1	Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of Scottish Beef Supply Chain(SBSC).....	98
5.2.6.1.1	Artificial Insemination.....	99
5.2.6.1.2	Brand Strength	100
5.2.6.1.3	Product Quality	101
5.2.6.2	Theme 2 Challenges Faced by Scottish Beef Supply Chain	102
5.2.6.2.1	Structural Dependency and Processing Consolidation	102
5.2.6.2.2	Critical Mass	102
5.2.6.2.3	Land Deprivation	103
5.2.6.2.4	Lack of Preparedness against Disease	104
5.2.6.2.5	Lack of Export Ambition	104
5.2.6.2.6	Lack of Succession	105
5.2.6.2.7	Uncertain Government Policies	105
5.2.6.2.8	Potential Import of Australian Black Angus	105
5.2.6.3	Theme 3 Industry Development	106
5.2.6.3.1	Central Data Base	106
5.2.6.3.2	Genetic Diversity Research for Breed Resilience	106
5.2.6.3.3	Enhancing ScotEID data utilization for Readiness.....	107
5.2.7	Interview 5 Livestock Farmer Interview Participant (IP 5).....	107
5.2.7.1	Theme 1 Challenges in the Scottish Beef Supply Chain.....	109
5.2.7.1.1	Economic Challenges	109
5.2.7.1.1.1	Lack of Financial Returns.....	110
5.2.7.1.1.2	Decreasing Bull Sales	110
5.2.7.1.1.3	Competition for work force.	110
5.2.7.1.2	Structural and Operational Barriers	111

5.2.7.1.2.1	Retailer Dominance	111
5.2.7.1.2.2	Processor Dominance	112
5.2.7.1.2.3	Lack of Succession and Aging Population	112
5.2.7.1.2.4	No Rebuilding Plan / Post-Crisis Recovery Planning	113
5.2.7.1.2.5	Lack of Veterinary Services	113
5.2.7.1.2.6	Lack of Trust.....	113
5.2.7.1.2.7	Critical Mass	114
5.2.7.1.3	Technological Challenges	114
5.2.7.1.3.1	Slow technology adoption	114
5.2.7.1.3.2	Block Chain	115
5.2.7.1.3.3	Data Gathering.....	115
5.2.7.1.4	Environmental Challenges & Regulatory Pressures.....	115
	Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions	115
5.2.7.1.4.1	Slow Government Response.....	116
5.2.7.1.4.2	Auctions Marts.....	117
5.2.7.1.4.3	Supply chain fairness.....	117
5.2.7.2	Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC)	
	119	
5.2.7.2.1	Trust and Relationships	119
5.2.7.2.2	Response Against Disease Outbreak	119
5.2.7.2.3	Risk Mitigation and Redundancy	120
5.2.7.2.4	Psychological Resilience	120
5.2.7.2.5	Government Support.....	121
5.2.8	Interview 6 Livestock Farmer Interview Participant (IP) 6.....	122
5.2.8.1	Theme 1 Challenges faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain	123
5.2.8.1.1	Economic Challenges	123
5.2.8.1.1.1	Lack of Financial Returns.....	124
5.2.8.1.1.2	Farmers as Price Takers	124
5.2.8.1.2	Structural Imbalance (Retailer & Processor Dominance)	124

5.2.8.1.3	Environmental Challenges.....	125
5.2.8.1.3.1	Green House Gas (GHG) Emissions	125
5.2.8.1.4	Operational Challenges.....	126
5.2.8.1.4.1	Critical Mass.....	126
5.2.8.1.4.2	Land Deprivation.....	127
5.2.8.1.4.3	Lack of Labour and Succession.....	127
5.2.8.2	Theme 2 Traceability and Labelling Complexity.....	127
5.2.8.3	Theme 3 Factors Contributing to the Supply chain resilience of the Scottish Beef supply chain	128
5.2.8.3.1	Government Support.....	128
5.2.8.4	Theme Four	128
5.2.9	Livestock Farmer Interview Participant (IP) 7	130
5.2.9.1	Theme 1.....	132
5.2.9.1.1	Technology Adoption and Digital Transformation	132
5.2.9.1.1.1	Digital Tools for Livestock Movement.....	132
5.2.9.1.1.2	Performance Data and Breeding Efficiency Monitoring	132
5.2.9.1.1.3	Slow Adoption to Technology	132
5.2.9.1.1.4	Integration of Agri Tech data and Decision support software	133
5.2.9.2	Theme 2.....	133
5.2.9.2.1	Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC	133
5.2.9.2.1.1	Inherent Resilience	133
5.2.9.2.1.2	Brand Strength.....	134
5.2.9.2.1.3	Traceability	134
5.2.9.2.1.4	Stakeholder Collaboration	135
5.2.9.2.1.5	Artificial Insemination.....	135
5.2.9.3	Theme 3 Challenges Faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain	136
5.2.9.3.1	Regulatory Uncertainty.....	136
5.2.9.3.2	Competition from Dairy Cattle.....	137
5.2.9.3.3	Lack of Labor	137

5.2.9.3.4	Global Competition	137
5.2.9.4	Overview of IP7 interview	137
5.2.10	Livestock Farmer Interview Participant IP 8	138
5.2.10.1	Theme Factors Contributing to Resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain	139
5.2.10.1.1	Trust.....	139
5.2.10.1.2	Supplier Selection.....	140
5.2.10.1.3	Redundancy	141
5.2.10.1.4	Information Sharing.....	142
5.2.10.2	Theme 2 Challenges Faced by Scottish Beef Supply Chain	142
5.2.10.2.1	Lack of Succession and Aging population.....	142
5.2.10.2.2	Lack of Financial Returns.....	143
5.2.10.2.3	Lack of Collaboration	143
5.2.10.2.4	Critical Mass.....	143
5.2.10.2.5	Market Uncertainty and Long-term Planning.....	144
5.2.10.3	Theme 3 Impact of Subsidy Scheme on Efficiency and Profitability	144
5.2.10.3.1	Lack of Incentive for Efficiency	145
5.2.10.3.2	Ageing Farmer and Succession Issues.....	145
5.2.10.3.3	Upcoming Changes in Support Scheme Criteria	145
5.2.10.3.4	Resistance to Reform and Efficiency Requirements	145
5.2.10.4	Theme 4 Knowledge Exchange and Efficiency Improvement in Scottish Beef Farming 146	
5.2.10.4.1	Peer to Peer Learning as a tool for efficiency.....	146
5.2.10.4.2	Barriers to Knowledge Transfer.....	146
5.2.10.4.3	Potential for Productivity Gains through Knowledge Transfer.....	146
5.2.10.4.4	Need for Industry-CPD Standards	147
5.2.11	Livestock Farmer Interview Participant No.9	147
5.2.11.1	Theme 1 Challenges faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain	148
5.2.11.1.1	Operational Challenges.....	148
5.2.11.1.1.1	Critical Mass	149

5.2.11.1.1.2	. Lack of Veterinarian services.....	149
5.2.11.1.1.3	Lack of Succession and Aging Population.....	149
5.2.11.1.1.4	Systemic Impact of lack of production.....	149
5.2.11.1.2	Economic Challenges	149
5.2.11.1.2.1	Lack of Financial Returns.....	150
5.2.11.1.2.2	Uncompensated Sustainability Costs.....	150
5.2.11.1.3	Environmental and Regulatory Challenges	150
5.2.11.1.4	GHG Emissions	150
5.2.11.1.4.1	Regulatory Uncertainty.....	150
5.2.11.1.5	Technological Challenges	151
5.2.11.1.5.1	Slow to Adopt new Technology.....	151
5.2.11.1.6	Structural Challenges	151
5.2.11.1.7	151
5.2.11.2	Theme 2 Factors contributing to the Resilience of the Scottish beef supply chain.....	151
5.2.11.2.1	Communication and Collaboration.....	151
5.2.11.2.2	Government Support.....	152
5.2.11.2.3	Resilient thinking.....	152
5.2.12	Livestock Farmer Interview Participant (IP) 10	153
5.2.12.1	Theme 1 Challenges Faced by SBSC.....	154
5.2.12.1.1	Economic Challenges	154
5.2.12.1.1.1	Lack of Financial Returns.....	155
5.2.12.1.1.2	Supply Demand Imbalance.....	155
5.2.12.1.1.3	Domestic and International Competition.....	155
5.2.12.1.2	Operational Challenges.....	155
5.2.12.2	Theme 2 General Concerns regarding the SBSC	156
5.2.12.2.1	Risk Exposure.....	156
5.2.12.2.2	Disruption to Market Exposure	156
5.2.12.2.3	Disruption Disease Based.....	156
5.2.12.2.4	157

5.2.12.3	Theme 3 Factors Contributing to the resilience of SBSC	157
5.2.12.3.1	Supply Base Diversity	157
5.2.12.3.2	Supplier Selection.....	157
5.2.12.3.3	Operational Efficiency	157
5.2.12.3.4	Traceability	158
5.2.12.3.5	Operational Flexibility.....	158
5.2.12.3.6	Operational Diversity.....	159
5.2.13	Livestock Farmer Interview Participant (IP)11.....	160
5.2.13.1	Theme Factor Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC	161
5.2.13.1.1	Contingency Planning.....	162
5.2.13.2	Theme Challenges faced by SBSC.....	162
5.2.14	Overview of Livestock Farmer’s Interviews	163
5.2.15	Processing Sector Interviews	166
5.2.16	Trade Body Representative (Executive) for Meat Processors and Wholesalers Interview Participant (IP)12.....	166
5.2.16.1	Theme Challenges Faced by the SBSC.....	167
5.2.16.1.1	Economic Challenges	167
5.2.16.1.2	Structural Challenges.....	168
5.2.16.1.2.1	Bargaining Power of Big Finishers.....	168
5.2.16.1.2.2	Retailer Dependence.....	169
5.2.16.1.3	Operational Challenges.....	169
5.2.16.1.4	Regulatory Challenges.....	170
5.2.16.1.5	Other Challenges	170
5.2.16.2	Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC.....	171
5.2.16.2.1	Supply Chain Leadership.....	171
5.2.16.2.2	Supply Chain Intelligence.....	172
5.2.16.2.3	Government Support.....	172
5.2.17	Processor Interview Participant (IP) 13	172
5.2.17.1.1	Theme Factors contribution to the Resilience of SBSC	173

5.2.17.1.2	Flexibility.....	173
5.2.17.1.3	Supply Base Diversity	175
5.2.17.1.4	Supplier Relationships	175
5.2.17.1.5	Supply Chain Understanding	176
5.2.17.2	Theme Challenges Faced by the SBSC	176
5.2.18	Processor Interview Participant (IP) 14	179
5.2.18.1	Theme Factors Contributing to Resilience of SBSC	180
5.2.18.1.1	Risk Management Culture	180
5.2.18.1.2	Traceability	182
5.2.18.1.3	Adaptability	182
5.2.18.2	Theme Challenges faced by the SBSC	183
5.2.18.2.1	Market Consolidation and Processor Dominance.....	183
5.2.18.2.2	Disease Outbreak Recovery.....	183
5.2.18.2.3	Poor Infrastructure	184
5.2.19	Overview of the Processing Sector Interviews	185
5.2.20	Auction Marts	187
5.2.21	Auction Mart Trade Body Executive Interview Participant (IP) 15	187
5.2.21.1	Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC	188
5.2.21.1.1	Transparency.....	188
5.2.21.1.2	Traceability	189
5.2.21.1.2.1	Traceability Process at Auction Marts	190
5.2.21.1.3	Inherent Resilience	191
5.2.21.2	Theme Challenges faced by the SBSC	191
5.2.21.2.1	Transportation and Logistical Challenges	191
5.2.22	Auction Mart Interview Participant IP 16.....	192
5.2.22.1	Theme Factor Contributing to the resilience of SBSC.....	193
5.2.22.1.1	Transparency.....	194
5.2.22.1.2	Traceability	195
5.2.22.2	Theme Challenges faced by SBSC.....	196

5.2.22.3	Perspectives of Auction Marts on the Resilience and Challenges of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain	196
5.2.23	Retail	198
5.2.24	Retail Interview Participant (IP)17	198
5.2.24.1	Theme factors Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC.....	199
5.2.24.1.1	Supplier Relationships	199
5.2.24.1.2	Supplier Selection.....	200
5.2.24.1.3	Traceability	201
5.2.24.1.4	Risk Management	201
5.2.24.1.5	Logistical Capabilities	202
5.2.24.1.6	Provenance.....	202
5.2.24.1.7	Contingency Planning.....	203
5.2.24.1.8	Flexibility in Sourcing	203
5.2.24.2	Theme Challenges Faced by SBSC.....	204
5.2.25	Retail Industry Specialist Interview Participant IP 18	204
5.2.25.1.1	Inherent Resilience	206
5.2.25.1.2	Supplier Relationship.....	206
5.2.25.1.3	Collaboration and Supply Chain Integration	206
5.2.25.2	Theme Challenges Faced by Scottish Beef Supply Chain	207
5.2.25.2.1	Retailer Dominance	207
5.2.25.2.2	Declining Consumption of Red Meat	208
5.2.25.2.3	Low Profitability and Investment	208
5.2.25.2.4	Environmental Concerns and Emissions	208
5.2.25.3	Perspective of Retailers on the Resilience and Challenges of the SBSC.....	210
5.2.26	Policy Manager Interviews Livestock and Animal Health	210
5.2.27	Policy Manager (Livestock Farming) Organisation Interview Participant 19	210
5.2.27.1	Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC.....	212
5.2.27.1.1	Transparency.....	212
5.2.27.1.2	Market Position.....	212

5.2.27.1.3	Stakeholder Collaboration	213
5.2.27.1.4	Government Support.....	213
5.2.27.1.5	Theme Challenges Faced by SBSC	214
5.2.27.1.5.1	Lack of Income Diversification	214
5.2.27.1.6	Limited Infrastructure	214
5.2.27.1.7	Regulatory Uncertainty.....	215
5.2.28	Policy Manager (Animal Health & Welfare) Farming Organisation Interview Participant 20 216	
5.2.28.1	Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC	217
5.2.28.1.1	Traceability	217
5.2.28.1.2	Risk Management	217
5.2.28.2	Theme Challenges Faced by the SBSC	218
5.2.28.2.1	Poor Infrastructure	218
5.2.28.2.2	Trust	218
5.2.29	Overview of the Perspective of Policy Managers (Farming Organisation)	219
5.2.30	Industry Practitioner Traceability Organisation Interview Participant (IP21)	220
5.2.30.1	Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC	221
5.2.30.1.1	Traceability	221
5.2.30.1.2	Big Data Analytics	222
5.2.30.1.3	Transparency.....	222
5.2.30.2	Theme Challenges faced by the SBSC.....	223
5.2.30.2.1	Disease outbreak	223
5.2.31	Market Intelligence Manager (Non-Departmental Public Body) Interview Participant (IP) 22 223	
5.2.31.1	Theme Factor Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC.....	224
5.2.31.1.1	Inherent Resilience	224
5.2.31.1.2	Government Support.....	225
5.2.31.1.3	Traceability	225
5.2.31.2	Theme Challenges faced by SBSC.....	225

5.2.32	Head of Industry Development (Non-Departmental Public Body) Interview Participant (IP)	
23	226	
5.2.32.1.1	Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC	227
5.2.32.1.2	Traceability	228
5.2.32.1.3	Supplier Relationship.....	228
5.2.32.2	Inherent Resilience	228
5.2.32.3	Theme Challenges faced by SBSC.....	229
5.2.32.3.1	Lack of Risk Management.....	229
5.2.32.4	Lack of Industry Engagement	229
5.2.33	Public Affairs and Industry Strategy Manager (Non-Departmental Public Organisation)	
Interview Participant (IP)24	231
5.2.33.1	Theme Factor Contribution to the Resilience of the SBSC.....	232
5.2.33.1.1	Traceability	233
5.2.33.1.2	Response Against Disease Outbreak	233
5.2.33.1.3	Government Support.....	233
5.2.33.1.4	Inherent Resilience	234
5.2.33.2	Theme Challenges Faced by SBSC.....	234
5.2.33.3	Overview of the IP24's Interview	234
5.2.34	Member of Scottish Parliament (MSP) Interview Participant IP (25)	235
5.2.34.1	Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC	236
5.2.34.1.1	Adaptability	237
5.2.34.1.2	Inherent Resilience	237
5.2.34.1.3	Theme Challenges faced by the SBSC	237
5.2.34.1.4	Lack of Financial Strength.....	238
5.2.34.1.5	Overview of the IP25's interview	238
5.3	Main Themes	239
5.3.1	Main Theme 1 Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain	239
5.3.1.1	Traceability.....	241
5.3.1.2	Inherent Resilience	243

5.3.1.3	Supplier Selection.....	244
5.3.1.4	Supply Base Diversity	245
5.3.1.5	Transparency	245
5.3.1.6	Contingency Planning	246
5.3.1.7	Risk Mitigation.....	247
5.3.1.8	Market Position	247
5.3.1.9	Logistical Capabilities	248
5.3.1.10	Redundancy	248
5.3.1.11	Government Support	249
5.3.2	Application of DCV in the exploration of capability factors.....	249
5.4	Main Theme 2 Challenges faced by the SBSC.....	254
5.5	Cross-Stakeholder Perspectives on Supply Chain Resilience in the Scottish Beef Supply Chain 260	
5.5.1	Propagation against the Livestock Farmers	261
5.5.2	Structural Imbalances	262
5.5.3	Supply Demand Imbalances	262
5.5.4	Lack of Financial Returns.....	263
5.5.5	Traceability	264
5.5.6	Government Support.....	266
5.5.7	Retailer Dominance	266
5.5.8	Product Quality	267
5.5.9	Collaboration	268
5.6	Temporal Escalation of Systemic Challenges and Resilience Capability Impacts in the SBSC 270	
5.7	Resilience Capability Effectiveness in the Scottish Beef Supply Chain	273
5.7.1	Proactive Resilience Capabilities	276
5.7.2	Reactive Resilience Capabilities.....	277
5.8	The Interdependency of Challenges and Resilience Capabilities in the SBSC	277
5.8.1	Lack of Financial Returns as the Primary Systemic Constraint	279

5.8.2	Structural Imbalances	280
5.8.3	Decline in the Suckler Herd.....	280
5.8.4	Absence of KPIs and Export Ambition	280
5.8.5	Slow Government Response and Policy Uncertainty	280
6	Conclusion and Recommendations.....	282
6.1	Objective 1: To explore the current resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain.	282
6.2	Objective 2: To identify the key factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC.....	283
6.3	Objective 3: To explore the key challenges impacting the resilience of the SBSC.....	285
6.4	Empirical Contribution to Supply Chain Resilience Literature.....	285
6.5	Theoretical Contribution.....	288
6.6	Recommendations.....	291
6.6.1	Reform Agricultural Subsidies to Incentivize Efficiency and Innovation.....	292
6.6.2	Creation of a Centralized and User-Friendly Database	292
6.6.3	Creation of Future Markets.....	293
6.6.4	Promote Supply Chain Fairness.....	293
6.6.5	Enhancing Disease Preparedness and Biosecurity Measures	294
6.6.6	Formulation of Long-Term Policies	294
6.7	Stakeholder Implications and Recommendations.....	295
6.8	Research Limitations	296
6.9	Recommendations for Future Research.....	297
7	References.....	299

List of Figures

Figure 2.1 Structure of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (Created by Author)	10
Figure 2.2 Average herd size by Region Source (Red Meat Industry Profile 2024- QMS 2024)	14
Figure 2.3 Share of Holdings and Beef Herd Size (Source Red Meat Industry Profile 2024).....	15
Figure 2.4 Cattle Population in Scotland since 1990 Source QMS Red Meat Industry Profile 2024-QMS 2024	16
Figure 5.1 Initial Coding of Interview Transcript in NVivo IP1	69
Figure 5.2 Major Beef Exporting Countries Source Statista 2024	78
Figure 5.3 Initial Coding of Interview Transcript in NVivo IP2	79
Figure 5.4 Challenges Identified By Academia.....	85
Figure 5.5 Initial Coding of Interview Transcript in NVivo IP3	87
Figure 5.6 Challenges identified by Consultant	91
Figure 5.7 Initial Coding in Nvivo IP4.....	98
Figure 5.8 Challenges Identified by Cattle Society Official.....	106
Figure 5.9 Initial coding of Transcript in Nvivo IP 5	109
Figure 5.10 "Proportion of Beef by Country of Origin Across Major UK Retailers" (Source NFUS Shelf watch report 2024).....	118
Figure 5.11 Initial Code Generated in Nvivo IP6	123
Figure 5.12 Initial code generation from the transcript IP7.....	131
Figure 5.13 Interview Coding in NVivo IP8	139
Figure 5.14 Interview Coding in NVivo IP 9.....	148
Figure 5.15 Interview Coding in NVivo IP10	154
Figure 5.16 Interview Participant Profile IP (NM) 11	160
Figure 5.17 Interview Coding in NVivo IP11.....	161
Figure 5.18 Challenges Identified by the Livestock Farmers.....	164
Figure 5.19 Interview Coding in NVivo IP12	167
Figure 5.20 Interview Coding in NVivo IP 13.....	173
Figure 5.21 Interview Coding in NVivo IP14	180
Figure 5.22 Challenges Identified by the Processors.....	186
Figure 5.23 Interview Coding in NVivo IP15	188
Figure 5.24 Interview Coding in NVivo IP16	193
Figure 5.25 Challenges Identified by Auctioneers	198
Figure 5.26 Interview Coding in NVivo IP17	199
Figure 5.27 Interview Coding in NVivo IP18	205
Figure 5.28 Interview Coding in NVivo IP19	211
Figure 5.29 Interview Coding in NVivo IP20	216

Figure 5.30 Initial Coding of Interview Transcript in NVivo IP21	221
Figure 5.31 Interview Coding in NVivo IP22	224
Figure 5.32 Interview Coding in NVivo IP23	227
Figure 5.33 Interview Coding in NVivo IP24	232
Figure 5.34 Challenges identified by policy managers	235
Figure 5.35 Initial Coding of Interview Transcript in NVivo IP25	236
Figure 5.36 Key Factors contributing to Scottish Beef Supply Chain Resilience.....	241
Figure 5.37 Challenges face by SBSC.....	255
Figure 5.38 Challenges faced by the SBSC.....	256

List of Tables

Table 2.1 Classification of Farms Source Scottish Government (2011).....	12
Table 2.2 Classification of Farms based on Hectares (Source Scottish Government 2015)	13
Table 2.3 Calf Registration in Scotland Source QMS RMIP 2024 QMS 2024.....	17
Table 2.4 Scottish Abattoir output Source QMS RMIP 2024 QMS 2024	17
Table 3.1 Supply Chain Resilience Definitions	23
Table 3.2 Supply Chain Resilience Definitions based on Phases and Attributes	25
Table 3.3 Operational and Structural Drivers	30
Table 3.4 Relational and Organisational Drivers	33
Table 3.5 Technological, Strategic and Learning Drivers.....	35
Table 3.6 Agri-Food Supply Chain Resilience Drivers	43
Table 3.7 Theories Used in Supply Chain Resilience Literature	53
Table 3.8 Contemporary Research in Agri Food Supply Chain	55
Table 3.9 Challenges faced by the AFSC	57
Table 4.1 List of Participants	64
Table 4.2 Interview length and Transcribed words.....	65
Table 5.1 Interview Participant Profile IP (AM) 5	108
Table 5.2 Interview Participant Profile IP (PR) 6	122
Table 5.3 Interview Participant Profile IP (NJ) 7	130
Table 5.4 Interview Participant Profile IP (JR) 8.....	138
Table 5.5 Interview Participant Profile IP (KR) 9	147
Table 5.6 Interview Participant Profile IP (GL) 10.....	153
Table 5.7 Key themes generated in the dataset.....	239
Table 5.8 Supply Chain Resilience Capability factors	240
Table 5.9 Application of DCV	251
Table 5.10 Temporal Escalation of Systemic Challenges.....	271
Table 5.11 Resilience Capability Effectiveness.....	275
Table 5.12 The Interdependency of Challenges and Resilience Capabilities in the SBSC	279
Table 6.1 DCV Application Sequential vs Non sequential path	291

1 Introduction

The Scottish red meat supply chain is a major contributor to Scotland's economy and rural livelihoods, generating approximately £2.72 billion annually (QMS, 2025). Beef production represents the largest share of this contribution, underscoring the sector's economic, social, and strategic importance. National policy and industry vision further reinforce this significance. The Beef Sector Strategy articulates an ambition for the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC) to harness modern technologies and deliver high-quality beef to domestic and international markets through sustainable production systems (Scottish Government, 2014). Recent industry evidence confirms this contribution, in 2020 the Scottish red meat sector generated £1.29 billion, of which beef accounted for £849 million, followed by sheep (£299 million) and pigs (£139 million). Beef alone contributed approximately 24.4% to the rural economy, highlighting its central role in sustaining rural communities (QMS, 2024).

Despite its importance, the SBSC is facing persistent structural pressures that threaten its future viability. The cattle population continues to decline, with beef cow numbers falling by 2.5% in 2023 and calf registrations declining by 2.7%, signalling a contraction in herd size (QMS, 2024). This downward trend persists even under relatively favourable market prices and raises concerns regarding the sector's capacity to meet future domestic and export demand. Sustained reductions in suckler cow numbers point to deeper challenges within primary production, including financial pressure, demographic change, and long-term confidence in the sector (QMS, 2024).

These challenges must be understood within the context of a large, complex, and highly interdependent supply chain. The Beef Sector Strategy 2030 highlights that Scottish beef production involves over 10,000 farms and crofts, generating approximately £850 million in annual farm-gate output and supplying around 450,000 cattle to 20 abattoirs, which together produce more than 165,000 tonnes of beef annually (QMS, 2024a). This scale of production requires effective coordination among multiple actors, including livestock farmers, auction marts, processors, logistics providers, wholesalers, and retailers. However, previous research has highlighted weaknesses in coordination and price transparency, particularly for farmers engaging with processors and retailers (Leat and Giha, 2016). The industry's future depends on the coordination of each member of the supply chain to benefit the whole industry (QMS 2024a).

1.1 Research Context

The 2022 Climate Change Committee (CCC) recommendation, urging the Scottish Government to reduce meat consumption by 20% and 30% by 2030 and 2050, respectively, could profoundly affect the Scottish Beef Industry (CCC 2020). The Scottish beef industry faces formidable challenges, including low profitability, a trust deficit in the supply chain, climate change, market volatility, livestock production issues, and post-Brexit trade (QMS 2024a). Addressing these challenges is imperative for the industry's survival and growth.

In 2023, twenty-one slaughterhouses were licensed in Scotland, with the five largest handling 75% of the cattle, indicating a concentrated throughput and 0.7% kill in five smallest abattoirs (QMS 2024). Animal diseases have significantly impacted the Scottish beef industry. The 2001 Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) outbreak cost Scottish agriculture approximately £231 million (EPIC, 2014). Similarly, the Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE) crisis led to a ban on British beef from 1996 to 2006 (EPIC, 2014). A plant closure due to an infectious outbreak can disrupt the entire supply chain (Hayes et al., 2023).

The concept of supply chain resilience, borrowed from different disciplines, is multidisciplinary and multidimensional. Cranfield University conducted one of the earlier studies in 2003 on the directive of the UK Government's Department for Transport, Trade, and Industry (Pettit et al., 2010). The economic crises of September 2000 and February 2001, triggered by fuel protests and the FMD (Foot and Mouth Disease) outbreak, respectively, formed the basis of the study conducted by Cranfield University.

Supply chain resilience is related to supply chain risk management but differs in its approaches (Ponomarov & Holcomb, 2009; Pettit et al., 2010). Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009) and Hohenstein et al., (2015) define supply chain resilience as the ability to prepare for unanticipated risks, respond and recover swiftly from disruptions, and return to the original position or move to a more desirable one. They emphasise the time frame, continuity of operations, level of connectedness, and control over structure and function, which can lead to better financial performance, customer service, and market share.

The existing literature views supply chain resilience as preparing for, responding to, and recovering from disruptions, primarily focusing on operational continuity and risk management (Christopher and Peck, 2004; Ponomarov and Holcomb, 2009; Hohenstein et al., 2015; Ali and Gogeci, 2019). This narrow focus neglects the systemic challenges that continuously influence the resilience of the supply. In an environment where challenges such as climate change, pandemics, and geopolitical conflicts are causally linked and often intensify one another's effects, organisations must prioritise the development of comprehensive and

multi-faceted resilience strategies to anticipate, manage, and mitigate the cascading impacts of these interconnected challenges (Zheng, 2024).

Research on agri-food supply chains has identified a wide range of risks that increase exposure to disruption. Zhao et al., (2020) identified sixteen key risks affecting agri-food supply chains and recommended that resilience strategies be developed to mitigate them. The authors concluded that extreme weather conditions and political and economic instability represent the most significant threats, followed by poor agricultural infrastructure, risks from pests and disease, and supply–demand imbalances.

These risks manifest in the form of disruptions such as natural disasters (e.g., floods and hurricanes), pandemics, trade barriers, infrastructure failures, contamination incidents, and political instability. Such disruptions can significantly impact operations by reducing food availability, increasing costs and price volatility, disrupting transportation and logistics, halting production processes, causing supply chain delays, and raising food quality and safety concerns (Sutar, Kolte and Yamini, 2025).

To manage exposure to disruption risks, supply chain resilience research has emphasised the development of specific resilience capabilities. Shekarian and Parast (2021) developed an integrative framework that categorises supply chain disruption risks into demand, supply, process, control, and environmental risks and identifies the corresponding resilience capabilities required to mitigate each category. Their analysis highlights the importance of capabilities such as flexibility, collaboration, and information visibility in managing disruption risks. The framework explains how capabilities align with different risk categories, while the conditions influencing the sustained effectiveness of these capabilities over time remain outside the scope of the analysis.

Alongside disruption and capability focused research, a separate stream of literature has examined the challenges faced by agri-food supply chains. Agrawal, Tiwari and Singh (2025) categorised agri-food supply chain challenges into seven categories: integration, quality, sustainability, infrastructure, knowledge and awareness, technological, and climatic issues. The sub-challenges identified include inadequate and improper information flow, poor linkages between supply chain partners, improper collaborative planning, insufficient traceability, lack of transparency, low remuneration to farmers, and technological issues. The authors examined how these challenges affect supply chain efficiency, while their implications for risk exposure, disruption occurrence, and resilience capabilities associated with response and recovery were beyond the scope of the analysis.

Agri-food supply chains operate as interrelated chains embedded within a wider food system in which shocks propagate across actors and stages, necessitating a systems-based perspective rather than a sole

focus on firm-level continuity (Hobbs, 2021). Disruptions to food or energy supplies therefore carry more severe economic and societal consequences than those experienced in many manufacturing supply chains (Hobbs, 2021). However, existing research has largely focused on firm-level resilience and has not fully accounted for the complex, multi-tiered, and decentralised structure of agri-food supply chains (Hendry et al., 2019). As a result, there remains limited theoretical and empirical understanding of how resilience operates across the Scottish beef supply chain, particularly in relation to systemic and long-term challenges.

The economic implications of resilience capability development further emphasise this gap. Both underinvestment and overinvestment in resilience capabilities can lead to profit erosion, either through disruption losses or unnecessary resilience costs (Pettit et al., 2010; Pettit et al., 2013). While Shekarian and Parast (2021) emphasise the importance of targeted investment in capabilities such as flexibility and collaboration, there is limited insight into how persistent systemic challenges may constrain the effectiveness of such capabilities in practice.

In the context of the Scottish beef industry, challenges such as low profitability, trust deficits, climate change, market volatility, livestock production issues, and post-Brexit trade uncertainties (QMS, 2025) form a persistent backdrop against which disruptions occur. Low profitability constrains the financial capacity of stakeholders, particularly farmers, to invest in resilience measures. Because resilience investment involves developing specific capabilities, such as collaboration or flexibility, understanding how ongoing challenges affect the functioning and effectiveness of these capabilities is critical. Without this understanding, investments risk being misaligned or wasted, further eroding already constrained profit margins. Consequently, when disruptions such as disease outbreaks or extreme weather events occur, stakeholders may be less prepared to absorb their impact or recover effectively.

Existing definitions of supply chain resilience in agri-food contexts largely focus on disruptions (Stone & Rahimifard, 2018) and do not adequately incorporate the persistent structural, economic, regulatory, and demographic pressures that characterise the Scottish beef supply chain. Given these gaps, this study aims to explore the resilience of the Scottish beef supply chain comprising primary producers, processors, auctioneers, and retailers. It investigates the key factors that contribute to resilience and examines how current challenges affect the industry's ability to prepare for, respond to, and recover from disruptions.

1.2 Research Aim and Objectives

Despite the increasing recognition of the importance of supply chain resilience, there remains a limited understanding of how the SBSC's resilience is impacted by the challenges which are diverse and interconnected. This lack of understanding stems from lack of in-depth research that explores the

perspectives of various stakeholders across the Scottish beef supply chain, from farmers, auction marts, processors to retailers and policymakers. Understanding their perspective of resilience, the specific challenges they face, and the strategies they employ to mitigate disruptions is crucial for developing effective interventions to enhance the industry's overall resilience.

The aim of this research is to explore the resilience of the SBSC and how it is impacted by the challenges. To achieve this aim, following objectives have been formulated.

Objectives:

1. To explore the current resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain.

This objective would explore the resilience capability of the key Scottish Beef Supply chain players in terms of their readiness, response and recovery.

2. To identify the key factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC.

This objective would identify the key factors contributing to the resilience of the Scottish Beef supply chain in terms of proactive and reactive factors.

3. To explore the key challenges impacting the resilience of the SBSC.

This objective would the key challenges faced by the SBSC, the interconnectedness of the challenges and how they are impacting the resilience of the SBSC.

1.3 Research Questions

How are the challenges impacting the resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC)?

What factors contribute to the resilience of the SBSC?

1.4 Research Methodology

This research employed a qualitative case study methodology to explore and understand the resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC). A case study approach is particularly well-suited for this exploratory study as it enables an in-depth investigation of complex, real-world phenomena within their specific context (Yin, 2018). Given the SBSC's decentralised and multi-actor nature, the case study method allows for a comprehensive exploration of how stakeholders identify the contributing factors for a resilient SBSC in the face of diverse challenges. To collect rich and detailed data, the study conducted twenty-five semi structured interviews with key stakeholders across the SBSC. The participants comprised of Academic

Experts (02), Industry Advisor (01), Official Cattle Society Representative (01), Livestock Farmers (07), Industry Representative Processors (01), Processors (02), Industry Representative Auction Marts (01), Auction Mart (01), Retailer (01), Retail Industry Expert (01), Policy Managers Livestock & Animal /Market (03), Executive Traceability Organisation (01), Head of Industry Development (01), Public Affairs and Industry Strategy Manager (01), and Member of Scottish Parliament, Rural Affairs Committee Member (01). The qualitative data collected through interviews were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis.

1.5 Research Significance

This research makes several significant contributions. It extends the application of the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV) beyond firm-level analysis to a supply chain-wide perspective. The theoretical foundation of this research is situated within the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV), representing a deliberate paradigm shift from traditional strategic frameworks such as Porter's Five Forces and the Resource-Based View (RBV). While Porter's and RBV frameworks primarily emphasize static resource ownership and industry positioning, they are increasingly considered insufficient for maintaining a competitive advantage in "high velocity" or rapidly changing environments. In contrast, the DCV, as defined by Teece et al., (1997), focuses on an organization's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competences to address rapidly changing environments.

A central objective established at the outset of this thesis is to explore the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC), where supply chain resilience is explicitly identified and explored as a dynamic capability. This study utilizes the DCV framework specifically the micro foundations of Processes, Positions, and Paths as the primary mechanism to define the resilience capability factors contributed by different supply chain players. By adopting this holistic view, the research addresses the gap identified by Scholten et al., (2020), who emphasized that resilience studies at the supply chain level require further exploration to identify how individual actors contribute to the collective strength of the network.

Furthermore, this study intends to extend the Dynamic Capabilities View by examining its enactment within a specific sectoral and decentralized context. Although existing research has utilized process classifications such as Sensing, Seizing, and Transforming (Teece, 2007) to analyse responses to "one-off" disruptions like Brexit (Hendry et al., 2019) or natural disasters (Martins de Sá et al., 2020), there remains limited insight into how these processes are enacted in decentralized operations.

This thesis contributes to knowledge by proposing an empirically grounded definition of agri-food supply chain (AFSC) resilience, developed through an in-depth study of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC). While existing supply chain resilience literature (Hendry et al., 2019; Martins de Sá et al., 2020; Payne-Gifford et al., 2022; Zhao G et al., 2024) has predominantly focused on responses to discrete disruption

events, this study advances the field by explicitly incorporating the role of persistent structural challenges alongside acute disruptions in shaping resilience outcomes.

The contribution of this thesis lies in demonstrating that resilience in agri-food supply chains cannot be fully understood through an event-centric lens alone. Instead, resilience is shaped by the interaction between chronic challenges, such as low profitability, declining herd size, labour and succession constraints, and market power imbalance, and acute disruptions, including disease outbreaks, market shocks, and extreme weather events. These chronic challenges do not constitute disruptions in themselves; however, they condition the level of vulnerability, preparedness, and adaptive capacity within the supply chain. Accordingly, this thesis offers an empirically grounded definition of AFSC resilience, which is later formalised in Chapter 6 but conceptually introduced here as part of its contribution to knowledge.

By exploring the SBSC holistically, the study provides valuable insights for policymakers, industry leaders, and practitioners to develop targeted strategies to strengthen supply chain resilience. The findings can inform policy interventions, industry practices, and collaborative initiatives that enhance the SBSC's capacity to withstand and recover from disruptions.

1.6 Thesis Outline

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter introduces the study, detailing the background, rationale, research problem, aims, and scope. It establishes the context of the importance of the Scottish beef industry and the growing need to explore its resilience amid various disruptions. The chapter presents the research questions that guide the inquiry and justifies using a qualitative case study methodology. It also discusses the significance of the research and provides an outline of the thesis structure.

Chapter 2: Industry Context

This chapter offers a comprehensive overview of the Scottish red meat industry, emphasising the key players of SBSC. It covers the entire SBSC by profiling key stakeholders such as livestock farmers, processors, auction marts, and retailers. The chapter provides foundational knowledge for understanding the SBSC.

Chapter 3: Literature Review

This chapter reviews existing literature on supply chain resilience, particularly within the agri-food sector. It examines theoretical frameworks such as the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Dynamic Capabilities

View (DCV), alongside other theories relevant to supply chain resilience. The chapter identifies key resilience drivers and the gaps in current research, justifying the need for this study.

Chapter 4: Research Methodology

This chapter explains the research philosophy, design, and strategy underpinning the study. It details the case study approach, the selection and recruitment of participants, and the data collection through twenty-five semi-structured ss. Thematic analysis is described as the primary method for data analysis. Ethical considerations guiding the research process are also outlined.

Chapter 5: Analysis and Discussion

This chapter presents the findings from the interviews, identifying key resilience drivers and challenges within the Scottish beef supply chain. The findings are discussed in relation to existing literature and theoretical framework.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendations

The final chapter synthesizes the research findings and discusses their practical implications for enhancing resilience in the Scottish beef supply chain. It provides actionable recommendations for stakeholders, acknowledges the study's limitations, and suggests directions for future research.

2 Industry Context

To develop an in-depth understanding of the Scottish beef industry's supply chain resilience, we will first examine the Scottish Red meat industry profile to assess the contribution of cattle to the red meat industry and economy. Afterwards, we will scrutinise the complete profile of the Scottish beef supply chain.

2.1 Scottish Red Meat Industry Profile

The Scottish Red Meat Industry in 2023 showcased a strong performance across various aspects, including production, employment, and exports. The abattoir sector alone supported 2,800 employees, contributing £88.4 million in wages, with a significant 45% of the workforce based in rural areas. Regarding per capita meat consumption, the average Scottish person consumed 17.5 kg of beef, 1.8 kg of lamb, and 18.2 kg of pork. The Scottish Red Meat Industry, a significant contributor to the economy, accounted for 32% of greenhouse gas emissions in Scotland, while the rest of the UK was responsible for 58%, and 10% came from international exports (QMS 2024).

The overall output of the Scottish red meat sector was strong, with abattoir output reaching £975 million, representing a 1% increase compared to the previous year. Beef led the way with £714 million, followed by sheep meat at £121 million, pig meat at £49 million, offal at £71 million, and bone and hide contributing £20 million. The industry's exports were also significant, with 45,103 tonnes of meat and meat preparations shipped, generating £144.5 million, making red meat the fourth largest category in Scottish food and live animal exports (QMS 2024).

The Scottish Red Meat Industry demonstrates a robust structure with substantial economic contributions, with the beef sector as the primary contributor. These indicators reflect the sector's significant role within Scotland's broader agricultural economy.

Although beef output rose to the estimated £836 million in 2024 and accounting for 59% of finished livestock output (The Scottish Government, 2025). This increase presents a misleadingly positive picture of sector performance. The growth is driven primarily by elevated market prices rather than improvements in production capacity or herd expansion. Scottish cattle numbers continue to decline, creating a structural vulnerability that is obscured by short-term price inflation. The cattle population in Scotland has seen a steady decline since the late 1990s, falling from 2.11 million head in 1990 to 1.68 million in June 2023. This represents a 20.1% reduction over the period (QMS 2024). This underlying contraction in the national herd represents the more significant long-term risk to the beef sector, yet it receives comparatively limited policy and industry attention despite its implications for resilience of the SBSC.

2.2 Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The Scottish Beef supply chain (SBSC) comprises of various stakeholders. The origin of the supply chain is the resources utilised by the livestock farmers, such as veterinary services, animal feed, fertiliser, machinery, etc. (QMS 2023).

In this thesis, the SBSC comprises of four core stages: livestock farmers, auctioneers, processors and retailers. These actors form the central operational pathway through which production, exchange, processing and retailing take place. The main structural pressures affecting the Scottish beef sector such as the long-term decline in supply from primary producers, the coordination of sales and movements through auction markets, the need for stable volumes to sustain processing capacity, and the influence of retail buying practices are concentrated within these stages (QMS, 2025). Organisations such as transport providers, service firms and regulatory bodies are not included, as they perform supporting functions rather than forming part of the core production to retail. Since the functioning of these four stages is interdependent, the challenges arising within them can have a disproportionate impact on the overall resilience of the SBSC. Their scale, economic contribution and operational centrality make them the most relevant stages for examining resilience at the supply chain level.

The key stakeholders are discussed below

2.2.1 Livestock Farmers

Over 10,000 farm and croft holdings support Scotland's beef industry. These farms and crofts supply around 450,000 cattle each year to 20 abattoirs across Scotland. However, most of the beef produced is distributed within the UK, outside Scotland, which consumes about two-thirds of abattoir output (QMS, 2022).

Figure 2.1 Structure of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (Created by Author)

Livestock farmers are central to the functioning of the SBSC, and their roles vary depending on the resources, geography, and production models available to them. Farmers may specialise exclusively in cattle or sheep, though mixed enterprises remain common. Within cattle production specifically, farmers are typically classified as breeders, rearers, or finishers, with some undertaking multiple stages of production (NFUS, 2023).

The organisation of these roles is influenced by regional characteristics: for example, farmers in the Northwest of Scotland generally rear calves for six to twelve months before selling them as store cattle for finishing in the lowland regions. Conversely, many lowland farmers focus solely on fattening cattle rather than breeding. Additional sources of beef include male and surplus female calves originating from the dairy sector. Production across Scotland is predominantly extensive and grass-based, supplemented by indoor feeding during adverse weather or during calving and lambing periods (NFUS, 2023). Some farmers specialise in finishing because, although feed costs are high and feed conversion efficiency declines as cattle nears slaughter weight, finishing allows control over diet, growth, and market-ready carcass quality, avoiding the labour and long-term management burdens of a breeding herd (FAS, 2023).

Once cattle reach the appropriate stage, farmers market them through auction marts, direct sales to processors, or transfers to other farmers depending on their production system and market conditions. Following processing, retailers emerge as the principal downstream actors, shaping the flow of beef products to consumers (QMS, 2023).

2.2.2 Structure of the Livestock Farms

In Scotland, farms are classified based on their size, land use, and the type of farming practiced, with distinct types specializing in crops or livestock. The Scottish agricultural landscape is diverse, and this diversity is reflected in the types of farms across the country. Farms are classified into various categories but the one's pertaining to the cattle are Dairy Farms which are Found mainly in lowland areas such as Dumfries & Galloway and Ayrshire, dairy farms focus on milk production and operate more intensively than other types. Cattle and Sheep Farms LFA and Lowland farms are common in both Less Favoured Areas (LFA) and lowland regions. LFA farms are typically located in more challenging areas like the Highlands and Islands, where grazing land is poor. In contrast, lowland cattle and sheep farms have better grazing conditions and are able to raise livestock more intensively. Mixed Farms engage in both crop and livestock production, allowing for flexibility depending on market conditions and environmental factors (Scottish Government, 2016).

2.2.3 Classification of Cattle Farms in Scotland

The classification of cattle farms is based on several factors, including the number of cattle and the size of the land, particularly in terms of hectares used for farming. Cattle farms are typically categorised as small, medium, or large based on these factors (Scottish Government, 2016).

The classification of cattle farms by size in Scotland can be broken down as follows:

Farm Size Classification	Number of Cattle	Farm Characteristics
Small Cattle Farms	Fewer than 50 cattle	Family-run or small-scale, subsistence or supplemental income
Medium Cattle Farms	Between 50 and 150 cattle	Commercially oriented, structured beef or dairy production
Large Cattle Farms	More than 150 cattle	Large-scale commercial operations focus on premium beef or dairy for large markets.

Table 2.1 Classification of Farms Source Scottish Government (2011)

2.2.4 Classification Based on Hectares

Cattle farms in Scotland are further classified based on their land size or hectarage. The majority of cattle and sheep farms in Scotland are located in Less Favoured Areas (LFA), where land use is extensive, and livestock graze over large areas. For example, farms in the LFA regions often exceed 200 hectares, especially in the Highlands and Islands, where large areas of rough grazing are common. These farms tend to be extensive, meaning the stocking density is lower, but more land is required to sustain the cattle herds.

In contrast, lowland cattle farms tend to be smaller in size but more intensively managed, with higher stocking densities. These farms may range from 50 to 200 hectares, depending on the scale of operations. For example, a dairy farm in the lowlands may require a smaller area of land but can support a larger number of cattle per hectare due to more favourable environmental conditions and access to feed (Scottish Government, 2015)

In 2015, the distribution of cattle by farm type and region reflected these geographic variations. Approximately 72% of cattle were located on LFA holdings, where the emphasis is on using extensive grazing lands. Non-LFA holdings, particularly in regions like Dumfries & Galloway and Ayrshire, host large dairy operations that rely on more intensive land use (Scottish Government, 2016).

Farm Size Category	Size (Hectares)	Key Features	Key Observations
Small Holdings	< 10 hectares	High number of small farms and crofts, reflecting crofting traditions.	They account for 52% of holdings but only 1.6% of the total land area.
Medium Holdings	10 - 200 hectares	Suitable for mixed farming and livestock grazing.	Provide flexibility for mixed farming systems, balancing crop and livestock.
Large Holdings	200+ hectares	Focus on extensive livestock farming with cattle and sheep grazing (LFA).	Occupy 76% of the total land area, used mainly for rough grazing.

Table 2.2 Classification of Farms based on Hectares (Source Scottish Government 2015)

This classification system illustrates the diversity of cattle farming in Scotland, where the size of the farm, the number of cattle, and the type of land used significantly influence the type of cattle farming practised across different regions.

Figure 2.2 Average herd size by Region Source (Red Meat Industry Profile 2024- QMS 2024)

The pie chart illustrates the average beef cow herd size by region in Scotland as of June 2023. It highlights significant regional variations in herd sizes, reflecting differences in farming practices, land availability, and economic focus across Scotland (QMS, 2024).

The Scottish Borders recorded the largest average herd size at 82.3 cows, indicating a concentration of larger-scale beef farming operations in this region. Other areas with relatively large herd sizes include Lothian 66.8, Dumfries & Galloway 64.0, and Fife 59.9, which are also known for productive agricultural land and established livestock industries (QMS, 2024).

Regions such as Orkney 58.2, Tayside 57.7, and North East 57.0 also maintain above-average herd sizes, suggesting a strong focus on beef production. By contrast, areas like Na h-Eileanan Siar 7.5 and Shetland 13.3 reported much smaller herd sizes, likely due to geographical constraints, limited grazing land, and more fragmented farming systems (QMS, 2024).

The national average herd size for Scotland was 48.6 cows, with regions such as Ayrshire 47.2, Clyde Valley 44.6, and East Central 36.9 falling close to or below this average. The Highland 29.2 and Argyll & Bute 34.0 regions also reported smaller herd sizes, reflecting more extensive grazing systems and challenging terrain. Overall, this distribution underscores the diversity in Scotland's beef production systems (QMS, 2024).

Figure 2.3 Share of Holdings and Beef Herd Size (Source Red Meat Industry Profile 2024)

This bubble chart illustrates the share of holdings and beef herd by herd size group in Scotland as of June 2023, highlighting the distribution of herd sizes across the industry.

Smaller herds of 1–4 cows account for 20% of holdings but contribute only 0.9% to the total beef herd, reflecting their limited role in overall production. In contrast, herds of 150 or more cows, while making up only 5.6% of holdings, contribute the largest share 31.1% of the national herd, indicating a concentration of production in larger-scale operations. This distribution highlights the dual structure of Scotland’s beef sector, where small farms are numerous but contribute modestly, while larger herds dominate production (QMS, 2024)

It is important to examine the structure of cattle farming within the SBSC, as this provides the context needed to understand how production is organised and how cattle move through different stages of the system. Outlining this structure helps situate the roles and interactions of cattle farmers within the wider supply chain, thereby framing the subsequent analysis of the challenges they face and the factors that may contribute to resilience across the system.

2.2.5 Cattle output in 2023

The red meat supply chain struggled with increased input costs and rising interest rates in 2023 but managed to offset the cost for the livestock producers with the record level of farm gate prices, which eased the pressure. Despite the favourable prices for stored and finished cattle, the Beef herd showed a 2.5% decrease year on year in December 2023. Likewise, Calf Registration squeezed by 2.7% (Macdonald, 2024).

The cattle population in Scotland has seen a steady decline since the late 1990s. Figure 2.4 illustrates the long-term decline in Scotland’s cattle population, falling from 2.11 million head in 1990 to 1.68 million in

June 2023. This represents a 20.1% reduction over the period. The figure shows a sharp drop around 2001, largely associated with the Foot and Mouth Disease outbreak, followed by only a partial recovery before the herd resumed its downward trajectory. The continuing contraction reflects structural pressures within the sector, including rising costs, policy changes and reduced profitability (QMS, 2024).

Figure 2.4 Cattle Population in Scotland since 1990 Source QMS Red Meat Industry Profile 2024-QMS 2024

The table 2.3 on calf registrations in Scotland from 2021 to 2023 highlights the trends across various cattle breeds. Angus continues to grow in popularity, increasing its share from 22.9% in 2021 to 25.6% in 2023, reflecting a 0.2% rise in births from 2022 and a significant 55.9% increase since 2015(QMS, 2024). In contrast, Limousin, once a dominant breed, has steadily declined, with registrations dropping from 18.4% in 2021 to 16.6% in 2023, marking a 7.3% decrease from the previous year and a 28.5% drop since 2015. Black and White Dairy Breeds, Charolais, and Simmental have also experienced declines, with birth rates falling by 2.5%, 5.1%, and 5.4%, respectively, compared to 2022. The "Other" category, which includes less common breeds, has shown a slight growth, rising to 22.3% of total registrations in 2023, up by 0.5% from 2022 and 34.1% since 2015. Total calf registrations show a continued long-term contraction in Scotland's cattle sector. Registrations declined from 562,000 in 2022 to 547,100 in 2023, representing a year-on-year reduction of 2.7%. When viewed over a longer period, the number of calves registered in 2023 is 4.1% lower than in 2015. The figure therefore reflects a sustained downward trend in breeding activity rather than a short-term fluctuation, signalling ongoing structural pressures within the Scottish cattle industry (QMS, 2024).

Breed	2021 (% of total)	2022 (% of total)	2023 (% of total)	% change in number of births 2023 v 2022	% change in number of births 2023 v 2015
Angus	22.90%	24.9%	25.6%	+0.2%	+55.9%
Limousin	18.4%	17.4%	16.6%	-7.3%	-28.5%
Black and White Dairy Breed	14.2%	13.4%	13.4%	-2.5%	-26.9%
Charolais	12.5%	12.1%	11.8%	-5.1%	-26.5%
Simmental	10.8%	10.6%	10.3%	-5.4%	-24.5%
Other	21.2%	21.6%	22.3%	+0.5%	+34.1%
Total registrations (head)	563,100	562,000	547,100	-2.7%	-4.1%

Table 2.3 Calf Registration in Scotland Source QMS RMIP 2024 QMS 2024

2.3 Processing Sector

Scotland has a total of 21 abattoirs, with 20 of these facilities also functioning as cutting plants, highlighting their dual-purpose capabilities for slaughtering and meat processing. Additionally, there are 61 dedicated cutting plants that further process meat products, ensuring efficient handling and preparation for distribution. (QMS 2022).

2.3.1 Processing Sector Output

Scottish abattoir output in 2023 shows a decline in the number of animals processed across all categories compared to 2022. Cattle processing saw the largest year-on-year drop, with an 8% reduction in the number of animals slaughtered and a 7.6% decrease in the volume of meat produced, though the estimated sales value still grew by 1.4% to £792 million, reflecting higher prices per unit. Offal sales dropped by 5.2%, and the value of skins and hides fell significantly by 13.7%, highlighting some areas of decline within the broader market. The data suggests that while fewer animals were processed in 2023, higher prices, particularly for beef and pork, helped offset some of the decline in production volumes (QMS, 2024).

Scottish abattoir output									
Year	Number of animals			Volume of meat (t)			Estimated sales value (£m)		
	2022	2023	y/y change	2022	2023	y/y change	2022	2023	y/y change
Cattle	448,770	412,780	-8.0%	163,275	150,895	-7.6%	781	792	+1.4%
Sheep	1,052,795	995,705	-5.4%	22,350	20,890	-6.5%	139	130	-6.0%
Pigs	240,445	230,565	-4.1%	22,305	21,195	-5.0%	46	53	+14.7%
Combined	1,742,010	1,639,050	-5.9%	207,930	192,980	-7.2%	966	975	+1.0%
Offal	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	75	71	-5.2%
Skins and hides	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	23	20	-13.7%

Table 2.4 Scottish Abattoir output Source QMS RMIP 2024 QMS 2024

2.3.2 Major Processing Plants of Scotland

The Scottish beef processing sector is driven by a range of large and small companies. In 2023, 17 abattoirs processed cattle in Scotland. The QMS red meat industry profile 2024 mentioned that in 2023, 75.0% of the total cattle kill occurred in the five largest abattoirs, demonstrating the dominance of large-scale facilities in the industry. In contrast, the five smallest abattoirs account for just 0.7% of the total kill,

indicating that smaller facilities play a minimal role in overall processing capacity. The leading processing plant in Scotland are ABP Food Group, Scotbeef, AK Dunbia Highland Meats, AK Stoddart Ltd, Border Meats, Millers of Speyside, Woodheads-Morrisons Farming (SAMW, 2025).

This distribution reflects the centralisation and efficiency of larger abattoirs in handling higher volumes, which contributes to economies of scale. However, it also highlights the limited capacity of smaller abattoirs, which may serve niche markets or provide local services, emphasising the structural imbalance within the processing sector. A study was done by the Scottish Government in 2020 to explore the feasibility of the mobile abattoirs. The report confirmed the feasibility of mobile abattoirs in Scotland, but unfortunately, the problem persists. (Scottish Government 2020).

2.4 Auction Marts

Auction Marts also play an important role in the SBSC. The Institute of Auctioneers and Appraisers in Scotland (IAAS), founded in 1926, is the professional body that represents auctioneers, valuers, and livestock markets throughout Scotland. The IAAS plays a pivotal role in promoting the livestock auction system, which is regarded as one of the most transparent and fair mechanisms for trading livestock. By upholding high standards in auctioneering and valuation, the IAAS ensures that all participants, including farmers, buyers, and sellers, benefit from a system that guarantees competitive pricing and prompt payments (IAAS, 2025).

The IAAS actively works with government and regulatory bodies to influence policies that affect Scotland's agricultural and rural sectors. This collaboration helps ensure that regulations are designed to support the sustainability and growth of Scotland's farming industry. The organisation also plays a key role in shaping the future of the profession by developing educational programs and examination structures to train and nurture new talent in auctioneering (IAAS, 2025).

In addition to its regulatory and advocacy roles, the IAAS is instrumental in providing market intelligence. It collaborates with Quality Meat Scotland and ScotEID to offer up-to-date data on livestock prices and market trends. This real-time market information helps farmers and buyers make informed decisions, which is crucial for maintaining the economic vitality of the agricultural sector.

The farm advisory service has issued guidelines for the new participants to be engaged in the sale and purchase from the livestock auctions. Although buying and selling at auction marts can be a straightforward process, proper preparation needs to be done. First, buyers must ensure they have the necessary registrations, such as a Main Location Code (MLC) and herd or flock numbers from relevant authorities, allowing them to purchase livestock legally. Researching local marts and understanding their sale schedules is essential, as different stock types, for instance, breeding, store, fat, or cull, are sold on specific days. On

sale day, bidders should be clear about their budget and inspect the livestock in the penning area before bidding. Purchases are recorded by the auctioneer, and payment is typically made on the day, with movement documents provided to facilitate the transfer of animals. Sellers, on the other hand, must ensure their livestock is properly tagged, accompanied by the necessary paperwork, such as cattle passports and movement forms. Arriving early at the mart allows time for penning and processing of paperwork, and sellers should set a reserve price for their animals. After the sale, sellers receive payment, minus any commissions or additional fees, and are provided with a sales receipt. Both buyers and sellers should engage with auctioneers and market staff to ensure a smooth experience at the mart (FAS, 2019).

Livestock auction marts in Scotland are pivotal to the agricultural economy, providing platforms for farmers to sell cattle, sheep, and other livestock in a competitive, transparent environment. These marts support the pricing of livestock and act as community hubs, especially in rural areas, by promoting fair and open trade. The operations of these auction marts vary in scale, location, and specialization (Balfour, 2024).

The prominent livestock auction marts are Aberdeen and Northern Marts (ANM Group), Caledonian Marts Ltd, United Auctions, Dingwall & Highland Marts Ltd, Wallets Marts Castle Douglas Ltd and Lawrie and Symington Ltd (IAAS, 2025).

2.5 Retailers

The major retailers comprise supermarkets and independent butchers. Retailers are the major buyers of the processing sector, which is evident from the fact that eight large-scale abattoirs handle 88% of Scottish beef processing, and these abattoirs primarily supply major UK supermarket chains (QMS Beef Report 2020).

Supermarkets such as Aldi, Lidl, Marks & Spencer, Morrisons, and Tesco demonstrate varying degrees of commitment to local sourcing, quality assurance, and sustainability (NFUS, 2024).

Lidl emerges as a leader in supporting Scottish agriculture, achieving the highest proportion of Scotch-certified beef among major retailers. Aldi also shows strong support for Scottish farmers through initiatives like the Beef Cross Dairy Supply Chain model, which promotes economic sustainability. Marks & Spencer prioritises quality and traceability, offering customers responsibly sourced beef while adhering to stringent ethical and environmental standards (NFUS, 2024). Morrisons actively collaborates with farmers, particularly through its partnerships and breed-specific programs, to ensure high-quality British beef. Tesco integrates sustainability and welfare standards into its supply chain, ensuring compliance with Quality Meat Scotland schemes. Despite these efforts, variations in the level of support for Scottish beef among retailers highlight areas for improvement after the key findings of the report of the NFU Scotland Shelf Watch Phase 3 (2024) about retailer support for Scottish agricultural products. According to the NFU Scotland Shelf Watch Phase 3 report, Lidl leads in Scottish beef support, with 93.5% of its own-label beef being Scotch-

certified, reflecting a significant 10.7% increase from the previous phase. Aldi, previously a strong supporter, experienced a substantial decline, with only 61.2% of its beef now being Scottish, a drop of 22.8%. M&S and Morrisons remained a strong supporter of Scottish Beef reflecting 92.1% and 85.6 % respectively. In contrast, Sainsbury's stocks only 6.8% of its beef as Scottish, the lowest among the retailers, while also carrying the highest proportion of Irish beef at 9.3%. These findings reflect varying levels of commitment by retailers to Scottish beef, with Lidl making the most significant improvement and Aldi showing the largest decline (NFUS 2024).

3 Literature Review

The literature review has adopted the narrative literature review style to review the relevant literature. It can be written in chronological order, conceptual frameworks, content analysis or other classification criteria (Paré, G et al., 2015; Lau and Kuziemy, 2016). The factors that led to the decision to adopt a narrative literature review in writing the thesis are based on the fragmented research undertaken in supply chain resilience. This fact can be gauged from the fact that despite the volume of research done in the field of supply chain resilience, no single definition of supply chain resilience exists which is consented upon (Ali et al., 2023).

The narrative review was used to trace the chronological evolution of the concept, showing how definitions shifted over time, moving from a simple focus on Business Continuity to incorporating the multiple phases of Preparedness, Response, Recovery, and Growth. The narrative approach allowed for the identification and discussion of diverse resilience drivers across two decades. By reviewing existing definitions, the review identified that even the most comprehensive definition of Agri-Food Supply Chain (AFSC) resilience (Stone & Rahimifard, 2018) is not empirically grounded. A contribution of this thesis is proposal of updated definition of AFSC resilience which is empirically grounded. By reviewing existing studies, it was determined that research on the resilience of the entire Scottish Beef Supply Chain as a holistic unit of analysis was significantly underexplored.

3.1 Conceptual foundations of resilience

Resilience originates in ecological systems theory, where Holling (1973) conceptualised resilience as the capacity of a system to absorb disturbance and reorganise while retaining its core functions and structure. This perspective challenged equilibrium-based assumptions and positioned resilience as a dynamic property of complex systems. Subsequent work extended resilience into socio-ecological and social systems, emphasising adaptive capacity, learning, self-organisation, and the role of interdependencies between system components (Adger, 2000; Folke et al., 2010).

While these foundations provide the conceptual roots, the operationalisation of resilience in supply chain management emerged later and with different emphases, shaped by concerns about vulnerability, continuity, and disruption management in supply chain networks.

3.2 Definitions of Supply Chain Resilience

The first comprehensive definition of supply chain resilience was formulated by Christopher and Peck (2004). Table 3.2 provides a chronological presentation of the focus of definitions of supply chain resilience. It is very important to mention that all definitions unanimously defined supply chain resilience

as an ability/capability confronting a disruption. The manner in which entities respond to disruptions, and the objectives they achieve, vary across the supply chain.

Definitions of Supply Chain Resilience	Author
<i>“The ability of a system to return to its original state or move to a new, more desirable state after being disturbed” (p.4)</i>	Christopher and Peck (2004)
<i>“Supply chain resilience is defined as not only the ability to maintain control over performance variability in the face of disturbance, but also a property of being adaptive and capable of sustained response to sudden and significant shifts in the environment in the form of uncertain demands”(p.189)</i>	Datta et al., (2007)
<i>“The adaptive capability of the supply chain to prepare for unexpected events, respond to disruptions, and recover from them by maintaining continuity of operations at the desired level of connectedness and control over structure and function” (p.131)</i>	Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009)
<i>“Managing the risk of an uncertain future is a challenge that requires resilience, the ability to survive, adapt, and grow in the face of turbulent change” (p.46)</i>	Pettit et al., (2013)
<i>“Supply chain resilience is the supply chain’s ability to be prepared for unexpected risk events, responding and recovering quickly to potential disruptions to return to its original situation or grow by moving to a new, more desirable state in order to increase customer service, market share and financial performance” (p.108)</i>	Hohenstein et al., (2015)
<i>“The adaptive capability of a supply chain to prepare for and/or respond to disruptions, to make a timely and cost-effective recovery, and therefore progress to a post-disruption state of operations – ideally, a better state than prior to the disruption” (p.5599)</i>	Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015)

<p><i>“The adaptive capability of a supply chain to reduce the probability of facing sudden disturbances, resist the spread of disturbances by maintaining control over structures and functions, and recover and respond by immediate and effective reactive plans to transcend the disturbance and restore the supply chain to a robust state of operations”(p.121)</i></p>	<p>Kamalahmadi & Parast (2016)</p>
<p><i>“the characteristics of a well-designed supply chain network with proactive and reactive capabilities, which enables the supply chain members to reduce the probability of disruptive events (or to reduce their impact) to take the organization to a stronger and more sustainable state”(p.188)</i></p>	<p>Chowdhury and Quaddus (2017)</p>

Table 3.1 Supply Chain Resilience Definitions

While reviewing the literature, it has been revealed that a common key attribute among all definitions is Business Continuity. Initially the definitions of supply chain resilience focused on business continuity (Rice & Caniato, 2003; Christopher and Peck, 2004; Sheffi & Rice, 2005; Datta et al., 2007). The supply chain resilience definitions focused on the response and recovery phases of supply chain till 2007. Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009) presented a definition which included risk management as a key attribute along with Business Continuity. Moreover, an addition in the supply chain resilience phase was also witnessed. The proposed definition by Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009) added prepared phase in the supply chain resilience making the phases as preparedness, response and recovery. In 2010 (Pettit et al., 2010) presented a definition which focused on the phases of response, recovery and growth. It was until 2015 that Hohenstein et al., (2015) provided a definition which mentioned four phases of supply chain resilience as preparedness, response, recovery and growth. Alongside the key attributes of risk management and business continuity, new attributes of customer service, market share and financial performance were also introduced. Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Kamalahmadi & Parast (2016) also focused on the four phases of supply chain resilience and introduced attributes of timely and cost-effective recovery which implied agility. Hendry et al., (2019) mentioned that the first and only comprehensive definition of agricultural food supply chain resilience was proposed by Stone & Rahimifard (2018, p. 232) as "the collective ability of agri-food supply chain stakeholders to ensure acceptable, sufficient, and stable food supplies, at the required times and locations, via accurate anticipation of disruptions and the use of strategies which delay impact, aid rapid recovery, and allow cumulative learning post-disruption". This definition of AFSC resilience also focused

on the four phases of supply chain resilience with a key attribute of cumulative learning which implied collaboration among the supply chain stakeholders.

Early studies (e.g. Rice & Caniato, 2003; Christopher and Peck, 2004; Sheffi & Rice, 2005) predominantly conceptualised resilience as post-disruption recovery, implicitly aligning resilience with business continuity alone. However, later definitions represented in Table 3.1 (e.g. Ponomarov & Holcomb, 2009; Pettit et al., 2010; Hohenstein et al., 2015) incorporated preparedness alongside response and recovery. This demonstrates that risk management is an integral mechanism through which business continuity is achieved. Consequently, presenting risk management and business continuity as a combined attribute reflects the literature's shift from a reactive recovery-based view to a proactive capability-based understanding of supply chain resilience. This thesis adopts the definitions of supply chain resilience proposed by Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009) and Chowdhury and Quaddus (2017) because they align most closely with the research aim, empirical context, and analytical requirements of the study. Both definitions conceptualise supply chain resilience as an adaptive capability, rather than a static outcome, and explicitly incorporate preparedness, response, and recovery as integral phases of resilience.

Year	Prepare	Respond	Recover	Growth	Key Attributes
2003		Rice & Caniato	Rice & Caniato		Business Continuity
2004		Christoper & Peck	Christoper & Peck		Business Continuity
2005		Sheffi & Rice	Sheffi & Rice		Business Continuity
2007		Datta et. al	Datta et. al		Business Continuity
2009	Ponomarov & Holcomb	Ponomarov & Holcomb	Ponomarov & Holcomb		Risk Management & Business Continuity
2010		Pettit et.al	Pettit et.al	Pettit et.al	Risk Management & Business Continuity
2012	Ponis & Kronis	Ponis & Kronis	Ponis & Kronis		Risk Management, Business Continuity & Competitive Advantage
2013					
2014		Melnyk et.al	Melnyk et.al		Business Continuity
2015	Hohenstein et.al	Hohenstein et.al	Hohenstein et.al	Hohenstein et.al	Risk Management, Business Continuity, Customer service, Market Share and financial performance
2015	Ambulkar et al.	Ambulkar et al.	Ambulkar et.a.		Risk Management and Business Continuity
2015	Tukamuhabwa et.al	Tukamuhabwa et.al	Tukamuhabwa et.al	Tukamuhabwa et.al	Risk Management, Business Continuity, Timely and Cost effective recovery
2016	Chowdhury and Qudus	Chowdhury and Qudus	Chowdhury and Qudus		Risk Management & Business Continuity
2016	Kamalahmadi & Parast	Kamalahmadi & Parast	Kamalahmadi & Parast	Kamalahmadi & Parast	Risk Management , Business Continuity, immediate and effective recovery
2018	Stone & Rahimifard	Stone & Rahimifard	Stone & Rahimifard	Stone & Rahimifard	Risk Management ,Business Continuity, & Collaboration (cumulative learning)
2021	Wieland & Durach	Wieland & Durach	Wieland & Durach		Risk Management, Business Continuity

Table 3.2 Supply Chain Resilience Definitions based on Phases and Attributes

3.3 Applicability of Supply Chain Resilience Definitions

The definitions of Supply Chain Resilience (SCRE) included preparedness as a core phase alongside response and recovery (Ponomarov & Holcomb, 2009; Hohenstein et al., 2015); however, applying these definitions consistently across sectors remains challenging. High-impact disruptions, such as the cyber-attacks experienced by the University of Manchester and the University of the West of Scotland (BBC, 2023; BBC, 2023a), illustrate differences between how preparedness is defined conceptually and how it is realised in practice. In both cases, the institutions responded to the disruption and eventually recovered, thereby aligning with SCRE definitions that emphasise response and recovery. For example, the University

of Manchester required approximately 90 days to restore full operations following the cyber incident (Jisc, 2024).

The institutions responded and recovered from the disruption by falling into the supply chain resilience definitions, which cover only two phases, i.e. Response and Recovery. The core concept of resilience where in disruption is followed by response and recovery remains consistent across contexts and is applicable to both cases discussed. The purpose is to highlight that, although resilience definitions have progressed from a narrow focus on response and recovery towards the inclusion of preparedness, their practical applicability in real-world settings remains limited. The examples are used to illustrate that organisations may still be classified as resilient under existing definitions because recovery occurs, even when preparedness is insufficient to limit the severity or duration of disruption. Therefore, the variation in impact and recovery time does not contradict the concept of resilience itself but instead points to challenges in translating theoretically defined preparedness into effective operational capability in practice.

Although SCR definitions have evolved from recovery-focused business continuity to multi-phase capability perspectives of preparedness, response, recovery, growth, this stream remains conceptually plural and sector-generic. In agri-food contexts, the most comprehensive AFSC definition (Stone & Rahimifard, 2018) remains largely conceptual rather than empirically derived. This creates a definitional gap: AFSC resilience lacks an empirically grounded definition that reflects how resilience is enacted across agri-food actors in practice.

3.4 Supply Chain Resilience Drivers

Building on the conceptual evolution of supply chain resilience, a significant volume of research has identified specific drivers that underpin a system's ability to withstand and recover from disruptions. However, this body of work remains highly fragmented, with resilience drivers dispersed across diverse operational, relational, technological, and strategic domains. To address this lack of theoretical consolidation, this study synthesized 57 distinct drivers identified in the literature spanning 2004–2024. Rather than treating these drivers as isolated factors, they are organized here into four interrelated domains: operational–structural, relational–organisational, technological–strategic, and learning–adaptive.

3.5 Operational and Structural Drivers

Operational and structural drivers represent the foundational layer of supply chain resilience. These drivers enable supply chains to absorb shocks and maintain functionality through design, configuration, and resource deployment. As shown in Table 3.3, key operational drivers include agility, flexibility, velocity, visibility, redundancy, diversity, dispersion, inventory management, postponement, manufacturing versatility, and supply chain re-engineering. Agility and flexibility consistently emerge as dominant drivers

(Christopher and Peck, 2004; Jüttner & Maklan, 2011; Pettit et al., 2013; Ali & Golgeci, 2019). Agility refers to the speed of response to disruptions, while flexibility captures the ability to reconfigure sourcing, production, and distribution. These capabilities are underpinned by visibility and velocity, which enable real-time awareness and rapid execution across the supply chain (Brandon-Jones et al., 2014; Mandal et al., 2016). Redundancy and inventory buffers function as structural shock absorbers (Fiksel et al., 2015; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2018; Ali and Golgeci, 2019) while diversity and dispersion reduce dependency on single sources and geographic concentration (Carvalho et al., 2012; Pettit et al., 2013; Fiksel et al., 2015) supply chain re-engineering and critical path analysis further enable firms to identify pinch points and redesign networks with resilience as a core objective (Christopher and Peck, 2004; Blckhurst et al., 2011).

No.	Resilience Driver	Definition / Basis in Literature	Sources
1	Agility	The ability of a supply chain to react quickly to untoward situations, composed of velocity and visibility.	Christopher and Peck (2004); Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009); Ponis & Koronis (2012); Wieland & Wallenburg (2013); Hohenstein et al., (2015); Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Mandal et al., (2016); Ali & Golgeci (2019); Zhong et al., (2024)
2	Flexibility	The capability to adapt to disruptions by changing sourcing, production, or distribution according to changing market needs.	Christopher and Peck (2004); Sheffi & Rice (2005); Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009); Pettit et al., (2010); Jüttner & Maklan (2011); Pettit et al., (2013); Johnson et al., (2013); Pereira et al., (2014); Fiksel et al., (2015); Scholten & Schilder (2015); Hohenstein et al., (2015); Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Chowdhury & Quaddus (2016); Mandal et al., (2016); Brusset & Teller (2017); Ali & Golgeci (2019); Sa et al., (2020); Zhao et al., (2024); Zhong et al., (2024)
3	Velocity	The speed at which a supply chain can react to changes and the rapidity of its response.	Christopher and Peck (2004); Jüttner & Maklan (2011); Ponis & Koronis (2012); Johnson et al., (2013); Scholten & Schilder (2015); Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Mandal et al., (2016); Ali & Golgeci (2019).
4	Visibility	Real-time monitoring and shared access to accurate, timely information across the supply chain network.	Christopher and Peck (2004); Jüttner & Maklan (2011); Blackhurst et al., (2011); Ponis & Koronis (2012); Pettit et al., (2013); Johnson et al., (2013); Brandon-Jones et al., (2014); Pereira et al., (2014); Fiksel et al., (2015); Scholten & Schilder (2015); Hohenstein et al., (2015); Tukamuhabwa et al.,

			(2015); Dubey et al., (2016); Mandal et al., (2016); Ali & Golgeci (2019)
5	Redundancy	The use of backup resources, excess capacity, or safety stock to provide immediate protection.	Christopher and Peck (2004); Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009); Blackhurst et al., (2011); Ponis & Koronis (2012); Pettit et al., (2013); Pereira et al., (2014); Fiksel et al., (2015); Hohenstein et al., (2015); Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Chowdhury & Quaddus (2016); Stone & Rahimifard (2018); Ali & Golgeci (2019); Sa et al., (2020); Zhao et al., (2024); Zhong et al., (2024)
6	Diversity	Maintaining diverse resources, suppliers, and transportation routes to reduce single-source dependency.	Carvalho et al., (2012)
7	Dispersion	Geographic scattering of suppliers and facilities to minimize exposure to localized threats.	Pettit et al., (2010); Pettit et al., (2013); Fiksel et al., (2015)
8	Facility Fortification	Investing in physical protection and strengthening of major facilities to reduce disruption risks.	Ivanov (2017)
9	SC Re-engineering	Designing supply chains with resilience as a core objective, identifying critical paths and pinch points.	Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Chowdhury & Quaddus (2016); Ali & Golgeci (2019); Zhong et al., (2024)
10	Efficiency	The focus on control, speed, and waste reduction during normal operations.	Christopher & Rutherford (2004); Pettit et al., (2010); Fiksel et al., (2015); Chowdhury & Quaddus (2016)
11	Postponement	Strategies that delay product commitment or customization until closer to actual demand.	Stone & Rahimifard (2018); Ali et al., (2017)

12	Inventory Management	Maintaining safety stocks and buffers as shock absorbers.	Blackhurst et al., (2011); Ponis & Koronis (2012); Hohenstein et al., (2015); Zhao et al., (2024)
13	Structure Knowledge	Understanding the physical and informational interconnectedness of the supply network.	Hong & Choi (2002); Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009); Ponis & Koronis (2012); Pettit et al., (2013)
14	Logistics Capabilities	Advanced risk management and communication infrastructures supporting material flow continuity.	Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009); Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Mandal et al., (2016)
15	Critical Path Analysis	Identifying supply chain nodes or links that, if disrupted, have the most severe impact.	Christopher and Peck (2004)
16	Manufacturing Versatility	The ability to quickly adjust or switch manufacturing processes during a crisis.	Ali et al., (2017); Brusset & Teller (2017)
17	Flexible Sourcing	Rapidly switching suppliers or production schedules when disruptions occur.	Pettit et al., (2010); Fiksel et al., (2015)
18	Demand Management	Techniques like dynamic pricing to stabilize operations and minimize financial impacts.	Urciuoli et al., (2015)

Table 3.3 Operational and Structural Drivers

3.6 Relational and Organisational Drivers

Relational and organisational drivers reflect the social and institutional dimensions of resilience. As shown in Table 3.4, these drivers include collaboration, trust, social capital, leadership, cohesion, cooperation, information sharing, human resource management, security, government support, and financial strength. Collaboration is the most frequently cited relational driver (Christopher and Peck, 2004; Scholten & Schilder, 2015; Ali & Golgeci, 2019), enabling joint planning, shared risk management, and coordinated response. Trust and social capital further reinforce collaboration by reducing behavioural uncertainty and facilitating resource mobilisation (Johnson et al., 2013; Dubey et al., 2016).

Leadership and top management support shape organisational commitment to resilience, while government support and institutional interventions become particularly salient in agri-food contexts characterised by policy sensitivity (Zhao et al., 2024; Yuan et al., 2024). Human resource management enhances

preparedness through training, cross-functional teams, and employee readiness (Hohenstein et al., 2015; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015).

No.	Resilience Driver	Definition / Basis in Literature	Sources
1	Collaboration	Joint working, shared risk management, and coordinated response efforts.	Christopher and Peck (2004); Rice & Caniato (2003); Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009); Pettit et al., (2010); Jüttner & Maklan (2011); Ponis & Koronis (2012); Pettit et al., (2013); Johnson et al., (2013); Pereira et al., (2014); Fiksel et al., (2015); Scholten & Schilder (2015); Hohenstein et al., (2015); Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Mandal et al., (2016); Ali et al., (2017); Stone & Rahimifard (2018); Ali & Golgeci (2019); Sa et al., (2020); Zhao et al., (2024); Zhong et al., (2024)
2	Trust	Relational competency ensuring commitments are honored and facilitates risk-sharing.	Johnson et al., (2013); Dubey et al., (2016); Kamalahmadi & Parast (2016); Sa et al., (2020); Zhao et al., (2024)
3	Social Capital	The structural network ties, cognitive mutual understanding, and relational trust enabling resource mobilization.	Johnson et al., (2013); Ali et al., (2017); Henry & McMullen (2018)
4	Supplier Development	To improve supplier efficiency, commitment, and reliability by providing various incentives.	Leat and Revoredo-Giha (2013) Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015)
5	Risk Management Culture	Integrating risk awareness and proactive management into organizational strategic objectives.	Christopher and Peck (2004); Sheffi & Rice (2005); Blackhurst et al., (2011); Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Ali & Golgeci (2019); Ali et al., (2021)

6	Leadership	Board-level governance and the role of management in mitigating biological and supply risks.	Christopher and Peck (2004); Pettit et al., (2010); Zhao et al., (2022); Zhong et al., (2024)
7	Government Support	Institutional aid through monetary support, tax benefits, and subsidies to strengthen sectoral survival.	Zhao et al., (2024); Zhong et al., (2024); Yuan (2024)
8	Cohesion	The strength of relationships among supply chain partners for a unified approach to disruptions.	Carvalho et al., (2012); Stone & Rahimifard (2018)
9	Cooperation	Mutual commitment among partners to cultivate reliability and coordinate resources during crises.	Wieland & Wallenburg (2013); Dubey et al., (2016)
10	Information Sharing	Accurate, timely exchange of shared access to actionable data among stakeholders.	Christopher and Peck (2004); Pereira et al., (2014); Dubey et al., (2016); Zhong et al., (2024)
11	Human Resource Management	Training, cross-functional teams, and cross-trained workforces enhancing employee readiness.	Hohenstein et al., (2015); Ali & Golgeci (2019)
12	Security	Strategies aimed at safeguarding against cyber threats and physical breaches	Pettit et al., (2010); Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Yang & Hsu (2018)
13	Financial Strength	Diversified portfolios and access to funds allowing organizations to absorb shocks.	Pettit et al., (2010); Pettit et al., (2013); Fiksel et al., (2015); Chowdhury & Quaddus (2016)
14	Coopetition	Simultaneous cooperation and competition between firms to enhance collective sectoral resilience.	Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015) ; Ali & Golgeci (2019)
15	Social Self-regulation	connectivity, response diversity, careful exposure to disturbance, reflective and shared learning, autonomy and reasonable profitability	Perrin & Martin (2021)

16	Appropriate Supplier Selection	Evaluating suppliers based on stability, reliability, and technological adaptability.	Christopher and Peck, 2004; Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015)
17	Market Position	Market share, Product differentiation, financial strength, brand equity, customer loyalty, customer relationships.	Pettit et al., (2010); Pettit et al., (2013); Fiksel et al., (2015); Ali et al., (2017)
18	Top Management Support	Commitment from leadership to prioritize and fund resilience initiatives.	Ali & Golgeci (2019)
19	Relational Competency	The ability to maintain high-quality communication and cooperation to build agility.	Wieland & Wallenburg (2013); Dubey et al., (2016)
20	Shared Cognition	Fostering mutual understanding through shared codes, language, and narratives.	Johnson et al., (2013)
21	Robustness	The capacity to endure disruptions without requiring major adjustments.	Christopher & Rutherford (2004); Brandon-Jones et al., (2014); Wieland & Wallenburg (2013); Dubey et al., (2016); Zhong et al., (2024)

Table 3.4 Relational and Organisational Drivers

3.7 Technological, Strategic and Learning Drivers

The third domain captures technological, strategic, and learning-oriented drivers. These include traceability, blockchain, big data and AI, Industry 4.0, innovativeness, resource reconfiguration, preparedness, contingency planning, adaptive learning, disruption mitigation, additive manufacturing, and knowledge management. Recent literature shows a marked shift toward digitalisation and anticipatory capabilities (Ali & Govindan, 2023; Zhong et al., 2024). Big data analytics, blockchain, and traceability enhance visibility and transparency, enabling early detection of risks. Resource reconfiguration and adaptive learning reflect dynamic capability processes through which supply chains sense, seize, and reconfigure in response to disruptions (Ambulkar et al., 2015; Ali & Golgeci, 2019).

No.	Resilience Driver	Definition / Basis in Literature	Sources
1	Traceability	Tracking and tracing down stream and upstream sources to reduce risk exposure.	Sarpong (2014); Ringsberg (2014); Zhao et al., (2022); Zhao et al., (2024)
2	Blockchain	Secure, transparent data exchange that improves AFSC transparency.	Zhao et al., (2022); Ali & Govindan (2023); Zhao et al., (2024)
3	Big Data / AI	Digital tools used for real-time monitoring and predictive visibility.	Ali & Golgeci (2019); Ali & Govindan (2023); Zhong et al., (2024)
4	Industry 4.0	Technologies like IoT used as resources to mitigate supply chain risks.	Ali & Golgeci (2019); Ali & Govindan (2023)
5	Innovativeness	Dynamic capability reflecting a firm's openness to adopting new ideas or processes.	Golgeci & Ponomarov (2013); Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015); Zhao et al., (2022); Zhong et al., (2024)
6	Resource Reconfiguration	The dynamic ability to adjust and reorganize resources to manage disruptions.	Ambulkar et al., (2015); Ali & Golgeci (2019); Zhong et al., (2024)
7	Preparedness	Strategic phase of anticipation and prevention before disruptions occur.	Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009); Hohenstein et al., (2015); Ali & Golgeci (2019)
8	Contingency Plans	Predefined protocols providing structured responses to minimize halts.	Blackhurst et al., (2011); Hohenstein et al., (2015); Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015)
9	Anticipation	Proactive capability for identifying potential events before they impact function.	Pettit et al., (2010); Pettit et al., (2013); Fiksel et al., (2015); Stone & Rahimifard (2018).
10	Adaptability	The capacity of a supply chain to remain flexible and evolve under challenges.	Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009); Pettit et al., (2010); Carvalho et al., (2012); Zhong et al., (2024)

11	Adaptive Learning	Systemic learning and reorganization after post-disruption reflection.	Stone & Rahimifard (2018); Sa et al., (2020)
12	Innovation Magnitude	The scale or impact of the innovative response to a severe disruption.	Golgeci & Ponomarov (2013)
13	SCDO (Supply chain disruption orientation)	Proactive mindset for an ongoing effort to anticipate and learn from disruptions.	Ambulkar et al., (2015); Yu et al., (2019)
14	Disruption Mitigation	Proactive strategies aimed at building a foundation to prevent disruptions.	Fiksel et al., (2015); Ali & Golgeci (2019); Zhong et al., (2024)
15	Additive Manufacturing	Technical ability to utilize novel production for rebound and recovery.	Ali & Golgeci (2019) ;(Ivanov, Dolgui and Sokolov, 2019)
16	Readiness	Proactive measures ensuring the supply chain is equipped to handle risks.	Chowdhury & Quaddus (2016)
17	Response	Timely and effective reactions to supply chain events to mitigate impacts.	Chowdhury & Quaddus (2016)
18	Knowledge Management	Enhancing future resilience by drawing lessons from past disruptions.	Mehfooz et al., (2017); Ali et al., (2021); Zhao et al., (2024)

Table 3.5 Technological, Strategic and Learning Drivers

This diversity of supply chain resilience drivers reflects the multifaceted nature of supply chain resilience, emphasising the interplay between operational efficiency, risk management, technological advancements, and strategic planning. The diversity of drivers also underscores the complexity of building resilient supply chains.

3.8 Agri-Food System Resilience

The UK food system faces significant vulnerabilities due to its reliance on global supply chains, environmental stresses, and socio-economic inequalities (DEFRA 2025). Nearly half of its food is imported, making it highly susceptible to geopolitical disruptions, trade policy changes, and external shocks like extreme weather and pandemics. For example, COVID-19 disrupted seafood trade, highlighting the fragility of global interdependencies (Zurek et al., 2022).

Tendall et al., (2015) provided a pivotal contribution by defining food system resilience as the capacity of a food system and its components, operating at multiple levels, to ensure sufficient, appropriate, and accessible food over time, even in the face of various unforeseen disturbances. This definition emphasises the dynamic and holistic nature of resilience, integrating the social, economic, and biophysical processes within food systems. The authors tie resilience explicitly to the functional goal of food security, thereby aligning it with sustainability by ensuring positive social and environmental outcomes. The approach excludes resilience that perpetuates undesirable outcomes, such as food insecurity or environmental degradation, positioning resilience as a tool to complement sustainability.

The work of (Tendall et al., 2015) builds on foundational theories of resilience from multiple disciplines. Key influences include Holling's (1973) ecological perspective on resilience, which examines a system's capacity to absorb disturbances and maintain function, and subsequent work on social-ecological systems by Adger (2000) and Folke et al., (2010). Additionally, the authors integrate insights from food system frameworks proposed by Ericksen (2008), which explored the interactions between food production, processing/packaging, distribution, and consumption, and their determinants and outcomes. Their work also mentioned Barrett and Constanas (2014), who emphasised resilience as a means to ensure human well being.

Tendall et al., (2015) identified several drivers affecting food system resilience as challenges. These include environmental changes such as climate variability, soil degradation, and pest outbreaks; socio-economic pressures like political instability, economic crises, and population growth and evolving consumer behaviours, including increased demand for meat and organic products. The authors highlighted the potential of resilience to capitalise on disturbances as opportunities for learning and improvement. This proactive stance is illustrated through the food system resilience action cycle, which encompasses capacities for robustness, redundancy, adaptability, flexibility, and learning, enabling continuous development and minimisation of food insecurity under dynamic conditions.

Stone and Rahimifard (2018, p.232) provided a comprehensive definition of agri-food supply chain (AFSC) resilience, positioning it as a systems-oriented approach to ensuring food security. They defined AFSC resilience as "the collective ability of agri-food supply chain stakeholders to ensure acceptable, sufficient,

and stable food supplies, at the required times and locations, via accurate anticipation of disruptions and the use of strategies which delay impact, aid rapid recovery, and allow cumulative learning post-disruption”.

The authors presented a comprehensive framework based on a systematic review that conceptualised resilience in agri-food supply chains (AFSCs). The framework separates organisational resilience and supply chain resilience, focusing on four distinct phases of readiness, response, recovery, and adaptive strategies. The first three phases are adopted from the research done by (Ponomarov & Holcomb 2009), and the fourth phase, growth, is adopted from the study conducted by (Hohenstein et al.,2015). Each phase incorporates specific core elements that directly enable resilience and are supported by complementary mechanisms to enhance the effectiveness of these elements. From the supply chain resilience perspective the readiness phase emphasised on the proactive measures to prepare for potential disruptions, ensuring the supply chain is equipped to handle risks before they occur. The first core element of readiness is redundancy (Ponis and Koronis 2012; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015) which refers to the existence of distributed resources such as alternative suppliers, multiple production sites, and backup transportation routes. Redundancy provides a buffer against disruptions by allowing operations to continue even if a critical part of the supply chain fails. The second core element, flexibility (Pettit et al.,2013; Tendall et al.,2015), which ensures that the supply chain can adapt dynamically to changing circumstances. Flexibility enables supply chain actors to reconfigure operations, switch suppliers, or adjust logistics in real time to mitigate risks. According to the authors, redundancy and flexibility can establish a robust readiness framework, allowing supply chains to remain operational under various scenarios of uncertainty. These core elements are enhanced by supporting mechanisms. Established communication channels (Hohenstein et al., 2015) and bargaining power (Durach et al., 2015) facilitate pre-disruption coordination among stakeholders, ensuring that all actors are prepared to act collaboratively. A risk management orientation fosters (Christopher and Peck 2004) a proactive culture of identifying and mitigating risks before they escalate. Additionally, maintaining buffer capacity (Hohenstein et al., 2015; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015), such as extra inventory or storage space, serves as a safety net to absorb shocks and minimise their impact on operations. These supporting elements collectively strengthen the supply chain’s ability to anticipate and prepare for disruptions effectively.

According to the authors, the response phase addresses the immediate actions required to mitigate the impact of disruptions. The first core element in this phase is collaboration (Hohenstein et al., 2015; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015), which highlights the importance of trust-based relationships among stakeholders. Collaboration (Christopher and Peck 2004; Johnson et al., 2013; Kamalahamadi & Parsat 2016) enables the efficient sharing of resources, Information, and responsibilities during a disruption, ensuring a unified and coordinated response across the supply chain. The second core element, visibility

(Pettit et al., 2013; Johnson et al., 2013; Pereira et al., 2014) refers to the ability of supply chain actors to access real-time data and monitor processes transparently. Visibility ensures that stakeholders are informed about the nature and scope of disruptions, enabling them to make timely and accurate decisions to minimise impacts. The authors proposed the combination of collaboration and visibility is essential in maintaining continuity during a crisis by reducing inefficiencies and delays in response efforts. Supporting these core elements are information flow and cohesion (Carvahlo et al., 2012) and trust (Kamalahmadi and Parast 2016), which enhance the effectiveness of response actions. Smooth information flow (Pereira et al., 2014) ensures that critical updates are communicated seamlessly across the supply chain, while cohesion and trust foster a cooperative environment where stakeholders prioritise collective resilience over individual gains. The authors implied that by leveraging these cores and supporting elements, the response phase ensures that disruptions are managed swiftly and effectively, minimising immediate risks to supply chain operations.

The recovery phase focuses on restoring supply chain functionality after a disruption. The sole core element for this phase is agility (Christopher and Peck 2004), which emphasises the ability of the supply chain to reconfigure its operations quickly and efficiently to resume normal functionality. The authors highlighted that in agri-food supply chains, where perishability and time sensitivity are significant concerns, agility is critical for ensuring that food supplies are maintained despite disruptions. Supporting agility are mechanisms that enhance its application during recovery. For instance, the authors have mentioned velocity as a supporting element of agility. The recovery phase underscores the need for quick reorganisation and adaptation to minimise the consequences of disruptions and maintain supply chain stability.

The adaptive strategy focuses on the long-term evolution of supply chains by incorporating learning and transformation into resilience-building efforts. The core element of this phase is adaptability, which involves the supply chain's ability to undergo structural and operational changes in response to evolving risks and challenges. Adaptability (Pettit et al., 2010) is supported by mechanisms that encourage systemic learning and reorganisation. Co-learning and self-organisation enable supply chain actors to reflect on past disruptions, share insights, and collaboratively develop innovative solutions. This fosters a culture of continuous improvement, where stakeholders proactively address vulnerabilities. The authors implied that the adaptive phase ensures that resilience is dynamic and forward-looking, enabling supply chains to thrive in an uncertain and volatile environment.

Stone and Rahimifard (2018) developed a conceptual framework emphasising the importance of aligning core and supporting elements across four key phases of readiness, response, recovery, and adaptive strategies. This framework highlights the importance of systemic and collaborative approaches to resilience

in ensuring the stability and functionality of agri-food supply chains in an increasingly complex global environment, but it lacks empirical evidence.

Ali et al., (2018) explored the resilient factors for the Australian Food Supply chain of perishable product citrus. The authors concluded that business certification as an important factor for achieving resilience in the cold supply chain. A cross-trained workforce also contributes to the resilience of the agri-foods supply chain in the Australian Citrus industry. The authors proposed the adoption of continuous improvement processes, buyer-supplier integration and quality tests before delivery to enhance the resilience in the supply chain of the small and medium enterprises in the Australian agri-food supply chain.

Hendry et al., (2019) investigated how local agri-food supply chains (AFSCs) in the UK are building resilience in response to constitutional changes, particularly Brexit. Using a dynamic capabilities framework, the research explored how supply chain actors prepare for and adapt to Brexit-induced challenges and opportunities through sensing, seizing, and transforming processes.

The findings emphasised the importance of collaboration across supply chain tiers, including vertical and horizontal partnerships, to anticipate disruptions and shape future strategies. In the sensing phase, participants identified threats such as uncertainty around subsidies, labour shortages, and trade disruptions, alongside opportunities like increased demand for local food. The seizing phase revealed proactive responses, such as diversifying production and creating new market channels. The transforming phase showed firms reconfiguring their resources and relationships to improve resilience. The study concluded that resilience-building in the face of constitutional change requires collaboration among supply chain stakeholders. This work is one of the first empirical studies examining supply chain resilience in the context of constitutional change and offers valuable insights for both practice and policy.

Aboah et al., (2019) explored the concept of resilience in agricultural supply chains, particularly focusing on tropical commodities like cocoa and coffee. The authors argued that traditional supply chain management literature often overlooks the upstream, raw material production side of the chain, where disruptions can significantly impact the entire system. The authors identified key elements of resilience as flexibility, collaboration, resourcefulness, and adaptability.

Sa et al., (2020) explored supply chain resilience (SCRES) within agri-food supply chains (AFSCs), focusing on the sugarcane and orange supply chains during an extreme drought in Brazil. The study underscores that resilience is not merely the sum of resilience at individual nodes but rather depends on the interconnectedness and interplay of resilience strategies across all stages of the supply chain. Through 41 in-depth interviews with farmers, processors, and manufacturers, the study identified flexibility, redundancy, collaboration, visibility, and adaptive learning as critical resilience drivers.

Flexibility emerged as a key driver of supply chain resilience, enabling processors and manufacturers to adapt their operations in response to the disruption. For instance, sugarcane mills implemented closed-circuit systems for water reuse, while manufacturers reduced water consumption and secured alternative suppliers to mitigate supply shortages. Flexibility proved particularly effective during the response phase, as it allowed firms to adjust quickly to unforeseen challenges and maintain continuity in their operations.

Redundancy (Ponis and Kronis 2012 ; Pettit et al., 2013) was another significant resilience driver identified in the study. Non-integrated processors relied on multi-sourcing and geographic diversification to access alternative suppliers, while integrated processors benefited from proprietary farms spread across various regions. This redundancy minimised the impact of supply shortages and ensured operational continuity during the disruption. The authors emphasised that redundancy plays a critical role in mitigating risks by providing alternative options, particularly in highly uncertain environments.

In the orange supply chain, cooperatives supported vertical collaboration by providing farmers with training and resources for irrigation and crop management. However, overall collaboration between farmers, processors, and manufacturers was fragmented. The lack of interfirm trust and coordinated efforts hindered the effectiveness of resilience strategies. This finding highlights the importance of fostering collaboration across supply chain partners to build collective resilience.

The study also revealed a notable absence of visibility in the supply chains, with limited information sharing among stakeholders. Farmers and processors lacked access to real-time data and weather forecasts, which diminished their preparedness for the drought. Visibility (Pettit et al., 2013) is a critical driver of supply chain resilience as it enables early detection of disruptions and facilitates coordinated responses. The authors underscored that enhancing visibility through improved information-sharing mechanisms is essential for building robust and resilient supply chains.

Finally, adaptive learning was observed in some processors and manufacturers who viewed the drought as an opportunity for improvement. These firms invested in new technologies, such as advanced crop management systems and water conservation projects, to enhance their resilience to future disruptions. However, adaptive learning was less prevalent among farmers, who perceived extreme events as rare and did not prioritise long-term resilience investments. In conclusion, Sa et al., (2020) provided valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of resilience in AFSCs. While flexibility and redundancy were effective in mitigating immediate impacts, the lack of visibility and limited collaboration undermined overall resilience. The findings highlight the importance of coordinated efforts across supply chain nodes and tailored resilience strategies that consider the unique contexts of each supply chain. Additionally, fostering

trust, improving information-sharing mechanisms, and promoting adaptive learning is essential for enhancing supply chain resilience in the face of increasing uncertainties.

Ali et al., (2021) explored agri-supply chain resilience in Australia by recruiting senior managers from the Australian food supply chain. The authors used multiple constructs of supply chain risks, knowledge management, knowledge acquisition, and Knowledge assimilation. The authors analysed how knowledge management leads to a risk management culture, consequently leading to a resilient supply chain. The authors concluded that knowledge application is positively associated with risk management culture, and this risk management culture is positively associated with supply chain resilience.

Zhao G et al., (2022) developed a one-to-one resilience risk framework for agri-food supply chain resilience by matching the capability factor against the risks mitigated by the identified capability. The study conducted employed a systematic literature review and performed a thematic analysis for analysis and synthesis. The study identified eight categories of AFSC risks, including supply, demand, financial, biological, environmental, weather-related, management, operational, logistical, infrastructural, policy, and regulatory risks. The study also identified seven key AFSC resilience capabilities, including supply chain collaboration, traceability, innovation, knowledge management, redundancy, leadership, and flexibility. The authors mentioned that supply chain collaboration reduces supply risk, demand risk, financial Risk and weather-related risk. Traceability capability reduces supply risk, demand risk, biological and environmental risk and logistical and infrastructure risk. Innovation reduces supply, weather related and logistical and infrastructure risk. Knowledge Management reduces biological and environmental risk, demand risk and management and operational risk. Redundancy reduces demand risk, biological and environmental risk, weather-related risk and policy and regulatory risk. Leadership mitigates biological and environmental risk and supply risk. Flexibility reduces biological and environmental risk and weather-related risk.

Payne-Gifford et al., (2022) examined the disruptions in British beef and sheep supply chains during the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors concluded that overall, the British beef and sheep supply chain remained resilient against the novel disruption of COVID-19 and suggested that any part of the supply chain should not be shut during a future crisis like this for instance the food service was shut. However, the authors mentioned that consumers' meat consumption increased during the lockdown. The authors explained that the farming operations were not much impacted, the processors faced a plant shut to due to disease outbreak among workers, the auction markets witnessed panic selling before the lock down but regained momentum after a temporary shut down and after reopening with social distancing measures in place. The retailers were also managed to keep their shelves filled with the red meat. The authors did not mention what led to

the resilience of the supply chain. It can be inferred from the research that for the livestock farmers the flexibility played a key role.

Zhao G et al., (2024) studied the agri supply chain resilience in a cross-cultural supply chain of China and Spain in relation to the COVID-19 crisis. The authors revealed that the recovery of agri supply chain resilience also depends on the nations' Cultural and value orientations. The authors proposed that for Spain's Agri-food supply chain resilience try to be more Agile, Flexible, Collaborative and Transparent. For China, the authors proposed improving the government's role by simplifying the complex policy. The study identified collaboration, redundancy, flexibility, leadership and innovation as the agri supply chain resilience capability factors.

Zhong, Cheng and Jia (2024) used expert consultations to authenticate their findings on the agri food supply chain resilience capability factors and identified 15 agri food supply chain resilience capability factors in China. The two most important capability factors emphasised by the authors were the role of leadership and government support. The key factors were classified as Supply chain collaboration, information sharing and leadership. These capability factors were termed to be having low dependence on other capability factors. The other capability factors included Supply chain innovation, Visibility, Supply chain Redesign, Flexibility, agility, government support, disruption mitigation, adaption, resource reconfiguration, robustness and redundancy.

3.8.1 Agricultural Food Supply Chain Resilience Drivers

The key agri supply chain drivers are discussed below

3.8.1.1 Collaboration

Collaboration is recognised as a intra supply chain capability referred to joint working of two or more supply chain players and could be shared forecasting, postponement and risk sharing, shared forecasting, postponement and risk sharing. Cooperation and partnership, aim of reducing uncertainties and complexity and integration of systems (Stone and Rahimifard 2018). Aboah et al., (2019) proposed collaboration as an agriculture supply chain resilience based on citation analysis of the supply chain resilience literature and emphasised on the motivation of supply chain players to work together to mitigate disruptions. Kumar and Kumar (2022) studied the impact of COVID19 on the agricultural food supply chain and concluded that collaboration is one of key supply chain resilient capability factor to control the impact of the pandemic. Sa et al., (2020) explored supply chain resilience (SCRES) within agri-food supply chains (AFSCs), focusing on the sugarcane and orange supply chains during an extreme drought in Brazil and concluded that there was no collaboration among nodes in the supply chain. Zhao G (2024) investigated the agri food supply chain resilience of China and Spain to explore the resilience factors amid COVID-19 . The authors

concluded that the in Spain low level of collaboration was witnessed in the supply chain and proposed to improve the level of collaboration. Likewise, the authors mentioned limited collaboration in the supply chain in the response and recovery stage. Although Collaboration is seen as a key supply chain resilience capability factor in the supply chain (Hohenstein et al.,2015; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015) however, in the empirical literature on agri-food supply chain resilience, low levels of collaboration are witnessed.

Strategies	Articles and Publications								
	Stone and Rahimifard (2018)	Aboah et al. (2019)	Perrin and Martin (2021)	Hendry et al (2019)	Zhong et al. (2024)	(Zhao et al., 2024)	(Zhao et al., 2023)	(Yuan et al., 2024)	Kumar and Kumar (2022)
Collaboration	✓	✓			✓	✓			✓
Flexibility	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓			
Agility	✓		✓		✓			✓	
Visibility	✓		✓		✓				
Adaptability	✓	✓			✓				
Redundancy	✓		✓		✓	✓		✓	
Resourcefulness		✓							
Information sharing			✓		✓		✓	✓	✓
Government support				✓	✓		✓	✓	
Risk assessment				✓					
Supply chain relationships				✓					
Diversification				✓				✓	
Resilience culture					✓				
SC Innovation					✓	✓			
SC Leadership					✓	✓			
Robustness					✓				
Resource reconfiguration					✓				
Disruption mitigation					✓				
SC redesign					✓				
Traceability						✓			
Knowledge management						✓		✓	
Collectiveness and sense making							✓		
Accredited suppliers							✓		
Financial resource sharing							✓		
Joint purchases							✓		
Resource Integration								✓	
Contingency plans								✓	
Transparency								✓	
Predictive capacity								✓	
Continous learning								✓	
SC networks								✓	
Resource sharing									✓
Coordination between the stakeholders									✓
Digitisation of the processes									✓

Table 3.6 Agri-Food Supply Chain Resilience Drivers

3.8.1.2 Flexibility

The importance of flexibility was emphasised in the initial framework proposed by Christopher and Peck (2004) as it enables the supply chain to move to a desired state, which may be better than the original one after bouncing back from the disruption. Ali & Golgeci (2019) referred to flexibility as the ability to change according to the changing needs of the market demand. Flexibility has been viewed from different angles in the literature, Ivanov (2017) viewed flexibility as a capability originating from multiple sourcing and by having process flexibility. Mandal et al., (2016) proposed that collaboration and visibility lead to flexibility. Chowdhury and Quaddus (2016) mentioned flexibility in production, sourcing, and distribution. Bruce and

Teller (2017) emphasised that flexibility originates from contingency planning and production processes. In Agriculture food supply chain resilience flexibility is identified as a readiness phase capability (Stone and Rahimifard, 2018). Aboah et al., (2019) classified flexibility as a capability factor into readiness and response phase and mentioned that flexibility can be achieved through investment and by securing necessary raw materials to sustain operational continuity. Sa et al., (2020) identified Flexibility as response phase capability factor adopted by the processors and manufacturers during the extreme drought in Brazil in 2014-2015. Zhong, Cheng and Jia (2024) used expert consultations to authenticate their findings on the agri-food supply chain resilience capability factors and concluded that flexibility leads to agility and improves collaboration among the supply chain members. Perrin and Martin (2021) provided strong evidence of resilience among French organic dairy cattle farms and their supply chains during the COVID-19 pandemic. Most farms experienced little to moderate disruption, and supply chains effectively continued to meet consumer demand. The key resilience factors were identified as autonomy, social self-regulation, connectivity, local interdependence agility and flexibility in quickly and cost-effectively reorganising around a simplified product range. The literature shows that flexibility can be achieved in products, processes and sourcing. However, there are studies which also imply that flexibility leads to agility and collaboration (Zhong, Cheng and Jia, 2024) and collaboration and visibility leads to flexibility (Mandal et al., 2016). It is quite interesting that Zhong, Cheng, and Jia (2024) emphasise flexibility as an originating point by suggesting it is a core capability that drives agility and collaboration, whereas Mandal et al., (2016) positioned flexibility as an outcome, arguing it is enabled by pre-existing collaboration and visibility

3.8.1.3 Agility

Agility is also a very highly recognised supply chain resilience capability factor. It was explained as the ability to quickly react to untoward situations by Christopher and Peck (2004) in the initial framework of resilient supply chain. The authors concluded that agility is composed of velocity and visibility. Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009) proposed agility as a response capability factor for resilience. Ponis and Kronis (2012) mentioned that flexibility and velocity are the antecedents of agility. Wieland and Wallenburg (2013) described agility as the visibility and speed. Pereira et al., (2014) analysed the role of procurement in building supply chain resilience (SCR) and identified agility and visibility as separate resilience drivers. Hohenstein et al., (2015) described agility as being composed of velocity, visibility and quick supply chain redesign. Aboah et al., (2019) mentioned that flexibility and agility are used interchangeably and the author focused on flexibility as an agri supply chain resilience contributor. Stone and Rahimifard (2018) proposed that agility is composed of velocity, rapidness and responsiveness and identified as a recovery strategy in the agri supply chain resilience. Zhong, Cheng and Jia (2024) proposed that flexibility is a prerequisite of agility in agri food supply chain resilience. This shows the diverse findings on what exactly agility is? If

we take a holistic approach in describing agility based on the research literature, it can be said that agility is the speed of response or recovery.

3.8.1.4 Redundancy

Redundancy is a highly acknowledged resilience driver. It is mentioned by different names by the researcher for instance Christopher and Peck (2004) used surplus capacity to describe it. Blackhurst et al., (2011) used the word Safety stock as a resilience enhancer. Fiksel et al., (2015) used the phrase of reserve capacity, Chowdhury and Quaddus (2016) mentioned redundancy as proactive resilience capability. Ali and Golgeci (2019) defined redundancy as keeping excess capacity and backup system to reduce the likely impact of potential disruption. In Agriculture supply chain resilience (Stone and Rahimifard 2018) mentioned redundancy as a resilience driver in the preparedness phase. Zhao G (2024) investigated the agri food supply chain resilience of China and Spain to explore the resilience factors amid COVID-19. The authors found safety stock as a capability factor in the preparedness phase for the organisational resilience in both Countries China and Spain. The authors propose that the AFSC companies with safety stock would serve the customers in short time and achieve higher turnovers. Zhong, Cheng and Jia (2024) found that redundancy leads to supply chain robustness. Overall, the redundancy is a capability factor, but Christopher and Peck (2004) mentioned that there should be a balance between redundancy and efficiency because the funds have to be tied up in buffer stock.

3.8.1.5 Government Support

Government support is also a resilient capability factor in Agri foods supply chains. Zhao G (2024) investigated the agri food supply chain resilience of China and Spain to explore the resilience factors amid COVID-19. The authors revealed that Government aids as a contributing factor for resilient agri supply chain both in China and Spain's agri food supply chain in during the response and recovery phase of supply chain. Zhong, Cheng and Jia (2024) emphasised that government support can enhance redundancy, robustness, adaption and disruption mitigation. Yuan (2024) highlighted the importance of government support in a resilient agri food supply chain and proposed that monetary support, tax benefits and subsidies will strengthen the agrifood supply chain resilience.

3.8.1.6 Traceability

Schwägele (2005) mentioned that traceability consists of two primary functions tracking and tracing. Tracking refers to the ability to monitor the journey of an item as it progresses through the supply chain, from its origin to its destination. In contrast, tracing involves identifying the source of an item or batch by reviewing upstream records within the supply chain. Sarpong (2014) mentioned that the horsemeat scandal of Tesco shook Consumer confidence and highlighted the irregularities in the regulation of food safety. The

author concluded that the traceability systems can reduce the risk exposure of the organisations. Ringsberg (2014) identifies four key approaches to managing food traceability, including logistics, information, production, and quality management, emphasising the importance of transparency and the unique identification of goods to prevent food safety failures.

Zhao G et al., (2022) developed a one-to-one resilience risk framework for agri food supply chain resilience by matching the capability factor against the risks mitigated by the identified capability. The authors proposed that traceability capability reduces supply risk, demand risk, biological and environmental risk and logistical and infrastructure risk. The study also proposed the use of blockchain technology in the agri foods supply chain to improve traceability to be resilient. Therefore, traceability is key resilient factor in agri food supply chain.

3.9 Limitations of Supply Chain Resilience Drivers

Despite the supply chain resilience drivers identified in the literature, it is important to consider the limitations of the drivers to develop a resilient supply chain.

Traceability (Sarpong, 2014; Ringsberg, 2014; Zhao et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2024) has been widely recognised as a critical supply chain resilience driver, enabling enhanced visibility, transparency, and monitoring across the supply chain. However, its practical implementation is often challenged by financial constraints faced by many actors within the supply chain, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which lack the necessary capital to invest in traceability infrastructure and technologies (Razak et al., 2023). This financial burden limits widespread adoption and restricts the full potential of traceability systems to support resilience-building efforts.

Similarly, transparency (Zhao et al., 2024; Yuan et al., 2024) another essential resilience driver faces operational challenges, particularly due to insufficient information sharing among supply chain partners. A significant barrier to achieving transparency is the lack of confidence in data security protocols. Concerns regarding data misuse or breaches reduce the willingness of firms to share information, thereby limiting collaborative efforts and slowing response times during disruptions (Holloway, 2025). The absence of secure and trusted communication platforms hinders coordinated action and restricts the development of collective resilience capabilities (Dwivedi et al., 2023).

Drivers related to operational redundancy, such as buffer stock, safety stock, and inventory management (Stone & Rahimifard, 2018; Ali & Golgeci, 2019; Sa et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2024) also play an important role in mitigating the impact of disruptions. Nevertheless, these strategies often conflict with lean operational principles, which aim to minimise waste and reduce excess inventory. The resulting trade-off

between efficiency and resilience creates strategic dilemmas for firms, particularly those operating under cost constraints or lean manufacturing models (Yang et al., 2024).

Supplier selection (Christopher and Peck, 2004; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015) while recognised as an important aspect of supply chain resilience, continues to face challenges rooted in traditional procurement criteria. Most supplier selection frameworks prioritise factors such as price, quality, delivery, and service (Fallahpour, 2021). Failures at the supplier level have the potential to impact both the top-line revenue and the overall cost structure across the complete supply chain (Craighead et al., 2007; Ali and Golgeci, 2019) Agility (Wieland & Wallenburg, 2013; Hohenstein et al., 2015; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015); Mandal et al., (2016); Ali & Golgeci, 2019; Zhong et al., 2024) regarded as a core resilience capability, enables supply chains to adapt quickly to changes and disruptions. However, to establish an agile supply chain, firms must navigate the inherent trade-off between agility and lean practices. Balancing the need for flexibility with the goal of operational efficiency remains a key challenge, particularly in industries that prioritise cost minimisation (Shi, 2024).

Collaboration (Ali et al., 2017; Stone & Rahimifard, 2018); Ali & Golgeci (2019); Sa et al., (2020); Zhao et al., (2024); Zhong et al., (2024) another extensively studied resilience driver, is critical for enabling coordinated responses and resource sharing during disruptions. However, collaboration efforts are often constrained by several factors. It can introduce additional risks, particularly through the exchange of sensitive information (Jüttner and Maklan, 2011). A lack of trust, insufficient financial resources, and an absence of strategic alignment among supply chain partners hinder the establishment of collaborative mechanisms. Additionally, without adequate transparency, it becomes difficult to identify potential risks and disruptions, further weakening collaborative capacity (Dwivedi et al., 2023).

Risk mitigation (Ali et al., 2017) while central to resilience planning, is similarly constrained by the difficulty of selecting the most appropriate strategies. Organisations must carefully evaluate the trade-off between investing in preparedness for hypothetical or unlikely events and underpreparing for disruptions that were not anticipated. This uncertainty complicates the decision-making process and often results in suboptimal allocation of resilience resources (Bret et al., 2021).

In summary, although the literature has identified a comprehensive set of supply chain resilience drivers, their effectiveness is contingent on various contextual, operational, and financial factors. Attempts to strengthen one dimension of resilience by targeting a specific antecedent may inadvertently weaken other dimensions through unintended effects on other antecedents (Hohenstein et al., 2015). Recognising and addressing these limitations is essential for developing tailored and effective resilience strategies.

3.10 Theoretical Frameworks used in Supply Chain Resilience

Various theoretical frameworks have been used in supply chain resilience studies. The most notable theoretical frameworks are elaborated below. The framework is described first, and then a brief description of the studies that have used those frameworks is also mentioned. The purpose is to provide an in-depth understanding of how different dimensions of supply chain resilience are explored while using the respective frameworks. To begin with, the most widely used theory in Supply chain resilience is resource-based.

3.10.1 Resource Based View

The resource-based view (RBV), later termed the resource-based theory (RBT), emphasises the role of a firm's internal resources in achieving and sustaining a competitive advantage. Initially proposed by Penrose (1958), the theory identifies resources as unique and valuable assets within a firm that can differentiate it from competitors. Barney (1991) further refined the RBV, categorising firm resources into three groups: physical capital, human capital, and organisational capital. These resources must meet four criteria to confer a sustained competitive advantage—they must be valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable. By leveraging these unique resources effectively, firms can outperform competitors and adapt to dynamic environments. This framework suggests that strategic success is primarily rooted in how well a firm develops and exploits its internal resources rather than relying solely on external market positioning. Thus, RBV/RBT provides a robust lens to analyse and enhance firm-level capabilities and resilience.

Ali and Govindan (2023) applied the resource-based view (RBV) to analyse how firms in the Australian agri-food supply chains leverage Industry 4.0 technologies (I4Ts) as unique and valuable resources to mitigate supply chain risks (SCRs) and improve firm performance. RBV emphasises that competitive advantage stems from a firm's ability to acquire, develop, and exploit resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (Barney, 1991). The study conceptualises I4Ts, such as IoT, blockchain, and big data analytics, as critical technological resources that enable the development of capabilities like real-time information exchange, visibility, and traceability. These capabilities help address operational risks, including supply-demand mismatches, transportation disruptions, and financial risks. Empirical findings demonstrate that firms adopting I4Ts perform significantly better under risk-laden environments than non-adopters, reinforcing RBV's central premise that strategic resource exploitation enhances resilience and firm performance.

Dubey et al., 2016 applied the resource-based view (RBV) to explore how the strategic bundling of critical resources, such as supply chain connectivity and information sharing, creates the capability of supply chain visibility, which is essential for enhancing supply chain resilience. The study integrated RBV with the

relational view (Dyer and Singh 1998), emphasising the importance of relational constructs like trust and cooperation among supply chain partners. Trust and cooperation are identified as critical relational capabilities that strengthen the ability of supply chains to withstand disruptions. The study demonstrates that combining RBV (Barney 1991) and the relational view (Dyer and Singh, 1998) provides a more comprehensive understanding of how resource bundling and inter-organisational relationships jointly contribute to building resilient supply chains.

Yang and Hsu (2018) used the resource-based view (RBV) to examine how maritime firms leverage relationship orientation as a strategic resource to enhance resilience capability and cargo operational performance through security management practices. The study demonstrated relationship orientation as a strategic resource, security management practices as lower-order capabilities, and resilience capability as an operational capability. The study established a resource-capability-performance framework, demonstrating that relationship orientation enables maritime firms to acquire and integrate critical inter-organisational resources, which facilitate the implementation of security management practices. These practices, in turn, strengthen resilience capability, allowing firms to adapt to disruptions with agility, flexibility, and speed.

Dynamic capabilities theory extended the resource-based view (RBV) by focusing on how firms integrate, build and reconfigure their internal and external resources to address rapidly changing environments. The theory developed by Teece et al., (1997) emphasised that competitive advantage in dynamic markets arises not just from owning valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources (as RBV suggests) but from an organisation's ability to transform these resources into capabilities that respond to environmental changes. Teece (2007) developed the micro-foundations of dynamic capabilities, providing a more granular analysis of the processes and structures underlying these capabilities. The authors introduced three key elements: sensing opportunities and threats, seizing opportunities, and reconfiguring resources.

3.10.2 Dynamic Capabilities View

Golgeci and Ponomarov (2013) utilised dynamic capabilities theory (DCT) to investigate the role of firm innovativeness in achieving supply chain resilience (SCR) in the face of disruptions. This study conceptualised firm innovativeness as a dynamic capability, reflecting the ability to respond to supply chain disruptions through innovation.

Brusset and Teller (2017) used DCT in their research and found that integration and flexibility capabilities positively impact resilience, whereas external capabilities have proven insignificant in achieving resilience.

Yu et al., (2019) applied the dynamic capabilities theory (DCT) to examine the relationships among supply chain dynamism, supply chain disruption orientation (SCDO), supply chain resilience (SCR), and financial

performance. This study conceptualises SCR as a dynamic capability that allows firms to be prepared, respond to, and recover from supply chain disruptions while maintaining operational continuity.

Hendry et al., 2019 employed the dynamic capabilities theory (DCT) to explore how local agri-food supply chains (AFSCs) in the UK are building resilience to constitutional change, specifically Brexit. The research employs the dynamic capabilities framework to investigate how AFSC actors prepare for and respond to Brexit-induced challenges and opportunities.

The study applied the three core processes of Dynamic Capabilities view of sensing, seizing, and transforming. In the sensing stage, AFSC actors identified potential threats, such as uncertainty about agricultural subsidies, labour shortages, and disrupted international trade agreements, while also recognising opportunities, such as increased demand for local food and improved domestic supply chain models. This stage involved gathering information and sharing it across supply chain tiers to anticipate the impacts of Brexit.

In the seizing stage, firms begin to capitalise on identified opportunities. For instance, some local farms diversified their production and developed new market channels. These actions reflect proactive strategies to adapt to the changing regulatory and economic landscape.

Finally, in the transforming stage, firms reconfigured their resources, operations, and supply chain relationships to enhance resilience.

By combining these processes, the study highlights how dynamic capabilities enable AFSCs to respond effectively to constitutional change, ensuring both operational continuity and competitive advantage. The research concludes that disruptions like Brexit require an emphasis on horizontal and vertical collaboration between supply chain actors in the sensing, seizing and transforming process

3.10.3 Contingency Theory

Brandon-Jones et al., (2014) integrated contingency theory with the RBV by addressing critiques of the RBV's static nature. Contingency theory suggests that the effectiveness of resources and capabilities is context-dependent, and organisations must adapt to environmental conditions to sustain competitive advantage (Donaldson, 2001). The authors focused on two key resources supply chain connectivity and information sharing and conceptualised supply chain visibility as a capability emerging from the bundling of these resources. Visibility, in turn, is seen as a critical antecedent to two performance outcomes: resilience, defined as the ability of a supply chain to recover quickly from disruptions, and robustness, which refers to the ability to maintain operations despite disruptions. The study also incorporates supply

base complexity as a moderating factor, examining its impact on the relationship between visibility and the performance outcomes of resilience and robustness.

Ali et al., (2018) used both Contingency Theory (CT) and Resource-Based Theory (RBT) as their foundational theoretical frameworks. These theories guided the study in understanding cold chain logistics risks (CCLRs) dynamics, resilience, and firm performance in perishable product supply chains. Contingency Theory was employed to identify and classify the cold chain logistics risks within the context of internal and external environmental conditions. Resource-based theory was used to identify and evaluate the tangible and intangible resources that firms leveraged to build supply chain resilience.

3.10.4 Complex Adaptive System

Choi et al., (2001) argued that supply networks are not static systems but Complex adaptive systems that evolve, self-organise, and adapt dynamically without centralised control. The authors identify three main aspects of CAS: internal mechanisms, environment, and co-evolution. These aspects collectively define how supply networks behave and adapt.

Day (2014) analysed disaster relief efforts as Complex adaptive supply networks and concluded that achieving supply network resilience cannot depend solely on deterministic or reductionist approaches. Instead, a complexity-based perspective on disaster relief supply networks offers a theoretical framework to better understand the variability in their performance. This perspective also provides valuable insights into management strategies that can enhance collective resilience.

Yarosan et al., (2021) employed Complex Adaptive Systems (CAS) theory to explore pharmaceutical supply chain (PSC) resilience, emphasising its systemic and dynamic nature. CAS theory is utilised to explain how PSC actors interact with internal and external mechanisms and co-evolve to build resilience.

Ali & Golgeci (2019) mentioned in their systematic literature review that the Dynamic Capabilities view is widely used in supply chain resilience research. The review of theoretical frameworks in Section 3.10 demonstrates that supply chain resilience has been examined through multiple lenses, each contributing valuable but partial insights. Table 3.7 synthesises these perspectives to clarify their analytical strengths and limitations and to justify the selection of the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV) as the primary theoretical framework for this study.

Theoretical Framework	Use in Supply Chain Resilience (SCR) Literature	Limitations and Gaps	Justification for Selecting DCV
Resource-Based View (RBV) (Ali & Govindan, 2023; Dubey et al., 2016; Yang and Hsu (2018)	Explains how (VRIN) valuable, rare inimitable and non-substitutable resources contribute to sustainable competitive advantage	Static, firm-centric, does not explain how resilience capabilities evolve or are reconfigured over time.	DCV extends RBV by explaining how resources are continuously integrated, built, and reconfigured in dynamic environments
Contingency Theory (CT) (Brandon-Jones et al., 2014; Ali et al., (2018)	Explains how resilience outcomes depend on environmental conditions and contextual fit.	CT explains the necessity of contextual fit but lacks a clear process-based explanation of how resilience capabilities are proactively developed or renewed. It identifies the need for adaptation but not the mechanism of execution.	DCV was selected because it provides a specific managerial mechanism through the micro-foundations of sensing, seizing, and transforming.
Complex Adaptive System (CAS) Choi et al., 2001; Day(2014); Yaroson et al., (2021)	Emphasises dynamic interactions among agents and between agents and their environment; system evolves through learning and emergence	It offers limited guidance on the specific organizational routines or managerial actions required to build collective resilience.	DCV provides a more actionable, routine-oriented framework. By focusing on Processes, Positions, and Paths, it enables the identification of specific resilience routines enacted by supply chain actors.

Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV) Golgeci and Ponomarov (2013); Brusset and Teller (2017); Yu et al., (2019); Hendry et al., 2019	Emphasizes sensing threats, seizing opportunities, and transforming resources.	Existing DCV research is predominantly firm-centric and focuses on linear, sequential processes. There is limited insight into how these processes are enacted in specific sectoral contexts or decentralized networks.	DCV is the most appropriate lens to explore SCR as an integrated capability. This study addresses theoretical gaps by extending DCV to the sectoral and whole-supply-chain level, capturing distributed and concurrent resilience routines.
--	--	---	---

Table 3.7 Theories Used in Supply Chain Resilience Literature

The Resource-Based View (RBV) has been extensively applied in supply chain resilience research (Ali & Govindan, 2023; Dubey et al., 2016; Yang and Hsu, 2018) to explain how valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources underpin competitive advantage and resilience outcomes. However, RBV remains fundamentally static and firm centric. While it explains what resources contribute to resilience, it offers limited insight into how these resources are renewed, reconfigured, or deployed over time in dynamic environments. This limitation is particularly problematic in volatile environments such as agri-food supply chains, where resilience is not a fixed attribute but an evolving capability.

Contingency Theory (CT) addresses some of RBV's limitations by emphasising the importance of contextual fit between organisational strategies, resources, and environmental conditions. Research (Brandon-Jones et al., 2014; Ali et al., 2018) adopting CT demonstrates that resilience outcomes vary depending on factors such as supply base complexity and environmental uncertainty. Nevertheless, CT primarily identifies when adaptation is required rather than how it is enacted. As summarised in Table 3.7. CT lacks a clear process-based explanation of how resilience capabilities are developed, coordinated, and renewed across time and across supply chain actors. This constrains its usefulness for examining resilience as an active, capability-building process.

Complex Adaptive Systems (CAS) theory conceptualises supply chains through internal mechanisms, external mechanisms, and co-evolution (Nair and Reed-Tsochas (2019); Yaroson et al., 2021) offering a useful lens to explain complexity and emergent adaptive behaviour at the system level. However, the aim of this study is not to conceptualise resilience as an emergent outcome, but to examine supply chain

resilience as a dynamic capability by identifying the specific capability factors and routines enacted by supply chain actors. Therefore, it offers limited analytical clarity on how resilience capabilities are developed, enacted, and reconfigured by supply chain players.

In contrast, the Dynamic Capabilities View explicitly focuses on the processes through which organisations integrate, build, and reconfigure resources in response to changing environments (Teece et al., 1997). Through its micro-foundations of sensing, seizing, and transforming (Teece, 2007), DCV offers a process-oriented and action-based framework capable of explaining how resilience capabilities emerge, evolve, and are sustained over time. Prior studies applying DCV in supply chain contexts conceptualise resilience as a dynamic capability (Golgeci & Ponomarov, 2013; Yu et al., 2019; Hendry et al., 2019).

Accordingly, this study adopts the Dynamic Capabilities View not only because it addresses the limitations of RBV, CT, and CAS, but also to extend DCV itself. By applying DCV at the level of the SBSC, this research advances the framework beyond organisational boundaries and demonstrates how sensing, seizing, and transforming processes are enacted by multiple supply chain actors. In doing so, the study responds directly to calls in the literature to move supply chain resilience research beyond firm-level analysis and towards a more holistic and sectoral based understanding.

3.11 Gap in Literature

After reviewing the literature, the following gaps are identified.

1. Despite the growing body of research on agri-food supply chain (AFSC) resilience, the field continues to rely heavily on conceptual definitions proposed by Stone and Rahimifard (2018). This definition has become the most consistently cited and adopted in AFSC resilience research (Zhao et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2024; Montanyà and Amat, 2023; Yuan et al., 2026). This creates a significant gap as there is no universally accepted, empirically validated definition of AFSC resilience. This thesis addresses this gap with the aim of contributing toward an empirically informed agri food supply chain resilience definition.
2. The Agrifood supply chain resilience studies in the Red Meat Supply Chain with the entire supply chain resilience as a unit of analysis are under explored. As illustrated in the Table 3.8, contemporary literature tends to concentrate on either specific nodes or isolated disruption events rather than a comprehensive sectoral analysis. For instance, the work of Hendry et al., (2019) examined resilience within local food tiers specifically in response to the constitutional shock of Brexit, while Perrin and Martin (2021) limited their scope to the farm-level resilience of organic dairy systems in France. Similarly, Ali et al., (2018) focused on technological and logistical assets within the cold supply chain for citrus in Australia, and Payne-Gifford et al., (2022) addressed the immediate impacts of

the COVID-19 pandemic on the British beef and sheep sectors. Sá et al., (2020) analysed resilience in response to drought at individual production nodes in sugarcane and orange supply chains. These approaches provide insight into localised adaptation but do not capture interdependencies between upstream, midstream, and downstream actors.

Study (In-text Citation)	Research Focus / Unit of Analysis	Geographic Location
Hendry et al., (2019)	Examined the resilience of local food supply chains in the context of Brexit-related disruption	United Kingdom
Perrin and Martin (2021)	Focused specifically on the resilience of organic dairy farms	France
Ali et al., (2018)	Resilience factors for the cold supply chain of citrus	Australia
Payne-Gifford et al., (2022)	Impact of COVID-19 on beef/sheep (event-specific)	United Kingdom
Sá et al., (2020)	Sugarcane/orange resilience during drought (single-node shocks)	Brazil
Leat and Ghia (2013)	Resilience within the specific ASDA PorkLink chain	Scotland

Table 3.8 Contemporary Research in Agri Food Supply Chain

This pattern of research indicates that the lack of a holistic study on the SBSC as a single unit of analysis is largely due to the structural complexity and data fragmentation inherent in the sector.

This research gap is also indicated by Scholten et al., (2020), who suggested that the supply chain resilience research should extend beyond the individual and organisational context to the supply chain and sector level, and the authors quoted the example of the research done by (Leat and Ghia 2013).

3. The Agri-Food Supply Chain (AFSC) operates within a framework of inherent vulnerabilities. Supply chain disruptions are unexpected events with severe negative impacts such as tsunamis, fires, or strikes. The ripple effect in the supply chain occurs if a disruption cannot be localized and cascades downstream impacting supply chain performance such as sales, stock return, service level,

and costs (Ivanov, Tsipoulanidis and Schönberger, 2021). The main types of disruptions that can affect food supply chains include natural disasters such as floods, hurricanes, and wildfires, which can damage production areas, transport networks, and infrastructure. Pandemics and animal disease outbreaks represent another major category, disrupting labour availability, production continuity, and market access. Trade-related disruptions, including tariffs and changes in trade policy which can alter cost structures and restrict market flows. Infrastructure failures, such as breakdowns in transport, energy, or processing facilities, can interrupt the movement and transformation of food products. Contamination and food safety incidents pose risks to public health and can lead to product recalls and loss of consumer confidence. Finally, political instability and conflicts can disrupt governance, logistics, and international trade, creating uncertainty and volatility across the food supply chain (Sutar, Kolte and Yamini, 2025). However, disruptions do not occur in isolation their likelihood, magnitude, and ability to cascade through the AFSC are strongly conditioned by pre-existing structural, environmental, technological, and economic challenges. The challenges are not merely operational hurdles and are deeply rooted in the biological, structural, and socio-economic nature of the industry (Minqian, 2026). Contemporary literature identifies a multidimensional array of challenges that persistently pressure the AFSC. These challenges are categorized into four core domains environmental, structural, technological, and economic as shown in Table 3.9.

Although these challenges are well-documented, particularly with regard to their contribution to inefficiencies and disruptions in agri-food supply chains (Kumar & Agrawal, 2023). There is a profound lack of empirical evidence exploring how underlying challenges undermine the resilience capability of the supply chain, rather than merely triggering a disruption. This thesis seeks to address this gap by investigating how challenges within the SBSC impact its resilience.

Category	Key Challenges	Sources
Environmental	Climate Sensitivity, Extreme weather Shocks: Droughts, Heat waves	Kumar and Agrawal (2023); Yim and Dall'erba (2025); Yadav et al., (2022); Yuan et al., (2026)
Structural	Fragmented Chains due to weak integration in supply chain, large numbers of unorganized small farmers have weak bargaining power and fragmented land holdings, lack of Collaboration	Yuan et al., (2026); Kumar and Agrawal (2023); Yadav et al., (2022); Sa et al., (2020)

	and Coordination, Transport network and Infrastructure issues	
Technological	IoT Adoption Barriers, High upfront costs, lack of technical skill sets, Information Asymmetry, Cybersecurity & Privacy	Shoomal et al., (2024); Kumar and Agrawal (2023); Yadav et al., (2022)
Economic	Intermediary Monopoly, High Transaction Costs, Food Fraud & Safety, Farmer as price takers, uncertain market price	Kumar and Agrawal (2023); Yadav et al., (2022); Shoomal et al., (2024)

Table 3.9 Challenges faced by the AFSC

4 Methodology

In this Chapter the Research Methodology is explained.

4.1 Research Philosophy

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) discussed about ontology as what assumptions we make about the world, the nature of reality. They described two main ontological positions objectivism and subjectivism. Objectivism assumes that social entities exist independently of the social actors involved. In contrast, subjectivism posits that social phenomena are created through the perceptions and actions of social actors, emphasising the importance of subjective experiences and interpretations.

For this study on the resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC), a subjectivist ontological stance is most appropriate. The SBSC is composed of tangible and intangible resources, and it can be seen as a socially constructed system shaped by the interactions, decisions, and perceptions of various stakeholders, including farmers, processors, auctioneers, retailers, and policymakers. To understand what makes SBSC resilient, within this context it requires exploring how these stakeholders perceive the capability factors and the challenges it is confronting. For instance, farmers may view resilience as their ability to sustain operations during economic or environmental challenges, while processors may prioritize maintaining consistent supply levels. These diverse interpretations are central to understanding resilience and cannot be captured solely through an objectivist lens.

Epistemology, as discussed by Bell, Bryman, and Harley (2022), refers to the theory of knowledge and is closely linked to ontology, as the latter determines the former. Ontology shapes how researchers view reality, and epistemology determines how they gain knowledge about that reality. For instance, adopting an objectivist ontology suggests that knowledge should be acquired through direct or indirect observation, as reality is seen as external and independent of social actors. Conversely, a constructionist ontology implies that knowledge is best gained through methods like interviews or observation to understand how individuals perceive, interpret, and shape their world. These distinctions are critical for selecting an appropriate epistemological position, such as positivism or interpretivism, to align with the research objectives.

For this study on the resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC), an interpretivist epistemological position, informed by a constructionist ontology, is most suitable. Positivism, which aligns with objectivist ontology, assumes that reality exists externally and can be objectively measured using tools such as surveys or experiments. However, the nature of this research, which aims to understand the resilience of the SBSC, goes beyond simply measuring external phenomena. Resilience within the supply chain is shaped by the perceptions, actions, and interactions of various stakeholders, including farmers, processors, auctioneers,

retailers, and policymakers. These elements are not external realities but are socially constructed through human action and collaboration.

The use of qualitative methods, specifically semi-structured interviews, enables the study to explore participants' subjective interpretations in depth.

4.2 Research Design

Research Design provides a framework for the Collection and analysis of data. A case study design is used in the business research at a wider scale (Eisenhardt and Grabner 2007). Yin (1994) defined case study as an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context especially when the boundaries between the phenomenon and context are not clearly identified. He further elaborated that a case study question are formulated with a how and why question and it focused on Contemporary events. According to Yin (2003) a case study can be embedded and holistic. Scholten (2020) suggested that the supply chain resilience research should extend beyond the individual and organisational context to supply chain and sector level. Recent studies on Agrifood supply chain resilience have adopted the multiple case study design (Hendry et al.,2019). The holistic multiple-case study design is the most appropriate methodological approach for this research on the supply chain resilience of the Scottish beef industry. This design allows for a comprehensive exploration of the complex dynamics within the entire supply chain by examining multiple interconnected cases within a single overarching context. By treating the entire SBSC as the primary unit of analysis, this approach facilitates a holistic understanding of the capability factors of resilience in the SBSC and how it is challenged across the industry. The study recruited 25 participants, representing the key supply chain actors and institutional stakeholders within the SBSC. The participants comprised of Academic Experts (02), Industry Advisor (01), Official Cattle Society Representative (01), Livestock Farmers (07), Industry Representative Processors (01), Processors (02), Industry Representative Auction Marts (01), Auction Mart (01), Retailer (01), Retail Industry Expert (01), Policy Managers Livestock & Animal Health (02), Executive – Traceability Organisation (01), Market Intelligence Manager (01), Head of Industry Development (01), Public Affairs and Industry Strategy Manager (01), and Member of Scottish Parliament, Rural Affairs Committee Member (01). Examining these multiple cases enables a nuanced understanding of how supply chain players consider the enabling factors for a resilient SBSC amid the challenges it is facing. It also highlights the interdependencies among these actors and how their collective actions impact overall supply chain resilience. Analysing multiple cases within the same supply chain allows for the identification of similarities and differences in resilience strategies across stakeholder groups. This comparative perspective facilitates the recognition of best practices, common vulnerabilities, and areas where collaborative efforts can strengthen the overall resilience of the supply chain.

Yin (2003) also emphasised that in case study research, theory development is a vital step in the design process, regardless of whether the goal is to create new theoretical insights or validate existing ones. This research has taken this factor into consideration and is informed by Dynamic Capabilities view which is widely used in the supply chain resilience research (Ali & Golgeci 2009).

A mono method study can utilize in depth interviews as data collection technique (Saunders et al., 2009). This study has chosen mono method and used semi structured interview as a data collection tool. The semi structured interviews are aimed at providing greater importance to the Interviewee's point of view as the researcher's objective is to acquire elaborated answers (Bell, Bryman and Harley 2022). The Interview guide is an important component of case study research (Yin 2003). The case study protocol is used to prove the reliability of the research. A case study protocol is also developed for this study based on the guideline of Yin (2003) to ensures a systematic and rigorous methodology for data collection, analysis, and reporting. The case study design treats the SBSC as the overarching unit of analysis, with multiple cases focusing on key stakeholders, including livestock farmers, processors, auction marts, retailers, and policymakers.

4.2.1 Case Study Protocol

Participants for this research were selected through purposive sampling to ensure representation from diverse stakeholder groups, including farmers, processors, auctioneers, retailers, policymakers, and industry experts. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 25 participants across different regions of Scotland to capture geographic diversity and sectoral variation. Secondary data, including government reports, industry publications, and market analysis, were also reviewed to enhance the depth of the analysis.

Semi Structured Interviews were well planned to ensure consistency and reliability. Access to participants was obtained through formal invitations, and informed consent was secured for all interviews. Data collection involved conducting semi structured interviews via Microsoft Teams with videos recordings and auto transcription with the Participant's consent and detailed note-taking to ensure accuracy. Ethical considerations, such as confidentiality and anonymity, were adhered to throughout the research process.

Kallio (2016) described the interview guide as a set of questions which leads the discussion towards the topic of interest and emphasised on the pilot testing of interview guide. Therefor this study also did pilot testing of the interview guide. The objective of pilot testing is to make the relevant changes which may lead to improved data collection. The Pilot testing took place during the Big Road Beef Show, an event centred on herd fertility, feed efficiency, and the future outlook of the Scottish beef industry. This setting provided an excellent opportunity to engage directly with key stakeholders in the SBSC. Three participants were interviewed as part of this pilot phase: a livestock farmer, a processor, and an industry expert. These

stakeholders represented critical perspectives within the supply chain and offered insights into the practical application of the interview guide.

The initial interview guide was designed to explore key themes related to supply chain resilience and challenges. It included the following questions: How do you perceive the resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain? With Follow-up question like: What does resilience mean to you in the context of your operations? What are the main challenges you face in maintaining or improving resilience within your segment of the supply chain? With Follow-up questions like How do these challenges affect your ability to respond to disruptions? What support or strategies have been effective in addressing these challenges?

The feedback from the pilot interviews highlighted two significant areas for improvement:

Both the livestock farmer and processor found the term "resilience" too abstract and difficult to relate to their daily operations. To address this, the term was defined explicitly in the revised guide as "the ability of a supply chain to be ready for, respond to, and recover from disruptions" This clarification ensured that participants could engage meaningfully with the question. The second question, which focused on challenges, was found to be using the word resilience. Based on this feedback, the guide was revised for better understating and clarity.

The refined interview guide included three core questions to ensure focus and coherence:

1. Could you please introduce yourself and describe your role in the Scottish Beef Supply Chain?
2. What are the factors contributing to the resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain
 - Hint: It is the ability to prepare, respond and recover from disruptions.
3. What are the key challenges you face in contributing to or maintaining the resilience of the supply chain?

4.2.1.1.1 Case Study Methodological Rigor

The methodological rigor in qualitative study has been looked at differently by researchers. LeCompte and Goetz (1982) mentioned the external reliability which is the degree of replication of a study is not easy to achieve as the social settings cannot be frozen. Yin (2003) proposed that the rigor of the case study can be assessed by Construct Validity, Internal Validity, External Validity and Reliability. Guba and Lincoln (1994) proposed the quality assessment criteria based on trustworthiness and authenticity. They proposed that the credibility as an alternative to internal validity. Transferability, dependability and confirmability to be an alternative of external validity, reliability and objectivity respectively. Construct validity refers to the degree to which the conceptualization or operationalisation of a concept is of accurate measurement. It is an essential aspect to consider during the data collection process. In essence, construct validity evaluates

whether the study accurately examines what it intends to investigate, ensuring that the procedure effectively captures and reflects reality (Gibbert et al., 2008). To ensure construct validity this research is conducted by developing an interview protocol based on literature and piloting the protocol with a livestock farmer, a processor and an industry expert who are key stakeholders of the SBSC and data triangulation.

The external validity is the degree of generalizability of the research and has been confused with the ease of statistical generalization. The case study research can have an analytical generalization (Gibbert et al., 2008) which was termed as transferability by Lincoln and Guba (1994) and mentioned that it can be achieved by thick description. The Internal validation assesses whether the researcher provides a convincing and logically sound argument to support their conclusions. Internal validity is not typically a concern in descriptive or exploratory studies, such as case studies, surveys, or experiments, where the aim is not to make causal inferences but rather to observe and describe phenomena. This distinction ensures that internal validity is applied appropriately depending on the research's objectives and methodology (Yin 2003). However, to ensure internal validity cross case analysis is done to explore how resilient the SBSC is from farm to the fork and the challenges it is confronting supply chain wide. Reliability which is an alternative to dependability as proposed by Lincoln and Guba (1994) is an auditing approach which ensures that complete records of the research are kept from the start to the finish. In this study the reliability is assured by securing all recorded videos on the Institutional Data base which is secure and the auto generated transcripts are imported alongside the videos in the NVivo 12 software where in the coding of the interview transcripts was carried out. The ethical approval for data collection and the consent forms are held on record.

Bell, Bryman and Harley (2022) mentioned the use of triangulation in qualitative studies enhances the confidence in the findings. Data triangulation involves gathering information from multiple sources (Carter et al., 2014).

Zhao, G. (2024) mentioned the use of data triangulation comprising of semi-structured interviews and a review of documents, including government reports, policies, public announcements, and information from company websites in a case study on the Agri food supply chain resilience. In this study we have also used data triangulation by conducting the 25 semi structured interviews with the stakeholder of the SBSC and statutory government policy instruments, such as the Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme (SSBSS), national regulatory and traceability databases, notably the ScotEID portal, industry benchmarking and market intelligence reports produced by Quality Meat Scotland (QMS). In addition, the study drew on retailer sourcing specifications and procurement standards published by major retailers, including Marks & Spencer and Aldi, alongside sector advocacy publications issued by NFU Scotland and regional agri-food news briefings from The Scottish Farmer. Evidence of this triangulation is demonstrated throughout the

thesis where primary data are consistently examined alongside independently produced secondary sources to support analytical rigour and academic rigour.

4.3 Selection and Recruitment of Participants

The Participants are recruited by using nonprobability purposive sampling technique. The other sampling choice which came under consideration was theoretical sampling. The study has taken a holistic approach with the entire SBSC as unit of analysis therefore generic purposive sampling was more appropriate. Rigby and O'Brien-Smith (2010) used purposive sampling to capture the participants at different levels of the organisation. The purposive sampling is fixed or priori and it is dependent on the researcher to establish the selection criteria which will help answer the research question. (Bell, Bryman and Harley 2022). Marshall et al.(2013) mentioned the concept of data saturation, initially developed for grounded theory studies but now widely applicable to qualitative research using interviews as the primary data collection method, refers to the point at which no new information or insights are emerging from additional participants. Saturation occurs when the researcher continues to gather data until there is repetition or redundancy in the findings, and collecting further data no longer adds significant value. In essence, it is the point of diminishing returns in data collection. This concept is closely tied to determining an appropriate sample size, as saturation provides an indication of when enough data has been gathered. However, despite its significance, data saturation remains a somewhat ambiguous standard in qualitative research due to the lack of clear, universally accepted guidelines. The study also proposed that 20-30 interviews are sufficient for qualitative research. For this study a sample size of 25 is chosen. This research has used reflexive thematic analysis and according to Braun and Clarke (2021) the codes are not static, and they evolve, merge, renamed, fragmented and even discarded. The analysis rests on the interpretation of the data which vary from surface to the implicit meaning. Therefore, the data saturation is particularly relevant to grounded theory and is not a particularly useful and theoretically coherent concept for thematic analysis. Nonetheless, analysis showed recurring challenges and supply chain resilience capability factors across interviews, indicating sufficient thematic depth. During this process, government intervention emerged as a significant cross-cutting issue. To further probe it an Honourable Member of Parliament was purposively recruited as the 25th interview participant.

4.4 Participant's Profile

This research aimed to collect data from the key stakeholders of the SBSC. Therefore 25 participants were chosen from the key stakeholder comprising livestock farmers, processors, auctioneers, retailers, Industry advisor, Farmer union representatives, Non-Public body representatives and Policy makers. The detail profile of each participant is discussed in the analysis section.

S.No	Interview Participant (IP)	Stakeholder Position
1	IP1	Academia
2	IP2	Academia
3	IP3	Industry Advisor
4	IP4	Official Cattle Society Representative
5	IP5	Livestock Farmer
6	IP6	Livestock Farmer
7	IP7	Livestock Farmer
8	IP8	Livestock Farmer
9	IP9	Livestock Farmer
10	IP10	Livestock Farmer
11	IP11	Livestock Farmer
12	IP12	Industry Representative Processors
13	IP13	Processor
14	IP14	Processor
15	IP15	Industry Representative Auction Marts
16	IP16	Auction Mart
17	IP17	Retailer
18	IP18	Retail Industry Expert
19	IP19	Policy Manager Livestock
20	IP20	Policy Manager Animal Health and Welfare
21	IP21	Executive Traceability Organisation
22	IP22	Market Intelligence Manager
23	IP23	Head of Industry Development
24	IP24	Public Affairs and Industry Strategy Manager
25	IP25	Member of Scottish Parliament (Rural Affairs Committee Member)

Table 4.1 List of Participants

4.5 Data Collection

The data is collected via Microsoft Teams from 2nd July 2024 to 1st November 2024. All meetings were video-recorded and auto-transcribed. Informed consent was obtained from the participants and is held on

record. The participants were also provided participant information sheet before the interview. The interviews ranged in duration from 31 minutes to 106 minutes, with an average interview length of approximately 58 minutes. Cumulatively, the recorded interview duration amounted to 24 hours, 15 minutes, and 55 seconds. All interviews were fully transcribed verbatim, generating a total corpus of 227,347 words.

Interview Participant	Interview Length	Transcribed Words
IP1	43 minutes 31 seconds	6341
IP2	31 minutes 11 second	4234
IP3	51 minutes 38 seconds	10192
IP4	90 minutes 40 seconds	14975
IP5	69 minutes 56 seconds	11471
IP6	81 minutes 10 seconds	10714
IP7	47 minutes 39 seconds	6964
IP8	66 minutes 27 seconds	10826
IP9	38 minutes 47 seconds	6738
IP10	34 minutes 11 seconds	5478
IP11	106 minutes 25 seconds	16621
IP12	43 minutes 07 seconds	6561
IP13	95 minutes 24 seconds	17713
IP14	44 minutes 46 seconds	6281
IP15	66 minutes 03 seconds	10580
IP16	63 minutes 34 seconds	10518
IP17	34 minutes 19 seconds	5129
IP18	58 minutes 02 seconds	8965
IP19	83 minutes 54 seconds	14112
IP20	46 minutes 07 seconds	7333
IP21	64 minutes 57 seconds	8627
IP22	45 minutes 57 seconds	7531
IP23	36 minutes 15 seconds	5992
IP24	35 minutes 48 seconds	5112
IP25	50 minutes 45 seconds	8339

Table 4.2 Interview length and Transcribed words

4.6 Data Analysis

Thematic Analysis is the most used qualitative data analysis approaches. The reason for the popularity of its use is the flexibility of this analysis strategy. Bell, Bryman and Harly (2022) mentioned the importance of themes in paving the way for literature contribution. A theme is a category identified by a researcher, relating to the researcher's research questions, based on the codes identified from the transcripts providing the researcher the basis for theoretical understanding of the data collected that can make a theoretical contribution to the literature with relation to the research focus.

Qualitative data can be methodically coded and analysed, allowing it to be connected to various theories or conceptual frameworks (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The method of theme identification vary among researchers. Gioia et al., (2013) proposed step wise analysis wherein first step is identification of 1st order concepts leading to second order themes and finally merging to aggregate dimension. Ryan and Bernard (2003) proposed that while searching for themes the researcher should focus on repetitions, indigenous typologies or the expressions which are uncommon or used in a unfamiliar manner, metaphors used by the participants to describe something, transitions, and focusing on the usage of words like since, because as they indicate casual connections in the minds of participants. Braun and Clarke (2006;2022) proposed a six steps process for thematic analysis. The use of thematic analysis is used by various authors in the agri foods supply chain studies. Sa et al., (2020) used thematic analysis to examine resilience in agri-food supply chains during Brazil's 2014–2015 drought. They followed an inductive approach, utilising Gioia et al., (2013) methodology to identify and organise themes. Payne-Gifford et al., 2022 employed thematic analysis to examine the disruptions in British beef and sheep supply chains during the COVID-19 pandemic. Zhao et al., 2024 utilized thematic analysis to identify and analyse key resilience capability factors within the agri-food supply chains of Argentina and France. Braun and Clarke (2006)'s six-step process was employed and NVivo software was used for initial generation of codes. This study has employed Thematic Analysis by following Braun and Clarke (2006; 2022) and NVivo 12 software for data analysis.

4.7 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were integral to this research. Diener and Crandall (1978) mentioned that four things should be considered in research. The first and the foremost is to ensure that participants are not vulnerable, to ensure that there is informed consent, to ensure privacy is not invaded and to ensure that no deception is involved. This research has provided participant information sheet and consent form to each participant. Participant confidentiality and anonymity were ensured throughout the study. Informed consent was obtained for all interviews and video recordings with auto transcriptions, and the research adhered to institutional ethical guidelines. Moreover, no invasion to privacy and deception are involved. These measures ensured that the study maintained high ethical standards while safeguarding participant rights.

5 Analysis and Discussion

5.1 Analysis and Discussion

This research has used Braun and Clarke (2006; 2022) reflexive thematic analysis. The steps proposed by (Braun and Clarke, 2006; 2022) were meticulously followed for an in-depth analysis of the data. In this research, 25 qualitative interviews were conducted with the various stakeholders of the SBSC. The interviews involved livestock farmers, auctioneers, processors, retailers, membership bodies representatives, levy bodies, and support institutions like ScotEID, SRUC (Scotland's Rural College), and SAC consulting.

The six steps of Braun and Clarke (2022) were followed to conduct the thematic analysis

1. The first step is familiarisation with the data. In this stage, the auto-transcribed transcripts were read and re-read along with watching the video recording of interviews to make the corrections and note down initial ideas. According to Braun and Clarke (2006) as there is no one way to conduct thematic analysis, there is no one set of guidelines to follow when producing a transcript. Although thematic analysis does not demand the same level of detail in transcription as methods such as conversation analysis, discourse analysis, or narrative analysis, it does require a careful and comprehensive “orthographic” transcript, which provides a verbatim record of all spoken words and, at times, relevant non-verbal sounds (e.g. coughs or pauses). In this stage all the video recorded interviews along with the transcripts were imported into the software Nvivo 12.

2. The second step is “Generating Initial Codes”. In this step the advice (Braun and Clarke, 2006) was followed to try to identify as many potential themes or patterns as possible, within the time available. Even if something seems insignificant at first, it could prove to be valuable later in the analysis. Keeping an open mind allows for a richer exploration of the data. Therefore, the coding of data from the interview transcripts was started in Nvivo12. Braun and Clarke (2006) also mentioned the flexibility of coding, an extract as it may be uncoded, coded once, or coded many times, as relevant.

3. The third step is generating initial themes. In this stage the clusters of coded data were scrutinised to identify a shared pattern or a core idea leading to answer the research question. According to Braun and Clarke (2006; 2022) semantic themes tend to be more descriptive, and the latent themes tend to explore the underlying assumptions and the implications. Therefore, the thematic analysis that tends to be latent tends to be more constructionist. There are no strict or universally fixed rules regarding this process, allowing for combinations and approaches to be applied.

4.The fourth step is developing and reviewing themes. The initial themes and sub themes generated are further developed and reviewed in this step. As mentioned by Braun and Clarke (2006) data analysis is not a linear process of simply moving from one phase to the next. Instead, it is more recursive process, where movement is back and forth as needed, throughout the phases, which provides a greater flexibility to the researcher.

5.Refining, Defining and naming themes. After the initial generation of subthemes and themes the two major themes emerged were the factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC and the Challenges it is confronting.

6.The last step is reporting themes. One of the criteria proposed by Braun and Clarke (2022, p. 35) for written report is “The Researcher is positioned as active themes do not simply emerge”. In this research the active role of the researcher is evident in the coding and theme development process and by discussing how themes were shaped by the interpretation of participant data.

5.2 (CASES)

5.2.1 Academic Expert Research Institute Interview Participant No 1 (IP1)

Two interviews were conducted with the Lecturers of SRUC (Scotland’s Rural College). Scotland’s Rural College (SRUC) is a leading institution dedicated to agriculture, rural research, education, and consultancy, with a history spanning over 100 years. SRUC is also known for its industry-facing approach, fostering partnerships with businesses and government to drive workforce development and economic growth in the rural sector (SRUC 2018).

The purpose of recruiting two academic experts from Scotland’s Rural College (SRUC) was to capture their unique and valuable perspectives on the challenges and resilience of the Scottish beef supply chain. SRUC’s lecturers are deeply embedded in the agricultural and rural ecosystem, combining academic rigor with practical insights through their work in research, education, and consultancy. Their industry-facing approach and active collaboration with businesses, policymakers, and rural communities position them as key knowledge holders in the domain of supply chain resilience.

The codes identified in the first interview are shown in the figure below. Based on the identified codes, clusters were developed and labelled as sub-themes, and final themes were identified based on those sub-themes.

Figure 5.1 Initial Coding of Interview Transcript in NVivo IP1

5.2.1.1 Theme1 Factors Contributing to the Resilience of Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC)

The IP1 identified the factors contributing to the SBSC at the various steps of the SBSC.

5.2.1.1.1 Provenance

According to IP1, the first factor that has been attributed to the resilience of the SBSC is provenance. According to the Cambridge Dictionary, it is about the origin and history of something. Wallace and Manning (2020) defined Provenance as the specific origin or source of a food product and its individual ingredients, as well as the claims regarding how the product is produced and the marketing assertions associated with it.

Scottish beef is a well-known worldwide brand (QMS 2024b). QMS mentioned in its five-year strategy 2024-28 that provenance provides a competitive advantage for the Scottish beef sector.

“The factors that have contributed to the resilience so far, I think, has been the provenance has been the fact that for a long time there has been the Scotch brand”IP1

In the statement above, IP1 implied that the resilience of the SBSC is primarily attributed to its strong provenance and the long-established reputation of the Scotch brand. Provenance highlights the product's authentic Scottish origin, quality, and traceability, fostering consumer trust and providing a competitive advantage.

As highlighted by IP1, Provenance closely aligns with the Market Position capability factor identified by Pettit et al., (2013) because it directly influences how a product is perceived and positioned within the market. The Scottish beef industry's emphasis on the provenance of its authentic origin, traceability, and heritage strengthens the Scotch brand's identity and reputation for quality by differentiating its products from competitors.

5.2.1.1.2 Production Systems

The SBSC is quite complex and has various players involved in providing the meat from the farm to the fork. The production systems in Scotland for livestock farmers vary based on their nature of operation. The research participant IP1 mentioned that the production system has contributed to the resilience of the Scottish beef supply. The Scottish Government's Climate Change Adaptation Plan (2024–2029) places increasing emphasis on the need for agricultural systems to adapt to climate-related risks such as extreme weather, flooding, and temperature variability.

The IP1 implied that the resilience of the SBSC is partly due to its production systems, particularly the scale of farms and their capacity for large-scale production. This scalability allows producers to maintain consistent supply, adapt to market demands, and recover more effectively from challenges. Therefore, IP1 suggested that the structural advantages of larger production systems contribute significantly to the industry's overall resilience.

“I think the production systems here, the scale of farms, the ability to. Umm Produce on a relatively large scale, has added to the resilience”IP1

5.2.1.1.3 Resilient to Market Volatility

The SBSC showed resilience against market volatility. During the disruption caused by COVID-19, it can be witnessed that the SBSC remained resilient during that disruption. The QMS submitted a written response to the UK parliament (2022) committee, which mentioned that from June 2021 to June 2022, over 90% of Scottish households bought unprocessed red meat.

“Volatility and and also market volatility as well. I know some people talk about Other changes, but relatively if you took a long view of the Scottish beef price, that's not really very volatile at all. It's pretty much the same year in, year out”IP1

In the above-mentioned interview extract, IP1 implied that, despite general concerns about the market and economic volatility, the Scottish beef industry had experienced relatively stable pricing over the long term. The IP1 suggested that the price of Scottish beef has remained consistent year after year, indicating low volatility in comparison to other markets. This price stability contributes to the industry's resilience by providing producers with predictable income and reducing financial uncertainty.

5.2.1.2 Theme 2 Challenges faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (Current and Future)

This theme identifies a range of current challenges facing the SBSC, alongside emerging challenges that may affect it in the future.

Sub Themes

5.2.1.2.1 Lack of Infrastructure

IP1 highlighted a specific infrastructure constraint within the SBSC relating to the availability of organic processing facilities.

“There are no abattoirs in Scotland that are doing Scotch organic on a significant scale. There'll be some that are producing for butcher trade, but as far as supermarket trade exists, that doesn't happen. Anything that's going for organic now has to be transported all the way, the closest abattoir is in Northumberland”IP1

The absence of large-scale organic processing facilities for supermarket distribution implies that organic producers face limited market access and reduced growth potential. Moreover, the need to transport organic cattle long distances for processing introduces additional logistical complexity and cost, which may discourage farmers from transitioning to or expanding organic production.

5.2.1.2.2 Lack of Hygiene and Cleanliness of Livestock

Another challenge affecting the operational efficiency of processing plants is inadequate livestock hygiene and cleanliness. The impediment is that when the cattle arrive at the abattoir, you cannot send them back, irrespective of their apparent condition.

“the biggest problem we had was the hygiene and cleanliness of livestock coming into the plant”

“So, but that was our biggest problem was cleanliness of livestock coming in to maintain hygiene levels”

“the problem you had was if livestock arrived at the abattoir, as soon as they step foot on the ground at the abattoir, they cannot then leave that site again. So if cattle, for example, were unloaded, and then you find actually they're filthy and they're not suitable for slaughter, you can't put them back on the trailer and send them back to the farm”

“because of the rules and regulations around movement and transport of livestock, you can't take something from an abattoir and take it back to a farm again without a license”IP1

The problem is further augmented if the meat is contaminated then the abattoir has to either dispose it off or find a suitable buyer for that produce.

5.2.1.2.3 Lack of Product Quality

The following factors highlight the lack of product quality.

5.2.1.2.3.1 EUROP Grid

The Scottish Beef industry uses the EUROP grid system for payment to the farmers. The EUROP grid is a standardised system used throughout Europe for classifying Beef carcasses based on their conformation and fat levels. If the farmer follows the grid, the produce will fetch a higher return (AHDB 2023.).

IP1 identified the EUROP grid-based payment system as a key factor contributing to inconsistency in product quality within the SBSC. IP1 stated that *“the payment system is a problem, the grading system is a problem”*, indicating dissatisfaction with how carcasses are classified and rewarded. The EUROP grid classifies carcasses based on conformation and fat levels, however, IP1 suggested that the system does not adequately differentiate quality in practice. IP1 described the grading structure as overly broad, referring to it as *“this massive grid that goes from very good to very bad”*

“And then you know, if that meat is contaminated. It either gets disposed of or you know, depending on the level of contamination, then the abattoir has to find a suitable market for where they can sell that meat too, and it further diminishes the value” IP1

According to IP1, *“As long as I hit somewhere on that on that board on that grid, it's it's meet the specification”*, highlighting that animals of widely varying quality can fall within the same specification range. This suggests that the grading system prioritises minimum compliance rather than incentivising consistently high-quality production.

In addition, IP1 emphasised that processors and supermarkets seek cattle within a narrow conformation range, explaining that *“They want it in a confirmation range. They want everything they want it to be narrowed down..... as long as it hits that board somewhere and they get paid”* However, the breadth of

the grading grid allows significant variation in size and quality to enter the processing system. IP1 highlighted that when cattle with huge variation based on the quality and size arrive at processing plants, operational efficiency is reduced. This indicates a misalignment between grading criteria and processor requirements. IP1 characterised this situation as a “*big question mark*” for the sector, pointing to a tension between market expectations for uniformity and the structural design of the grading system.

5.2.1.2.3.2 Misalignment in Production

The failure to maintain a consistent quality has also surfaced as a challenge. There needs to be tighter controls to be introduced.

“Because and in Aberdeen, particularly one of the biggest issues was overweight cattle. Farmers thought if they sent in something that weighed 450 kilos, they were gonna have money to bone”IP1

The IP1 implied that there is a misalignment between farmers' perceptions and the EUROP grading system used for pricing cattle. In Aberdeen, farmers believed that sending in heavier cattle would result in higher payments, assuming that more weight equates to more value. However, the Overweight cattle may fall outside the preferred weight range, leading to lower grading and reduced payments. This suggests a lack of understanding or communication about how the EUROP grid system evaluates and prices cattle, causing farmers to make production decisions that do not align with market requirements

“they need to be clean, they need to be hygienic and they need to be uniform”IP1

This lack of alignment between farmer perception and technical grading underscores why maintaining a consistency of quality is so vital for the integrity of the premium Scottish brand. To address these discrepancies, quality must be viewed as a holistic standard that encompasses specific rearing practices and the welfare conditions maintained during transport to the slaughterhouse. Ultimately, these findings suggest that meat quality is a direct reflection of industry practices that require tighter regulation to ensure farm-level production is systematically synchronized with market requirements.

5.2.1.2.3.3 Shorter Shelf Life

The product has a shorter shelf life because the production systems can produce cattle targeted for supermarket shelves. The production system needs to be improved to produce cattle, which will have an increased shelf life, and this can help improve the exports of meat as it is a perishable commodity.

“There is no abattoirs in Scotland that are doing Scotch organic on a significant scale. There'll be some that are producing for butcher trade, but as far as supermarket trade exists, that doesn't happen”IP1

“See the the the product doesn't have a big enough a long enough shelf life. And particularly around, you know, the production systems are completely different. Everything is geared here for an animal slaughtered and it very quickly ends up on a supermarket shelf and I listen aging processes with with beef, but essentially it's got a very short shelf life”IP1

If the objective is only to serve the supermarkets the vision to produce a consistent and quality product will surely remain a challenge.

5.2.1.2.4 Procurement Issues

The livestock buyers who cannot visit book the cattle on the phone, and when the actual cattle is received, it is much different from what was seen in the photo. These practices can lead to a lack of trust among the supply chain players. This shows that unethical practices also need to be strictly regulated in the Scottish Beef supply chain.

“The livestock buyers wouldn't or didn't always go on farm and hand pick the stock that they were buying.OK, a lot of it was brought over the phone so there wouldn't see these animals.They didn't know what condition they were in.They would just take a phone call.There's four cattle booked in on such and such a day.This is their ages and breeds and type.They're coming in now.Anything could show up OK.You know, imagine that like the.Imagine it like the livestock buyers were operating some sort of tender system and the photo looked fantastic.And then you'd you'd date shows up, and it's not quite like it is on the photo”IP1

5.2.1.2.5 Limited Use of Modern Farming Practices

The Scottish livestock farmers have not adopted modern farming practices, which have limited their capability of producing a consistent quality product.

“I don't think the Scottish beef supply chain has been umm used enough novel. Sort of methods for enhancing or improving the very traditional and they're very much focused on umm I domestic market which is for supplying supermarkets”IP1

The shelf life of the Scottish beef product is small as compared to the beef produced in the other parts of the world. As per FSA (2022), the shelf life of Beef products is up to 13 days. In Australia (ABSF 2024), the shelf life of chilled beef is 120 days, and they are using it in the Middle Eastern markets. Therefore, the adoption of new ways of producing cattle is aimed at a product which will have a higher shelf life, taste and consistent quality.

“So I yeah, I don't, I don't think I don't think there has been enough adoption of novel methods to improve particularly around the efficiencies of production genetic enhancement. Umm, it's very much. Do what we've always done and then expect something different”IP1

5.2.1.2.6 Lack of Export Ambition

UK is meeting its demand in Cattle up to 87% as mentioned in the UK Food security index 2024 (DEFRA 2024). Since the demand of the local market is not fully serviced therefore the livestock farmers know that whatever they will produce will be find a buyer.

“We're not relying on exports to sell the product on a significant scale”IP1

“the UK is not self sufficient in in anything particularly with food production, it's not self sufficient. So why they? Uh, looking at export markets and not trying to improve the domestic market. Umm. And and if you know for decades been vulnerable to to whatever the supermarket say”IP1

If there is a drive to export our product, then it can lead to better product quality not only in the domestic market because we will have to elevate our quality standards as we have to compete with other large producers like Australia and New Zealand.

5.2.1.2.7 Market Power Imbalance

The structure of the Scottish supply chain in terms of power dynamics varies; according to the interviewee, the SBSC is dominated by Retailers.

“so basically that was the supermarkets using their muscle and power did away with a product in Scotland, OK. If you use that example, you could say, well, the whole Scotch brand could disappear as well”IP1

“Scottish people might say why are we paying a premium on it. Yeah. Why don't we just have British Red meat? So there's an example of how the supermarkets actually dictated and changed the market. Umm, so that's I think the most the biggest vulnerability and possibly the biggest challenge that that the Scotch brand. Umm could just disappear”IP1

“without a doubt, first thing that pops to mind is supermarket pressure. ok, Supermarkets dictate umm price. They dictate where they get their products from”IP1

This dominance initiates a level of reduced trust in the entire supply chain. The alarming thing highlighted is the fear that this dominance can lead to the disappearance of the Scotch Brand.

This refers to the fact that Scottish beef is a premium brand, and it entails a premium, and if Scottish beef is organic, then it demands two premiums. This retailer dominance has also resulted in a challenge to the

SBSC. The dominance is empowered by the fact that the final destination of farms' produce is the retailer shelves.

5.2.1.2.8 Knowledge Transfer

Ganguly (2020) argues that knowledge sharing among key supply chain actors in agri-food supply chains which are particularly vulnerable to disruptions due to their perishable nature can enhance supply chain resilience.

The participant mentioned that the knowledge transfer in the SBSC will be a big challenge.

“I think future challenge is gonna be knowledge transfer and developing a better relationship between retailers and farmers. Umm, getting getting farmers to understand what the consumers want, what the processes want, what the retailers want. You know, and they need to. They need to produce something that is fit for purpose” IP1

5.2.1.2.9 Relationship Between Farmers and Retailers

The relationship between stakeholders can lead to a resilient supply chain. Qazi et al., (2024) proved that supplier and customer relationships could significantly impact supply chain resilience. The participant also mentioned that the relationship between the farmer and the retailer needs to be bridged so that the livestock farmer should know what is required.

“They need to understand that they're producing a commodity product.....retailers will be selective or could be selective and say we don't actually want what it is that you produce” IP1

5.2.1.3 Theme 3 Future Resilience

5.2.1.3.1 Improve Farmer Knowledge in Livestock Farming

As mentioned in the theme under the SBSC challenges, the livestock farmers have not adopted modern livestock farming practices. The adaption of modern livestock farming focused on sustainability can lead to livestock farming resilience. Moreover, the lack of farmers' training in modern farming practices can be a barrier to resilient farming (CGIAR 2024)

“They need to be educating farmers if they genuinely want to improve the integrity of the supply chain. They need to educate farmers to improve the quality of their livestock, make their livestock more uniform that you know you can't sell rubbish if you want to go into a premium market, there has to be a premium product and it has to be a premium product from the farm gate” IP1

The need to improve the product quality is reiterated, and it is mentioned that the livestock farmers have to realise that they are selling a premium product, so it has to be a premium product from the farm gate. If the

farmers will be provided training to improve their technical knowledge and learn new sustainable farming ways it can lead to the resilience SBSC.

5.2.1.3.2 Carcass Specification as KPI

The Europ grid system is used to make payments to livestock farmers. The Carcass specification should be used as a key performance indicator for better supply chain resilience, as it will assist the supply chain to bounce back after any disruption caused by price volatility in the export markets. The present Europgrid is quite flexible, and the livestock farmers are complacent as they know their produce will be accepted while just being on the grid. Stewart et al.(2024) mentioned that the Australian beef and lamb industries have transitioned from traditional carcass classification to consumer-focused grading through the Meat Standards Australia (MSA) system. Grading systems must remain adaptable to evolving consumer preferences. The use of objective technologies enhances the accuracy of yield and eating quality measurements, supporting more precise grading models. Integrating carcass yield estimates with consumer value enables transparent, value-based trading systems. This approach benefits the industry by delivering products that meet consumer demand, improving processing efficiency, optimising operations, and providing detailed carcass feedback and market insights to livestock suppliers.

“One KPI that I would use to assess the resilience or performance would be umm carcass specification.OK.I would ask that question that that's something that should be used to assess resilience.Are they getting better or are they getting worse?Or are they not changing and I think Carcass specification does the product meet the requirements of the customer or the retailers”IP1

Therefore, in order to compete in the global markets we have to improve our Carcass specification standards.

5.2.1.3.3 Follow Global Trends

The SBSC can enhance its resilience by adopting practices used by leading beef-producing countries, such as Australia and New Zealand, which are actively engaged in the global export of livestock products. For the Scottish beef industry, this may imply the need to adapt production systems to meet niche and international market demands.

“You know there will be someone that is producing red meat for a specific processing, red meat for a specific market and they say right actually we want and you see it in New Zealand with dairy cows, all the dairy cow meats ends up going to the US for processing”IP1

Figure 5.2 Major Beef Exporting Countries Source Statista 2024

5.2.2 Academic Expert Research Institute Interview Participant No 2 (IP2)

The second interview participant is a Senior lecturer working at SRUC. The initial coding from the interview transcript is shown in the figure below; after rigorous reviewing of the nodes and interview transcript and watching the video-recorded interview, The nodes were clustered into sub-themes from which the main themes were developed.

Figure 5.3 Initial Coding of Interview Transcript in NVivo IP2

5.2.2.1 Theme 1 Challenges Faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC)

Sub Themes

5.2.2.1.1 Critical Mass

Critical Mass is very important for Scotland’s beef supply chain. It ensures that sufficient livestock numbers are available to sell at the auction marts and processors. Scotland's beef supply chain is witnessing a consecutive decline in the suckler cow herd. The absence of livestock numbers results in unviable auction marts and processors. Critical mass maintenance is vital for the Scottish livestock sector's long-term resilience (Fraser, 2023). The interview participant highlighted that critical mass is essential to ensures that

enough consistent beef production is available to support expanded market opportunities without risking supply shortages.

“I do worry about that critical mass of just having enough to keep the supply chain going both domestically, but also if we are trying to look to have more and trade deals with foreign countries Is there are actually enough beef to supply all of that and then a beef prices are really quite good at the moment”IP2

While current beef prices are strong, indicating healthy market conditions, IP2 is cautious that this profitability might not be sustainable if production cannot scale to meet growing demands.

5.2.2.1.1.1 Lack of Financial Returns

The main challenge identified is the historical unprofitability of the entire supply beef supply chain. The farmers at all levels are suffering from a lack of returns; this includes the livestock farmers who are breeders, finishers and breeder finishers.

“I think the main challenge and that you just can't get away from at the moment is the historical unprofitability within the beef industry and I'm across the whole of the beef industry as well. I'm talking about like farms here, and so both are suckler producers and our finishers”IP2

5.2.2.1.1.2 Suckler Herd efficiency

The decreasing suckler herd efficiency is also identified as a challenge. The decreasing herd efficiency does impact the critical mass. The ripple effect can be that if there are fewer cattle produced, fewer cattle will be available for slaughter and to be sold at auction marts, and consequently, the retailers will also have more empty shelf space.

“there has been a long term decrease in cow numbers in Scotland and it's a trend that is we are continuing to see and I don't think anybody really predicting that to you know bottom out and go up yet”IP2

5.2.2.1.1.3 Lack of KPIs

As mentioned earlier, the Europ payment grid is used in Scotland. This grid is focused only on the shape of the animal. The largest meat exporters, like America and Australia, have developed their payment grids not entirely focusing on the shape of the animal. On the contrary, they use payment grids linked to the meat's eating quality. In the USA, Beef is graded based on traits like tenderness, juiciness, and flavour (USDA 2024). The interview participant extensively discussed about the introduction of new KPIs.

“And so our cattle, when somebody takes cattle to slaughterhouse, they're paid on the Europe payment grid, but there's nothing about actual quality. So the actual eating taste in the marbling that Beef, where is, if we look at the big producers around the world, likes of your America or Australia, their payment grid is

quite different to our one and it is mainly a lot of their payment is driven on marbling so then that directly correlates to the eating quality of meat. We don't have anything like that here in Scotland, it is all just about the fat cover, but that cover doesn't have near as much correlation on the eating quality as you enter muscular fat does. And about the shape of the animal so it favors your more Belgian blue lemons and quite sheepy type of cattle, but those don't tend to be the ones that have the highest eating quality. And so that long term and if that changes could have because well it's been talked for a while about changing the payment structure, but I don't know if I see it happening, but if that did change, it could be quite an opportunity, but it would cause quite a lot of upsetting quite a lot of change within the breeding of these cattle” IP2

It is also mentioned that the statistics which are provided by ScotEID do not fully cover the weight and performance aspect of the cattle. Therefore, it is suggested that the KPIs be improved.

“And so that is, yeah, there's some information that can come out there, but it wouldn't give you all of the KPIs you would want to look at. I don't think so. The likes of I mentioned your daily life weight gains earlier and to see if you're animals are actually performing and what your output off your farm is, or your output per cow and you don't get anything like that off ScotE ID” IP2

5.2.2.2 Theme 2 Government Support

The role of government support in enhancing agrifood supply chain resilience is explored by Yuan (2024). The study highlights that government support helps protect the agri-food supply chain against disruptions through resource allocation and also contributes to building its capacity to withstand and sustain disruptions.

Sub Themes

5.2.2.2.1 Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme

Government support plays a vital role in the SBSC, especially at the livestock farming level. The Scottish Government introduced a Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme (SSBSS) in 2019, which makes payments to beef producers. This scheme has introduced an amendment from January 2025 in the calving interval to reduce the greenhouse gases impact and a helpful measure of beef production in the Suckler herd (Scottish Govt, 2025). The participant emphasised that the SSBSS is based on the Irish Scheme, and the stipulations are less complicated and easy than the Irish Scheme.

“And I think that's the Scottish Government did have a wee go at it with the Beef efficiency scheme. It's been finished for 2-3 years now. But I don't know if there was a huge amount came out of the Beef efficiency scheme. The Irish scheme that mirrored had more requirements than Scottish scheme did. I do assess maybe

in some ways where it fell down, so some of the in conditions of that one was that you had to do a carbon audit and so that's fine. But then, for actually it was encouraging you to do more, recording of your cattle to try and make your beef production more efficient. But the likes of the weighing you only had to weigh once in a year. So if you're only taking one weight, it doesn't actually really tell you anything, because you can't work out a daily life weight gain, so they can't work out if they're performing as well as they should be or not. It just gives you a snapshot at point in time and that could be. I didn't even need to be an individual weight. It could be if you sold them, pair up five at the market, you could take the average weight. So it wasn't hugely accurate”IP2

5.2.2.2.2 Role of Subsidies

Agri-producer subsidies can be ineffective when they focus primarily on reducing producers’ operational costs, as this may encourage the excessive use of fertilisers and other inputs. Moreover, such subsidies can place a significant burden on public funds (Amaglobeli et al., 2024).

The interviewee also highlighted that the subsidies can lead to inefficiencies.

“Think it's a difficult one because in some ways if there's no investment, there'll be no moving forward, but also subsidies can increase inefficiencies”IP2

5.2.2.2.3 MyHerd Stats

The Scottish government has provided a free tool to livestock farmers. The objective is to improve the herd management and improve efficiency. Only livestock farmers can access the statistics of their own herd. The statistics are called Myherd (ScotEID 2023).

“And so within ScotE ID, now they've got a section. What's it called? My herdstats I think it's called that actually gives you some pretty decent information and calculates some KPI for you, and so it tells you what your calving interval is, your replacement rates, and heifer retention though average age your cows, those sorts of things, that one is quite a good source of information”IP2

5.2.2.3 Theme 3 Recent Disruptions

5.2.2.3.1 COVID-19 and the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

COVID-19 was discussed as the recent disruption in the SBSC. The study done by (Payne et al., 2022) on the supply chain disruptions in the British Beef and sheep supply chain during COVID-19 concluded that the British cattle supply chain remained quite resilient. The closure of a processing plant was witnessed due to the disease outbreak. The food services faced a major disruption. Overall, the SBSC remained resilient. The consumer demand became so high that mince from Poland had to be imported because the local

industry could not meet the demand. The interview participant also discussed that consumer demand remained healthy during the disease outbreak.

“Well, yeah, it definitely did at the time and more so not in the farm inside of things so much, but within the supply chain itself and mostly at the slaughterhouses markets, pretty much ran as normal. But it was the outbreaks of COVID-19 at slaughterhouses and that had an effect. It probably had a positive effect, though, on consumer behaviour, so more people were buying and roasting joints and things like that because they were staying at home and there were making different sorts of meals than they would have been in the past”IP2

5.2.2.4 Theme 4 Lack of Communication and Collaboration

It surfaced during the interview that the level of communication and collaboration is not ideal in the SBSC. The special mention was of the livestock farmers and highlighted that efforts are underway to increase industry representation. However, there are membership organisations like NFUS, SAMW, SBA, IAAS, and Levy organisation QMS, so it is difficult to comprehend why the representation is not there. If we explore the number of committees run by NFUS and QMS, it is slightly difficult to accede that the livestock farmers are underrepresented.

“There is some, but..... isn't enough and..... larger producers as well, or larger finishers that would go to the types of industry meetings or would be chosen by and if you are whoever it is, it's facilitating the meetings. So, I don't think they'd be able to say that there was full Industry representation at these things, but I think there is efforts being made”IP2

5.2.2.5 Theme 5 Factors Contributing to the Supply Chain Resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC)

Sub Themes

5.2.2.5.1 Diversified Income Stream

Income diversification has contributed to the supply chain resilience of the Scottish beef industry. The mixed farming system integrates livestock farming and crop cultivation (Nature Scot, 2023). The diversification of agricultural products results in the agri-food supply chain resilience (Yuan 2024).

Income diversification was identified by IP2 as an important contributor to resilience within the SBSC, particularly at the level of primary production. IP2 mentioned that *“a lot of the beef production is happening on mixed farms and so it is not the only thing in the business,”* indicating that beef enterprises are typically embedded within broader mixed farming systems rather than operating as stand-alone activities.

While IP2 emphasised that beef production is “usually... alongside sheep production, which historically also hasn’t been profitable” This is analytically significant, as it demonstrates that diversification in this context is not driven by consistently profitable alternatives, but by the need to maintain a functioning whole-farm system. Rather than seeking high returns from each enterprise, farmers appear to use diversification as a risk-spreading and stabilising strategy, reducing dependence on any single income source even when none are strongly profitable in isolation.

IP2 further observed that sheep production “in recent years... has seen quite a change and has been more profitable” This indicates that mixed farming systems allow farmers to benefit when one enterprise improves, even if others remain under pressure. In this way, diversification provides adaptive flexibility, enabling farms to adjust to changing market conditions without fully restructuring their production systems.

IP2 concluded that *“the majority of people at that base level of producing the calves have diversified income streams so they have been able to take the hit a little bit more compared to if that was their sole income stream”* This directly evidences diversification as a shock-absorbing mechanism, enabling farmers to withstand financial pressure and market volatility more effectively. The ability to *“take the hit”* reflects enhanced absorptive capacity, allowing production to continue despite adverse conditions.

5.2.3 Academia’s Perspective on the Challenges of the SBSC

The challenges identified by the academic practitioners are presented in Figure 5.4. The challenges are grouped into four categories: economic, structural, operational, and other. Economic challenges are represented through procurement issues and a lack of financial returns, where limited profitability restricts reinvestment in farm improvement, technology adoption, and productivity enhancement. Procurement practices, particularly remote purchasing, were identified as weakening transactional reliability and trust within the chain.

Structural challenges are captured through the lack of infrastructure and market power imbalance. The shortage of local slaughtering facilities results in extended transportation distances, increasing costs and animal welfare risks. Market power imbalance reflects the concentration of influence at the retail end of the chain, limiting upstream actors’ ability to shape specifications, pricing, and contractual conditions.

Operational challenges include critical mass, suckler herd efficiency, and the lack of KPIs. The decline in herd numbers reduces throughput for auction marts and processors, threatening their commercial viability. Suckler herd efficiency directly affects productivity and supply consistency. The absence of meaningful KPIs beyond basic carcass grading limits performance monitoring and coordinated improvement across the chain.

The category other captures product quality issues, limited use of modern farming practices, lack of export ambition, weak knowledge transfer, strained farmer–retailer relationships, and hygiene concerns. These factors relate to behavioural, capability, and coordination constraints within the supply chain. Together, they influence consistency, shelf life, market positioning, and the ability of the chain to meet premium and export market requirements.

Figure 5.4 Challenges Identified By Academia

5.2.4 Academia ‘s General Concerns Regarding the SBSC

The role of the Scottish Government in supporting the SBSC was discussed. The main focus of the discussion was on the support provided to the livestock farmers. It was indicated that although the Government has extended significant support towards livestock farmers through schemes such as the Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme. For herd management, the Government has provided livestock farmers with a free tool called Myherds, which ScotEID manages. It was also mentioned that the subsidies can lead to inefficiencies. The recent disruption of COVID-19 was discussed, and it was concluded that during COVID-19, the SBSC showed resilience at the entire supply chain level except in a few instances wherein the processing plants were closed due to a disease outbreak.

5.2.5 Industry Expert / SAC Consultant Interview Participant (IP) 3

The Interview Participant (IP) 3 works for SAC Consulting, a Scotland's Rural College (SRUC) division, offers independent, research-driven expertise and solutions for agricultural, food, and land-based businesses. With over two decades of experience in beef production, the IP3 specialises in management, health, genetics (Estimated Breeding Values), and nutrition. His role involves advising stakeholders across the beef industry, including farmers, processors, and retailers, on enhancing efficiency and sustainability.

After transcribing and rigorous repetitive reading of the transcript and repeatedly watching the recorded video, the following nodes were identified, as shown in the figure below. Afterwards, the nodes were clustered to formulate sub themes and themes.

Figure 5.5 Initial Coding of Interview Transcript in NVivo IP3

5.2.5.1 Theme Challenges Faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The industry expert highlighted various challenges faced by the SBSC.

5.2.5.1.1 Lack of Financial Returns

A lack of financial return is reported across the entire SBSC. Livestock farmers, in particular, indicate that returns on investment are insufficient.

“there's a number of reasons that they are dispersing, the first thing is simply they don't believe the economics are adding up for what return they're getting from the market. It's not equating to what costs are involved”IP3

The other SBSC players also perceive they are not obtaining the desired profitability. This also leads to a lack of trust in the supply chain, as the industry practitioner indicated that the supply chain players perceive that their margins are squeezing.

“So we're now left with a perception, a sector at the moment where you've got the farmers producing, you've got the finishers finishing, you've got the processors processing and the retailers selling each one of them currently thinks they are not getting a big enough share of the pie”IP3

“The producers are finding that their costs are too much compared to the return they are getting in the market. The finishers are feeling that they're paying too much for store cattle. For what they're getting finishing. The processors feel that they're paying too much money for what the retailers prepared to pay them, so their margins are squeezing, and the retailer feels that if he puts the price up at the end point, then they'll just the consumer will move to chicken or pork. Everybody's feeling squeezed”IP3

So, this is one of the industry's challenges in experiencing low profitability.

5.2.5.1.2 Poor Infrastructure

The IP3 also identified the poor infrastructure for processing part of the SBSC as a challenge. The processing sector in the SBSC is highly concentrated. The need for small abattoirs is highlighted and is also negated by commenting on its financial viability. Interestingly, the practitioner discussed that small abattoirs can be very useful in case of a disease outbreak like Foot and Mouth disease. This issue has also been raised in the past in the SBSC. A study was done by the Scottish Government in 2020 to explore the feasibility of the mobile abattoirs. The report confirmed the feasibility of mobile abattoirs in Scotland, but unfortunately, the problem still persists. The interview respondent also indicated that the small abattoirs are needed but are not financially feasible (Scottish Government, 2020).

“The slaughtering capabilities, they make it out the processing when they cut it up and put it in packaging, that's where they make it is too costly and that, but there is always a fight of we should have more and more small local abattoirs, but we have too many as it is in the larger scale. The problem would be that it costs too much. However, there's always an argument that if we ever got foot and mouth again, it's good to have local, so you don't have to travel too far. These are the things that I've got to look at and balance in that, but at the moment we'll have too much capacity as it is at the moment, To create small local abattoir is not correct economically”IP3

5.2.5.1.3 Slow Adoption of Technology

Slow technology adoption is also seen as a challenge in the SBSC. However, this challenge is focused on the livestock farmers. The Scottish Government has provided livestock farmers with a free tool called Myherd Statistics for herd management. However, the main limitation of Myherd statistics is that it collects only basic data regarding the cattle herd. It is inferred from the discussion that there is no central database which the livestock farmers and the abattoirs wherein the abattoirs also provide feedback to the livestock farmers regarding their performance. A study on adopting digital technologies by Joshi & Sharma (2022) in the agricultural food supply chain concluded that reliance on the latest technology will lead to improved food security, less food wastage, and improved operational efficiency. The industry practitioner also emphasised the use of the power of big data, which is not currently available to the stakeholders of the SBSC players.

“I think we're always want the power of data and I think what's lacking is a system the ScotEID, picked up at the start of producing all that. But what you want to be able to do is you want every producer giving data of how their cattle are getting on breeds, weight, age, sex, weight gains, to put to the finisher for the finisher to then take that data that data for him to performance, for him to then put the abattoir, the abattoir, then to feedback how they performed to the finisher, the finisher then to be able to read, respond back to the producer to say your cattle are good but this genetic line or this family didn't do so well we don't have enough people using the power of data”IP3

5.2.5.1.4 Lack of Supply Chain integration

Integration plays a more complex role in the context of supply chain resilience. Wieland and Wallenburg (2013) note that communication and cooperation can enhance supply chain resilience; however, integration itself may have limited impact, as excessive integration can restrict the autonomy of other supply chain actors.

The interview extract shows that the interviewee perceived the integration from the communication perspective. It further emphasises the importance of feedback, which should be spread across the entire SBSC.

“So it's not very integrated at all, it's not integrated. We don't even have good communication, good data flows of finding out what the prices are and how the finishers got on, and we're able to feed that information back”IP3

5.2.5.1.5 Critical Mass

Critical Mass is also identified as a challenge. The practitioner was very concerned about the lack of capacity and critical mass. The critical mass is based on the assumption that in the wake of the rising cost

of business and eroding productivity, what would be the required level of production which will keep the industry economically viable? The failure to have that threshold for the critical loss may lead to the closure of allied industries (Nousaine and Jolley 2013).

“We don't have the critical capacity, the critical mass in the future on that and so we are under extreme pressure at the moment, extreme pressure”IP3

In New Zealand, the farmer's cooperative has proposed closing a processing facility due to reduced cattle numbers (Sheep Central 2024). The importance of critical mass for the SBSC can be sensed from the interviewee's comments. If the suckler herd in Scotland keeps on declining, it means that it may impact the steady supply of cattle to the processors and ultimately to the retailers. The decreased production level may lead to reduced business of inputs and the closure of processing facilities.

5.2.5.1.6 Lack of Succession and Labour

QMS submitted a written response in UK Parliament (2022) mentioning the shortage of labour and the problems caused by it. (EPIC 2014) also mentioned that livestock farmers have started ceasing their businesses due to a lack of succession, which is persistent even after a decade. The interviewee emphasised on the lack of labour alongside succession.

“Many, many farms feel as a lack of labour young people coming on and also succession on the farms where your son or your daughter same as mine ,they're not there anymore and when it becomes like that, farmers are saying why should it keep farming or keep suckler cows when it's becoming too hard for me and my wife and I haven't got sons and daughters”IP3

5.2.5.1.7 Lack of Product Quality

The lack of product quality was also brought forward as a challenge. The importance of standardisation was also mentioned. It can be inferred from the interview extract below that, irrespective of the variety of breeds, a system must ensure the product's consistency. If the quality of cattle is not consistent, it may lead to increased food waste because the retailers sell products with definite specifications. If the livestock farmers keep ignoring their produce's quality, it may lead to a decrease in demand wherein they may not be able to opt for a premium price because to get a premium price, the product should be a premium product.

“we never provide uniformity and that means that problem with no uniformity in different breeds and all that is, how do we standardize it and make sure that we have what we call quality, how do you measure quality and that's going to be the biggest battle that we have is how do you actually measure quality”IP3

Figure 5.6 Challenges identified by Consultant

5.2.5.2 Theme Factor Contributing to the Supply Chain Resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC)

The IP3 identified Traceability, Supplier relationships and integrated business model as the contributors to resilience in the SBSC

5.2.5.2.1 Traceability

The industry practitioner mentioned in the interview that the quality assurance schemes introduced by QMS contribute to the resilience of the SBSC. The objective of QMS in starting those assurance schemes is to improve the quality of the cattle produced. The schemes have been designed in a manner wherein QMS claims the whole supply chain is assured. The horse meat scandal of Tesco shook consumer confidence in the originality and quality of the product. It was proposed that the government should take the initiative to ensure food safety and rebuild consumer trust in the supply chain (Barnett et al., 2016). The assurance schemes of QMS ensure that the Cattle & Sheep are born, reared and slaughtered in Scotland by complying with the highest standards of animal health and welfare, traceability, environmental sustainability and food safety (QMS, 2024c; 2024d). The feed assurance scheme of QMS ensures that the feed the suppliers provide is healthy and safe for the animals. The feed assurance schemes have set a high standard and operate under

the universal feed assurance scheme (QMS, 2024e). The haulage scheme ensures that the means of transport are safe for humans and animals. The prime importance is given to traceability and biosecurity. The drivers should be skilled, the vehicles should be well-maintained for the safety of the livestock (QMS, 2024f). The auction mart assurance scheme is also focused on traceability and biosecurity. It also ensures that the animals are properly handled (QMS, 2024g) The processor assurance scheme ensures that the Food Safety Act is complied with. Food safety, traceability, quality and animal welfare standards are adhered to (QMS, 2024h). The whole chain assurance is aimed at providing the consumer with the confidence that the product's journey from farm to fork has ensured the highest quality standards at each stage of the supply chain. It was very important to discuss the assurance schemes of QMS to infer from the interview extract why the industry practitioner believes that the QMS assurance schemes lead to a resilient supply chain.

“ I think they do. One of the things about the assurance schemes they have too many assurance schemes in farms. Some farmers will talk about four or five assurance schemes they need to tidy that up, they need to make sure it's done correctly and things like that. We need some way of making sure that we differentiate our product in the marketplace or as a niche or will become a commodity. You become a commodity, you just get just in the same boat, the same boat as Irish beef or beef from the dairy or New Zealand beef or Australian beef. We have to have that little bit extra on us to be able to see. This is our standards”

A recent study by Zhao G et al., (2022) discussed the role of traceability in ensuring resilience in the agri-food supply chain. The traceability was found to safeguard the supply chain against the demand, supply, biological, environmental, and transportation risks. If we try to map the assurance schemes of QMS with the traceability study of Zhao G et al., (2022), wherein the study presented a one-to-one resilience to risk model. The demand and supply risk can be mitigated by the Cattle assurance scheme, the biological and environmental risk is mitigated by the haulage and auction mart schemes, which have a special focus on biosecurity. Lastly, the logistical risk is mitigated by the haulage assurance schemes.

5.2.5.2.2 Supplier Relationships

To avoid supply risk, it is very important to develop supplier relationships. Yaun (2024) mentioned that the relationship with suppliers should be dynamic so that it can be adjusted to meet the varying customer demand and evolving market conditions. Blackhurst et al., (2011) discussed that a high level of trust needs to be developed with the suppliers. Apart from the supplier's capacity, the knowledge of alternate suppliers should be held. The building of supplier relationships leads to a resilient supply chain.

As evident from the interview extract, if the cattle supply meets the desired criteria, the buyer is unlikely to change the supplier. This shows that the buyer-supplier has reached a certain level of trust, and a robust feedback mechanism is in place.

“If you're producing cattle and the finisher comes and buys your cattle three years in a row, their cattle must be doing OK because he keeps coming to buy them”IP3

5.2.5.2.3 Integrated Business Model

A processing plant integrated with an abattoir serves many customers across the supply chain. It can be livestock producers, wholesalers, food service providers and retailers. Pereira (2014) mentioned that internal integration improves supplier responsiveness. Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009) also proposed that integration can lead to increased resilience in the supply chain.

“It's the abattoirs who manage themselves by making sure that they've got the processing part as well. The processing part is where they cut up, package and that's what they make their money, their add-on value” IP3

5.2.5.3 Theme 3 General Issues Related to the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

5.2.5.3.1 Lack of Trust

One of the characteristics of the SBSC is a lack of trust. The interviewee disclosed that, at present, the entire supply chain is suffering from a lack of trust from the livestock farmer to the retailers. Each player in the supply chain perceives that they are not getting the appropriate return and thinks that the other players are pocketing a higher return than themselves. Dubey et al., (2016) revealed that trust facilitates risk-taking among supply chain partners by ensuring that commitments are honoured and accurate information is shared. The study concluded that trust can improve supply chain resilience. It is concerning that low levels of trust within the SBSC are also associated with a lack of collaboration and the sharing of accurate information.

“So we're now left with a perception, a sector at the moment where you've got the farmers producing, you've got the finishers finishing, you've got the processors processing and the retailers selling each one of them currently thinks they are not getting a big enough share of the pie. The producers are finding that their costs are too much compared to the return they are getting in the market. The finishers are feeling that they're paying too much for store cattle. For what they're getting finishing. The processors feels that they're paying too much money for what the retailers prepared to pay them, so their margins are squeezing and the retailer feels that if he puts the price up at the end point, then they'll just the consumer will move to chicken or pork. Everybody's feeling squeezed”IP3

Quality Meat Scotland (QMS), as the levy body, along with the National Farmers Union Scotland (NFUS), the Scottish Association of Meat Wholesalers (SAMW), the Scottish Beef Association (SBA), and retailers should engage in transparent dialogue to address shared challenges. As discussed earlier, trust is a key contributor to supply chain resilience. A consensus should be developed on fair pricing, and a framework

should be proposed which is acceptable to all the stakeholders of the SBSC. With an industry already struggling, the supply chain partners are assuming that a supply chain partner retains a fraction of my profit can erode the relationship on a long-term basis. It is again reiterated that fair pricing system should be introduced.

5.2.5.3.2 Profitability Misrepresentation

One more thing which attracted attention was the appropriate profit sharing. For livestock farmers, it has been repeatedly mentioned that livestock farming in Scotland is suffering from a lack of returns. (SEPA 2024). From the interview extract below, it can be inferred that the retailers and processors are profitable, whereas the real challenge is for the livestock farmers who, even with the subsidies, are not able to meet the cost of doing business. It is mandatory to address this issue to ensure the long-term sustainability and resilience of the Scottish beef industry. If a decline in the number of suckler cows worsens in the future, then where will the processing sector get the critical mass, and retailers can easily exit by simply importing the meat and filling their shelves.

“The retailers will still be making money and the processors are still making money is because the processors have got the fifth quarter; whether it be bones, whether there be the tongue, the kidney and the liver wherever it is, the hide for sheepskin rugs or cars and all that, they aren't making money, but with all they're pleading or not”IP3

5.2.5.3.3 Cross Border Trade

Cross-border trade can lead to a lack of critical mass. Another alarming thing which was noted from the interview extract is the sale of cattle in England. As mentioned in the interview extract, a significant amount of cattle is sold in England because they offer higher prices. If such practices are not strictly dealt with, then the domestic beef supply chain may have a very detrimental effect. For instance, if the abattoirs and processing plants cannot meet the minimum threshold of critical mass, how can their economic viability be secured?

“and interesting thing would be to say that about one in six, one in seven of our store cattle store cattle in England and Scotland sorry, go down into England.They go down into England because they're getting short of beef Sukler beef”IP3

5.2.5.3.4 Slow Government Response

During the interview, the industry practitioner disclosed that the Government is very slow to respond. The farming sector has been subsidised in the past and is still subsidised. Due to subsidies, the efficiency of livestock farming has remained at a stagnant pace. The livestock farmers who are used to the subsidies are not happy with the present response of the government.

“as government and being very slow to come to the table to develop a policy, they say they're going in the right direction where it might be slow. And we're saying, well, the farmers haven't got that time for you to be slow because as you all know, farmers who used to it's beef farmers used to be well subsidized. Given suckler cow premiums, extensification and slaughter premiums. Now they're not giving anything. They've given money based on your areas of what you farm and they're just saying, so why should I do when I'm not getting support?”IP3

The below-mentioned extract further shows that the Government is not only slow to respond but their representatives are not well informed. This shows that the liaising between Government officials and industry stakeholders need to be improved.

“We need government to talk about it. I don't think the government have got the knowledge of people within them to actually know what they're going to do”IP3

5.2.5.3.5 Food Security

Stone and Rahimifard (2018) mentioned that resilience in agriculture food supply chains is vital but should not solely focus on the performance of the entities only. A resilient supply chain should have the goal of food security as well. The interview respondent is an industry practitioner, and his level of commitment can be gauged from his own word.

“I could be talking to our farmer one day, a retailer next day, a processor the next day and a estate owner next day a crofter the next day. It's the whole chain approach that we talk about and give advice and the main part of advice will be on genetics, health management, Veterinary and the Mark the markets and profitability that side of things. So it's the whole chain approach that I can give advice to farms”IP3

“if government have got to open up their eyes and can't, they've got to look at food security, they've got to look at food security and not realise that every time that the Irish could give us Beef because they could go elsewhere, the Australians give us because they're more interested in the Asian market.

These other countries can't be there to supply us, and don't rely on them doing that because there may be problems of imports and that and the problems the disease outbreaks and supply and we can will and we don't want to be left in a situation where we're not able to feed their own our own population. Now that was. That's why subsidies were brought into Europe after the World War Two, when they said we will never have to rely on imports or starve again. We need to be encouraging production and that's what we need to do, but the stories and the right signals are not there very much. So therefore, for the farming sector, especially for beef sector”IP3

After reading the interview extract, we can imagine the seriousness of the situation where food security is at risk alongside the resilience of the Scottish Bee supply chain. In the previous sections, we have discussed the challenges the Scottish beef industry faces. The respondent has proposed that to produce food for the Nation the Government has to make prompt decision making.

5.2.5.3.6 Uncertainty in Recovery Trends

As mentioned above, the SBSC stakeholders are waiting for the Government's response towards the announcement of new policy directions. An already struggling industry is pushed into uncertainty where they are not getting any information on how the suckler cow numbers will improve. The QMS focuses on promoting the brand strength, and the livestock farmers are sceptical about the future.

“At the moment there is no indication that no indication that numbers will come back up because there's nothing showing why numbers should come back up”IP3

5.2.5.3.7 Group Think

Another interesting thing which was noticed was group think. For instance, the representative body for farmers is, a membership body. People from different groups within the organisation are not opposing other groups if they are underrepresenting the members' interests in other institutions or forums. This shows a lack of consensus to be assertive in fighting for the farmer's rights. Groupthink (Vien 2016) can impair the ability to make sound decisions. As mentioned below, the industry practitioner highlighted that the representative bodies lack the strong drive to pursue issues based on the different fractions with different interests within the organisation.

“The N.... Union is meant to be our lobby body out there and you got ??? in there But the problem is that quite often he's within these groups at the same things you're quite often you if you, if you're within the groups, you get sucked up within the groups, you should be independent to these groups that actually be battering at their doors”IP3

The overall interview extracts revolve around the challenges the SBSC faces. Due to the interviewee's extensive experience, very classified knowledge regarding the SBSC is obtained. After analysing the interview extract, it has become evident that the SBSC is currently under a very stressed phase. The factors contributing to the resilience are also surfaced during the interview. Still, it is noteworthy that to attain the desired level of supply chain resilience, the SBSC has to confront the challenges. The identified challenges overlap, and it is certain that by addressing one challenge, the subsequent challenge may lose its strength. For instance, the SBSC is currently suffering from a lack of profitability. Another identified challenge is the lack of product quality. If the quality of the product gets improved, then it means that the premium product will fetch a premium price, and it may lead to a profitable industry with a healthy return. Likewise,

when the industry return increases, the succession can also be addressed because it may become easier to attract the youth if the industry is making profits. Moreover, if the slow adoption of technology is addressed, it may reduce the labour challenges as less physically intensive work will be required to look after the cattle herd.

5.2.6 Interview 4:Cattle Society Official Interview Participant IP4

This interview was conducted with the official of a cattle society. The society was Established in 1879, and it serves as the official body overseeing the Aberdeen-Angus cattle breed in the United Kingdom. Its primary mission is to ensure the breed's authenticity, quality, and advancement.

The initial coding is shown in the figure below.

Figure 5.7 Initial Coding in Nvivo IP4

5.2.6.1 Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of Scottish Beef Supply Chain(SBSC)

The following resilient contributors were identified by the IP4.

5.2.6.1.1 Artificial Insemination

The interview respondent extensively discussed artificial insemination during the interview. Moses (2024) discussed the advantages and disadvantages of artificial insemination in livestock cattle. It gives a freedom of selection of breed with superior genetic traits and a greater control over disease. Since it is a process, due care must be exercised while administering it. Tadesse et al., (2022) explained that the economic loss associated with artificial insemination cannot be ignored. It may happen that the cow does not conceive on the first attempt, leading to multiple attempts to execute the process successfully. The consideration for economic viability and the success rate has been pressed upon since the initiation of reproductive technologies (Vishwanath 2003). Artificial insemination is mainly used in Dairy Herds. In Scotland, artificial insemination assists in reproducing its prime cattle brand, Aberdeen Angus. The purpose of this is to ensure the traceability of the cattle. The program is called the Sire Verification Programme. This is entirely voluntary to the members of the society. The members who want to participate will provide the cattle's DNA sample, which will be verified against the Herd Book at the society. Upon confirmation, it will be stamped as Sire Verified (Aberdeen Angus 2024). This gives increased confidence to the consumers, especially after the horse meat scandal, which badly shook consumer confidence (Barnett 2016)

It was mentioned in the interview the level of disease preparedness of the SBSC is very poor.

“I would argue as a as a broad piece, the entire industry is woefully underprepared for any disease shock”IP4

The role of artificial insemination was reiterated in the following words

“So if there was something that wiped out a pile of bulls, there's still a lot of semen frozen in tanks all over the country that we could very quickly get back to. I'm the other one would be replacement females”IP4

“We have a year, but there's, you know, there's quite a lot of embryos again sitting frozen in tanks that you could you could spin up and get get into cows and bring to the marketplace” IP4

“But I think on a resilience term, there are a lot of eggs and tanks around the country or embryos and tanks around the country that we could bring back to the market quite quickly. But it's just the length of time from those embryos going into a cow to actually having marketable Livestock, at the end of it”IP4

This highlights the important fact of a disease outbreak, like Foot and Mouth and cattle loss. Then, to resume the supply chain operations, the semen kept frozen shall be used for rebuilding the herd. It can be inferred from that arrangement that this practice will augment the SBSC capability against a disruptive

disease that has hit the livestock on a larger scale through quick recovery. If we look at the earlier comment in which the respondent disclosed that the disaster preparedness of the SBSC is not ideal, Therefore artificial insemination can be considered a contributing factor in the supply chain resilience of the SBSC because it increases traceability (Zaho G et al .2022) and it is recognized as one of the contributing factors of agri-food supply chains. It should be considered by one of the key players of the SBSC, farmers, that the economic cost and the probability of success should be checked from time to time. Notably, the Scottish Government mentioned in their Beef Sector Report 2020 (Gov 2014) that resilience in the beef sector can be obtained by relying on the quality of genetics. Teece (2016) mentioned processes or routines as a strong capability factor; therefore, we have also classified artificial insemination as a process and contributor to the resilience of the SBSC as identified by the IP4.

5.2.6.1.2 Brand Strength

Consumer preferences are changing from meat consumption to vegetarian-based products seen as substitutes for meat products Kerslake et al., (2022). The interviewee highlighted the brand strength of the Scottish Beef.

“Angus brand is worldwide. You go back to the early 20th century, well, early to mid-20th century, and you had People coming from all over the world to buy genetics here because they recognize the quality of the genetics that we produce, and I think that association has carried on from then to now that Scotland has seen as a place of quality”

Teixeira and Rodrigues (2019) mentioned that the meat industry faces significant challenges stemming from evolving consumer preferences influenced by environmental concerns, public health impacts, and ethical considerations. The disease outbreaks and horse meat sold as beef led to reduced consumption of red and processed meats, severely impacting the industry. Simultaneously, demand for natural, organic, and grass-fed meats is rising, often associated with regenerative agriculture practices that improve soil quality and sequester CO₂. Consumers increasingly priorities' higher animal welfare standards and scrutinise meat brands on emotional and ethical grounds, seeking alignment with their values. This shift, particularly towards alternatives beyond traditional beef, pork, and chicken, necessitates that meat brands adapt by understanding and responding to diverse consumer lifestyle trends.

The changing consumer behaviors based on the perception that meat consumption is unhealthy, and the beef sector is polluting the environment may lead to demand disruptions. In the event of a demand disruption the brand strength can be seen as a contributor to the resilience. For instance, in a demand disruption, the band strength can be projected to offset the consumers' negative perceptions. This relationship needs to be empirically proven. But we look at the production of Scottish beef, it is mainly grass-based, and higher animal welfare standards are observed. The assurance schemes run by QMS are

based on whole-chain assurance. The assurance schemes range from feed assurance so that the consumer should know what the cattle are being fed with. What is the quality of feed and its impact on the quality of the meat produced. The cattle and sheep assurance scheme can then gain the consumer confidence that the highest level of animal welfare is complied with. The safety and health of the livestock is assured. It also serves as the traceability to provide the consumer that confidence that the animal is born and reared on the Scottish land. Likewise, the haulage assurance scheme ensures that the vehicles in which they are being transported are safe for the transportation of animals. The auction assurance schemes also ensure that the traceability of the animals is assured. The assurance scheme for processors assures that the cleanliness standards and health and safety requirements are completed at the processing plants. These assurance schemes have mainly focused on traceability and welfare of the livestock animals. QMS is already promoting Scottish Beef in the global markets. Therefore, to avoid demand disruption, brand strength can surely be used for preparedness against demand disruption, which is based on changing consumer preferences.

5.2.6.1.3 Product Quality

During the interview the interviewee also discussed about the product quality.

“Scotland is seen to be synonymous with a quality aspect in beef worldwide” IP4

Another comment was very interesting wherein the interviewee mentioned that the Angus Breed itself is resilient based on its characteristics.

“So I think the the Angus breed lends itself to a more a more resilient supply chain system because.

Much, far reduced labour” IP4

Kolpakov (2024) mentioned that Aberdeen Angus has specific characteristics which distinguish it from other breeds for instance its capability to adapt to the environmental conditions, the rate of growth due to enhanced fertility and expectancy of life.

Aberdeen Angus Cattle Society (2024) mentioned that it is a breed which is reliant on grass based feed and therefore has low input costs. Consequently, Aberdeen angus provides a better profit margin to the producer and also helps the producer to meet its environment goals.

Therefore, the product quality of Aberdeen angus based on its genetic characteristics make it a strong contributor to resilience of the SBSC. If we consider it from the supply side that if there is an increase in input cost of fertilisers or a disruption of fertiliser it will impact the breed in a least manner. The reason is that it grass based. This means that from the preparedness perspective to avoid any disruption caused by input costs or its availability the supply chain will remain resilient because the supply of a consistent quality product will not be discontinued. Another characteristic of Aberdeen angus is that it is not labour intensive.

This also ensures a steady supply of cattle by addressing the issue of lack of labour which the livestock farmers are experience now.

The strength of being a grass-based livestock farming was also expressed during the interview.

“There's a very simple fact Scotland's over 70% grass and people own that grassland and so they have to receive a, you know, most folks want to receive a return for the investment and cows are a good way of doing it”IP4

The capability factors of Product Quality and Brand Strength closely align with the capability factor of Market position identified by Pettit et al., (2013).

5.2.6.2 Theme 2 Challenges Faced by Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The following Challenges were highlighted by IP4.

5.2.6.2.1 Structural Dependency and Processing Consolidation

During the information gathering about the SBSC through various sources, industry statistics were provided by G. Hill, a Beef specialist and Industry Consultant, via (email communication, 21 August 2024). The SBSC is witnessing decline in cow numbers for the last several years. Scotland now falls below 400,000 suckler cows sitting at 394,709 which is a fall of 3.5% since last year and approximately 7% since 2018. With already decreasing herd size and the processing sector dominated by the Irish companies may limit the Scottish farmers to be the price takers.

“I think the other problem within it also is good if you go back to the Irish point, the vast majority of beef imported into this country comes from Ireland, and the vast majority of the owners of the abattoirs in this country come from Ireland, you know, so they've actually, they've done a beautiful job from an Irish perspective of guaranteeing a higher value market by owning the abattoirs here with those cozy relationships and being able to pipeline product in where they where they can”IP4

Based on the comments, this can further disturb the market equilibrium of Irish companies if they start channelising and prioritising the processing of Irish beef due to the lack of Scottish beef. This dependency on external entities can be aggravated during economic downturns, supply chain disruptions or pandemics where Irish entities could prioritize the processing of Irish Beef over Scottish Beef

5.2.6.2.2 Critical Mass

The economic viability of an abattoir depends upon a certain number of livestock animals being processed so that it can meet its overhead expenses. The Scottish Government Beef Report 2020 mentions that the throughput of Scottish abattoirs decreased by 15%.

“And you know those each of the processing plants in the country rely on a certain number of animals per day going through that line to cover the costs and there's not, you know, that's put the processing sector does operate on very thin margins” IP4

Therefore, if the processing sector remains unable to meet the threshold to be economically viable and may lead to closure of the abattoir as mentioned in the interview extract.

“I can see Scotland losing an abattoir in the next five years if we can't stop the cow numbers going down”IP4

The closure of an abattoir not only puts pressure on the remaining abattoirs but can also lead to logistical challenges as the farmers have to travel far places to get the cattle slaughter.

Over the last 15 years, Scotland has experienced a 10% annual reduction in abattoirs, leading to the closure of 10 facilities between 2008 and 2018. This reduction has disproportionately affected rural and remote areas, particularly the Highlands and Islands, leaving many producers without nearby slaughtering options. The closure of the Orkney abattoir in 2018, for example, forced producers to travel approximately 5 hours via ferry and road to the Dingwall abattoir, resulting in increased costs and logistical challenges for farmers in this region. Scottish Producers travel an average of 54 miles, often requiring journeys of approximately 90 minutes. In contrast, producers in England and Wales travel significantly shorter distances, averaging 26-31 miles, with journey times of around 42-50 minutes. (SAOS 2024). This also increases the cost of doing business. Therefore, the loss of critical mass can lead to other challenges, such as the closure of abattoirs and logistical issues.

5.2.6.2.3 Land Deprivation

The land used for livestock farming is now being allocated to tree plantation.

“then the problem we now have is that the land that a lot of these guys are on is very, very eligible for planting for trees, for carbon”IP4

Scottish Government (Gov, 2021) issued its third land use strategy in 2021. This land use strategy for the period of 2021-2026 outlines the significant shift in land use priorities in Scotland, emphasising sustainable land use to address climate change and biodiversity crises. The Scottish Government is prioritizing increased woodland creation, with a target of planting 18,000 hectares of trees annually by 2024-25, and significant peatland restoration goals. These initiatives often involve converting land previously used for agriculture and livestock farming into forestry. This shift supports carbon sequestration, biodiversity enhancement, and Scotland's net-zero targets but poses challenges for traditional farming, especially

livestock farmers, who face reduced land availability for grazing. This is seen as a challenge by the livestock farmers.

5.2.6.2.4 Lack of Preparedness against Disease

The interviewee expressed that the industry is underprepared for the any large disease outbreak.

“I would argue as a as a broad piece, the entire industry is woefully underprepared for any disease shock”IP4

The interviewee expressed his personal experience that he noticed a lack of biosecurity practices on farms, which can lead to disease spread from one farm to another.

“the five years that I worked with that company that I was asked to dip my boots into disinfectant before I went on farm having been at all the other farms, I think.I could only remember 3 farmers and five years of 4000 farm visits a year actually asking me to dip my boots. So, you know, we are woefully underprepared for a disease outbreak or for certainly for control, for managing any issue ourselves”IP5

Maye and Chan (2020) mentioned that Biosecurity is critical for livestock farming as it helps prevent and control the spread of diseases, ensuring the health and productivity of farm animals. Effective biosecurity measures such as disinfecting equipment, controlling farm visitor access, isolating new stock, and proper disposal of waste act as barriers to the introduction and spread of infections. Disease outbreaks can severely disrupt farming operations, leading to financial losses, decreased production efficiency, and animal welfare concerns.

Therefore, this shows that the farmers should be trained on biosecurity to avoid the spread of infection and disease outbreaks.

5.2.6.2.5 Lack of Export Ambition

Lack of Export ambition is also surfaced as a problem.

“UK market is whoops 60-70% self sufficient.So you're always going to have imports, and my mind actually means that the abattoirs will always lack ambition to export and seek higher value markets because they dare not lose the domestic marketplace because that's their bread and butter.That's their daily piece and as long as we have those cozy relationships between the retail landscape and the abattoir landscape will never actually have proper processesor .I'm processor ambition to seek new markets and drive for higher value markets for a broad piece” IP4

The cozy relationship between the processors and the retailers reflects the structural rigidity of the SBSC where the cattle produced is aimed to be sold to the supermarkets.

5.2.6.2.6 Lack of Succession

Scottish livestock farming is labour-intensive, and due to a lack of returns, the younger generation is unwilling to join the family businesses.

“No new generation following them through. I'm no umm. You know, not only did not succession”IP4

5.2.6.2.7 Uncertain Government Policies

After the Brexit of UK from EU the government response towards policy initiatives has been very slow. The government is focusing more on environmental concerns, and it was reported by Mackie (2021) that a national farming official has accused the Scottish government that they are planning to reduce the suckler herd by a significant number to reduce carbon emissions. Due to such rumours the livestock farmers have been very sceptical and remained uncertain about the government's future directive. This is evident from the below mentioned interview extracts.

“I think the other one that I would say is always a and issue and will always be an issue as the fear of future government policy”IP4

“You know there was that narrative floating about for a while It seems to have gone away for now, but I'm not sure it's gone away completely that the Scottish Government thinks that, you know, are there are those who have said the Scottish Government thinks the easiest way of solving the agricultural carbon problem is to eliminate 100,000 suckler cows now. You know, if your government is not going to support you, then where does that leave you”IP4

5.2.6.2.8 Potential Import of Australian Black Angus

During the interview, the interviewee expressed a fear of the potential import of Australian black Angus. The interviewee mentioned that the quality of both is the same, but the cost of production of Australian Angus beef is less than Aberdeen Angus. It is, therefore, noteworthy that the Government should consider this fear of the livestock farmers.

“the one that actually fears me the most because it's using the same brand as Australian Black Angus, I think Australian Black Angus will start to make inroads in this marketplace probably more in the catering sector for a start and but you know, the Australians can produce it or do produce it cheaper. Umm, but actually it's not a bad, you know, it's it's not a bad standard and realistically, the genetics that we're using and they're using are you know, they're that”IP4

Figure 5.8 Challenges Identified by Cattle Society Official

5.2.6.3 Theme 3 Industry Development

The interviewee emphasised the need for a central database for industry development. It was proposed that government funding should be allocated for research in genetic diversity. It was also proposed that the government should invest more in SoctEID so that they should be able to generate more effective data to make appropriate strategic decisions. Yuan (2024) proposed that information sharing and integration can lead to supply chain resilience.

5.2.6.3.1 Central Data Base

“One central database rather, as you know, three separate databases across the UK”IP4

5.2.6.3.2 Genetic Diversity Research for Breed Resilience

“I think the one thing that would be really useful would be a database of embryos that exist across the country”IP4

“if government were to fund anything, I think it would be research around the genetic diversity of embryos in tanks across each breed to make sure there was sufficient diversity”IP4

5.2.6.3.3 Enhancing ScotEID data utilization for Readiness

The IP4 implied that the Government should invest in ScotEID to enhance the readiness of the SBSC against potential disruptions.

“I think there's really simple the government just needs to put more money into ScotEID to allow ScotEID to to gather, hold and carry and analyse the data better. You know, I think that's where we're lacking is the exploration of the existing data and the understanding of the existing data. And I think that would that would vastly improve the readiness” IP4

The big data analytics can guide the farmers to make informed decision to improve their decision making (Neethirajan and Kemp 2021). Therefore, it can inferred that the use of big data analytics and by creation of a central database will greatly benefit the SBSC.

The interview with the cattle society official identified the factors contributing to the supply chain resilience and the challenges faced by the SBSC. It also reflected on initiative the government should take to enhance the supply chain resilience. Artificial insemination is to be used to enhance the supply chain resilience by recovering after a major disaster outbreak. The product quality and brand strength contribute to the supply chain resilience. The challenges are very diversified ranging from lack of succession and use of lack of resources to use big data analytics. The most alarming concern is lack of preparedness of the supply side against any major disease outbreak. The absence of clear future government directives has further contributed to scepticism among livestock farmers, who are already facing low returns, labour shortages, and succession challenges. The interviewee expressed that the government support required to make the industry resilient is lacking. Instead of investing in improving livestock farming the government is redirecting land usage from livestock farming to tree planting. Actionable suggestions for industry development were also proposed by the participant.

5.2.7 Interview 5 Livestock Farmer Interview Participant (IP 5)

IP 5 (AM)

The interview participant IP 5 is a dedicated livestock farmer who manages a mixed farming operation alongside his wife. The IP5 brought a unique perspective to the SBSC, combining hands-on agricultural experience with professional expertise as a veterinary doctor. His veterinary background has provided him with valuable insights into animal health and welfare, contributing to the resilience and sustainability of his farming practices The IP5 operates a mixed farm spanning approximately 173 hectares (430 acres), focusing on beef production alongside the cultivation of barley and hay. In addition to managing his farm, the IP5 holds a senior executive position in a farming union, where he plays an influential role in representing and advocating for the interests of the agricultural community.

Initials	Role/Position	Farm Size (Ha)	Farm Type	Years in Farming	Primary Activity	Organisational Role
AM	Livestock Farmer and Vet	Approx. 173 (430 acres)	Mixed (Cattle & Crops)	Approx. 20 years	Beef Production, Barley, and Hay	Senior Executive in a Farming Union

Table 5.1 Interview Participant Profile IP (AM) 5

The interview was transcribed, and the initial codes generated are displayed in the below-mentioned figure

Figure 5.9 Initial coding of Transcript in Nvivo IP 5

5.2.7.1 Theme 1 Challenges in the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The interview participant highlighted various challenges during the interview, and challenges were grouped based on their similarity to each other

Sub Themes

5.2.7.1.1 Economic Challenges

The economic challenge faced by the livestock farmers needs immediate attention. During the interview, the participant reiterated how this challenge is impacting livestock farmers.

“You've got a cash flow going or you may have to buy young females heifers and put them in calf and calve them, which means you're looking at, you know, 12 months before you get your first calves 2 years before

you get any money back. So, there's a lot of money lying out of cost up front and getting there. And that's going to be one of the big difficulties in terms of resilience” IP5

5.2.7.1.1.1 Lack of Financial Returns

The SBSC's main economic challenge is the lack of financial returns from the livestock farmers' perspective. The financial distress is linked to the declining cattle numbers. The interviewee mentioned the lack of financial returns on three occasions. On one occasion, he attributed the lack of returns to the decline in the cattle numbers. The consequences of the lack of profitability were also mentioned, and it was pointed out that due to this persistent unprofitability, livestock farmers are giving up farming.

“What's happening in Scotland is the returns and in supply chain there's a lot of folk getting out, but actually commissioned at work with QMS, which we're just going to hopefully be into discussions within the next week” IP5

“And I think you'll find consistently cattle numbers are falling and it's exactly the same reasons as here the returns aren't there”IP5

“one of the biggest issues I see in the industry is the lack of returns, lack of margin” IP5

5.2.7.1.1.2 Decreasing Bull Sales

As mentioned earlier, the number of suckler cows has decreased considerably over the last several years. Consequently, it has also impacted bull sales and the livestock farmers selling bulls to the other livestock farmers suffer losses and the interview participant termed it as the big picture. It can be inferred from this comment that the overall Scottish beef industry is confronting the issue of a decrease in the sale of Bulls. This may lead to lack of motivation for livestock farmers to buy and rear bulls as the demand has decreased.

“particular trouble selling Bulls, but what I am finding is the number of Bulls are selling per year is going down because the number of cows just aren't there. That's that's the big picture”IP5

5.2.7.1.1.3 Competition for work force

A serious concern was expressed regarding the financial strength of the Livestock farming segment of the supply chain. It was mentioned that due to the lack of profit margins, the livestock farmers are not able to provide good salaries to hire competent staff. A specific mention of the renewable sector was mentioned. The following comment expresses this concern.

“when it comes to paying salaries to get good staff, we can't compete with other sectors like the renewable sector. We just can't compete in price because we're not meeting the profit margins”IP5

5.2.7.1.2 Structural and Operational Barriers

The structural and operational barriers confronted by the SBSC were also discussed. The participant highlighted various aspects of the SBSC, which signifies a power imbalance in the supply chain. Power imbalances in supply chains reduce profitability by enabling dominant players to prioritise individual gains over collective performance (Edirisinghe et al., 2011). Such imbalances often reduce financial performance and innovation by discouraging collaboration and fairness (Glavee-Geo 2022).

5.2.7.1.2.1 Retailer Dominance

The major concern of the participant as a livestock farmer was the role retailers are playing in the power dynamics. The pertinent interview extract is shared below. A very important element in the extract is that the retailers are not focused on building relationships. The staff employed by the retailers who are engaged in procurement are not focused on building long-term relationships, and this is due to the high turnover of the employees of the retailers.

“One of the issues we've got with retailers is that in their purchasing teams, it's not a long term arrangement you have. There's a high turnover of buyers, so people will sit in a job for two to three years and then move on somewhere else and somebody else comes in who I've got the cat. I've got the meeting, the margins to make my mark, to get my promotion and that is one of the biggest issues I see in dealing with retailers. Isn't that long term?”IP5

“Maturity of relationship is not developed and it's simply because young whippersnappers, as I've called them, are, you know, upward mobile young people who want to make that impression. Oh, I've done this that in the next I need a promotion. That's one of the biggest things we're up against. Whereas if we got people who are in there and away from this culture, you know, a job for no more than four years and you move on, let's get people to sit down and create long term relationships”IP5

Another serious concern was the lack of trust and business ethics. As mentioned above, the power imbalance leads to a lack of financial returns in the supply chain. It is also evident from the interview extract below that the interviewee has expressed his grave concern that the desire to conduct the business ethically is missing. The supply chain partners need to discuss how they can collaborate with one another to reduce the loss, and instead of profit sharing, a loss-sharing approach needs to be developed.

“Let's sit down. Have these discussions as you see about where as value gained and where is value lost in the whole chain”IP5

“Where can I save you a loss and where Can you gain me value? “IP5

“These discussions just don't take place because at every stage of the supply chain, it's all about the self-interest and self-preservation and it's a whole different mindset. We're going to have to develop”IP5

5.2.7.1.2.2 Processor Dominance

Alongside the Retailer dominance of how they are manipulating the products on their shelves. Another structural complication that was noticed was the concentration of the processing sector. Rather than a complication, it is a fear that Irish companies own most of the big processing plants. In a news editorial, Sleight (2023) reported that ABP, an Irish processing firm, has announced the acquisition of Scot beef. The entire industry was very concerned about this development, which was leading to high power concentration in a single processor. This acquisition put ABP among the largest processing plants in Europe.

The implications of this acquisition were highlighted in the discussion. The interviewee mentioned that due to this concentration, the small businesses already struggling have ceased their operations. Due to the closure of the small abattoirs, the livestock farmers have to make long journeys to get their animals slaughtered. Due to the structural imbalances and lack of bargaining power of the farmers, the participant mentioned that as a Researcher, I am trying to unravel a complex thing. The interview transcript is shared below to show the concerns of the interviewee.

“You know ABP have just invested a massive amount in Perth. We've got a couple of North East there. One is getting a bit tired. There's one locally in Dingle here. He's losing money hand over fist and doesn't know what to do. He's sold to his butcher shop chain to tie themselves over financially, unless something turns out quickly, I can't see him surviving much more than two three years. And he's not the only one that others are going to go as well”IP5

“So we end up with stock having to travel further to get slaughtered, fewer options, more control falling at the hands of processors, which again is going to drive down the margins in the industry”IP5

“It's a very, very complex thing you're trying to unravel”IP5

5.2.7.1.2.3 Lack of Succession and Aging Population

The participant also highlighted an operational barrier, the lack of succession. He shared his own example: his children do not want to join livestock farming as a profession. The reason is that the level of commitment which the job demands is not appropriately rewarded.

“The children are not taking it on because the returns for the amount of money raised each year is not worth the pressure. They have seen their parents going through and they've left farming altogether. My two children out of farming, they're not interested. They will not be coming back”IP5

Another concern expressed was the ageing population. It was mentioned in the Scottish Government's scheme (2022) for new entrants that the average age of male and female farmers is over 55. The same fact was expressed by the interviewee as under

“And Population farming is getting old very quickly. The average age is now over 62. That's not healthy” IP5

It is very alarming for the Scottish beef Industry that there is a lack of succession, and the population is ageing. Livestock farming is a physically intensive job, and the interview participant correctly mentioned that the average age is over 62 and it is not healthy.

5.2.7.1.2.4 No Rebuilding Plan / Post-Crisis Recovery Planning

IP 5 mentioned that although procedures are laid down on how to respond to a disease outbreak, there are no recovery plans to rebuild after the disease outbreak.

“Where the disease outbreak, you see it coming. Bam, back and forth. Start to rebuild already. There is no rebuild plan on the go for this. That's, I think the big message. There is no plan” (IP5)

The comment “Bam, back and forth” implies a reactive approach where actions are taken only after a crisis has occurred, rather than having proactive measures in place to mitigate damage. This lack of preparedness is further compounded by the absence of a structured rebuilding plan, which the speaker identifies as the “big message” Without a clear framework for rebuilding the livestock, farmers may not return to farming, which can be very detrimental to the SBSC.

5.2.7.1.2.5 Lack of Veterinary Services

The lack of veterinary service was also mentioned as a challenge. The limited access to veterinary services may result in late detection of disease and its treatment. This can lead to poor herd management regarding vaccination and period check-up's. It may also contribute to the mental stress of the livestock farmers who are already combating a lack of financial return and day-by-day increasing regulatory pressures. It was submitted by FSS (Food Standards Scotland) to the Scottish Parliament that they are facing a shortage in the recruitment of Veterinarians (Scottish Parliament, 2024).

“Getting a lot of veterinary treatments is becoming more and more difficult for reasons that we can't seem to elicit” IP 5

5.2.7.1.2.6 Lack of Trust

The IP5 mentioned a lack of trust among the supply chain players. The major retailers are squeezing the other supply chain players because they have greater bargaining power. As mentioned in the comment, the retailers are answerable to their shareholders and meet their shareholders' higher profit expectations, which

can leave the farmers with very thin margins and make them price takers. The lack of transparent communication between the retailers and the producers seems to have created a structural imbalance.

“Is the supply chain fair ? that is going to take a lot of honest talking, plain talking and I can't see that happening, particularly the retailers, because they're answerable to their shareholders and shareholders demand more and more returns. So that is that dichotomy that is going to be difficult to unravel” IP5

The following comment shows that the livestock farmers have suspicions about the role of QMS, a levy body. This shows that the government's influence can impact fair policymaking and funding priorities.

“the major stakeholder in QMS is the Scottish Government. So they're not going to argue with Scottish Government because he who pays the piper calls a tune with Organisation that lobbies government for these bits and pieces” IP5

5.2.7.1.2.7 Critical Mass

The IP5 also mentioned the importance of Critical Mass. In the absence of a critical mass of livestock supply, the supply chain will not be able to sustain its operations. The IP 5 commented on the critical mass as follows.

“Again, we often the Union talk about critical mass. There are certain number of livestock units to support an auction market to support a feed farm to support haulage companies” IP 5

The IP5 has pointed out the ripple effect of lack of livestock animals which can impact the auction marts and the haulage companies

5.2.7.1.3 Technological Challenges

5.2.7.1.3.1 Slow technology adoption

The SBSC, from the perspective of livestock farming, is slow to adopt new technology. The participant mentioned that they are trying to persuade the government to buy a system called smaXtech, which can drastically improve the efficiency in livestock farming. The smaXtec system enables proactive health management for dairy cows by providing early detection of diseases through continuous monitoring of internal body temperature, drinking behavior, rumination, and activity levels. It helps detect illnesses such as mastitis, ketosis, and pneumonia before clinical symptoms appear, reducing treatment costs and improving herd health and productivity. The system also supports veterinarians with detailed health data, minimizing medication use and enhancing animal welfare (smaXtec, 2024).

“There is technology. There's a system called smaXtech, which is a major leap forward. It's a bolus that goes in the rumen and monitors the body temperature and gives you health and welfare indicators and

breathing indicators from the temperature and the timing of it is a major step forward pushing government to give us some support to get that system out and running”IP5

5.2.7.1.3.2 Block Chain

Blockchain technology is widely recognized today by the industry, and it is used to build trust among supply chain partners. The adoption of blockchain leads to enhanced cooperation by executing transparent transactions (Ali & Govindan 2023).

The participant also highlighted the risk associated with the usage of blockchain but emphasised that fair trade practices in term of profit distribution can be achieved by using blockchain technology.

“Other thing that's interestingly coming on into the game now is blockchain and selling animals using blockchain? It carries risks, but it also has a potential much bigger returns back to the primary producer and that is an underdevelopment. At the minute there's a guy who's from Australia is working on that with a few folk in Scotland”IP5

5.2.7.1.3.3 Data Gathering

The interview participant also showed concern regarding data gathering. It was mentioned that although the Scottish Government has provided a free tool for herd movement, it is insufficient. Livestock farmers need performance-based data to be more efficient and more resilient, more prepared, and respond to disruptions.

“Access to some data in terms of calving interval and calves per cow and things like that, but the performance data is not getting recorded anywhere. And it's simple tools for farmers in terms of efficiency if you take”IP5

5.2.7.1.4 Environmental Challenges & Regulatory Pressures

The environmental challenge of Greenhouse gas emissions came under discussion during the interview

Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions

The greenhouse gas emission calculation is a question mark. The FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations) does not consider the offsetting measures of carbon sequestration. FAO published its report in 2023 on pathways to reduce livestock emissions, and it is recognised that carbon sequestration is also part of the solution (AHDB, 2024). The interview participant IP5 raised his concern about the calculation of GHG emissions by the livestock. As evident in the interview transcript, he highlighted the inaccurate calculations of GHG emissions are not putting the industry under pressure. It was also pointed out that the government should consider this and be ready to invest in the livestock sector instead of reducing the cattle herd to less contribute to the emissions. The Scottish Government has set a target to

reduce greenhouse gas emissions to net zero by 2045 (Scottish Government, 2020) and instead of pursuing the farmers and crofters who want to give up livestock farming is encouraging them to alternate land use for tree plantation.

5.2.7.1.4.1 Slow Government Response

The IP 5, expressed his concern regarding the slow government response. This slow response is fostering a fear amongst farmers as to how the future will look like. The livestock farmers who are already price takers are fighting with lack of financial returns and the future payments are linked with sustainability and biosecurity objectives.

“Something that puzzles me because I like to get decisions made quickly and get on with things I've worked in government and even my time in government. It never went as slowly as it's going today and what I'm not sure is just are they too busy trying to balance competing ideologies like you're vegans and you're re welders and you're? Let me call them the animal rights activists. Are we too busy trying to balance out and say this? Look, come on” IP 5

Scotland's post-Brexit agricultural policy framework includes a four-tier support system under the "Future Support Framework" This comprises a base-level direct payment, enhanced payments, elective payments, and complementary support, blending direct and competitive payments to achieve sustainability targets. Furthermore, Scotland has committed to aligning its policies with CAP (Common Agriculture Policy) principles to ensure continuity and adaptability in changing social, economic, and environmental conditions. Despite these reforms, criticisms have emerged, with the National Farmers Union (NFUS) Scotland describing the Agricultural Reform Route Map as inadequate, highlighting the tension between maintaining EU-aligned policies and addressing domestic agricultural needs in a post-Brexit context (Greer and Grant, 2023).

The comment of IP5 "get on with things" implies a desire for decisive leadership and practical solutions rather than being caught up in ideological debates. The IP5 also mentioned that by balancing the competing interests of vegans, animal welfare advocates and traditional farmers.

The extract highlights the challenge of balancing divergent views of vegans, animal welfare advocates, and livestock farmers, which may create policy gridlock. These divergent views on livestock farming, sustainability, and ethical practices can further delay decision-making.

5.2.7.1.4.2 Auctions Marts

The participant also presented a solution to offset this structural imbalance by suggesting that the livestock farmers should try to route more sales through live auction rings. The comment below mentions that the auction rings can lead to better transparency.

“if we started losing auction marts because that sets the base open market price. It would be good if a lot more farmers would start putting stuff back the auction marts for the live sale ring”IP5

5.2.7.1.4.3 Supply chain fairness.

NFUS recently started a campaign called Shelf Watch. This campaign explores how the retailers in Scotland treat Scottish Beef products. The interviewee also mentioned that ALDI is very supportive of promoting Scottish beef. ALDI is increasingly concerned about the decline in suckler cow numbers, raising questions about future beef supply. While dairy herds can supplement some of the supply, retailers like Marks & Spencer have already secured much of this source, leaving limited availability for others. The participant speculates that retailers may need to explore new strategies to secure their supply chains, such as forming direct partnerships with farmers, investing in farm collaborations, or developing vertically integrated systems to ensure consistent production.

“I don't know if you're aware or not, but NFU Scotland is, on the running a campaign called Shelf Watch? And that is looking at what is on the supermarkets own label stuff, where it's actually coming from and the naming is Scotch, British or abroad”IP5

“ALDI have been a big supporter of Scotland and worth your while having a chat with ALDI because they are getting very concerned the support, not just Scottish produce but British produce, and they're trying to source 100% from Britain. And what they're really concerned about is this drop in the suckler cow numbers. Where are they going to get the beef from? Yes, the percentage will come out of a dairy herd, but you like some Marks and Spencer's have tied a lot of that up already. So the Dairy Herd source is not really open to all that they move into. What does all they do ? Do they start moving in and working with farmers and putting money in to ensure their own supply chain. Do they develop their own farm system and farm partnerships or farm collaborations to Guarantee a supply system? How do the structures? How do you pay it?” IP5

The results of the shelf watch of NFUS for December 2024 have been published and shared below. Surprisingly, the participant mentioned that ALDI is very supportive towards Scottish beef, but the shelf watch result showed that ALDI has considerably reduced the reliance on Scottish meat. This conforms to the interviewee's claim that ALDI is very much concerned about the decrease in the number of suckler

cows, and it shows that they have perceived that the number will keep on declining, and they started reducing the shelf space with Scottish Beef products.

Figure 5.10 "Proportion of Beef by Country of Origin Across Major UK Retailers" (Source NFUS Shelf watch report 2024)

The figure illustrates the proportion of beef sourced by origin across major UK retailers, highlighting variations in the percentage of Scottish, UK, Irish, and other beef sources. Lidl leads with the highest proportion of Scottish beef at 93.5%, reflecting a strong commitment to local sourcing, followed by Morrisons (81.6%), Co-Op (69.3%), Tesco (69.7%), and M&S (65.5%), all maintaining a majority share of Scottish beef. In contrast, Aldi shows a significant decline, with Scottish beef dropping to 61.2% while 38.8% of its beef is now sourced from the broader UK market. Asda stocks 24.6% Scottish beef, relying heavily on 74.4% UK-sourced beef, and also includes a small 1% share of Irish beef. Sainsbury's, however, has the lowest proportion of Scottish beef at 7.8% and the highest share of Irish beef at 9.3%, indicating a greater dependence on imports compared to other retailers. The figure highlights shifts in sourcing strategies, with some retailers, like Lidl, increasing their reliance on Scottish beef. In contrast, others, such as Aldi and Sainsbury's, demonstrated a reduced focus on local supply in favour of alternatives from the UK and Ireland.

5.2.7.2 Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC)

5.2.7.2.1 Trust and Relationships

Trust

Dubey et al., (2016) found that trust can lead to supply chain resilience, but the study was conducted from the manufacturer's perspective. The IP 5 mentioned that they are gaining customer trust by maintaining product quality and educating customers to recognise good quality.

“Easy calving, quite temperament..... locomotion and we use We use a lot of genomic analysis of for carcass traits and survivability, and we are pushing hard to the top 10% of Carcass traits, you know meat yielding carcass traits which our customers are now understanding, and they.... Just phone up. I want to buy a bull. Can we pick it up? And that's the way I see it going forward” IP5

The extract highlights the increasing reliance on genomic analysis to enhance carcass traits and survivability, reflecting a shift toward data-driven breeding practices to improve meat yield and quality. By targeting the top 10% of carcass traits, farmers are trying to align with market demands, enabling the production of high-performing livestock that meets consumer expectations for quality. The mention of streamlined transactions, where buyers no longer need to physically inspect animals but instead make purchases based on data and performance metrics, suggests a modernisation of procurement processes driven by trust in genomic data. This also implies that by gaining customer trust, the supply chain can prepare itself against demand disruptions, which the industry has previously experienced due to the horsemeat scandal

5.2.7.2.2 Response Against Disease Outbreak

Chowdhury and Quaddus (2016) mentioned response and recovery as a reactive capability to achieve supply chain resilience. The IP5 mentioned that in case of a major disease outbreak like Foot and Mouth disease. The Scottish Government (2018) issues the control guidelines if any case is identified. Although the rebuilding plan against FMD is not there, the response system against the disease outbreak is resilient, and this can be gauged from the report of a single case of BSE identified on a Scottish farm, which was effectively dealt with.

A single case of Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE), also known as mad cow disease, was detected on a farm in Dumfries and Galloway. The Scottish government implemented movement restrictions and isolated animals in contact with the infected one. The identified strain was atypical BSE, which is not transmissible to humans and poses no public health risk, according to Chief Veterinary Officer Sheila Voas and Food Standards Scotland (FSS). This detection resulted from routine BSE surveillance. Authorities, including Agriculture Minister Jim Fairlie, emphasised that swift action was taken to protect the agricultural

sector. Monitoring for BSE has been ongoing since the 1980s outbreak, with strict safety measures in place to prevent the disease's spread (BBC News, 2024).

This shows the strength of identification and containment of the disease.

This argument is further strengthened by the comment of the IP 5 that the recovery from the massive destruction in the aftermath of a major disease outbreak like FMD is very unlikely.

“In terms of recovery, there'll be those after foot mouth outbreak, if they get affected, they get paid out. They'll just take the money and go now because there's not that many young folk in cattle. No, it's not. Not a rosy picture. It's quite a serious picture because at the end of the day, we've got to keep the countryside under control if we don't keep it grazed, it'll go rank and we'll end up with a massive fire and that will reverse all the carbon sequestration that's been” IP5

This can be inferred from the comment that apart from the economic losses suffered due to the disease outbreak. The affected farmers may choose to leave and exit the industry after receiving the financial compensation. It has also been implied that the youth are unwilling to join cattle farming. The absence of cattle farming will lead to reduced grazing and the risk of the countryside becoming overgrown, exposing it to wildfires. Consequently, reversing the carbon sequestration.

5.2.7.2.3 Risk Mitigation and Redundancy

Risk management (Christopher and Peck 2004) and redundancy (Zhao et al., 2022) lead to supply chain resilience. The IP 5 mentioned their rebuilding plan after a disease outbreak.

“if you got an outbreak of disease, yes, it will recover. I mean what we've done in our own herd here is we have put a lot of embryos into long term storage. So we do get an outbreak of disease. It won't take us long to rebuild the same genetic basis we have just now in terms of what we're doing here. We're focused on a small number of characteristics. Easy calving, quite temperament, correct adders, length and locomotion” IP5

Embryo preservation as backup provides a biological reserve, ensuring the herd can be rebuilt. The focus on desirable characteristics can lead to uniformity in production and consistency in quality. The genetic preservation approach can serve as a buffer against disruptions caused by disease outbreaks.

5.2.7.2.4 Psychological Resilience

Adobor (2019) mentioned that supply chain resilience is a multi-compositional concept and to attain supply chain resilience at an institutional level, an important component is individual resilience. The workforce will better cope with the disruptions if they are mentally resilient. The IP5 mentioned that supply chain

resilience is a mental attitude, which implies that supply chain resilience does not comprise the strength of the physical infrastructure but is also related to emotional stability.

“key to resilience is is actually having a heart for what you're doing and it's more just. If we have foot and mouth here.I wouldn't go back into cattle again.I'll just call it a day and a lot of folks I know of that same mind and that's the that is the biggest issue”IP 5

The comment below shows that if the mental health of the livestock farmer deteriorates, it will impact the day-to-day affairs. Therefore, it is important to address this issue to avoid the likelihood of livestock farmers' early exits from the industry.

“Resilience is the mental attitude to it. And it's not by coincidence. There's been a big rise in mental health charities working in the agricultural sector”IP 5

5.2.7.2.5 Government Support

Yuan (2024) mentioned that government support plays an important role in the agricultural supply chain's resilience by allocating resources. The IP5 also mentioned that Government support has enabled the supply chain to survive.

“The EU and the way the support payments were made were was covering up a lot of inefficiency”IP 5

The Scottish government has initiated the Scottish Suckler Beef support scheme to extend financial relief. Moreover, to respond to a disease outbreak, the government has a control mechanism in place. Therefore, the government support at the current level leads to the supply side of the SBSC.

The IP5 provided very insightful information on the factors contributing to the supply chain resilience and challenges faced by the SBSC from the livestock farmers' perspective. SBSC is facing various challenges, identified as economic, structural, operational, Technological, and environmental challenges. To overcome the structural challenges, the IP5 also proposed solutions. Government intervention is required to address these challenges because livestock farming is already facing a lack of return. Irrespective of the fact that the livestock farmers are subsidised. These challenges will aggravate if appropriate actions are not taken to address them. The factors which contribute to the supply chain resilience of the Scottish Beef supply were identified as Customer Trust, Response against Disease outbreak, Risk Mitigation and Redundancy, Psychological Resilience and Government support.

5.2.8 Interview 6 Livestock Farmer Interview Participant (IP) 6

The interview participant is an experienced livestock farmer based in Orkney, managing a mixed farming operation spanning approximately 101 hectares (250 acres). With over 25 years of experience in farming, IP6 has developed extensive expertise in beef production and barley cultivation, contributing significantly to the local agricultural sector. PR holds a senior executive role in a member organisation of beef producers.

Initials	Role/Position	Farm Size (Ha)	Farm Type	Years in Farming	Primary Activity	Organisational Role	Area
PR	Livestock Farmer	Approx. 101 hectares (250 acres)	Mixed (Cattle & Crops)	25 + years	Beef Production, Barley	Senior Executive in a member organisation of Beef Producers	Orkney

Table 5.2 Interview Participant Profile IP (PR) 6

The figure below shows the initial code developed after reading the transcript. After rigorous reading, sub-themes and themes were identified, which are discussed below.

Figure 5.11 Initial Code Generated in Nvivo IP6

5.2.8.1 Theme 1 Challenges faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The IP6 mentioned various challenges that are clustered under different sub-themes.

5.2.8.1.1 Economic Challenges

The IP 6 pointed towards the financial difficulties livestock farmers face due to structural and demand imbalances.

5.2.8.1.1.1 Lack of Financial Returns

IP 6 expressed his primary concern about the lack of profitability from the perspective of a small livestock farmer.

“So poor profitability that's been for a number of years”IP6

Moreover, the lack of profitability was attributed to reduced numbers of livestock cattle.

“The latest figures that come out from QMS, the national herd, was doing another 2.5% on the year.”IP 6

5.2.8.1.1.2 Farmers as Price Takers

The IP 6 expressed the limitation of the small producers. It can be inferred from the below mentioned extract that the small producers face reduced returns on their produce due to a lack of bargaining power, which the big producers have. The price volatility exposes the small livestock farmer to greater financial vulnerability. The larger producers can enjoy economies of scale and certainty of sales due to their production size.

“Well it it's one of the difficulties with the supply chain that the primary producer is a price taker. And there are a few large finishing units now that supply to Abattoirs and they'll be on a contract or they'll be on an agreement where they're getting the base price, which the small producer like myself would get, and they might be getting considerable more than that”IP6

5.2.8.1.2 Structural Imbalance (Retailer & Processor Dominance)

The IP 6 mentioned the SBSC's structural imbalance and how it impacts small farmers. As mentioned earlier, the small farmers are price takers, which is mere exploitation. The Supermarkets have the largest bargaining power, followed by processors. The big retailers do not want to pass on the price pressure to their customers and try to squeeze the farmers. Likewise, the processor, although very concentrated it is reflected in the below-mentioned comment of our IP 6.

“We are really quite at the mercy of the processor who was probably I think and in Scotland probably 70% of that processing capacity is Irish owned and they tend to show that they are making no profit because quite a lot of the money is made offshore. I think how much money they make is anybody's guess”IP6

“We are really quite at the mercy of the processor who was probably I think and in Scotland probably 70% of that processing capacity is Irish owned and they tend to show that they are making no profit because quite a lot of the money is made offshore.I think how much money they make is anybody's guess”IP6

The Red Meat Industry Profile (2023) of QMS mentioned that in 2022, 75.1% of the cattle were slaughtered in five big abattoirs. The IP6 also underlined during the interview that the processors still claim that they are operating on things margins. The processing sector output as of 2022 was £ 733 M compared to £ 681

M in 2021, which shows an increase of 7.7% (QMS 2023). This affirms the claim of the IP6, as mentioned in the comment box that the processors claim that they are not making any money, but the figures show that they are profitable.

Another harsh reality was exposed by IP 6, which can lead small farmers to frustration and further financial burdens. This issue was highlighted by IP6 and is illustrated below in the interview extract.

On various occasions, it happens with small farmers that if the cattle have been booked for sale and there is a lack of demand or the processing capacity is operating at its optimal level, then the small livestock farmer will be told to keep the cattle for another week. This further adds to the overhead cost of the farmer because they have to look after the cattle for one further week.

“Then small farmer just has to take what does being available sometimes. If there's some backlash demand, you'll have cattle booked to go away, but they'll just come back and say we don't want them this week. You'll have to leave them for a week so that impacts the space in our sheds, perhaps feed supply’ IP6

5.2.8.1.3 Environmental Challenges

The IP 6 mentioned greenhouse gas emissions as the leading environmental challenge faced by the SBSC.

5.2.8.1.3.1 Green House Gas (GHG) Emissions

The livestock sector is known as the largest contributor to the GHG emissions. The FAO has recently released its report on pathways toward lower emissions. Cattle are identified as the largest contributors to GHG emissions, contributing to 60% within the livestock sector. It was mentioned in the report that the meat demand is projected to increase in 2050, and if mitigation strategies are not adopted, it would increase the emissions by 20% (FAO 2023). The report outlines pathways to reduce emissions through improved animal health, feed quality enhancement, waste reduction, circular bio economy approaches, and grassland carbon sequestration.

The IP 6 expressed his concern for the GHG emissions. The media has projected a false image of the livestock sector by holding it as the primary contributor to GHG emissions and providing inaccurate information.

The extract mentioned below shows that the livestock farmer in Scotland is very aware of this, takes pride in his work, and is ready to refute any false allegations. The first thing that was expressed by IP 6 was annoyance at the media because they had circulated the wrong figures. The IP 6 said blanketing the overall livestock emission to the Scottish Beef sector is unjust. He pointed out that Scottish livestock is reared on grassland, and their reliance on external output is minimal; therefore, these facts should be considered. The IP 6 has also shown his annoyance with how the Government has handled this issue. The IP6 also references

scientific evidence that the methane lifecycle is shorter than CO₂; therefore, realities should be considered. This argument of IP 6 is entirely valid, and the FAO is now also considering carbon sequestration to calculate GHG emissions.

“I know that that has been and huge annoyance to myself as how the media have portrayed farmers how they they seem to have played with the figure. They take global figures for emissions of Livestock, where the cattle has been fed on produce that's been grown under irrigated conditions. The cattle would be far less productive than the cattle in Scotland and I, the Scottish figure, are amongst the lowest in the world.

But when the media have produced figures, and sadly, I would suggest the government of actually use these figures that that are not accurate it and it came out looking like farmers are really polluting the climate polluting the atmosphere but the methane but disappointedly 27 to 30 times more pollutant than carbon dioxide. They're starting to calculate it differently now with because scientists would say that the methane is all broken down and recycled within 10 years. So, provided your Livestock, numbers are static, it has no effect on the climate for a carbon dioxide lasts for 100 years”IP6

5.2.8.1.4 Operational Challenges

The IP6 identified the operational challenges of critical mass and land deprivation,

5.2.8.1.4.1 Critical Mass

The concept of critical mass highlights the need to maintain a sufficient level of agricultural activity to sustain the economic viability of farming in a region. Costs increase when production drops below a certain threshold, and supporting businesses may shut down or relocate. This can lead to higher inputs, services, and transportation expenses, while reduced processing capacity may lower product prices or raise operational costs. Such challenges can drive farmers to abandon agriculture for more profitable land uses, accelerating farmland loss. To remain viable, specific agricultural sectors often require a minimum scale of production, acreage, or sales (Carpenter and Lynch 2002).

“These plants need a certain amount of throughput to make it profitable and I fear that we might lose another sizeable abattoir in the future which just gives the ones that's left more power”IP 6

The IP 6 pointed out the harsh reality wherein the livestock face a lack of financial returns. The suckler cow herd is decreasing every year. Due to the lack of cattle numbers, the abattoirs are also under pressure because they need a specific throughput to remain profitable. This can be seen as a systemic impact where the lack of supplies impacts the processors. If we look at the processing sector figures for 2023, 75% of cattle slaughter was done in five big abattoirs and 0.7% of the cattle in the smallest abattoirs (QMS 2024).

This authenticates IP 6's concern that he is foreseeing the closure of another abattoir in Scotland, which will further disturb the balance of the processing sector.

5.2.8.1.4.2 Land Deprivation

The increased land usage for tree plantation has been a bone of contention between the livestock farmers in Scotland and the Government (Farmers Weekly, 2021). The land usage for woodlands reduces livestock farming opportunities. IP 6 has also raised this point that the Government is giving up agricultural land suitable for livestock farming for tree plantation to boost their sustainability drive.

“Another difficulty that has been that Institutions buying up land and making it unprofitable for businesses to buy land and expand, and these institutions have been buying it for trees and Picnic restoration and such like to greenwash their own company to make them look like they're net zero” And that just put back a lot of land and has come out of cattle production and gone into trees in the last 10 to 15 years”IP6

The IP 6 also gave the example of corporate companies who are buying land to offset their carbon footprint.

“Aviva Insurance Company, they bought up land. I think I'm fairly accurate in saying British Airways bought land to plant in trees so they can fly planes net zero”IP 6

5.2.8.1.4.3 Lack of Labour and Succession

The IP 6 also mentioned that the Livestock farmers do not have proper succession, and their children are unwilling to support them in the farming business. The fundamental issue is the low profitability. IP 6 also mentioned that farming is a 24-hour commitment, and sometimes we don't have much time free off the farm.

“I mean that challenges that we're facing are labor a lot of farmers are getting older because of that” IP6

Due to this, the younger generations are not interested in livestock farming. Because when they calculate the cost-benefit analysis, it does not appeal to them.

“And the fact that you don't have much time off at the times of the year, you're so like 24 hours a day sometimes and the younger generation are not too keen to come back to that when the older generations reach and retirement, always so that is a challenge going forward”IP 6

5.2.8.2 Theme 2 Traceability and Labelling Complexity

Traceability is one of the contributors to supply chain resilience. Zhao et al., (2022) presented a one-to-one resilience-to-risk model and proposed that traceability can mitigate the demand, supply, and environmental and biological risks. The IP6 pointed out a very strange practice which involves product labelling. The IP 6 said that a labelling practice exists where information is manipulated in the country of origin. For instance,

if you are buying steak and a sauce is added to that product, it may change in the name of the declared origin. This is evident from the IP6's comment below.

“I think the worrying thing is that the labelling is so confusing. Have you go in the shop and when you buy a steak, It might have country of origin on it, and it generally is quite accurate, but as soon as you put a sauce on that steak, you can put on the country for that steak has been processed with the sauce on it and that will be totally irrelevant”IP6

Such practices can lead to the non-disclosure of accurate country of origin and may undermine consumer confidence, leading to reduced supply chain visibility. It was reported by Jordan and Simpon (2023) that the National Crime Unit (NFCU) investigated a case where a beef product was labelled as British, whereas its original was South America and Europe. The supermarket was told to empty its shelves with the product. It was reported that the investigating agency conveyed that this matter pertains to food fraud instead of food safety.

5.2.8.3 Theme 3 Factors Contributing to the Supply chain resilience of the Scottish Beef supply chain

The IP 6 identified Government Support as a contributing factor a resilient SBSC.

5.2.8.3.1 Government Support

The role of government support in improving the agri-food supply chain resilience capability was explored by Zhong et al., (2024). It was analysed that government support can enhance redundancy, robustness and adaptation. The Scottish Government has also extended significant support to the livestock farmers in by extending various schemes. The notable Scottish Government Schemes aimed to provide financial relief to livestock farmers are SSBSS (Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme) and Less Favoured Area Support Scheme (LFASS). The former supports herd management, and the latter provides financial relief to the farmers engaged in farming in areas with fewer amenities than other areas (FAS, 2024).

The IP 6 also mentioned that Government support has been instrumental in preventing the further deterioration of the cattle herd.

“The Suckler Support Scheme get a payment for the calve certainly helped in recent years to keep cow number high up in the would have been otherwise” IP6

5.2.8.4 Theme Four

Collaboration / Forming of Cooperative for Farmers

The IP 6 proposed a solution to improve the position of the livestock farmers as they are termed as the Price takers. The livestock farmer has expressed his serious concern regarding the survival of the small livestock farmers. According to the IP6 the small livestock farmers lack the economies of scale alongside the transparency in the pricing. Therefore IP 6 proposed the forming of a Cooperative for the farmers which will act on the behalf of the farmers. Wang et al., (2022) concluded that the farming cooperatives can regulate the pricing operations in the supply chain based on the centralised decision making. Therefore the proposed idea by the IP 6 can be endorsed by the research. However the comment by the IP 6 also sparks a debate on the role of the membership body of Farmers in Scotland and the Levy Body in Scotland. This indicates that the institutions needs to be more vigilant in addressing the transparency issues in the supply chain.

“I Think that it should be possible that farmers, but they're very the like to be individuals and they're not very good at working together. But I think a farmer's cooperative. Well, that cooperative sells product to the next person in the supply chain is needed to get a farmer for more strength. And bygone days most cattle went through a live ring when they were finished and when they were ready for slaughter not has Increased slightly again in recent years”IP6

Another important fact which has highlighted by the IP6 was the role of Auction Marts. The Auction marts are a medium of regulating prices and ensure transparency in the market. Nye et al., (2022) identified another important aspect of livestock auction marts in UK that they are a very good medium of socialisation and can improve the mental well-being of the agricultural community. The IP 6 also implied that the farmers tend to work as individuals therefore a forum like forming cooperatives and to increase the practice of starting to sell through the livestock auction will improve the bargaining power of the livestock farmers.

The IP 6 highlighted various aspects of the SBSC. The most important element was the improper practice of labelling which is an issue of food fraud. The challenges of the small livestock farmers were also discussed and the main concern was the lack of bargaining power of the small farmers due to which their return are further minimized. This reflects that the fair pricing is not prevalent in the SBSC. The IP 6 also indicated toward the dominance of retailers and processors in the SBSC and due to their size they are regulating the prices which has put the small farmer at the verge of financial distress. The IP 6 also proposed a solution to increase the bargaining power of the small livestock farmers by formulating a farmers' cooperative. This also shows the lack of trust of the small livestock farmer on the membership bodies of farmers in Scotland. The IP 6 also affirmed that the Government support in form of the support scheme has saved the livestock from financial distress. The IP6 commented on the importance of critical mass for the survival of the processing sector. It is noteworthy that the small livestock farmer was well aware and also

discussed how government is encouraging to use the land for plantation in order to fulfil its sustainability drive and how corporate companies are buying land to offset their carbon emissions.

5.2.9 Livestock Farmer Interview Participant (IP) 7

The interview participant (IP) 7 is a livestock farmer specializing in livestock breeding and operating as a store producer in East Lothian. The IP7 manages a substantial mixed farming enterprise spanning approximately 1,214 hectares (3,000 acres), focusing primarily on beef production alongside the cultivation of barley. With 18 years of farming experience, the IP7 has developed significant expertise in managing large-scale agricultural operations, particularly in breeding high-quality livestock for the Scottish beef industry. In addition to hands-on farming the interview participant holds a senior executive position in a prominent levy organisation.

Initials	Role/Position	Farm Size (Ha)	Farm Type	Years in Farming	Primary Activity	Organisational Role	Area
NJ	Livestock Farmer (Breeding Farm /Store Producer)	Approx. 1214hectares (3000 acres)	Mixed (Cattle & Crops)	18 years	Beef Production, Barley	Senior Executive in a Levy Organisation	East Lothian

Table 5.3 Interview Participant Profile IP (NJ) 7

After transcribing the interview and rigorously reading and watching the video recorded interview, the following nodes were generated, as shown in the figure below. The nodes were then used to formulate themes. and sub themes.

Figure 5.12 Initial code generation from the transcript IP7

5.2.9.1 Theme 1

5.2.9.1.1 Technology Adoption and Digital Transformation

Ali and Govindan (2023) provided empirical evidence from the Australian agri-food supply chain that automation such as EDI (Electronic Data Interchange) can enhance the visibility and traceability of the supply chain. It was also revealed that the digital transformation of the supply chain can lead to better alignment of demand and supply. It was concluded that the adoption of advanced technologies lead to improved performance.

5.2.9.1.1.1 Digital Tools for Livestock Movement

The IP7 mentioned that the Scottish Government has provided a website which is managed by ScotEID which can be used to record animal movements. This has resulted in better traceability and efficiency. Moreover, as the comment below mentions, the system tends to be user-friendly. This also indicates the Scottish Government support available to livestock farmers for better traceability and herd management.

“I Think that it should be possible that farmers, but they're very the like to be individuals and they're not very good at working together. But I think a farmer's cooperative. Well, that cooperative sells product to the next person in the supply chain is needed to get a farmer for more strength. And bygone days most cattle went through a live ring when they were finished and when they were ready for slaughter not has Increased slightly again in recent years” IP7

5.2.9.1.1.2 Performance Data and Breeding Efficiency Monitoring

Another aspect of the ScotEID was emphasised during the interview was monitoring breeding performance. It was noted that it is not a one-way system where the farmers input the data into the system, but the feedback is also available to the farmers. The farmers can get the information about the calving interval. It is very important for the livestock farmers to know the calving interval. Due to the declining number of suckler herd and calf registration, the Scottish Government has reduced the calving interval to 410 days to be eligible for the support payments. This new initiative will be implemented from the first of January 2025. It will serve two objectives. First, it will help reduce the unproductive cattle from the herd, and second, it will assist in achieving the sustainability objectives of the Scottish Government (Scottish Parliament 2024).

5.2.9.1.1.3 Slow Adoption to Technology

The IP7 indicated that the livestock farmers are using technology, but it is very basic technology. For instance, they are using Electronic Identification for cattle, which is mainly focused on weighing the cattle and is more focused on visibility and data collection.

“I am more kind of day-to-day farming, things like that use of EID, although we aren't yet unfortunately on until kind of. It's becoming a legal requirement. There is a lot of low frequency EID's being used in cattle

and that helps more with them visibility and a collection of data. Uh, mainly the main collection of data that you do with the EID tagging is weighing animals, so measuring their weights through their production cycle and identifying disease” IP 7

5.2.9.1.1.4 Integration of Agri Tech data and Decision support software

Decision support systems can optimise farming efficiency by integrating data analysis and predictive tools. The decision support tools can assist in making informed decisions about crop management and resource allocation (Rupnik et al., 2019). The IP 7 pointed out that integrating software with hardware can greatly assist livestock farmers in making informed decisions.

“We have visual cameras, we have satellite imagery, we have lots and lots of things that we have the hardware to detect, but we have very little, very little Software to amalgamate all that information to present it to a farmer like me to then help make a decision” IP7

It can be inferred from the comment that with the help of an appropriate decision support system, Scottish livestock farmers can develop better strategies for herd management, disease prevention, and environmental sustainability. This can lead to better risk management and a resilient supply chain.

5.2.9.2 Theme 2

5.2.9.2.1 Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC

The IP 7 pointed out practices and initiatives which contribute to a resilient supply chain.

5.2.9.2.1.1 Inherent Resilience

The IP 7 pointed out that the Scottish land is meant for livestock farming. It can be inferred from the comment that the geographical suitability of Scottish lands for extensive grazing with a temperate climate makes it suitable for livestock farming. This can lead to reduced input cost and reliance on other processed feed.

“we have a land use suited to growing cattle or growing red meat outdoor grazing and things like that and we’ve had historically have the skills for rearing and they have genetic improvement of our Livestock” IP7

This comment was very interesting, and it resulted in probing more about inherent resilient. Umar and Wilson (2024) discussed inherent resilience in the agriculture food supply chain from the perspective of logistical operations. It was discussed as the ability of food supply chains to withstand disruptions through pre-existing structures, resources, and relationships. The study highlights that inherent resilience components, like redundancy and contingency planning, serve as stepping stones for adaptive responses during disruptions. It was also revealed that that inherent and adaptive resilience are interrelated rather than distinct, suggesting that inherent resilience supports adaptability and enables quicker recovery after

disruptions. The authors conclude that resilience-building is an ongoing process where adaptive capabilities, over time, become inherent traits of the supply chain. The implications for the Scottish supply chain resilience from the livestock farming perspective can be that livestock farming has been pursued for ages in Scotland, and this good adaptation can lead to resilience. It can be inferred that the inherent supply chain results from the knowledge gained, retained or utilised from the previous disruption and makes it more adaptive to similar disruptions.

5.2.9.2.1.2 Brand Strength

The IP 7 mentioned that Scottish beef has made strong recognition as a brand, and it also leads to its resilience.

“But essentially, and the resilience of supply chain I, I suppose it's historic reputation and strength of the brand” IP7

This is interesting that the IP 7 believes that the brand strength leads to the resilience of the Scottish beef supply change. If we try to assess this statement from the demand side perspective that the Scottish beef is renowned world-wide and it has a reputation of quality so it means that in this case the new entrants of processed beef or who label themselves as sustainable beef may be not at an advantage as compared to Scottish Beef. This means that the Scottish beef will be resilient against any demand disruptions. This leads the discussion towards brand resilience which may lead to a resilient supply chain by sustaining any negative propagation against the brand and confronting any demand disruptions.

5.2.9.2.1.3 Traceability

Traceability is recognised as a contributing factor in the resilience of agri-food supply chains. Zhao et al., (2022) formulated a one-to-one resilience and risk framework. It was revealed that traceability can lead to supply chain resilience by combating supply, demand, biological, environmental, and logistical risks. The IP 7 pointed that the traceability of animals through the supply chain contributes to resilience.

“A high provenance and well, which is the traceability essentially of the animals through the supply chain, high food safety” IP 7

Considering Tesco's horsemeat scandal, this statement becomes very important if we analyse it. The Scottish government has provided a free online tool for livestock farmers to record their cattle's movement, providing better traceability. The supermarkets have also learned the lesson after the horsemeat scandal. The IP7 mentioned that the supermarkets are now doing DNA testing of the meat products they are receiving for better traceability.

“We're talking more of genetic testing. I am and it can be tied into or potentially could be tied into what we talked about the horse meat scandal and traceability and there are supply chains doing it or there are supermarkets certainly doing it Marks and Spencer's and ALDI will take our DNA swab or DNA scrape off the carcass and hold it to prove that is to prove what it is. It says it is essentially, so you can do it in terms of breeding. You could you can do it to prove that it wasn't having Angus animal. If it's, if it's being marketed, there's that. Or you could do it just to prove that it's a beef animal and so that's already happening”IP7

The IP7 comment was verified, and Marks & Spencer disclosed on their website that they employ DNA sampling to trace the origin of its beef to each individual farm and animal. Samples are collected from every animal supplied to M&S and its suppliers. Thousands of tests are conducted on randomly selected products from M&S stores and warehouses each year to ensure traceability and quality (M&S, 2024). This entails that traceability contributes to the supply chain resilience of the SBSC from farm to fork.

5.2.9.2.1.4 Stakeholder Collaboration

Collaboration is a widely recognised contributor of supply chain resilience. Christopher and Peck (2004) provided the initial framework for supply chain resilience, and collaboration was an important component of the framework. Collaboration has held an important place throughout the evolution journey of supply chain resilience. A recent study by Zhao et al., (2022) also found that collaboration can contribute to a resilient supply chain by confronting demand, supply, financial, and weather-related risks.

“but getting all the major stakeholders together around in one organisation I think it is key so that they can share either information or problems coming and and yeah, highlight issues that are coming between all the major stakeholders. So that's the role of the group and the how does how do, what did you, how do we, how do we work within it? Well, we have members of QMS on it and uh, some of the the group meeting information is fed back to our board”IP 7

The IP 7 pointed out that the QMS has formulated a Scottish Red Meat Resilience, which has engaged the key stakeholders of the Scottish Red Meat Industry, and it is an effective forum for jointly addressing any issues or challenges which the industry is currently facing. It was also pointed out that QMS has close contact with the Scottish Government, and in case of any issue, they write to the Cabinet Secretary or the First Minister to update them on what is happening in the Scottish Beef Industry.

5.2.9.2.1.5 Artificial Insemination

The IP7 mentioned that artificial insemination is helping to produce resilient animals. It was discussed that a lot of animals are using international genetics to improve certain qualities. The IP7 is implied that the widespread adoption of artificial insemination in the Scottish beef industry is significantly enhancing the

supply chain's resilience by enabling targeted genetic improvement. By selectively breeding cattle with superior genetics, farmers can produce animals that are more resilient to diseases, better adapted to varying health conditions, and more efficient in utilising nutrition.

“I mean things that are that I would say are wide scale happening is. Uh AI. Artificial insemination for breeding, for genetic improvement. It's definitely kind of improving the resilience so for selecting better genetics, more resilient animals to either disease, health, nutrition” IP7

5.2.9.3 Theme 3 Challenges Faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The IP7 pointed out multiple challenges faced by the SBSC ranging from global competition to domestic competition from the dairy sector.

5.2.9.3.1 Regulatory Uncertainty

The IP 7 pointed that the Scottish Government is reviewing the support payments, and this has led to a greater uncertainty. The comment is verified by the fact that the Scottish Government (2024) has introduced a route map for Agricultural reform which is tier based. The implementation will start in 2025 and fully implemented until 2027. New conditions have to be complied under the tier systems. The comment of IP 7 points out toward the impact of late policy direction on the business operations of the livestock farmers.

“Ultimately, it is political and that I will have the we regulation brought in that will and restrict my ability to do certain things and you now, as with all kind of political explanations and intervention and possibly Support Payments going forward, there is in Scotland we're currently under review that with that and as I suppose, the challenge for me as a farmer. It's not having clarity on future either regulation or agriculture policy does restrict your ability to reinvest and make certain decisions that will impact. And in five years time beef farming is quite a slow business. So I need to make a decision in, you know, I made a decision in June this year that wouldn't really impact my business until two years time. And so if I need to make a change, it takes me three years to make that for that change to come to fruition”IP7

The IP 7 has shown his high concern that the delayed government response adversely impact the planning of the livestock farmers. The IP7 mentioned that if he takes a business decision today, it will take two years to materialise the impact of that decision. This shows the lifecycle and operational nature of the farming business. The IP7 also expressed his fear of expecting things to improve, taking into account the existing state of profitability of livestock farming. His comment that in five years' time, beef farming will be quite a slow business points out that uncertainty.

5.2.9.3.2 Competition from Dairy Cattle

The IP7 expressed his concern regarding competition from the domestic dairy industry. He mentioned that this challenge may not impact the other stakeholders but for him as a livestock store farmer it does impact his business. The dairy herd size is increasing and the calf registration in 2023 decreased by 2.7% as mentioned in the Red meat industry profile report (QMS, 2024).

“I'm a suckler producer, so the challenge for me producing beef calves in Scotland at the moment. There's a significant change from and an increased number of calves, Dairy Cross calves coming from the dairy.

The dairy industry at the moment, so that's the challenge to me to produce a calf that can compete with a kind of a surplus calf essentially from the dairy, the dairy system that's not necessarily challenging for the whole of the industry because it means that there's still Beef numbers being slaughtered in Scotland.

But I farming point of view I'm keeping a cow every year to uh, have a calf to rear calf and then I'm selling that calf on whereas there's I'm competing with dairy and that is increasing, you know, as the dairy herds like it does increase”IP7

The comment on the competition from the dairy system as pointed by the IP 7 shows a serious concern of lack of profitability because the dairy herds are increasing.

5.2.9.3.3 Lack of Labor

The IP 7 also mentioned the shortage of labour is present is witnessed not only in the livestock farming but also in the processing sector.

“the current challenges are not going away in terms of Labor and skills, but technology will be able to take up some of that slack”IP7

5.2.9.3.4 Global Competition

The IP7 mentioned that every country follows the same production strategy, which is based on the principle of producing at a low cost and selling it at a high price. The example of New Zealand was given, as it has a low input system and access to markets in South East Asia and America, which are quite lucrative. He implied that the low input systems can be adopted in Scotland.

5.2.9.4 Overview of IP7 interview

The IP7 discussed important dimensions of the Scottish Beef Industry. From the supply chain resilience perspective, the role of genetics in producing a resilient herd came under discussion. The collaboration among the stakeholders was also discussed. An important element of the SBSC was revealed as inherited resilience in the Scottish System. The traceability and the means of traceability were also highlighted. The

challenges of the SBSC were also discussed, and the main concern was the regulatory uncertainty. The technological advancements and their usage by the livestock farmers was also highlighted and it was pressed by the IP7 that a fast adoption to technological advancement is required.

5.2.10 Livestock Farmer Interview Participant IP 8

The Interview Participant (IP)8 manages a breeding farm in Perthshire that spans approximately 272 hectares (672 acres). The farm primarily focuses on beef production and barley cultivation. As a second-generation farmer, IP8 has inherited a wealth of farming knowledge and experience, contributing to the family farm's long-term sustainability and resilience. With years of practical experience in livestock farming, IP8 has developed a deep understanding of both cattle breeding and crop production, ensuring the farm remains productive and efficient. Additionally, IP8 serves as a member of the Executive Committee of a prominent farming organisation. Based on his combined expertise in livestock breeding, crop production, and industry leadership positions the IP8 provided valuable insights about the SBSC.

Initials	Role/Position	Farm Size (Ha)	Farm Type	Years in Farming	Primary Activity	Organisational Role	Area
JR	Livestock Farmer (Breeding Farm)	272 Hectare (672 Acres)	Mixed (Cattle & Crop)	Second Generation Farmers over	Beef Production, Barley	Executive Committee member in a Farming Organisation	Perthshire

Table 5.4 Interview Participant Profile IP (JR) 8

The initial coding from the interview transcript is shown in the figure below.

Figure 5.13 Interview Coding in NVivo IP8

5.2.10.1 Theme Factors Contributing to Resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The interview participant (IP 8) pointed out various practices that can be evaluated to ensure their contribution to the supply chain resilience of the SBSC.

5.2.10.1.1 Trust

Trust among supply chain partners leads to a resilient supply chain by fostering confidence in information sharing, dependability and corrective actions (Dubey et al 2016)

Zhao et al., (2024) proposed a food supply chain resilience model for Argentina and France. Trust significantly contributed to the supply chain's resilience in both supply chains. However, the role of trust in

enabling supply chain resilience varied in both supply chains based on their characteristics. In the supply chain resilience model proposed for Argentina, trust leads to collaboration and knowledge exchange. Trust also encourages participation in training sessions, ultimately improving product quality. In the model proposed for France, trust leads to joint decision-making and ensures transparency.

“but it suits my character.I like to know what I'm getting before the leave the farm so all the business decisions that between me and the other farmers are all made even before the cattle leave the farm.So I know exactly what I'm getting.They know exactly what they are paying and and it for us and the two farmers are worked with”IP 8

The IP 8 pointed out that he has established trust with his suppliers and buyers. He also mentioned that he has a limited number of suppliers, and he also sells to a limited number of buyers for the last several years. The IP 8 mentioned in the comment that all the business decisions are made before the cattle leave the farm. Dubey et al.(2016) noted that reduction of behavioural uncertainty fosters trust and leads to a resilient supply chain. The part of the comment “ it suits my character” shows behaviour certainty wherein the IP 8 is confident about the livestock he buys and sells.

The IP 8 also mentioned how trust is developed. He pointed out that it is based on mutual interest, and this trust is not built easily. You have to be transparent and honest. As mentioned by IP 8, you even discuss sensitive issues like disease and animal welfare because if you want to develop trust, you have to be honest and open. If we compare the comments of IP 8 regarding trust with the resilience model presented by Zhao (2024) et al., then the trust elements are more aligned with the trust in the French Agri-food supply chain, where trust leads to transparency and joint decision-making.

“I try and work with the farmers we deal with so that it's it's mutually beneficial.They know they're getting cattle that comes off a certain system that will suit their system.They know that the health and status of the animals, either you know, I'm very open on where we are and what diseases animals have on farm.And so it's a very transparent relationship where trust is a big thing and and but it's it's a mutual, it's a mutual benefit for both parties for us to work together going forward”IP8

5.2.10.1.2 Supplier Selection

Appropriate Supplier selection leads to a resilient supply chain (Christopher and Peck, 2004); by selecting appropriate supplier criteria, a proactive approach towards supply chain management is adopted (Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015). IP 8 also discussed the selection criteria of his suppliers, and it is evident from the comment below that this selection criteria is based on suitability and dependability.

“On that regard, we sometimes go to the auction, but I would far I would far rather work with a farmer or farm within I can go and see the animals and the system that they're bringing them up and then I can see if those animals are going to suit my system and I get to see the health status, everything like that” IP8

Interestingly, the IP 8 expressed that the supplier selection criteria vary based on the commodity. To buy feed, they work with only one company, and he calls five to six companies for fertiliser. IP 8 doesn't believe supplier relationship is essential for buying fertiliser.

“And regarding like inputs into the farm and so we've got one feed company, we're gonna have a grass based system. So that we try and that buy as little, concentrate feed as as possible. So we're actually working with one feed company and that that we work with and with the other inputs that we'll use will buy fertilizer. That's very much commodity driven, so I can phone up five or six different merchants and it's really that there's no to certain extent, there's not much of a relationship there that just purely done on price” IP 8

The relationship between a farmer and a vet is very important. The FSS (Food Standards Scotland) submitted to the Scottish Parliament that they face difficulties recruiting vets (Scottish Government, 2024). IP 8 also mentioned that the relationship with vets is crucial, and the farmers have a strong relationship with their vets as they have to seek professional advice from them. The vaccinations cannot be bought without a prescription. To purchase other animal welfare products, the IP 8 said he works with 2-3 companies, and it depends on the price. Without any loyalty to any specific company, it is purely price-driven.

5.2.10.1.3 Redundancy

Redundancy, buffer and safety stocks lead to a resilient supply chain (Christopher and Peck, 2024; Ali and Golgeci, 2019). Zhao et al., (2022) mentioned that redundancy can confront biological, weather and policy-related risks, leading to a resilient supply chain. The only issue with redundancy is that it has to be offset against efficiency, as Christopher and Peck (2004) indicated in the initial framework of a resilient supply chain. Zhong et al., (2024) explored the supply chain resilience capability factors in agricultural food supply chains. They mentioned that government support could lead to redundancy, which implies that the subsidies and grants obtained from the government can provide the supply chain players with adequate financial means to buy additional buffers or safety stock. It was also highlighted that redundancy leads to better resource configuration and limits the disruption's financial impact. The IP 8 also mentioned that he holds buffer stock to hedge against a disruption.

“And so regards like disruption in the supply chain, like you know, fertilizer 2 years ago went from 250 pounds a ton to 750 pounds a ton. You know, to a certain extent we'll forward buy fertilizer six months in

advance of when we actually need it. So we'll take home. We'll be bringing home fertilizer, probably in September. That won't be used until next spring, purely as a way I can have just hedge in a little bit" IP 8

5.2.10.1.4 Information Sharing

Pereira et al., (2014) analysed the role of procurement in building supply chain resilience and mentioned that information sharing can enhance responsiveness during a disruption. Zhong et al., (2024) noted that information sharing is a key driver for supply chain redesign. Supply chain design is one of the components of the supply chain resilience framework proposed by Christopher and Peck (2004), and it was emphasised that information sharing reduces uncertainty. The IP 8 also mentioned information sharing and discussed how he uses this information.

"I get feedback from them regarding how the animals are doing and that will help me influence maybe breeding objectives on the farm. What does I'm using to breed cattle and things like that? It just means that I have a bit of autonomy, although I can't take those animals right the way through to the finished product. I try and work with the farmers we deal with so that it's it's mutually beneficial" IP 8

It can be inferred from the comment that information sharing leads to the alignment of breeding objectives with customer demands. The livestock farmer discussed the lack of autonomy because this livestock farmer deals in breeding and storing cattle and does not finish the cattle. This means that his participation in the supply chain is up to the point when he sells the cattle to the next livestock farmer. From there, the finisher's job is to further fatten the cattle to meet the requirements of the processors and supermarkets.

5.2.10.2 Theme 2 Challenges Faced by Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The IP 8 pointed out various challenges confronting the SBSC.

5.2.10.2.1 Lack of Succession and Aging population

IP 8 mentioned that efficiency and productivity have eroded in the Scottish Beef industry due to the ageing population of farmers. It was also noted that there is no succession planning in the livestock farming sector because the younger generation does not want to join the farming business. The main reason was expressed as the lack of financial returns.

"I probably think that's why a lot of suckler cows have disappeared because there's a lot of farmers thought right now I can't make this pay. We've got a massive issue in the industry with I think the average age of farmers is about 64 65, so we've not got that. We've kind of missed the generation and they've not come forward. So at the moment at me as a beef farmer is probably we're probably living off that legacy because the numbers aren't there" IP8

5.2.10.2.2 Lack of Financial Returns

The IP 8 mentioned the lack of profitability in livestock farming. He revealed a novel perspective that, although the profit margins are thin if the livestock farmers think they are not making money, they will never be able to make money because they are getting the best price the market can pay.

"Yeah, the profit margins suckler and beef production, there's no doubt that and so uh, profit margins are thin and I think that to a certain extent with the whether change for cattle is not just now if you're not making money now, I don't think you're ever gonna make money in in the beef industry because we are. We're probably at the peak of what the market can afford to pay" IP8

It can be inferred that IP 8 is pointing toward the market imbalance dominated by the processing and retailers, which has restricted the livestock farming sector to a minimum income threshold.

5.2.10.2.3 Lack of Collaboration

Collaboration is a key element in achieving resilience in the supply chain (Christopher and Peck, 2004). The importance of collaboration has been highlighted in various studies (Ali & Golgeci, 2019; Sa et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2024). The IP 8 mentioned a lack of collaboration in the entire SBSC. The livestock farmers, the processors and the retailers are not integrated. He is trying to imply that supply chain fairness is lacking. He admitted that the aforementioned supply chain players are businesses, and the objective of every business is to earn a profit, and this objective has restricted collaboration. The IP 8 showed his concern that because every player is fighting to get the larger share of the profit, the ideal collaboration will not be found in the entire supply chain, but it can be improved.

"I just think sometimes that's that that whole integration and the supply chain is just too isolated. It's not. There's not enough collaboration between the three and which, maybe because it's business and because it's, you know, it's got a commercial aspect, it's never gonna be maybe the panacea that we want it to be. But I just think that it could be like it could be a lot better, I think" IP 8

5.2.10.2.4 Critical Mass

IP 8 mentioned that the Critical Mass is another main challenge in livestock farming. The number of Scottish livestock has declined over the last 10 years. The loss of critical mass can endanger Scotland's supply and processing supply chain (SAMW, 2024). It can be inferred from the comment that the seriousness of the matter is how the critical mass will be improved when the farmers get older. The lack of profitability is even making it more complicated. This implies the need for necessary intervention by the government to make reforms and ensure a fair supply chain that becomes attractive for the youth so that they can join the livestock farming business and make it prosperous.

"And so it's it's just keeping that critical mass is is key and and and having introducing suppose other big issue is the age of our farmers and trying to attract young people into the industry and the only way we can attract young people and into the industry really is to make it profitable make it you know make it look attractive to make it get folks to get started coming into" IP 8

5.2.10.2.5 Market Uncertainty and Long-term Planning

The IP 8 discussed the uncertainty and the long-term risks that a livestock farmer faces. One aspect which he mentioned earlier is that, at present, the cattle are getting the best price because it is the best price that the market can pay. Considering the ever-decreasing cattle number, the cattle supply will remain tight, which may lead to higher prices. However, this future probability can be impacted by the unpredictability of the markets due to the long production cycles in beef farming. Livestock farmers must make investment decisions years in advance without knowing the market conditions or prices they will get when their cattle are finished and ready for sale. This lack of price visibility and market stability, as compared to other industries where pricing and profitability are more predictable, underscores the financial vulnerability that livestock farmers routinely face.

"We've got cows that'll calve next spring, you know, and I have no idea what the trade for them, you know, and those animals won't be slaughtered for two years. So, three years down the line from now, these animals won't be slaughtered. So I have no idea what the trade will be, what the marketplace will be and as I suppose, as farmers, that it's been like that for time in memorial" IP 8

The IP 8 mentioned that this uncertainty has always been a norm rather than an exception in livestock farming.

"But it's if you ask anyone else to run a business and not know what you're gonna get to your your product at the end of it. You know, a lot of folks would think you were mad, but I suppose it's just what we're used to doing" IP8

5.2.10.3 Theme 3 Impact of Subsidy Scheme on Efficiency and Profitability

This theme reflects the various aspects of the Scottish Suckler Beef Support scheme (SSBSS). It is pointed out by IP 8 that the subsidy scheme introduced complacency in the livestock farmers, and from 1st January 2025, there will be a change in the SSBSS, which is the change in the calving interval. The new reform is aimed at efficiency and will discourage livestock farmers who keep cows that do not have calves. The IP 8 has highlighted a need for farmers for peer-to-peer learning and consultation for improved profitability.

5.2.10.3.1 Lack of Incentive for Efficiency

The IP 8 mentioned that the current subsidies emphasised more on land management and less on productivity which led to lack of motivation of the farmers to improve productivity.

“the support scheme, you know, the subsidy scheme that we’ve got in Scotland just now, it really only rewards you to be in control of the ground. You know you have. You do farming to a certain standard, but the standard is very, very, extremely loose and so there’s not, there’s not that and then there’s not the drive. There’s not the initiative…… Am I gonna chase efficiency? Am I gonna chase? No. When when the government’s gonna pay me my substance every year, you know. I’ll. I’ll quite happily just Tootle along doing what I’m doing” IP8

5.2.10.3.2 Ageing Farmer and Succession Issues

The younger population could not be attracted due to lack of financial returns, and consequently, the ageing population could not improve efficiency.

“You know, if I was a 60-year-old farmer, you know you had. Yeah, your children may not be interested in farming because to be fair, they can go and make a lot more money in other industries doing other things…… So I think that that mentality over the last 10-15 years hasn’t helped our industry” IP 8

5.2.10.3.3 Upcoming Changes in Support Scheme Criteria

The new amendment introduced in the scheme are now focused to reward higher productivity.

“Well, so the so the beef support scheme you know so it changes as of next year. So you’re only get payment on a calf if the carrier has a calving interval of 410 days, and unless so the big push that we’re getting in the industry just now is a lot of farmers are saying, well, that’s not fair. We’re personally, if you ask me if I have a carrier that’s got a calving interval of 410 days I wouldn’t have it on the farm because she wasn’t gonna make any money. You know our calving interval for our farms is 367 days and so we’re very much focused on Cows having a calf every year at the same time. So that it makes the system simple and it makes the system efficient. So actually our payment for our calves will go up roughly by 20% purely because we’ve got cows that are doing what cows are meant to do and as have a calf every year.’ IP8

5.2.10.3.4 Resistance to Reform and Efficiency Requirements

Farmers with inefficient herds feel that they are at a disadvantage, but they must learn that to improve efficiency, they must consult with industry experts.

“Unfortunately, that’s maybe not the same as a lot of farms where, you know, farmers will keep cows that aren’t producing a calf every year. They’re not looking at efficiencies ………and they’ve maybe never sat down there with a Consultant. They’ve never sat down, another group of farmers and said, well, actually,

if you want this cow herds to be profitable, you need to make sure your cows are doing what they meant to do, and that is have a calf” IP 8

5.2.10.4 Theme 4 Knowledge Exchange and Efficiency Improvement in Scottish Beef Farming

Ali and Golgeci (2021) explored the importance of knowledge acquisition, assimilation, and application in the agri-foods supply chain. The study concluded that knowledge application resulted in a better risk management culture, leading to supply chain resilience.

5.2.10.4.1 Peer to Peer Learning as a tool for efficiency

The IP 8 mentioned the importance of peer-to-peer learning in the Scottish beef industry, which can be used to improve efficiency in livestock farming. Jalil (2024) explored peer-to-peer learning via informal methods such as conversation-based learning. The study identified that this peer-to-peer learning can be implemented in phases and allows livestock farmers to develop one-on-one contacts. This approach can be more tailored based on the size and nature of the farm operations.

“I think knowledge exchange like peer-to-peer learning between farmers is probably the biggest tool that we've got for improving efficiencies and Scottish beef farming” IP8

5.2.10.4.2 Barriers to Knowledge Transfer

The IP 8 discussed that knowledge transfers are difficult because the farmers are very busy, and it becomes difficult for them to take time off farming to engage in other activities.

“And but it's very difficult to get cause, you know, farmers are busy and and a lot of farmers don't value time and off-farm and they're doing” IP 8

Moreover, there is no drive to improve efficiency.

“They're not looking at efficienciesthey've maybe never sat down there with a consultant. They've never sat down, another group of farmers”IP 8

5.2.10.4.3 Potential for Productivity Gains through Knowledge Transfer

The IP 8 also indicated that knowledge transfer could improve productivity just like other industries but again expressed that it is challenging to achieve in Scottish Agriculture.

“So there's a big, you know, there's a 10% increase in productivity there within most Scottish herds that can be done and a lot of that could just be done through knowledge transfer, a bit of mentoring and think that all these kind of things that a lot of industry other industries have embraced. But it's it's quite hard to get it into Scottish Agriculture” IP8

5.2.10.4.4 Need for Industry-CPD Standards

IP 8 also pointed out that there is a need to initiate an industry-wide CPD program for the Scottish Farmer as well. He also mentioned that a large majority of farmers are working on their own. Therefore, engaging the livestock farmers in the CPD course is very important to increase efficiency.

“You know, most other industries, CPD as you know as mandatory you need to do that you need to go out and and and build your skillset, fight learn new skills where and in farming it’s not and because a lot of guys are farming on their own and it’s they find it difficult to have time or that or there’s not the incentive to go out and do. That and which is a real shame, because I think, you know, we’ve got we have got a really good industry and we’ve got a good story to tell” IP 8

The IP 8 highlighted the factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC, mainly from the perspective of livestock farmers. Trust, Supplier Selection criteria, Information sharing and redundancy were discussed as essential for mitigating disruptions and achieving resilience. Challenges of the SBSC were also mentioned, such as the ageing population, lack of succession, financial returns, limited collaboration, critical mass and market uncertainty, which are barriers to resilience. The impact of subsidy schemes was also examined with criticism of the current farming system fostering complacency and inefficiency. The need for consultation and peer-to-peer learning was also emphasised to improve efficiency and profitability.

5.2.11 Livestock Farmer Interview Participant No.9

Initials	Role/Position	Farm Size (Ha)	Farm Type	Years in Farming	Primary Activity	Organisational Role	Area
KR	Livestock Farmer (Breeding Farm) / Veterinarian	750 Hectare (1853 Acres)	Mixed (Cattle & Sheep)	Fifth Generation Farmers (150 years)	Beef Production, Barley	Chair Livestock Quality Board	Scottish Borders

Table 5.5 Interview Participant Profile IP (KR) 9

The Interview with Interview Participant 9 was very informative and enriched the research findings based on the experience ranging from being a fifth-generation farmer to working as a professional veterinarian and Chair of a non-departmental public body for livestock.

Figure 5.14 Interview Coding in NVivo IP 9

5.2.11.1 Theme 1 Challenges faced by the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

Various challenges were identified by the IP 9 which are classified as under.

5.2.11.1.1 Operational Challenges

The operational challenges ranged from Critical mass to regulator uncertainty. The IP 9 expressed the challenges as follows

5.2.11.1.1 Critical Mass

The lack of critical mass for the processing sector was discussed by the IP 9 and its impact on the processing sector was also highlighted. The concern of the IP 9 is justified as the Scottish processing sector is already concentrated and lack of critical mass may result into closure of existing processing sector and further distributing the competitive arena of the processing sector.

“You then got problems further downstream in the processing sector because if there isn't a critical mass of that Livestock, you don't have enough account service. All the processors that we have here, uh, if you lose processors, you then lose competition” IP9

5.2.11.1.2. Lack of Veterinarian services

Another challenge identified by IP 9 was lack of veterinarian service in the remote areas. It is a very important issue because the lack of vet. Service can lead to delayed vaccinations and timely identification of diseases.

“There aren't really enough vets, particularly in the more remote areas, to cover all the work that needs to be done, and so they are really stretched” IP 9

5.2.11.1.3 Lack of Succession and Aging Population

The changing demographics of the Scottish Livestock farming were also counted as an operational challenge. The livestock farmers are getting older, and the younger generation is not interested in pursuing the livestock farming as a profession. This can be gauged from the fact that the IP9 is itself a fifth generation farmer and a qualified veterinarian but the next generation does not want to pursue livestock farming.

“demographic challenges that we have in Scotland and the succession problems” IP 9

5.2.11.1.4 Systemic Impact of lack of production

The IP 9 also indicated that the fall in the number of cattle has impacted the whole supply chain. As in the livestock farming sector the key input are the cattle produced. If the cattle numbers are decreasing it means that the auction markets will have less number available for the buyers and sellers, the processing sector will struggle to meet its minimum threshold to remain functional and profitable and the retailers will also struggle to meet the consumer demand.

“So, a fall in the number of cattle can have a huge effect right across the supply chain” IP9

5.2.11.1.2 Economic Challenges

The main economic challenge faced by the livestock farmers is profitability.

5.2.11.1.2.1 Lack of Financial Returns

The IP9 indicated that due to decreasing financial returns the new entrants are not willing to join the livestock farming sector. The decline in the cattle herd is also leading to lack of profitability for the entire beef supply chain and threatening its resilience.

“So the biggest the biggest talking point at the minute in the sector is the the fall in suckler cow numbers and and I think that it creates a lot of problems that we need to to look at being resilient” IP9

5.2.11.1.2.2 Uncompensated Sustainability Costs

The IP 9 mentioned that the livestock farmers are under immense pressure to adopt sustainable practices that involve higher costs. However, on the other hand the livestock farmers are not receiving higher payments to offset these costs.

“You know the supply chain is pushing for more sustainable beef production, but are they paying anything more for it, not at the moment” IP9

5.2.11.1.3 Environmental and Regulatory Challenges

The IP9 told that the main environmental challenge is the misconception regarding the Green House Gas emissions. It was mentioned that the correct parameters needed to be set to accurately calculate the Methane emissions

5.2.11.1.4 GHG Emissions

The IP 9 mentioned that they are starting a project with AHDB of England to study the carbon stored in soil across 170 farms. This project will take into account the carbon stored in the hedges in the farms and the small areas of trees which in not counted at presented. The IP 9 said that only the methane emissions are taken into account but the carbon sequestration is not correctly calculated to offset its environmental impact.

“I think a lot of the perception out there is that we need to reduce the emissions to 0 and that's not, that's not net zero. Net zero is reducing your emissions, but also increasing your sequestration” IP9

5.2.11.1.4.1 Regulatory Uncertainty

The IP9 mentioned that pre Brexit the Common Agricultural policy provided predictable subsidies and support structures. After Brexit the slow response of the Scottish Government in policy formulation is leading to unpredictable future.

“one of the main changes I think we've seen since we came out of the EU is the loss of that long term sort of strategy and the long term policy and at the moment, without that certainty, farmers don't know what's coming around the corner, really” IP9

5.2.11.1.5 Technological Challenges

The technological challenge is the adoption of new technologies to improve efficiency.

5.2.11.1.5.1 Slow to Adopt new Technology

The IP9 also mentioned that one of the challenges is the adoption of new technologies. The farming community is slow to adopt new technologies. The advantages of the adoption of new technologies were also discussed, and a solution was also proposed by encouraging the livestock farmers to use the technologies to save their time and improve efficiency. The interview extracts below are

“I don't even think we need an awful lot more new technology. There's a lot of new technology out there that which hasn't been hasn't been used yet if you've got that technology that beats to your mobile phone to say this cow's gonna Calf, you can go straight to that” IP9

The IP 9 proposed that a mindset change is required to educate people about the usage of technologies.

“Education knowledge transfer mindset change and getting people to to take these technologies up and and all these things could make quite a lot of difference” IP9

5.2.11.1.6 Structural Challenges

The IP 9 mentioned that a better infrastructure is required in the processing sector. Due to lack of a proper infrastructure the livestock farmers have to take long journeys to take their cattle for slaughtering.

“...better infrastructure at a processor level so that people don't have to send animals quite so far would be would be an absolute dream” IP9

5.2.11.1.7

5.2.11.2 Theme 2 Factors contributing to the Resilience of the Scottish beef supply chain

The IP 9 also discussed about the factors which are contributing to the resilience of the SBSC.

5.2.11.2.1 Communication and Collaboration

Several authors (Stone and Rahimifard, 2018; Aboah et al., 2019; Zhong et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2024) have emphasised the critical role of collaboration in building resilient agricultural supply chains.

The IP 9 explained that their organisation conducts workshops aimed at improving communication and collaboration along the supply chain. These workshops focus on helping farmers connect with others in the supply chain, such as store producers and finishers, to ensure production aligns with market demands. For example, store producers can engage with finishers to better understand what types of animals are in demand, enabling them to adjust factors like genetics or breeding programs accordingly. Similarly, finishing farmers are encouraged to communicate with processors to gain insights into market preferences and

requirements. This approach helps ensure that farmers are producing what the market needs, resulting in a higher-quality product and better financial returns.

The IP9 emphasised that these initiatives are designed to streamline communication across the supply chain, preventing farmers from continuing to produce what they have always produced without regard to changing market conditions. Instead, the focus is on aligning production with market demands to improve profitability and efficiency.

“Our industry development part is the probably the smallest part of the organisation. Farmers in general want to see us marketing their product to consumers and developing new markets rather than us telling them what to do and so we don't we try to make it much more sort of them about communication and collaboration rather than just experts saying you should be doing this. You should be doing that because farmers, in my experience, don't take very well to being told things they get on much better if things are explained to them” IP9

IP 9 also mentioned that the industry development aspect of their organisation is relatively small, farmers generally expect the organisation to focus more on marketing their products to consumers and developing new markets rather than dictating practices. As a result, their approach prioritizes collaboration and knowledge sharing over issuing directives.

The IP9 highlighted that, based on their experience, farmers respond better to explanations and practical discussions rather than being told what to do. This reflects a preference for mutual learning and partnership-based strategies, which foster trust and engagement among farmers.

5.2.11.2.2 Government Support

A recent study by Yuan (2024) highlighted the contribution of Government support as an important strategy in achieving supply chain resilience in an agricultural supply chain. The IP 9 also mentioned that the Government policy has a significant impact on the future planning of the farmers. The government policies include subsidies, grants and incentives which can assist farmers to adopt resilient practices for instance buying buffer stock and hedging against other risks.

“the government policy is has a huge impact on what farmers decide to do” IP 9

5.2.11.2.3 Resilient thinking

The IP9 is a fifth-generation farmer, and the family is resident of that estate for 150 years. This implies towards resilient thinking which can be a component of a resilient supply chain. Darnhofer, Fairweather and Moller (2010) indicated that a farmer's role is very vital and resilience thinking may lead to resilient farming.

Overview of IP 9's interview

The IP 9 explained the challenges faced by the SBSC including declining cattle numbers, veterinarian shortages, aging farmers, low profitability, sustainability costs, regulatory uncertainty, and slow adoption of technology. Structural issues, such as inadequate processing infrastructure, further strain the sector. The IP 9 also mentioned that the supply chain resilience of the Scottish Beef industry is contributed by improved communication and collaboration, government subsidies, and resilient thinking rooted in generational farming experience.

5.2.12 Livestock Farmer Interview Participant (IP) 10

Initials	Role/Position	Farm Size (Ha)	Farm Type	Years in Farming	Primary Activity	Organisational Role	Area
GL	Livestock Farmer (Finisher)	242 Hectare (600 Acres)	Mixed (Cattle & Hen)	Over 30 years	Beef Production, arable crops	Chair Farming Cooperative	Scottish Borders

Table 5.6 Interview Participant Profile IP (GL) 10

The interview participant is a livestock farmer and is categorised as a Finisher. The farm finishes approximately 500 Aberdeen Angus Sire Cattle and has approximately 8000 egg laying hens. The farmer also publishes a farming magazine once a month. The discussion with the livestock finisher was very insightful and provided a rich context regarding the SBSC. The figure below shows initial coding in Nvivo.

Figure 5.15 Interview Coding in NVivo IP10

5.2.12.1 Theme 1 Challenges Faced by SBSC

There are various challenges identified by the finisher. The prime challenge, as identified by the other livestock farmers, remains the same, which is the economic challenge.

5.2.12.1.1 Economic Challenges

The economic challenge, as described by the IP10, can be further classified into the lack of profitability, supply-demand imbalance, lack of financial means, and domestic and international competition.

5.2.12.1.1.1 Lack of Financial Returns

The IP 10 mentioned that the financial returns are the biggest challenge which is being faced by the livestock farmers particularly and the beef supply chain overall.

“the biggest threat we have is lack of financial return” IP10

The IP10 reiterated that the biggest concern are the finances to run the business not the disease

“I think you're getting that you can get the idea we're much more aware of financially that is our biggest worry is finance is not disease” IP10

5.2.12.1.1.2 Supply Demand Imbalance

The IP10 also highlighted that the shortage of cattle supplies has created a supply-demand imbalance. The suckler cow numbers are declining consistently and the finishers have to pay more to buy the cattle to meet the increasing demand.

“All we need to do is buy cattle as cattle gets shorter and there are less and less suckler cows in Scotland. It's a declining number, so we're having to probably pay more for cattle if they get scarce”IP10

5.2.12.1.1.3 Domestic and International Competition

Another concern expressed by the IP10 was the competition from the domestic and international markets. Due to decreased cattle numbers, dairy cattle is also used to meet the beef demand. The demand supply imbalance has also paved the way for beef import from international markets. The IP10 is implying that due to increased supply of dairy sources beef and import from Countries like Ireland and Poland may lead to price competition potential driving down the market prices for Scottish Beef. This will be very detrimental to the SBSC source which are the livestock produces because in Scotland the quality assurance and animal health and safety regulations are strict then other beef producing countries which significantly increases the cost of production.

“a lot of meat is now coming out of the dairy industry, which makes up the shortfall in Suckler produced beef.Umm, but you know we have our we have competition from Ireland.You gonna put competition from Poland? There's nothing we can do about that” IP10

5.2.12.1.2 Operational Challenges

A few operational challenges were also identified by the IP10 which are common to all livestock farmers. The lack of succession and labour shortages are also impacting the day to day operations of the livestock farmers. The following extract show the concern of the IP10 regarding the operational challenges

“The sons of farmers who the fathers would have had cows, the sons go off and get other jobs once an easier life” *IP10*

“The reason I'll tell you the reason is sorry, lifestyle. It's very hard to get labour now to want to manage these cows. It's very hard to get people to come and work” *IP10*

5.2.12.2 Theme 2 General Concerns regarding the SBSC

The IP10 also revealed some other issues regarding the SBSC from the perspective of the livestock farmers.

5.2.12.2.1 Risk Exposure

The IP 10 implied that their risk exposure in the finish cattle business is relatively low due to the short duration approximately 120 days that cattle remain on the farm. This short production cycle reduces their commitment and provides flexibility, allowing them to exit the business quickly if necessary.

The IP 10 also mentioned that, even during disease outbreaks like foot and mouth, movement restrictions typically allow cattle to still be sent for slaughter, minimizing disruption for finishing farms like theirs. In contrast, breeding farms face greater challenges during such outbreaks because of their long-term investment in livestock production and their reliance on ongoing breeding cycles, making them more vulnerable to movement controls and operational disruptions.

“I mean the average, I would think the average time of cattle are on the farm is about 120 days, is about 120 days, so our exposure is not great so, and our commitment isn't huge either. We can get out of this business relatively easily” IP10

5.2.12.2.2 Disruption to Market Exposure

The IP10 implied that the primary risk originates from the market fluctuations such as price volatility and supply demand imbalance rather than supply chain disruptions within the supply chain.

“At the end of the day, so we're very, very exposed to market fluctuations, but we don't have supply chain disruptions” IP10

5.2.12.2.3 Disruption Disease Based

The IP10 expressed that disease outbreaks are not perceived as a major threat to their business, primarily because they operate as a finishing farm rather than a breeding farm. For this reason, TB (tuberculosis), which poses a more significant risk to breeding farms, is not a concern for them. However, IP10 acknowledged that foot and mouth disease could present a serious disruption if an outbreak led to movement restrictions in their area. Despite this, the interviewee views such outbreaks as infrequent, referencing the fact that there has not been a foot and mouth outbreak in the past 25 years. While the risk remains, they are

prepared to live with it and do not see it as a day-to-day operational threat. The IP10 also highlighted that the greater disease threat to their business comes from avian flu affecting their poultry operations, rather than from cattle diseases. For cattle, national outbreaks such as blue tongue and foot and mouth are recognized as potential risks, but these are largely beyond their control, as government-imposed movement controls would manage such situations.

“We don't see disease outbreak as a huge threat” IP10

5.2.12.2.4

5.2.12.3 Theme 3 Factors Contributing to the resilience of SBSC

The IP 10 identified various factors which lead to a resilience of SBSC. The following sub themes highlight the factors highlighted by IP 10.

5.2.12.3.1 Supply Base Diversity

Christopher and Peck (2004) mentioned that a single source may enable to save cost but it may compromise the resilience of the supply chain. Therefore, relying on multiple sources minimizes the impact of disruptions and allows greater sourcing flexibility. The IP 10 mentioned that they have a diverse supply source. They acquire cattle through multiple channels which includes auction marts, livestock agents and directly from farms with whom they have established relationships.

“We probably we totallyso 25% from auction markets, 20% from Livestock, agents, so they come straight from a farm farm to farm, but they are sold by an agent and 50 to 60% direct from farm from we have relationships with producers” IP10

5.2.12.3.2 Supplier Selection

Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015) classified appropriate supplier selection as a proactive strategy to achieve supply chain resilience. The IP10 emphasised the importance of appropriate supplier selection by highlight that they only source cattle from suppliers which follow the QMS assurance schemes. This reflects the strategic criteria for selection of suppliers for high quality, safety and traceability.

“we would never buy cattle from someone who doesn't have farm assurance that there are very few people now without farm assurance anyway. So all our cattle are definitely assured”IP10

5.2.12.3.3 Operational Efficiency

Chowdhury and Quaddus (2016) proposed that efficiency is in important component of proactive approaches for a resilient supply chain. The IP10 mentioned that operational efficiency is at the core of their farming practices, particularly focusing on feed management, performance monitoring, and data-driven decision-making to ensure profitability. The IP10 highlighted the importance of feeding efficiency,

where every aspect, from the cost of feed to its utilisation, is carefully managed to maximize growth rates and minimize costs. Regular weighing of cattle, conducted monthly, allows them to closely track growth performance and assess whether the feed inputs are yielding the desired economic returns. This process is supported by detailed record-keeping, which provides a clear understanding of figures and enables informed adjustments to practices if needed. By continuously measuring and analysing data, the farm can optimize resources, maintain profit margins, and respond effectively to market changes or unexpected disruptions. This approach clearly signifies that operational efficiency is adopted to make the supply chain resilient.

“it's efficiency, it's efficiency in everything we do....., we measure everything.IP10

“Everything is fed very accurately. We record everything and we we certainly know our figures and that tells us whether we're going to make a margin or not” IP10

5.2.12.3.4 Traceability

Zhao et al., (2024) highlighted the importance of traceability in the agriculture food supply chain resilience. The authors proposed that traceability in the agri food supply chain helps in reducing the supply risk, demand risk and biological and environmental risk. The IP10 also discussed the importance of traceability and genetic information for cattle management. After the horsemeat scandal at Tesco the consumer trust was badly shook and its sales sharply declined in its nine out of 11 global markets (The Guardian, 2013). Therefore, traceability is very vital in order to avoid food fraud and keep the consumer confidence intact.

“we need to know we have to know who the which actual bulls are the animal. We need to have the name of the bull” IP10

5.2.12.3.5 Operational Flexibility

Stone and Shahin Rahimifard (2018) identified flexibility as a core contributor for supply chain resilience. Sa et al., (2020) concluded that the flexibility is more prevalent at the processor and manufacturing in a agrifood supply chain resilience. The IP10 implied their operational flexibility to respond to market fluctuations and to mitigate the financial and market risks. IP10 mentioned that can adjust their purchasing decision based on market conditions and profitability forecasts.

“We can supply finished product Earlier or later, we can supply pretty well what the market wants We are flexible. We don't have to go and buy these cattle if we don't want to. Umm, we only buy them if we think we can make a margin on them” IP10

5.2.12.3.6 Operational Diversity

Diversity in supply chains means having backups like extra suppliers, products, processes, and resources. It also includes multiple transport options, stock levels, and flexible operations to handle disruptions effectively (Carvalho et al., 2012).

“So so we have we finish approximately 500 Cattle, Aberdeen, Angus, sire Cattle a year. We have 8000 organic egg laying hens which are organic. We have about 120 hectares of arable crops. We have a large game bird hatchery. Umm. And we published a magazine once a month. So we have a very and we do some contracting. So it's a very diverse business” IP10

The IP10 mentioned the diverse nature of their business, which includes finishing 500 Aberdeen Angus cattle annually, managing 8,000 organic egg-laying hens, cultivating 120 hectares of arable crops, operating a game bird hatchery, offering contracting services, and publishing a monthly magazine. This diversified business model has significant implications for resilience within their operations. By spreading activities across multiple sectors, the business reduces its dependency on any single revenue stream, mitigating risks associated with market fluctuations, disease outbreaks, or price volatility. For example, if cattle markets weaken, egg production or crop farming can act as alternative income sources, buffering against financial shocks. The integration of arable farming to support livestock feed further strengthens supply chain stability by reducing reliance on external suppliers. The inclusion of a monthly magazine also emphasises knowledge-sharing, networking, and community engagement, fostering collaboration and trust within the agricultural sector. This diversity leads to a resilient supply chain as pointed out by Carvalho et al., (2012).

The IP10 mentioned economic challenges as the primary issue, including low financial returns, supply-demand imbalances, and competition from domestic and international markets. It was noted that profitability remains a major concern, with declining suckler cow numbers forcing finishers to pay higher prices for cattle. It was mentioned by IP10 that competition can be intensified by imports from countries with lower production costs, such as Ireland and Poland, posing a threat to the SBSC, which adheres to stricter quality and safety regulations. Operational challenges, including labor shortages and succession issues, were also noted as ongoing difficulties affecting daily farm operations.

IP10 mentioned the lower risk exposure of finishers due to their short production cycle of approximately 120 days, which allows flexibility to exit the business quickly if needed. While disease outbreaks such as foot and mouth are a concern, movement restrictions typically still permit cattle to be sent for slaughter, minimizing disruption for finishing farms. However, avian flu poses a more significant risk to their poultry operations. Market fluctuations, including price volatility and supply-demand imbalances, were identified as more pressing threats than disease-based disruptions.

Several resilience strategies were highlighted by IP10. Supply base diversity was emphasised as critical, with cattle sourced through auction marts, agents, and direct farm relationships to minimise dependence on single sources. Supplier selection focused on quality and safety standards, prioritising suppliers under the QMS assurance schemes. Operational efficiency was achieved through careful feed management, performance monitoring, and data-driven decisions to optimize resources and profitability. Traceability was underscored as vital to maintaining consumer confidence and preventing fraud, especially in light of past scandals. Operational flexibility allowed adjustments to purchasing decisions based on market conditions, while operational diversity further reinforced resilience. The farm’s diverse activities including cattle finishing, poultry farming, arable crops, contracting services, reduced reliance on single revenue streams and provided buffers against disruptions.

IP10’s diversified operations, efficient resource management, and proactive strategies for supplier selection, traceability, and flexibility highlight a robust approach to building resilience in the SBSC. Their ability to adapt to market shifts, coupled with a strong focus on efficiency and collaboration, positions them well to mitigate risks and maintain stability in a volatile agricultural environment.

5.2.13 Livestock Farmer Interview Participant (IP)11

Initials	Role/Position	Farm Size (Ha)	Farm Type	Years in Farming	Primary Activity	Organisational Role	Area
NM	Livestock Farmer (Breeder / Rearer)	550 Hectare (1359 Acres)	Mixed (Cattle & Sheep)	Over 30 years	Beef Production	Former Chairman Farming Organisation / Member of a Research Institute	Scottish Borders

Figure 5.16 Interview Participant Profile IP (NM) 11

IP11 is a highly experienced professional in the livestock and agricultural sector with a background as a qualified veterinarian and extensive leadership experience. IP11 previously held senior positions in a national farmers' organisation, including serving as President from 2011 to 2015, following a term as Vice-President from 2007. Currently, IP11 operates a 1,500-acre upland hill farm in partnership with their family in the Scottish Borders. The farm supports a herd of 160 cows and over 1,000 breeding sheep. In addition

to farming, IP11 has held prominent roles in research and development organisations, contributing to advancing animal health and welfare. Bringing a wealth of experience from both policy advocacy and on-the-ground farming practices, IP11 provided valuable insights into the SBSC (SBSC). The following figure shows the initial coding of the transcription done in Nvivo.

Figure 5.17 Interview Coding in NVivo IP11

5.2.13.1 Theme Factor Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC

The IP11 highlighted only Contingency planning as a contributor to resilience of the SBSC.

5.2.13.1.1 Contingency Planning

Blackhurst et al., (2011) proposed contingency planning as an enabler of supply chain resilience. The role of contingency planning in achieving engineering resilience was also highlighted by Adobor and McMullen (2018).

“I think those contingency plans where you know very much built on experience from 2001 and and you know they tried to learn the lessons from that. So in some ways, I think they're actually quite good and quite robust. And they were then tested by Epic to ascertain whether one modeling they looked as if they were effective, and they also looked at the cost of them. So I you know, it was quite a deep a process and and I think it is quite good, but the reality is that it was based on the 2001 outbreak. So if you had a very difference in outbreak, well, maybe your contingency plan would look quite so good. And I think it also is quite uh, it relies on your traceability system working well and it probably relies on being having manpower available”

IP11

The IP11 implied toward the UK Government's contingency plans for managing animal disease outbreaks, particularly those developed in response to the 2001 Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD) outbreak.

*“the contingency planning and the structures of that go around that you know I suppose determine your preparedness and I think that you Scotland is quite lucky they've got the EPIC group which is a consortium of institutions and universities with the expertise and not only epidemiology and disease, but in economics as well and that group you'll gives advice to ministers and to the CVO (Chief Veterinary officer) on on your modifying or your thing You're changing the to approach Disease Control could actually model it and and I suppose to determine its value in cost benefit terms as well. So as well as Disease Control terms. So I think in some ways Scotland is quite well prepared”*IP11

The reference to EPIC (Epidemiology, Population Health, and Infectious Disease Control) suggests that these plans were tested and assessed for effectiveness and cost efficiency under government or public health frameworks. EPIC is a research centre that works closely with the Scottish Government to provide scientific evidence for managing animal disease outbreaks, further pointing to government-level preparedness strategies. The contingency plans are described as being robust but context-specific, meaning they were shaped by the 2001 FMD outbreak experience and might face challenges if applied to different types of outbreaks. This implies that the plans rely on functional traceability systems and manpower availability, which are critical for their success.

5.2.13.2 Theme Challenges faced by SBSC

IP11 identified various challenges, including economic, structural, operational, environmental, and regulatory challenges. IP11 identified Processor dominance, which was also highlighted by IP5 and IP6.

IP5 and IP9 mentioned the operational challenge of a Lack of Veterinary services. Likewise, IP11 highlighted the operational challenges of an aging population and labour shortage.

Lack of a National Vaccine

A lack of National Vaccine approach was a novel challenge introduced by the IP11.

“ the last of the blue Tounge outbreak or the only blue Tang outbreak, Scotland probably feared quite well and was quite radical and introduced a vaccine policy at an early stage to try and remain disease free. And I suppose I was involved that I was involved in selling that policy to the industry. I’m not sure whether you're at the time we had a pretty proactive and quite ambitious CVO I'm not sure whether that policy would ever be repeated and that I'm not sure whether there's the energy and commitment, and also the financial resources to actually deliver that sort of approach in the future. I think in many ways it was the right approach, certainly right at the time. There are epidemiological sort of evidence. Yeah, I suppose and modelling to suggest that blue tongue is very likely unlikely to establish north of the central belt just because of temperatures, so that you would Scotland or even if it had a freezing outbreak, probably it would wouldn't be a sustained incursion. You know, whatever you did so, so that may change thinking a bit, but I I guess that I suppose my concern is that they're probably isn't the will and the energy to look at a national vaccine approach”IP11

The IP11 provided valuable insights into the SBSC, drawing on extensive experience as a veterinarian, farmer, and industry leader. Operating a mixed cattle and sheep farm in the Scottish Borders, IP11 highlighted the importance of contingency planning as a critical factor in enhancing supply chain resilience. The IP11 identified key structural and operational challenges, including processor dominance, labour shortages, and an aging workforce. A lack of a national vaccine strategy was highlighted as a specific gap in disease prevention, with concerns about reduced government commitment and financial resources to support such proactive measures in the future.

5.2.14 Overview of Livestock Farmer’s Interviews

The analysis of the livestock farmer interviews provides an in-depth exploration of the challenges and resilience factors within the SBSC. Livestock farmers discussed a range of economic, structural, operational, environmental, and regulatory challenges that influence the sector. Among the most pressing concerns was the lack of financial returns, which has been exacerbated by declining cattle numbers. This financial strain has contributed to farmers exiting the industry, raising concerns about the long-term sustainability and viability of the supply chain.

Structural imbalances also emerged as a key challenge, with several farmers highlighting the dominance of processors and retailers. This imbalance created a power asymmetry, leaving primary producers with limited bargaining leverage and reducing profitability. The lack of long-term contracts and relationship-building with procurement teams was noted as a particular concern, making it difficult for farmers to plan and invest in improvements. Operational issues, such as labour shortages, aging populations, and succession planning difficulties, further strained farmers' ability to adapt and modernize their operations.

Figure 5.18 Challenges Identified by the Livestock Farmers

Environmental and regulatory pressures were similarly highlighted as barriers to resilience. Farmers expressed frustration over the portrayal of livestock farming as a major contributor to greenhouse gas emissions without adequate recognition of offsetting practices such as carbon sequestration. Government incentives promoting tree planting over livestock grazing were cited as a threat to agricultural land use and productivity. Regulatory uncertainty, particularly post-Brexit, created further ambiguity about future subsidies and support mechanisms, making it difficult for farmers to plan ahead.

The interviews also emphasised challenges related to technological adoption. While some farmers recognized the potential benefits of technologies such as electronic identification systems, decision support software, and block chain for improving traceability and efficiency, adoption remained slow. Barriers included high costs, limited technical expertise, and insufficient support from government bodies to facilitate adoption.

Despite these challenges, several resilience factors were identified within the SBSC. Contingency planning was specifically highlighted by one farmer (IP11) as a key component for addressing disruptions, particularly in the context of disease outbreaks. The 2001 Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD) outbreak served as a critical learning experience, prompting the development of robust contingency plans supported by organisations such as EPIC. These plans were noted for their ability to model disease scenarios and assess cost-benefit responses, emphasising the importance of preparedness.

In addition to contingency planning, recurring themes across participants included trust and collaboration among supply chain partners. Farmers described how trust-based relationships with suppliers and buyers ensured consistent quality standards and supported stability. Auction marts were particularly highlighted as platforms that improved price transparency and counterbalanced power asymmetries within the supply chain.

Traceability was also recognized as a crucial factor in resilience. Farmers discussed the importance of systems for tracking livestock movements and the use of DNA testing in meat products to ensure transparency and reduce the risk of food fraud. Such measures were viewed as critical for maintaining consumer confidence and safeguarding the reputation of Scottish beef.

Redundancy and risk mitigation strategies further contributed to resilience. Farmers emphasised maintaining buffer stocks, preserving genetic diversity, and utilising diverse supply sources to protect against disruptions. Operational flexibility, including adjusting production cycles and sourcing strategies based on market conditions, was also highlighted as an effective approach to mitigating risks.

Government support emerged as another key enabler of resilience. Farmers acknowledged the role of subsidies and grants, such as the Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme, in stabilising their operations. However, concerns were raised about whether current support mechanisms are adequate to address evolving sustainability requirements and compliance demands.

Psychological resilience also played a role in farmers' ability to manage disruptions. Several participants emphasised the importance of mental preparedness and adaptability, underscoring the need for industry and government initiatives to support farmer well-being.

In conclusion, the interviews highlight the complex challenges facing the SBSC, including economic pressures, structural imbalances, environmental concerns, and regulatory uncertainties. However, the resilience of the sector is underpinned by contingency planning, trust, collaboration, traceability, redundancy, and government support. Addressing these challenges while leveraging existing resilience factors will be critical to sustaining the Scottish beef industry in the future.

5.2.15 Processing Sector Interviews

The processing sector is a vital component of Scotland's beef supply chain. To gain deeper insights into this sector, three interviews were conducted. The first was with a representative from a trade body that advocates for meat processors in Scotland, providing an overview of industry standards, challenges, and regulatory interactions. The second interview featured insights from a family-owned processing plant in Lockerbie, which integrates farming and abattoir services. This facility emphasises local sourcing and full traceability, ensuring minimal food miles and high-quality meat products. The third interview was with the managing director of a long-established butchery and meat processing business founded in 1922, this company has evolved over generations, operating its own abattoir and multiple retail outlets.

5.2.16 Trade Body Representative (Executive) for Meat Processors and Wholesalers Interview Participant (IP)12

IP12 has extensive experience in the Scottish beef industry, with a career that spans both the farming and processing sectors. In the current role, IP12 holds a leadership position within an organisation representing meat processors and wholesalers in Scotland. The IP 12 collaborates closely with government bodies and regulatory agencies to address issues impacting the red meat sector. Previously, IP11 served as the Chief Executive of a major farmers' association in Scotland and represented beef farmers for over a decade. With immense experience in both farming and processing sectors the IP12 provided valuable information regarding the SBSC.

The initial codes from the interview transcript are shown in the figure below.

Figure 5.19 Interview Coding in NVivo IP12

5.2.16.1 Theme Challenges Faced by the SBSC

The IP12 identified various challenges faced by the SBSC which are discussed below.

5.2.16.1.1 Economic Challenges

The economic challenges highlighted by IP12 included low profit margin and competition from domestic and international markets.

High Capital Investment and Low Profit Margin

The IP 12 discussed about high capital investment requirements of the processing sector and indicated that the return on investment is insufficient

“Scotland so highly competitive industry one with a huge amount of capital investment and operates on very, very little margins” IP12

Competition from Import

The IP 12 highlighted the concern of future trade deal which may allow lower cost beef produced under less stringent conditions which may lead to a less profitable and unsustainable domestic market in the long term.

“So that has been a problem and the big fear for both farmers and processors looking forward to the future would be a future trade deals that the UK Government could do and the more they open up the UK market to products that you know aren't produced the same standards that we either ask our farmers to do or we ask our meat processors to to meet, that could undermine the the market price for the product here again making it a less profitable” IP12

Competition from Dairy Market

Another challenge highlighted by IP12 was the supply of beef from the Dairy Herd. The IP 12 implied that this shift may undermine the premium status of the Scottish Suckler Beef which is associated with higher quality and traceability.

“So in Scotland we are still predominantly suckler based industry, but increasingly it might Beef that comes out of the dairy herd a significant and that's changed over the years” IP12

5.2.16.1.2 Structural Challenges

Critical Mass

The IP12 emphasised the importance of maintaining livestock numbers for the viability of the SBSC highlighting the potential loss of critical mass. The IP12 implied that the lack of the livestock numbers could affect the processing plants which may lead to the underutilization of the facilities and making the industry financially vulnerable.

“You know, if you want to maintain the size of industry, you need to maintain Livestock numbers” IP12

“...therefore less likely that we could sustain the critical mass that we have” IP12

5.2.16.1.2.1 Bargaining Power of Big Finishers

The IP12 highlighted the structural disparity between large scale finishers and small farmers in terms of market access and relationships with the processors. Large finishers are able to establish direct contact with the abattoirs by assuring them supply consistency. This structural imbalance makes the small livestock

farmers more vulnerable to market fluctuations. Moreover the dependence of the small finisher on Auction Marts may lead to higher transaction costs and uncertainty.

“I think there is again a bit generalization, but I think there is a difference between if you're a big finisher with a lot of stock, you will tend to have a good relationship with an abattoir, cause you can send basic level truckload of stock to abattoir. If you're a smaller finisher or smaller farmer, then what? The auction mark system allows you to do is to sell into that system” IP12

5.2.16.1.2 Retailer Dependence

The IP12 mentioned that the Scottish beef industry is mainly dependent on the Retail sector. This interdependence leads to both opportunities and vulnerabilities for the supply chain. The big processor have established exclusive relationship with retailers and reliance on a single buyer may lead to reduced bargaining power.

“The single biggest customer for the industry as a whole would be the UK retail sector and what you generally have speaking is an individual processor tied up with an individual retailer” IP12

5.2.16.1.3 Operational Challenges

Labor Challenges Post Brexit

The interviewee (IP12) is mentioned that labour shortages in the processing sector, particularly due to policy changes imposed by the UK government regarding the recruitment of overseas butchers pose a major threat to the Scottish beef industry. These policy changes, including stricter immigration rules and higher wage requirements for hiring foreign workers, have made it more difficult and costly to recruit the skilled labour needed for meat processing operations.

Limited Collaboration in the Supply Chain

The interviewee (IP12) mentioned that while competition among processors in the Scottish beef industry prevents collaboration on pricing and contracts, there is still collective cooperation on shared regulatory and industry-wide issues. Specifically, processors and wholesalers work together through associations like the Scottish Association of Meat Wholesalers (SAMW) to address common challenges, such as compliance with Food Standards Scotland (FSS) regulations and consumer perceptions of beef consumption.

“So in terms of a Scottish Association..... we don't talk about pricing. We don't talk about contracts because that's all competitive issues for individual plants, but where they do work together because they all have a shared interest in it would be issues such as..... Food Standards Scotland say and with regards to beef consumption”. IP12

5.2.16.1.4 Regulatory Challenges

Post Brexit Trade Barriers

The interviewee IP12 mentioned that Brexit has created major disruptions in the European export market, resulting in increased costs and reduced profitability for the Scottish beef industry. The introduction of trade barriers, including customs checks, export documentation requirements, and logistical delays, has made it more challenging and expensive to access what were once profitable and easily accessible markets in Europe

“another big issue for us in recent times has been there disruption that we've had to the European export market because of Brexit, now markets that previously were accessible and were profitable that are no longer accessible and profitable to us” IP12

Uncertain Future Government Initiatives

The IP12 highlighted the uncertainty regarding the government support in terms of subsidies. The IP12 implied that government support is essential for the financial wellbeing of the livestock farmers.

“So I think there'll be a big issue going forward as how much our government is continuing to support farmers and is a big issue with regards to what conditions that they put on those payments that farmers receive in this, this country” IP12

5.2.16.1.5 Other Challenges

Labour Constraints and Social isolation

The IP12 implied that the livestock farmers are understaffed, overworked and heavily reliant on family labour which restricts their capacity to adapt to disruptions. The IP12 also mentioned social isolation which may lead to mental health risks.

“if generalized understaffed and overworked, you know, relying very heavily on family labour in in most cases and there's a lot of farmers who work in nice isolation they don't have the same sort of contacts as they used to” IP12

Changing Consumer Preferences

The IP 12 mentioned that the Consumer preferences have changed over year and to better meet current customer demands the producers and processors should monitor the trends and adjust the production practices accordingly.

“So, the types of products that the consumer bought 20 years ago now because people's eating habits have changed, sizes of families have changed” IP12

The IP12 highlighted a range of challenges impacting the SBSC, emphasising economic, structural, operational, and regulatory pressures. According to IP12 financial vulnerabilities arise from high capital investment requirements and low profit margins, compounded by competition from cheaper imports produced under less stringent standards and an increasing supply of beef from dairy herds, which threatens the premium status of Scottish suckler beef. Structurally, declining livestock numbers pose a risk to maintaining critical mass, potentially leading to underutilized processing plants and reduced profitability. Larger finishers benefit from direct relationships with abattoirs, while smaller farmers often rely on auction markets, facing higher costs and uncertainties. Operational challenges, particularly labour shortages exacerbated by post-Brexit immigration policies and rising wage requirements, further strain the sector's capacity. Limited collaboration among processors, restricted to regulatory compliance rather than pricing strategies, also hinders a unified approach to addressing shared issues. Regulatory barriers, including Brexit-related trade disruptions, have increased export costs and reduced profitability, while uncertainties around future government subsidies create additional financial instability. Social and workforce issues, such as understaffing, over-reliance on family labor, and farmer isolation, combined with shifting consumer preferences for convenience and smaller portions, highlight the need for adaptive strategies. IP12 implied that addressing these challenges requires policy reforms, and stronger collaboration to secure the long-term resilience of the Scottish beef industry.

5.2.16.2 Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC

The IP12 identified the factors which make the Scottish beef supply resilient. The contributors according to IP12 are supply chain leadership, supply chain intelligence and the role of government support. These aspects collectively shape the resilience of the SBSC and are elaborated below.

5.2.16.2.1 Supply Chain Leadership

Zhong, Cheng and Jia (2024) mentioned that Supply chain leadership can empower farmers to resist, adapt to and recover from disruptions. The IP12 implied the supply chain leadership of livestock farmers through the long term vision and strategic decision making demonstrated by the family owned farms within the Scottish Beef Industry. The IP12 highlighted that the resilience stems from the individual leadership of the livestock farmers wherein they are trying to balance the profitability motives with the intergenerational continuity.

“Farmers are traditionally very very resilientthe resilience comes down to the individual and the fact that there are family businesses, you know, with the intent of how do you pass this farm on to the next generation in, in the best, best way possible. So that allows them to take long term decisions” IP 12

5.2.16.2.2 Supply Chain Intelligence

The IP12’s statement about resilience in the supply chain being tied to keeping the industry informed about consumer demands and marketplace trends closely reflects the concept of supply chain intelligence proposed by Christopher and Peck (2004). Their framework mentioned market intelligence as a tool of Collaboration. The strategic knowledge created and shared via supply chain intelligence enable the supply chain to be informed of trends and emerging issues that can impair the future supply chain continuity.

“Resilience in the supply chain is about keeping the industry informed as to what the consumer wants, what the marketplace wants and how that keeps evolving over time” IP 12

5.2.16.2.3 Government Support

The IP12 mentioned the role of Scottish Government in supporting the Scottish Beef industry. The IP12 implied that the knowledgeable policy makers have made it easier to manage disruptions by taking appropriate measures. This aligns with the findings of Zhong, Cheng and Jia (2024) who mentioned that the government support is a contributor to Agri food supply chain resilience by specifically mentioning that the government can provide resources to procure buffer stock.

“Scottish Government, over the course of term, whoever has been in power, has been very willing to do that and generally speaking again be individuals who are in charge of animal health policy or agricultural policy, are knowledgeable and understanding about the industry and therefore that makes it far easier and better to deal with disruptions when, when, when they arise and try and put in place appropriate measures that will help safeguard the industry” IP12

The IP 12 concluded that the resilience of the SBSC is rooted in the individual leadership of farmers, , as well as the industry’s ability to remain informed about market trends and consumer needs. Furthermore, IP12 credited the Scottish Government’s proactive support and understanding of the sector as key to mitigating disruptions and ensuring the continuity and stability of the supply chain.

5.2.17 Processor Interview Participant (IP) 13

The IP 13 is the Managing Director of a family-owned regional meat wholesaler with an abattoir and a processing plant. The business has been in operation for over a century. The MD joined the business in 1986 after completing his Business Degree but his involvement began much earlier as he worked in the business from the age of 11, performing tasks such as washing tools, making sausages and learning the

trade secrets throughout his School and College years. The IP13 highlighted various aspects of the SBSC. The following figures shows the initial codes generated from the interview transcript and after rigorous reading and re reading and listening to the video the themes were generated.

Figure 5.20 Interview Coding in NVivo IP 13

5.2.17.1.1 Theme Factors contribution to the Resilience of SBSC

The IP 13 discussed various factors which contribute to the resilience of the SBSC.

5.2.17.1.2 Flexibility

Flexibility is recognised as a key supply chain contributor. In the initial supply chain resilience framework Christopher and Peck (2004) mentioned that flexibility is an important component of supply chain resilience. The later research (Pettit et al., 2013; Fiksel et al., 2015; Scholten and Schilder, 2015; Hohenstein

et al., 2015; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015; Ali and Golgeci, 2019; Sa et al., 2020) also highlighted flexibility as a key driver for supply chain resilience. In Agri supply chain resilience. Ali and Golgeci (2019) classified flexibility as a preparedness stage strategy.

The IP13 discussed about the flexibility in sourcing, logistical flexibility and operational flexibility.

Flexibility in Business Operations

The IP 13 implied that the resilience of their business is rooted in its flexibility and ability to adapt to fluctuations in the supply chain, including shortages, surpluses, and market stresses. This adaptability is supported by a combination of effective communication, traditional practices, and local knowledge, which have been cultivated over the years. By leveraging long-standing relationships with local suppliers and maintaining a deep understanding of regional dynamics, the business can quickly respond to challenges and capitalize on opportunities. The emphasis on tradition reflects a commitment to proven practices, while communication ensures that information flows seamlessly across the supply chain, enabling coordination and problem-solving.

“over the years we've built up a fairly flexible business that copes with all the stresses and strains and shortages and surpluses” IP13

“it works through a combination of uh, communication tradition, local knowledge”IP13

Flexibility in Logistical Operations

The interviewee (IP13) mentioned that the business has built logistical resilience through a combination of outsourcing and internal capacity to ensure reliable delivery operations, even in remote areas like Shetland. By outsourcing specific routes, such as transporting pallets to Aberdeen before further shipment to Shetland, the business demonstrates strategic use of external logistics providers to extend its market reach while maintaining cost efficiency. Mandal et al., (2016) discussed about the Integration of logistical capabilities at the supply chain level. The author proved that flexibility is a key supply chain resilience driver.

“We do outsource deliveries to Shetland, we take a pallet to Aberdeen and then check the transport, take it on to to to Shetland” IP13

“But in terms of getting product to market, we have sufficient spare vehicles, all the struggle for drivers, but we've got sufficient vehicles to cover our delivery network with reserves and vehicles back at Depot for loading up for the next day” IP13

At the same time, the business highlights its internal capacity with spare vehicles and a reserve fleet at the depot, enabling it to cover delivery networks without interruptions, even in cases of unexpected demands or vehicle breakdowns. However, the mention of a struggle for drivers points to labor shortages, a broader industry challenge that requires ongoing management.

This approach reflects a dual strategy of combining outsourcing for efficiency and in-house resources for reliability, ensuring the supply chain remains agile and capable of adapting to operational challenges without compromising service quality or timely delivery. It also highlights the importance of logistical planning and resource redundancy as key factors in supply chain resilience.

5.2.17.1.3 Supply Base Diversity

The IP13 mentioned that their sourcing strategy is quite diverse, and it also considers the geographical flexibility. The IP 13 implied that the ability to shift sourcing geographically, such as purchasing from Aberdeenshire when numbers are scarce in Dingwall and the Highlands, demonstrates operational flexibility and market responsiveness. This regional adaptability ensures a steady supply of livestock, mitigating risks related to local shortages, seasonal fluctuations, or environmental challenges.

“If numbers are scarce in my area and Dingwall and the Highlands, then we buy more from Aberdeenshire”
IP13

As mentioned in the section on IP10 that the supply base diversity is a contributing factor of supply chain resilience. *“...25% from auction markets, 20% from Livestock, agents, so they come straight from a farm to farm, but they are sold by an agent and 50 to 60% direct from farm from We have relationships with producers”* IP10. By sourcing 25% of livestock from auction markets, 20% through agents, and 50–60% directly from farms, the business reduces its dependence on any single supply channel, which minimizes the risk of supply disruptions.

5.2.17.1.4 Supplier Relationships

The significance of supplier relationships, as supported by relevant literature, is also examined under the heading Supplier Relationships for interview analysis of the consultant IP3. The IP 13 implied that long-term relationships with family farms and by working with multi-generational farms for decades, the business has established trust-based relationships that ensure a reliable and consistent supply of high-quality livestock. Additionally, the broad customer network, which includes 300 independent butcher shops and 200 hotels and restaurants, demonstrates a diverse sales strategy that reduces dependency on any single market segment.

“We've been dealing with the same family farms for generations”

“We've got a a large number of very, very good livestock farms and I've dealt with them for 30 years. My father dealt with their fathers for 30 years and my grandfather dealt with their grandfathers” IP13

“You know, we've got suppliers who have been, they've been farming cattle for the last 30-40 years” IP13

“we will supply 300 independent butcher shops. We will supply 200 to hotels and restaurants” IP13

5.2.17.1.5 Supply Chain Understanding

A key requirement for enhancing supply chain resilience is a clear understanding of the network that links a business to its suppliers, their suppliers, and its downstream customers (Christopher and Peck 2004). The IP 13 mentioned their familiarity with the supply chain network and the interview extract aligns with the findings of Christopher and Peck (2004).

“ I think we're, we're very fortunate that we very, very rarely experience supply chain disruption again, partly because with 100 years of tradition, 100 years of familiarity with the market and 100 years of dealing with the same farms, who broadly know what we need” IP13

“And we know generally what they've got. IP 13

The insights shared by IP13 highlighted key factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC. The IP 13 implied that flexibility in sourcing, logistics, and operations enables adaptability to fluctuations, shortages, and surpluses supported by a mix of internal capacity and outsourced logistics for continuity. Supply base diversity mitigates risks by allowing geographic shifts in sourcing, while long-term supplier relationships ensure a consistent supply of high-quality livestock and reduce reliance on single markets. Finally, supply chain understanding, built on decades of experience, provides the knowledge to anticipate and address disruptions.

5.2.17.2 Theme Challenges Faced by the SBSC

The challenges highlighted by IP 13 are mainly structural challenges

Retailer Dominance

IP 13 expressed his concerns about the market power and dominance of large supermarkets, which can lead to imbalances in the supply chain. This dominance allows supermarkets to dictate prices, set terms, and impose strict requirements on suppliers, potentially squeezing margins for wholesalers and limiting profitability.

“we consider that the the big supermarkets have too much control and they do” IP13

Supply Demand Imbalances

The interviewee IP13 implied that the decline in the national livestock population is creating increased competition among buyers for a limited supply of animals, leading to higher prices and cost pressures within the SBSC. This scarcity threatens profit margins, especially for wholesalers and processors who must pay more to secure stock. The implication also highlights concerns about the sustainability of the industry, as a shrinking livestock base could reduce critical mass, impacting the efficiency of processing facilities and supply consistency. Furthermore, increased competition may favour larger players with greater buying power, putting smaller businesses at risk and potentially leading to market consolidation, further challenging the resilience of the supply chain.

“I think as the national heritage gets smaller and smaller, we're all fighting for the same animals, which means ultimately, we'll all be paying more for them” IP 13

Dependence on Single Supplier

The interviewee IP13 discussed that the dependence of large supermarket chains on centralized processing facilities, such as the big abattoir in Aberdeen, poses a significant risk to the resilience of the supply chain. If this key relationship fails due to operational disruptions, market shifts, or contractual breakdowns, it could lead to supply shortages. This situation aligns with Christopher and Peck's (2004) discussion on the risks of dependence on single suppliers within a supply chain resilience framework wherein the authors draw the attention to the fact that single sourcing can be cost effective, but it is dangerous for supply chain resilience.

“you've got a big abattoir in Aberdeen, that's applies the biggest supermarket chain in Scotland. Is that relationship fails? What they're going to do” IP13

Industry Consolidation

The IP13 implied that industry consolidation, such as ABP's takeover of Scott Beef, has significant implications for the SBSC by further centralizing control within a smaller number of large processors. This consolidation reduces competition, potentially giving dominant players greater market power to influence pricing, terms of trade, and procurement practices, which can squeeze smaller farmers and wholesalers.

“sometimes simple internal industry factors such as ABP taking over Scott beef for most Scott beef” IP 13

The challenges highlighted by IP13 revealed significant vulnerabilities within the SBSC, stemming from market dynamics, structural dependencies, and resource constraints. Retailer dominance emerges as a critical issue, where the market power of large supermarkets enables them to dictate terms, leading to price

pressures and profit margin erosion for wholesalers and processors. This imbalance reduces the bargaining power of smaller players, potentially compromising their financial stability and competitiveness.

Similarly, supply-demand imbalances caused by a shrinking livestock population intensify competition for limited resources, driving cost pressures and threatening the sustainability of smaller businesses. This scarcity of livestock risks weakening the critical mass required to sustain processing facilities and supply consistency, further exacerbating market consolidation and widening the gap between large and small players in the industry.

The dependence on single suppliers, such as the centralized abattoir in Aberdeen, underscores systemic risks posed by supply chain concentration. As emphasised by Christopher and Peck (2004), single sourcing may appear cost-effective, but it leaves the supply chain vulnerable to disruptions that can lead to shortages and operational failures. This reliance highlights the need for alternative processing capacity and diversified sourcing strategies to enhance resilience.

Furthermore, industry consolidation, exemplified by ABP's takeover of Scott Beef, raises concerns about reduced competition and market dominance, which could further squeeze margins and limit opportunities for smaller suppliers. This centralization creates pricing pressures and barriers to entry, making the supply chain less flexible and responsive to disruptions.

The insights provided by IP13 highlighted both the strengths and vulnerabilities of the SBSC. On the resilience front, IP13 emphasised the importance of flexibility in sourcing, logistics, and operations, enabling adaptability to market fluctuations and disruptions. This flexibility is reinforced by diverse sourcing strategies, long-standing supplier relationships, and a deep understanding of the supply chain developed over decades of experience. Such factors contribute to the business's ability to maintain operational stability and respond effectively to challenges.

However, IP13 also pointed out significant structural challenges threatening the resilience of the SBSC. Issues such as retailer dominance allow supermarkets to dictate terms, putting pressure on profit margins and limiting the negotiating power of smaller players. Additionally, supply-demand imbalances caused by a shrinking livestock population intensify competition for resources, driving costs higher and threatening sustainability. Concerns about dependence on single suppliers and industry consolidation further highlight vulnerabilities, as these trends reduce flexibility, increase reliance on centralized facilities, and potentially undermine the resilience of smaller businesses.

In summary, IP13 implied the need for a balanced approach to address both strengths and weaknesses within the supply chain.

5.2.18 Processor Interview Participant (IP) 14

The Interview Participant (IP) 14 is a partner in a family-owned processing facility. The processing facility also owns a livestock cattle farm. IP 14's primary role focuses on the procurement of cattle to supply their processing plant, ensuring a consistent and high-quality supply of livestock that meets market specifications. The farm operates over 500 acres with approximately 1,000 cattle, focusing on an intensive indoor finishing system for efficiency and consistency in production. The business model demonstrates vertical integration, combining livestock farming with meat processing and distribution.

The figure below shows the initial codes generated in NVivo which formed the basis of identification of challenges and factors contribution to SBSC.

Figure 5.21 Interview Coding in NVivo IP14

5.2.18.1 Theme Factors Contributing to Resilience of SBSC

The IP14 mentioned risk management culture, traceability, and adaptability as contributors to SBSC.

5.2.18.1.1 Risk Management Culture

Kamalahmadi and Parast (2016) mentioned that developing responsive actions to address abnormal situations become easier and more effective when entities are well prepared and capable of contributing to swift and effective solutions.

The (IP14) highlighted the implementation of preventive health measures as a proactive strategy to mitigate biological risks and protect livestock health within the SBSC. Vaccinating cattle immediately upon arrival

addresses vulnerability to contagious diseases, which may lead to operational continuity, animal welfare, and financial stability.

“So that's from the farm as soon as the cattle arrive on farm, you've got to vaccinate them. We vaccinate them for three different vaccines to cover what would be the most contagious the diseases in our system and then and then at the other end” IP14

This approach reflects risk identification and assessment by administering three different vaccines, the farm creates multiple layers of defence, minimizing the likelihood and impact of outbreaks. This not only reduces the need for reactive treatments but also lowers the economic losses associated with disease control measures, such as quarantines or culling affected animals.

This approach aligns with the risk management culture proposed by Christopher and Peck (2004) as a contributor of supply chain resilience.

“But you do your best to sort of follow trends year on year and what tends to happen with a beef price and we would stock up quite heavily this time of year with cattle as that's when there's the most, the most cattle come out this time of year before winter, really” IP14

The P14 also discussed the importance of seasonal planning and market trend monitoring by stocking up heavily during periods of high cattle availability before winter. This approach highlights the importance of demand forecasting and inventory management as tools for risk mitigation. Tadayonrad and Ndiaye (2023) concluded that accurate demand forecasting and effective safety stock management are essential elements of a supply chain design and minimize the risk of stockouts during unforeseen demand surges or supply chain disruptions. By implementing robust forecasting techniques and inventory management practices, companies can lower costs, enhance operational efficiency, and deliver superior customer service.

“So ,Probably the best way we can mitigate risk is just by attention to detail across the whole system” IP14

The interviewee (IP14) also implied that risk mitigation within the SBSC is achieved through attention to detail and system-wide management practices. This approach emphasises the importance of thorough monitoring, quality control, and precision at every stage of the supply chain, from livestock management to processing and distribution.

The P14 also discussed the importance of seasonal planning and market trend monitoring by stocking up heavily during periods of high cattle availability before winter. This approach highlights the importance of demand forecasting and inventory management as tools for risk mitigation. It also reflects a proactive strategy to align purchasing decisions with market trends. The implications suggest that strategic timing in

procurement enhances supply chain resilience by balancing supply and demand, ensuring business continuity, and maintaining competitiveness in a volatile market environment.

5.2.18.1.2 Traceability

Traceability as a contributor to the resilience of SBSC was also highlighted by IP7 and discussed under the traceability heading.

The IP14 emphasised the importance of traceability as a core feature of the SBSC. By ensuring that each carcass, its quarters, and individual cuts are labelled and tracked throughout the processing stages, the system guarantees that every product can be traced back to the specific animal it *originated from*.

“So we ensure every carcass is obviously traceable. It's got a ticket on it for traceability as soon as that carcass is split into four, it's got a ticket on it, traceable. And then as soon as that's bone out, it's labelled in the Box so each Backpack of meat can be traced back to the animal it was produced from”IP14

The IP 14 implied that this approach ensures transparency and accountability in the production process, enabling processors to provide accurate records of origin. Such detailed tracking supports consumer confidence by offering assurances about the source and authenticity of the product.

5.2.18.1.3 Adaptability

Adaptability is the capacity of a system to completely transform or adjust to its operating environment. . Christopher and Peck (2004) mentioned adaptability as a feature of the supply chain resilience definition. The later research by Pettit et al (2013) identified adaptability as a supply chain resilience capability. Stone and Rahimifard (2018) proposed adaptability as an important contributor for agriculture food supply chain resilience. Zhong, Cheng and Jia (2024) also mentioned adaptation as a supply chain resilience contributor in agri food supply chain.

“to try and keep working and changing all the time so that we're changing with the times rather than letting something change and us having to dramatically change our whole system because of it”IP14

The IP14 implied the role of adaptability as a key contributor to supply chain resilience within the Scottish beef industry. By emphasising the importance of continuous adjustments to align with changing conditions, IP14 implied that making incremental improvements minimizes the necessity for major overhauls when responding to external shocks.

The insights provided by IP14 identify risk management culture, traceability, and adaptability as key factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC. Risk management culture is reflected in the implementation of preventive health measures, such as vaccinating cattle upon arrival, to reduce biological risks and maintain

operational continuity. This approach emphasises attention to detail and system-wide management practices to minimize the likelihood of disease outbreaks and associated economic losses. Traceability is highlighted as a core feature of the supply chain, ensuring that each carcass and its processed components are labelled and tracked throughout production. This enables complete traceability back to the source, supporting transparency and accountability in the production process. Adaptability is presented as another important factor, enabling the supply chain to make incremental adjustments in response to changing conditions, thereby reducing the need for significant disruptions or major system overhauls. These factors collectively demonstrate practical strategies employed within the SBSC to enhance resilience and maintain stability in operations.

5.2.18.2 Theme Challenges faced by the SBSC

The key challenges identified by IP 14 are structural challenges and focus on market consolidation, processor dominance, disease outbreak and poor infrastructure.

5.2.18.2.1 Market Consolidation and Processor Dominance

Hendrickson (2015) mentioned that the consolidation of agrifood systems has resulted in standardized and specialized production networks, which lack the resilience needed to withstand disruptions. This consolidation has reduced biodiversity, constrained ecological adaptability, and led to social and economic vulnerabilities by squeezing out smaller farms and businesses. Moreover, the dominance of large-scale corporate structures has created power imbalances, limiting decision-making capacity for farmers and local actors while failing to adequately address hunger and food security.

“Well, quite heavily controlled by likes of ABP have now got a massive market share” IP14

The interviewee P14 implied that the market dominance of large processors, such as ABP, poses significant challenges to the SBSC by creating market concentration and imbalances in bargaining power. The large market share held by ABP allows it to exert considerable influence over pricing structures, procurement terms, and supply chain practices, which can squeeze margins for smaller producers and processors.

This market consolidation reduces competition and higher dependency on dominant players. It may also limit opportunities for smaller businesses to negotiate favourable contracts, forcing them to operate under terms dictated by larger processors.

5.2.18.2.2 Disease Outbreak Recovery

The IP14 expressed his serious concern that a major disease outbreak, such as foot-and-mouth disease, poses a critical threat to the SBSC. IP14 pointed out that such an event could lead to massive herd losses,

and due to the high costs, risks, and lack of incentives for farmers to rebuild their herds, many might exit the industry permanently.

“I would say if there was a big say foot and mouth outbreak like there was in 2001, there would be a lot of the beef herd would vanish and would never, would never come back. You know there would be, there would be very little incentive for people to then start up again and breed their herd” IP14

This highlight concerns about the fragility of the livestock sector and its limited capacity to recover from catastrophic events without strong government support and financial incentives. The IP14 implied that a robust recovery plan is needed to support recovery in the event of a disease outbreak, ensuring the long-term viability of the Scottish beef industry.

5.2.18.2.3 Poor Infrastructure

The IP14 mentioned that the lack of small, local abattoirs poses a significant logistical and welfare challenge within the SBSC. The closure or reduction of small-scale processing facilities has resulted in long transportation distances for culled dairy animals, many of which already have poor mobility and are less fit for transport.

“I would say what's really lacking is Small abattoirs for either butcher processing or even locally here what we find is there's a lot of dairy animals, Culled dairy animals leaving the area and they're going on a lorry minimum 3 hours away” IP14

“So there's a lot of transportation in those animals and they're already not not great on their feet ,Poor mobility” IP14

This situation raises animal welfare concerns, as prolonged transportation can cause stress, injuries, and further deterioration in the health of these animals. It also highlights operational inefficiencies, as long-distance transport increases fuel costs, carbon emissions, and time-to-market, which can compromise meat quality and profitability.

Additionally, the lack of local abattoirs limits processing capacity and accessibility for small-scale farmers, reducing their market competitiveness and forcing dependence on larger, centralised processors.

This infrastructure issue was also discussed by the industry expert under the heading of Poor infrastructure wherein the Scottish Government’s study on feasibility of mobile abattoirs in Scotland is also mentioned. Likewise, a livestock farmer also expressed the closure of small abattoirs and its implications under heading of Processor dominance.

As mentioned by the Interviewee's this infrastructure deficiency leads to increased transportation times, causing animal welfare concerns, higher costs, and logistical inefficiencies. It reduces processing accessibility for small farmers, limiting their market competitiveness and profit margins. This reliance on centralized facilities weakens supply chain resilience and increases vulnerability to disruptions.

The IP14 highlighted several structural challenges affecting the resilience of the SBSC, emphasising issues related to market consolidation, disease outbreak recovery, and infrastructure limitations. The identified challenges highlight the need for improved infrastructure, more balanced market structures, and robust recovery plans to support long-term sustainability and resilience.

In this interview the IP14 emphasised key factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC. These include risk management culture, traceability, and adaptability. Preventive health measures, such as vaccinating cattle upon arrival, were highlighted as proactive strategies to mitigate biological risks and maintain operational continuity. Attention to detail, seasonal planning, and demand forecasting were also emphasised as tools for minimizing disruptions. Traceability was identified as a core component, ensuring that all products can be tracked back to their source, promoting transparency and accountability. Adaptability was noted as a critical capability, enabling incremental adjustments to align with changing market conditions and external shocks, reducing the need for major operational overhauls.

In addition to resilience factors, IP14 outlined several structural challenges affecting the SBSC, including market consolidation, disease outbreak recovery, and poor infrastructure. The dominance of large processors, such as ABP, was highlighted as a source of market imbalance, limiting competition and squeezing smaller producers. Concerns were raised about the industry's ability to recover from catastrophic events, such as disease outbreaks, due to high costs and limited incentives for farmers to rebuild herds. Infrastructure issues, particularly the lack of small local abattoirs, were identified as contributing to logistical inefficiencies, higher costs, and animal welfare concerns, reducing competitiveness for smaller farmers. These challenges highlight the necessity for enhanced infrastructure, more equitable market structures, and effective recovery plans to ensure the long-term sustainability of the SBSC.

5.2.19 Overview of the Processing Sector Interviews

The processing sector plays a critical role in the SBSC. To gain insights into this sector, three interviews were conducted, each providing perspectives on the challenges faced and factors contributing to resilience within the supply chain. These interviews covered the experiences of representatives from a trade body, a regional meat wholesaler, and a family-owned processing facility.

The first interview was conducted with IP12, a representative from a trade body advocating for meat processors and wholesalers in Scotland. IP12 highlighted economic, structural, and operational challenges,

such as low profit margins, competition from imports, dependency on large retailers, and regulatory barriers post-Brexit. The interview emphasised supply chain leadership, intelligence, and government support as resilience factors, focusing on proactive planning, collaboration, and regulatory assistance to navigate disruptions.

Figure 5.22 Challenges Identified by the Processors

The second interview with IP13, featured insights from the managing director of a family-owned regional meat wholesaler that has operated for over a century. The IP13 highlighted challenges such as retailer dominance, supply-demand imbalances, and infrastructure issues stemming from the closure of small abattoirs. To address these, IP13 emphasised flexibility in sourcing and logistics, supply base diversity, and strong supplier relationships as critical resilience factors, enabling adaptability to fluctuations and maintaining consistent operations.

The third interview with IP14, focused on a partner in a family-owned processing facility that also operates a livestock farm. The IP14 identified structural challenges, including market consolidation, disease outbreak recovery, and poor infrastructure. Resilience factors highlighted by IP14 included risk management culture, emphasising preventive measures like vaccination programs, traceability systems to ensure transparency, and adaptability to align operations with changing conditions.

The interviews collectively revealed that the processing sector in Scotland faces economic pressures, structural vulnerabilities, and operational challenges exacerbated by factors such as market consolidation, regulatory changes post-Brexit, and infrastructure limitations.

5.2.20 Auction Marts

Auction Marts are an essential component of SBSC, and their importance and functioning are discussed in section 2.4. Two interviews were conducted to identify the challenges faced by the SBSC and the factors contributing to its resilience.

5.2.21 Auction Mart Trade Body Executive Interview Participant (IP) 15

IP 15 is the Executive Director of a trade membership organisation representing livestock auction markets in Scotland. With extensive experience in farming and a corporate banking background, including tenure as Head of Agriculture at a major bank, IP 15 combines financial expertise with practical agricultural knowledge. IP 15 has been actively involved in managing industry operations, overseeing professional development programs, and ensuring members are certified and qualified to handle key responsibilities, such as livestock valuations during disease outbreaks. The IP15 role also includes data management and analysis. The IP15 also runs a small cattle farm. The diversified background of IP15 provided rich insights regarding the challenges and the resilience of the SBSC. The initial coding of the transcript is shown in the figure below.

Figure 5.23 Interview Coding in NVivo IP15

5.2.21.1 Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC

The IP 15 identified transparency, traceability, and inherent resilience as key contributors of the resilience of SBSC

5.2.21.1.1 Transparency

Zhao et al., (2024) mentioned transparency as a resilience capability factor in a comparative agri food supply chain study between Argentina and France. The authors mentioned transparency by commenting that anyone can see what happens, the price, who buys and everything.

IP 15 implied that transparency in the SBSC is relatively strong up to the point of auction markets, where buyers and sellers are connected in an organised and open manner. However, beyond the auction markets,

particularly in the stages involving finishers, processors, and supermarkets the supply chain becomes less transparent and opaque.

“Transparency, because I think the, I think transparency is pretty good then till it gets beyond the auction market if that makes sense and then it starts to get a bit opaque What happens between the finisher and the processor and the processor and the supermarket ,all you know the fields of the smoke and mirrors in there, but we it's it's there's not an area that comes up particularly often because people they can get very, very defensive about it and we need everything to try and collaborate in other areas and that that supply chain of the transparency of it's always one that upsets a few people. If you dig too deep into it” IP15

IP 15 suggested that while transparency within auction markets is well-maintained through price discovery systems and regulated processes, the subsequent stages are often viewed as complex and guarded, sometimes perceived as involving "smoke and mirrors" IP 15 also mentioned transparency in these later stages tend to be sensitive and defensive, making it challenging to address the issue directly. Despite these difficulties, IP15 stressed the importance of collaboration across all supply chain actors to improve transparency without causing conflicts that could hinder cooperation within the sector.

5.2.21.1.2 Traceability

Traceability in the SBSC is also identified as supply chain resilience contributor by IP3, IP6 ,IP9 and IP13 discussed Page 90,135,162 and 183 respectively. The IP 15 also identified traceability as a contributor to SBSC specifically in the event of disease outbreak. The IP15 also explained how traceability system at the auction marts work.

“So auction markets are actually pretty critical in this in terms of knowing where animals are and where they've gone, particularly for a disease outbreak because you want to be able to press a button and go right. We know where all the animals are Umm, that is probably in terms of the resilience element of this is one of the one of the outside of the trade that for the industry the use of auction markets is probably one of the key areas is actually the traceability element is knowing where animals are and where they have been in that they are properly recorded” IP15

The IP 15 implied that auction markets play a critical role in ensuring traceability within the SBSC, particularly in the context of disease outbreaks. It was emphasised that auction markets act as centralized hubs for tracking the movement of animals, maintaining accurate records of where animals have come from and where they are going. This traceability system serves as a key component of the resilience of the beef industry, as it can enable rapid responses during disruptions, such as disease outbreaks. It can allow authorities to quickly access movement data and consequently the industry can contain the spread of diseases, implement biosecurity measures, and minimize economic losses.

The IP 15 highlighted that this capability is one of the most valuable contributions of auction markets beyond facilitating trade. The ability to "press a button" and retrieve detailed movement histories provides confidence in the system's reliability and strengthens the industry's preparedness and resilience against potential threats

5.2.21.1.2.1 Traceability Process at Auction Marts

The IP15 explained the traceability process at the auction marts. The process begins when a farmer brings livestock to the auction mart, accompanied by an animal passport. This passport contains key details about the animal, such as its birth location, movement history, and identification numbers. Upon arrival, the farmer hands over the passport to the auction mart, which assumes full responsibility for processing and updating movement records.

The auction mart handles the movement off the farm to the mart, as well as the movement from the mart to its destination holding, whether that be another farm, a finisher, or an abattoir. This includes ensuring that the correct paperwork accompanies each animal, making it easier to verify its origin, movements, and health status. The auction mart also verifies that passports are properly completed and aligned with the cattle, enabling smooth transitions and regulatory compliance throughout the process.

This system significantly reduces the administrative burden on farmers, who only need to ensure that the passport matches the livestock before bringing them to the mart. The auction mart then processes all documentation and updates databases to reflect the movement history of the animal. This information follows the animal through the supply chain, allowing stakeholders, including abattoirs, to quickly check its origins and previous movements.

The traceability process also extends to ensuring that all regulatory requirements are met. Auction marts confirm that documentation for animals whether bovine or ovine is accurate, complete, and submitted in a timely manner. This guarantees that each animal can be tracked throughout its lifecycle, providing transparency and enabling authorities to respond swiftly in the event of a disease outbreak or compliance audit.

Ultimately, auction marts act as gatekeepers of data and compliance, maintaining the integrity of the traceability system. They ensure that the information accompanying each animal is reliable, making it easier for stakeholders to make informed decisions while enhancing the resilience of the SBSC. This process highlights the importance of auction marts in supporting biosecurity, market transparency, and regulatory enforcement within the SBSC.

5.2.21.1.3 Inherent Resilience

The IP 15 identified inherent resilience in the Scottish Beef industry as a contributor from the livestock farming perspective. The inherent resilience is also mentioned by IP7 as a resilience contributor.

“I think the fact that although we complain about extreme weather, the reality is we still are in our relatively temperate climate We still have a very forage-based diet and for cattle and in Scotland and I think that gives us a good bit of Resilience”IP15

IP15 implied that Scotland's temperate climate provides a natural advantage for the resilience of its beef industry, particularly in terms of forage-based feeding systems. Despite occasional challenges posed by extreme weather, such as prolonged rainfall, the reliable growth of grass ensures that cattle can be fed primarily on pasture rather than relying heavily on imported feed.

This self-sufficiency in feed production reduces dependency on external inputs, which in turn lowers costs and mitigates risks associated with supply chain disruptions. IP15 acknowledges that climate change may require adjustments to current farming systems but emphasises that Scotland's ability to maintain a forage-based diet for cattle already provides a strong foundation for adaptability. By highlighting this advantage, IP15 suggested that Scotland's natural resources and grass-fed systems not only enhance sustainability but also contribute to the long-term resilience of the Scottish beef industry in the face of environmental uncertainties and climate variability.

5.2.21.2 Theme Challenges faced by the SBSC

The IP 15 identified challenges such decreasing suckler herd efficiency which was also identified by IP2 at Page 79. The IP15 also identified the structural fragmentation of the livestock farming based on its size, location and practices. The key challenge identified by the IP 15 pertained to transportation and logistics.

5.2.21.2.1 Transportation and Logistical Challenges

The IP 15 identified transportation as a logistical as a key challenge in terms of resilience.

“one of the bigger challenges we've got in terms of resilience at the moment is actually the transport and links and things. So do I would see that most of our auction markets, if they had a sale today, would still have cattle hanging about tomorrow because we we can't actually get them moved off the premises because there is a shortage of hauliers, so you know, I know that we have a lot of auctioneers working hard with the hauliers and am the ferries coming in from the islands. But just as bigger challenge at the moment, because they're either not there or the breakdown or you get kicked off because they want a tourist”IP15

“And you know, there's a lot of work going on in the back and it's kind of unseen work, you know, to try and make sure that the logistics can all tie in”IP15

The IP15 implied that transport and logistical challenges present a significant threat to the resilience of the SBSC. The IP15 highlighted a shortage of hauliers and transport links, including ferry services from the islands, as critical issues that cause delays in the movement of livestock from auction markets to their destinations. These delays often result in cattle remaining at auction marts longer than intended, which can lead to operational inefficiencies, increased costs, and potential animal welfare concerns.

IP15 emphasised that the unreliability of transport infrastructure, such as vehicle breakdowns or ferry schedule disruptions, exacerbates the problem. Additionally, they mention that competition for ferry space, especially during tourist seasons, can result in livestock transportation being deprioritized, further complicating the situation.

Despite these challenges, IP15 acknowledges the behind-the-scenes efforts by auctioneers, hauliers, and ferry operators to ensure the coordination of transport schedules and minimise delays. The IP 15 implied that resolving transportation bottlenecks and strengthening logistical systems are critical priorities for improving the resilience and efficiency of the Scottish beef industry. Without addressing these issues, the sector remains vulnerable to disruptions that could adversely impact the supply chain continuity.

The IP15 provided valuable insights into the resilience and challenges of the SBSC. Auction marts were described as central hubs for recording and tracking livestock movements, particularly during disease outbreaks, enabling rapid responses to contain and manage disruptions. Transparency was identified as a strength within auction markets, though concerns were raised about opacity in later stages of the supply chain involving processors and supermarkets. IP15 emphasised the importance of Scotland's temperate climate and forage-based feeding systems in supporting inherent resilience by reducing reliance on external inputs. However, logistical challenges, including shortages of hauliers and disruptions to ferry services, were noted as significant issues affecting the timely transportation of livestock. These challenges often result in delays and inefficiencies, highlighting the need for improvements in transportation infrastructure to support supply chain continuity.

5.2.22 Auction Mart Interview Participant IP 16

IP16 is a senior representative of a long-established livestock auction company in Scotland, with extensive experience in the SBSC. With over 40 years of experience in the industry, IP16 has witnessed significant structural changes, including the decline of local markets, the consolidation of processors, and the rise of supermarket dominance. The IP 16 provide valuable insights regarding the SBSC. The initial coding of the interview transcript in Nvivo is shown in the figure below

Figure 5.24 Interview Coding in NVivo IP16

5.2.22.1 Theme Factor Contributing to the resilience of SBSC

IP 16 emphasised on the critical role of independent bodies, particularly auction markets, in maintaining the resilience of the SBSC. The participant suggested that the presence of these intermediaries ensures fairness, transparency, and competitive pricing, which protect farmers' interests. Auction markets operate independently and prioritize maximising returns for farmers through transparent commissions, acting as a buffer between farmers and processors. This structure prevents processors and supermarkets, which are

primarily profit-driven, from exerting excessive control and potentially prioritizing cheaper imports over local produce.

“but it's it's only resilient if it has the auction system or another independent body in between the farmer and the processor, as George said, if the processors have got complete control, then they have no loyalty to the Scottish beef industry. If they could import cattle from Poland to kill, to put in the supermarkets, they would be happy with that” IP16

IP 16 highlighted that farmers, while resilient and dedicated to producing high-quality livestock, lack the marketing expertise to secure competitive prices without external support. The removal of auction markets or similar intermediaries could make the supply chain highly vulnerable, as supermarkets and processors would focus solely on cost-cutting, threatening the profitability and sustainability of farmers. Additionally, the participant criticizes the government's cheap food policy and its failure to prioritize food security, arguing that this approach undermines long-term resilience.

“Your farmers are resilient..... they need help for someone to market them and with the auction industry we are. Although you know we really are there for the farmer, we are still independent. And we charge a very transparent commission.....our aim is to get the price higher for the farmer and that helps us and then the processor has the opportunity to look after themselves on the Super, you know On the on the supermarket price” IP16

IP 16 implied that the SBSC relies heavily on the presence of independent intermediaries to protect farmers' interests, maintain transparency, and balance power dynamics. Without these bodies, the supply chain would face greater vulnerability, as evidenced during disruptions like the Foot-and-Mouth outbreak, COVID-19, and Brexit, which exposed weaknesses in the system.

“So it's quite resilient effort as someone in between to make sure that the farmers interests are looked after. Now, I don't believe you can rely on the supermarkets to do that and it's unfair to. Well, I don't think you can rely on the government either because the government has this cheap food policy and has forgotten about food security and food security isn't as high up the agenda as it should be. So while they're independent bodies, whether it's an auction market or even quality meat Scotland that you help to push that. Oh, what then? It it's it's just resilient” IP16

“The auction markets is to give a transparent price to it” IP16

5.2.22.1.1 Transparency

The interview extracts strongly directed that transparency is a key contributor to the resilience of the SBSC. The IP 16 highlighted the role of auction markets as independent intermediaries that ensure fairness and

openness in pricing, protecting farmers from the dominance of processors and supermarkets. By operating with transparent commissions and prioritizing competitive pricing, auction markets create an environment where farmers can confidently sell their livestock without fear of being exploited by more powerful supply chain players.

The reference to auction markets providing a “transparent price” reinforces their function as a mechanism for price discovery, ensuring that transactions are conducted in a visible and equitable manner. This transparency prevents processors and supermarkets, which are primarily profit-driven, from imposing unfair pricing structures or prioritizing cheaper imports over local produce. The IP 16 further emphasised that auction markets safeguard farmers' interests, particularly by acting as a buffer between producers and processors, thereby reducing the risk of exploitation and preserving market balance. Therefore the analysis entails that the IP 16 is implying that the transparency generated through the auction systems contributes to the resilience of the SBSC.

5.2.22.1.2 Traceability

The IP 16 implied that traceability is a fundamental aspect of the auction process by detailing the systematic handling, documentation, and tracking of livestock throughout the sale. The process begins when cattle arrive at the auction market accompanied by passports that contain key details such as the date of birth, breed, age, sex, and tag numbers. These passports are carefully matched to each animal and verified to ensure that the information is accurate and complete before the auction.

“Once we procure them and put them in our sale catalogues.....the cattle arrive at our market in lorries with passports. Each animal has a passport with its date of birth, its breed, age, sex, and then we take these passports cattle's tag numbers and sort out the passports..... we have the correct 10 passports for these 10 cattle. All that is uploaded in our computer pre-sale. So, when the cattle come into our ring the age and sex of the cattle are displayed on a big display board. So, the buyers can look, glance up and see what they're buying and have the history, the age of them, etcetera” IP16

The details are then uploaded into a computerized system prior to the sale, enabling digital tracking of each animal. During the auction, information about the age, sex, and history of the cattle is displayed on a digital board, providing buyers with real-time access to critical data about the livestock. After the sale, the seller receives a detailed record of the transaction, including the price and buyer information, further reinforcing accountability and transparency in the process.

IP16 highlighted that this meticulous documentation ensures that animals are properly identified, and their movements are recorded, which is essential for regulatory compliance.

The discussion with IP 16 highlighted two key factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC namely transparency and traceability. Transparency is emphasised through the role of auction markets as independent intermediaries that promote fairness and openness in pricing, protecting farmers from exploitation by processors and supermarkets. These markets operate with clear and competitive pricing mechanisms, ensuring farmers receive fair returns while maintaining a balance of power within the supply chain. Traceability is also identified as a crucial component, with auction markets managing systematic documentation and tracking of livestock through passports and digital systems

5.2.22.2 Theme Challenges faced by SBSC

The IP16 identified several key challenges affecting the SBSC, including land deprivation, critical mass decline, poor infrastructure, and suckler herd efficiency. One major concern raised is land deprivation, where land traditionally used for grazing and growing grass is being repurposed for planting invasive species. These species, according to IP16, provide no economic or environmental benefits, thereby reducing the availability of productive agricultural land and threatening the viability of livestock farming. Another challenge highlighted by IP16 is the gradual erosion of critical mass within the beef industry. The closure of local auction markets and the decline in small-scale farmers have led to frequent cattle dispersals, reducing the volume of livestock required to sustain processing facilities and supply chain networks. This decline in livestock numbers threatens the economic efficiency of the industry and contributes to market instability, making it increasingly difficult for farmers to stay competitive and maintain profitability.

IP16 also drew attention to poor infrastructure, particularly the closure of local abattoirs, which has created significant logistical challenges. Farmers are now required to transport livestock over longer distances for processing, leading to higher costs and increased operational inefficiencies. This lack of infrastructure weakens the resilience of the supply chain, leaving it vulnerable to disruptions and external pressures. The suckler herd efficiency is identified as a pressing issue, as declining cow numbers have resulted in supply shortages and price volatility. The challenges identified by IP16 align with concerns raised by other interviewees. Land deprivation and critical mass decline were also highlighted by IP4 and IP6. Similarly, poor infrastructure was noted by IP3 and IP14, reflecting shared concerns about the lack of local processing facilities and transportation barriers. Suckler herd efficiency and price volatility were also discussed by IP2.

5.2.22.3 Perspectives of Auction Marts on the Resilience and Challenges of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The perspectives of auction marts on the resilience and challenges of the SBSC were captured through interviews with a trade body executive (IP15) and an executive from a long-established auction mart (IP16). Both participants emphasised the pivotal role of auction marts as intermediaries that promote transparency,

traceability, and resilience within the supply chain. They highlighted the significance of these markets in protecting farmers' interests, ensuring fair pricing, and maintaining operational continuity during disruptions. The IP15 highlighted transparency, traceability, and inherent resilience as key contributors to SBSC resilience. Transparency was emphasised within auction marts, where pricing and transactions are openly conducted. However, the IP15 pointed out that transparency diminishes further along the supply chain, particularly at the processing and retail stages, creating opacity and power imbalances. Traceability was identified as another resilience factor, particularly in responding to disease outbreaks. Auction marts act as centralized hubs for tracking livestock movements through detailed records and digital systems, enabling rapid containment measures and regulatory compliance. Furthermore the IP15 mentioned that Scotland's temperate climate and forage-based feeding systems contribute to inherent resilience by reducing dependency on external inputs and supporting sustainability.

The IP16 emphasised the importance of auction marts as independent intermediaries that ensure fairness and transparency in pricing while shielding farmers from exploitation by processors and supermarkets. The transparent commission structure of auction marts was highlighted as a mechanism that aligns the interests of farmers and markets, promoting competitive pricing and market balance. Traceability was also identified as a key contributor, with auction marts managing livestock documentation and tracking systems, enhancing accountability and regulatory compliance.

The IP15 identified transportation and logistical challenges as major threats to the resilience of the SBSC. Issues such as a shortage of hauliers, ferry disruptions, and unreliable transport infrastructure were noted to cause delays, increased costs, and operational inefficiencies. These problems were further compounded during peak tourist seasons, where ferry services prioritize passenger traffic over livestock transportation. The IP16 identified several challenges hindering SBSC resilience, including critical mass decline, land deprivation, poor infrastructure, and suckler herd inefficiency. The loss of productive grazing land to invasive species and the erosion of local markets were seen as weakening the economic base of livestock farming. Poor infrastructure, particularly the closure of local abattoirs, led to increased transportation distances and higher costs. Declining herd sizes further contributed to supply shortages and price volatility, posing risks to long-term sustainability.

The interviews featured the vital role of auction marts in maintaining the resilience of the SBSC through transparency, traceability, and inherent resilience. However, significant challenges, including logistical inefficiencies, land-use changes, and declining critical mass, seem to undermine the resilience of the SBSC.

Figure 5.25 Challenges Identified by Auctioneers

5.2.23 Retail

The major Retailers in Scotland are discussed under section 2.5.

5.2.24 Retail Interview Participant (IP)17

The IP17 is the Livestock Technical Development Manager for a major UK retailer that operates its own food manufacturing division and multiple abattoirs, including a processing facility in Aberdeenshire, Scotland. The retailer is heavily involved in the end-to-end beef supply chain, covering procurement, processing, and retail distribution to ensure a consistent supply of Scotch beef products to its stores across Scotland.

The IP17 shed light on various aspects of the SBSC. The factors contributing to the resilience of SBSC and challenges were also discussed. The initial coding based on the interview transcript are shown in the figure.

Figure 5.26 Interview Coding in NVivo IP17

The themes are identified after reviewing the nodes and watching the video transcript repeatedly.

5.2.24.1 Theme factors Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC

5.2.24.1.1 Supplier Relationships

The IP 17 mentioned supplier relationship as a strength. The supplier relationship is also identified as a contributing factor to the resilience of SBSC by IP 3 and IP13.

IP17 implied that strong relationships with suppliers plays a key role in the resilience of their beef supply chain as it ensures continuity of supply by mitigating the supply risk. By having a dedicated team of livestock buyers based in Scotland, the organisation ensures effective communication and close

collaboration with its supply base. This localized approach allows for better information gathering, quick responses to challenges, and proactive problem-solving, reinforcing supply chain stability.

“we have a dedicated team of livestock buyers” IP17

“I think one thing that strengthens us is the good relationship that we have with our supply base and having that Information, Direct Farm, So obviously if there needs to be any information gathering, etcetera, we can do that” IP17

“So it is our own teams that are going out to buy, we're not dealing with a third party, etcetera”IP17

IP17 implied that owning the direct supplier relationship eliminates intermediaries, providing greater control over sourcing and enabling traceability.

“so we own the direct relationship with our supply base so that our you know our suppliers and like I said, the dedicated Scottish team manage that relationship” IP17

IP17 implied that the strong and direct relationships with suppliers enables the organisation to effectively manage fluctuations in supply and demand throughout the year.

“I would say that the in terms of the supply across the year, yes, there are peaks and troughs I can mention in certain periods. But I would say that on the whole, it does seem fairly flat and there are a little sort of changes to demand on the whole, which means that obviously we can manage that very well”.

5.2.24.1.2 Supplier Selection

The Supplier selection as a contributor to supply chain resilience is also discussed by IP8 and IP10. Appropriate supplier selection is proposed as proactive supply chain resilience strategy by Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015). IP17 implied that the organisation follows a strict supplier selection criterion to ensure that all farms they purchase from are reputable, farm-assured, and comply with relevant industry standards. The emphasis on sourcing only from farms with which they have an active relationship highlights their focus on trust, quality assurance, and compliance within the supply chain.

“we would only purchase from a farm that we deem to be reputable, obviously with farm assured to the relevant standards and that we had an active relationship with as a supplier. So you've got that”IP17

The IP17 reiterated the importance of their procurement team and implied that this approach entails more control over the buying process and helps in maintaining strong supplier relationships.

“So it is our own teams that are going out to buy, we're not dealing with a third party, etcetera”IP17

5.2.24.1.3 Traceability

IP 17 identified traceability as a supply chain resilience contributor. This has also been identified by IP3, IP6, IP10, IP14 and IP 15.

IP17 mentioned that the organisation's vertically integrated supply chain provides traceability from farm to processing and back to the original supplier. This integration ensures that all livestock purchased meet compliance standards and are sourced exclusively from reputable, farm-assured suppliers with whom the organisation maintains active relationships. The use of sophisticated systems within processing facilities allows carcasses to be tracked throughout the entire process, linking them to the kill batch and ultimately back to the individual farm using ID numbers and E-tag identifiers.

“So ... unique vertically integrated supply.....very good traceability in terms of obviously back to the supply that we purchased it from and got the processing side of which we have sophisticated systems within the factory which allow obviously the carcasses to be traced throughout the whole system back to the kill batch and then obviously back to the supply themselves. Obviously, the use of ID numbers E tag numbers throughout the process etcetera, which mean that we do have that traceability back to the kill batch and then back to supplier. So, I would say that within our supply chain we feel confident that what we're purchasing is compliant to what we want it to be, and I think for us, like I said, being in that unique position that we are vertically integrated” IP17

From a traceability perspective, this system reinforces accountability, enabling the organisation to verify compliance with regulatory standards, animal welfare practices, and food safety protocols.

5.2.24.1.4 Risk Management

From a risk management perspective, IP17 implied that the organisation adopts a proactive and systematic approach to disease preparedness to mitigate risks and maintain operational continuity during a notifiable disease outbreak. By conducting site-specific assessments, such as at their Turriff site in Scotland, the organisation identifies potential risks and implements procedural changes to address vulnerabilities associated with specific diseases, like blue tongue.

“What I would also say so for disease preparedness. So, we'll assess it by processing site basis..... we would put together a site plan for that disease, understand any risk, understand any changes to procedures that need to be made..... then we would change from pre designation status to designated status and then we can operate as normal under those circumstances” IP17

The organisation's strategy of applying for pre-designation status before an outbreak occurs demonstrates anticipatory risk planning, enabling them to respond quickly to an outbreak by transitioning from pre-

designation to designated status. This approach minimizes downtime and ensures that operations can continue under regulatory compliance without delays.

IP17's emphasis on site planning, risk evaluation, and procedure adaptation reflects a structured risk management framework designed to reduce exposure to disruptions caused by any disease outbreak and enhance resilience

5.2.24.1.5 Logistical Capabilities

The IP17 highlighted the logistical capabilities owned by the company which are sufficient to meet any transportation disruption. The integrated logistical capabilities are proposed as a contributor to the supply chain resilience by (Ponomarov and Holcomb, 2009; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015; Mandal et al., 2016).

“So we have our fleet of transport, so we have our own livestock haulage vehicles and so we don't see ripple effects from any transport problems or any strikes, etcetera, So I think that's probably all of the disruptions sort of in a nutshell, I'd say” IP17

The IP 17 implied that for processing operations, the livestock haulage vehicles are directly associated with ensuring a reliable supply of livestock to the abattoirs, such as the Turriff site in Scotland. This in-house transport system allows the company to avoid disruptions caused by third-party hauliers or transport strikes, ensuring timely deliveries to maintain efficient processing schedules. It also supports traceability and compliance with animal welfare standards during transportation, reinforcing supply chain control from farm to factory. For retail operations, the fleet of transport vehicles plays a critical role in delivering products to stores consistently, ensuring shelf availability without being affected by external transportation issues. This capability is particularly important for serving the company's extensive retail network, which includes 500 supermarket stores and nearly 1,000 convenience stores. The dedicated fleet provides the agility needed to meet consumer demand by timely shelving their produce and adjust logistics in response to market fluctuations.

By owning and operating both livestock haulage vehicles and retail fleets, the company maintains end-to-end control over its supply chain logistics, reducing external dependencies and mitigating risks of disruptions, further enhancing its resilience and responsiveness across processing and retail sectors.

5.2.24.1.6 Provenance

Provenance is seen to be identified a contributor to the supply chain resilience. This was also identified by IP 1 as a supply chain resilience contributor. P17 implied that provenance, the origin and traceability of beef is a key factor influencing consumer preferences and purchasing decisions. According to IP17 Customers place high value on beef that is British-sourced, associating it with quality, sustainability, and

food safety standards. IP17 mentioned that the company has gathered this insight through customer roundtables and listening groups, confirming that local sourcing is an important expectation for consumers.

“Provenance I think people expect the especially beef that's on our shelves to be British. And we've conducted customer round tables and listening groups where, you know, people really do value the fact that we source British beef” IP17

5.2.24.1.7 Contingency Planning

The Contingency planning as a supply chain resilient contributor is also identified by IP11.

The IP 17 mentioned that organisation has multi-site processing infrastructure consisting of three abattoirs, provides flexibility to mitigate risks associated with sudden disruptions. This structure allows the company to redistribute processing activities across its facilities, ensuring that operations can continue even if one site is temporarily affected by a disruption. The ability to shift workloads between sites serves as a proactive contingency measure, enabling the organisation to respond quickly to disruptions and ensure supply chain continuity.

“I think in terms of sudden disruptions, I think because we are, it's not one single abattoir. So because it is one of three, we can work between our full processing plant chain to understand obviously if there are any sudden disruptions we can flatten that out by utilising other processing plants within in food group”IP17

5.2.24.1.8 Flexibility in Sourcing

Petitt et al., (2013) proposed flexibility in sourcing as a supply chain resilience capability factor. The IP 17 mentioned a In house Beef Scheme introduced by the Retailer which is aimed at diversifying the supply base by incorporating the dairy beef system. By incorporating dairy beef systems alongside traditional suckler herds, the scheme provides an alternative sourcing option, reducing dependence on any single production method and mitigating risks associated with declining suckler herd numbers. This approach allows the organisation to adapt to fluctuations in livestock availability and market demands, ensuring consistent supply even during seasonal variations or disruption.

“We actually have an integrated beef scheme which we operate. Its called Elite beef scheme. You know, we so this is a sorry, it's a dairy beef scheme that we operate and I think ultimately how we can give longevity to our supply base by utilising it and growing that arm of the business. I think will only help to bolster the supply chain as a whole” IP17

The IP17 highlighted key factors that support the resilience of the SBSC. The IP 17 implied that strong supplier relationships and a structured supplier selection process ensure consistency, compliance, and quality throughout the supply chain. Traceability is reinforced through vertical integration and advanced

tracking systems, enabling effective monitoring and regulatory adherence. Risk management and contingency planning, enhance the ability to respond to disruptions while maintaining operational continuity. Logistical capabilities, provenance, and sourcing flexibility also equip the supply chain to be resilient against disruptions.

5.2.24.2 Theme Challenges Faced by SBSC

The IP 17 discussed only one key challenge which is impacting the resilience of the SBSC. The IP17 mentioned that the decline in suckler herd numbers presents a significant challenge to the supply chain resilience of the SBSC as it threatens the long-term stability and consistency of livestock supply. While dairy beef systems are currently being used to supplement the shortfall, IP17 expressed his concerns about the sustainability of this approach, particularly if calf registration numbers continue to decline in the future.

“decline in suckler numbers”IP17

“I would say that the decline in suckler herds with being supplemented by dairy beef. How sustainable that is going forward and whether actually those calf registration numbers will look to decline as we go forward”IP17

The decline in suckler herd may lead to loss of critical mass in the long run impacting the processors, auction marts and retailers.

The IP17 identified the resilience contributors as strong supplier relationships, rigorous supplier selection process, traceability, risk management strategies, logistical capabilities, provenance, contingency planning, and sourcing flexibility. However, the IP17 also mentioned that decline in suckler herd numbers as a key challenge faced by the SBS. The insights provided by IP17 contributed to a broader understanding of the factors contributing to the resilience of SBSC and the challenges faced by it.

5.2.25 Retail Industry Specialist Interview Participant IP 18

The IP18 has extensive experience in the food retail industry, beginning his career in 1976 with a major UK retailer, where he progressed from store management to food buying operations at the head office. Over 20 years, he held roles including buyer and trading director, overseeing fresh food categories, including fresh meat during the BSE crisis in the mid-1990s. Following his retail career, IP18 transitioned to a non-executive role at a meat processing company, focusing on strategy development, industry representation, and policy engagement. He is currently a board member at a non-departmental public body representing the Scottish red meat industry.

The following figure shows the initial coding done from the recorder transcripts. After repeatedly watching the recorded video and going through the nodes the themes were identified.

Figure 5.27 Interview Coding in NVivo IP18

Theme Factors Contributing to Resilience of the SBSC

The IP 18 identified various factors which contribute to the resilience of the SBSC. Some factors were common and were identified by the other Interview participants as well. The key challenges are discussed below

5.2.25.1.1 Inherent Resilience

This factor was also identified by Interview participants IP6 and IP15. The IP 18 implied that Scotland's natural environment, including its climate, topography, and geography, provides a strong foundation for livestock farming, making it a sustainable and resilient agricultural system. The landscape and climate are better suited for grazing livestock than for arable farming, highlighting Scotland's comparative advantage in livestock production. This natural suitability supports the long-term sustainability of the SBSC by ensuring consistent forage availability and reducing reliance on imported feed, thereby enhancing supply chain resilience.

“So I think that that's a a strong vein which runs through the industry for Scotland, the climate, the topography, the geography all lend themselves to Livestock raising probably to a larger extent than than arable farming. So I think that's an aspect of it which is also important” IP18

5.2.25.1.2 Supplier Relationship

IP 18 identified supplier relationship as a contributor to supply chain resilience. The strength of supplier relationship was also identified by IP3, IP13 and IP17 in terms of a supply chain resilience contributor. The IP18 implied that strong, sustained relationships with farmer suppliers are a critical factor in maintaining resilience within the SBSC. By emphasising the need to nurture and sustain these relationships, the IP18 highlighted the importance of trust, collaboration, and long-term partnerships between processors, retailers, and farmers to ensure a stable and reliable supply base.

“There were so those are the kind of things I would point to awards to, to making sure that you, you remain resilient and another aspect of it I suppose and all of them would say this is that your relationships with your farmer suppliers are important as well and you need to nurture and sustain those” IP18

5.2.25.1.3 Collaboration and Supply Chain Integration

The IP 18 highlighted two aspects of supply chain resilience one is the collaboration in terms of mutual support and the other is the vertical integration in the supply chain. The IP 18 mentioned that Morrison's has an abattoir, Coop own a farm which are the examples of integration, and it leads to greater control and stability. The IP 18 also gave the example of Waitrose integration with Dovecote farms where in the open book policy illustrates a transparent and cooperative approach. It is very interesting that a recent study by Bakshi, Swinney and Tuna (2023) mentioned that vertical control can enhance supply chain resilience by reducing risks, but firms must weigh its costs and rigidity against alternative strategies to determine the most effective approach for their specific needs.

“I mean Morrisons, Morrisons, owns and abattoir and so he's more vertically integrated there than than the other. The other retailers are the coop is integrated, it has its farm. So there are examples of that through

the chain, but I think if you take a relationship with Marks and Spencer for example, and they have always supported British beef, Scott beef have been supplying them for over 60 years and so that's where it's a mutual support it it's not, you know, money changing hands out with the buying and selling. But it is a mutual level of support. We're there for them and they're there for us, and that, to my mind, is a support for the processor and for the industry.

I mean a good example of that if you another one is Waitrose, Waitrose have a completely integrated with Dove cut Farms in Yorkshire. I believe they work on an open book policy and dove cutter, their sole supplier of beef. So there's an example of, you know, mutual support across those parts of the supply chain" IP18

The relationship between M&S and Scotch beef shows a successful model of mutual support. The Collaboration is also identified as a resilient factor by IP 7. The IP18 implied that the beef supply chain benefits from strong, long-term relationships built on mutual support. This is illustrated through the example that Marks & Spencer and Scotbeef's 60-year partnership, where both entities demonstrate commitment beyond simple transactions. This "we're there for them, they're there for us" mentality fosters stability and resilience within the supply chain.

5.2.25.2 Theme Challenges Faced by Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The IP18 identified various challenges which relate to the power dynamics, economic pressures and changing consumer preferences and environmental concerns.

5.2.25.2.1 Retailer Dominance

The IP 18 highlighted the power dynamics in the SBSC, particularly the influence of large retailers. He suggests that these retailers prioritize keeping consumer prices stable, which puts pressure on processors to lower their prices, ultimately impacting farmers who may receive less for their livestock. While acknowledging that consumers ultimately drive demand, IP18 emphasised the role of retailers in resisting price increases, creating a potential imbalance of power in the supply chain. This imbalance can squeeze the profit margins of processors and farmers, making it more challenging for them to operate sustainably.

"So I'm to assert if you want to look at anywhere in the supply chain that potentially has the whip hand, it's probably the big retailers because they do not want to put prices up to their consumers. So if you like the consumer has the final final power, but the retailers are not prepared, they they do not like having to put their prices up to retailers and they will fight very, very hard to maintain prices. And therefore that can push its way back down the chain" IP18

"The processors get squeezed more than anybody and they they do get squeezed, but it it can blow back then to to the farmers as well" IP18

5.2.25.2.2 Declining Consumption of Red Meat

The IP 18 mentioned that the Scottish meat industry is facing a significant threat due to the long-term decline in red meat consumption in the UK. This decline is primarily attributed to health concerns and the relatively high cost of red meat compared to other protein sources like chicken, pork, and plant-based options. IP18 is highlighted that this trend that poses challenges for the Scottish meat industry. Consumers are increasingly choosing other protein sources, either due to perceived health benefits or because they are more affordable. This shift in consumer preferences can impact the demand for Scottish red meat, potentially affecting the industry's profitability and long-term viability.

“I do think the Scottish meat industry faces significant threats. Umm, I I and those those are these really I would say umm, a long term UK diminution in the eating of red meat due to principally health considerations. I think although another factor which can't be ignored is the fact that red meat sits at the top of the price ladder of proteins and it's constantly undercut, particularly by chicken, but also by pork and well, vegetable proteins” IP18

5.2.25.2.3 Low Profitability and Investment

The IP18 highlighted that the low profitability in the SBSC, particularly at the processing levels. This lack of profitability leads to low investment, which further hinders the industry's ability to innovate and adapt.

“So the processing industry, I would say, has suffered from low profitability and therefore low investment, which does which serves to make it, if you like, even even less viable as as things go forward. And I think that is a that is a problem” IP18

5.2.25.2.4 Environmental Concerns and Emissions

The IP18 expressed his concerns about the increasing pressure to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from the livestock sector.

“But those those attacks on it are are very strong and they are now being added to by the whole emissions and carbon net zero. Umm, the emergence of those issues, I would say where what I detect is that emissions can be looked at as a little bit from from agriculture, from Livestock, can be looked at as a bit of a an easy win, low hanging fruit to reduce the country's carbon emissions” IP18

The IP18 mentioned that agriculture is sometimes unfairly targeted as an "easy win" for emission reduction, potentially leading to simplistic solutions like reducing herd sizes without considering the broader implications or investing in more sustainable farming practices.

“You know, if we half the size of the cattle herd, bingo, we we we've arrived at, you know we're on our way to to net zero. And personally, I think that there's absolutely every reason to be looking at reducing the

emissions from livestock rearing every reason, but that is not the same as simply saying we'll reduce the herd"IP18

The IP18 acknowledged the need to address livestock emissions, IP18 advocated for a balanced approach based on scientific research and innovation. He suggested exploring solutions like feed additives, genetic improvements, and educating consumers about sensible meat consumption.

"But it's worth just considering when you are looking at the number of cattle that there are today and you know that they're responsible for what's going on. Well, maybe not entirely, but it it all needs to be calmed down and facts needs to be the basis of it and also what can we do, education of people about a sensible approach to meat-eating, a sensible approach to the amount of emissions and what we can do about it? and then for the research into how can we, you know, make me healthier, how can we reduce emissions through perhaps feed additives and things like that through genetics, if we can, those are the the ways that we, we tackle those things and work hand in hand with science"IP18

The IP18 raised a flag against those who might unfairly criticize the industry and highlights the importance of making decisions based on evidence and a thorough understanding of the challenges

"But I'm afraid that there there are definite vested interests out there who are more interested in knocking the red meat industry than not" IP18

In conclusion, the interview with IP18, a seasoned veteran of the UK food retail industry, provided valuable insights into the resilience and challenges facing the SBSC. The IP18 highlighted the inherent resilience of the SBSC, rooted in Scotland's natural environment and its suitability for livestock farming. He emphasises the importance of strong supplier relationships, collaboration, and vertical integration within the supply chain, citing examples like Marks & Spencer's long-term partnership with Scotbeef and Waitrose's integrated approach with Dovecote Farms.

However, IP18 also identifies significant challenges. He pointed to the dominance of large retailers, who prioritize stable consumer prices, potentially squeezing processors and farmers. The declining consumption of red meat due to health concerns and price sensitivity poses another threat. Furthermore, low profitability in the processing sector hinders investment and innovation. Finally, IP18 acknowledged the growing pressure to reduce emissions from the livestock sector, advocating for a balanced, science-based approach that considers the complexities of the issue and avoids simplistic solutions.

The IP18 implied to the need for the SBSC to adapt to changing consumer preferences, economic pressures, and environmental concerns. By fostering strong relationships throughout the supply chain the SBSC can navigate these challenges and ensure its long-term viability.

5.2.25.3 Perspective of Retailers on the Resilience and Challenges of the SBSC

From the perspective of retailers, the resilience of the SBSC hinges on several key factors. Firstly, strong and direct relationships with suppliers are crucial. This allows retailers to secure a consistent supply of high-quality beef, gather timely information, and collaborate effectively to address challenges. Secondly, rigorous supplier selection processes ensure that retailers source beef from reputable farms that adhere to quality and sustainability standards, building trust with consumers. Thirdly, traceability systems, often enabled by vertical integration, allow retailers to track beef from farm to shelf, ensuring compliance and reinforcing consumer confidence in the origin and safety of the product.

Retailers also recognize the importance of proactive risk management. Contingency planning, including multi-site processing infrastructure, enables them to adapt to disruptions and maintain operational continuity. Furthermore, logistical capabilities, such as owning dedicated transport fleets, help mitigate risks associated with transportation disruptions and ensure timely delivery to stores. Finally, understanding consumer preferences is vital. Provenance plays a significant role in consumer purchasing decisions, with a strong preference for British-sourced beef, associated with quality and sustainability.

However, retailers acknowledge the challenges facing the SBSC. The declining number of suckler herds raises concerns about the long-term stability of the supply base. While alternative sourcing options, such as dairy beef, can supplement the shortfall, there are concerns about the sustainability of this approach. Additionally, the influence of large retailers on pricing can put pressure on processors and farmers, potentially impacting their profitability and long-term viability.

In conclusion, retailers view the resilience of the SBSC as a complex interplay of strong supplier relationships, robust processes, proactive risk management, and a deep understanding of consumer preferences. Addressing challenges such as declining suckler herd numbers and ensuring fair pricing throughout the supply chain will be crucial for the continued success and sustainability of the SBSC.

5.2.26 Policy Manager Interviews Livestock and Animal Health

Two interviews were conducted to explore the perspective of the Policy Managers from Livestock and Animal Health and Welfare from a National Farming Organisation. The objective was to find out the perspective of industry specialist on the resilience of the SBSC and the challenges it is facing.

5.2.27 Policy Manager (Livestock Farming) Organisation Interview Participant 19

The Interview Participant (IP)19 serves as a livestock policy manager for a national agricultural organisation. The role focuses on supporting livestock farming policies, particularly related to beef and sheep production. At the farming organisation the Policy Manager is responsible for ensuring that the

interests of Scottish farmers and rural communities are represented and addressed at regional, national, and international levels.

The following figure shows the initial coding done from the interview transcripts and then after repetitive watching of the recorded videos and reviewing of the transcript and node, the final themes were generated.

Figure 5.28 Interview Coding in NVivo IP19

5.2.27.1

Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC

This theme explores key factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC based on insights provided by IP19. The participant identified several elements that reinforce resilience, including transparency, market position, and stakeholder collaboration.

5.2.27.1.1 Transparency

The IP 19 identified transparency as a contributor of a resilient SBSC. It has also been identified by IP15 as a key element of resilience in the SBSC.

“live ring is really important and really crucial to a primary producers business because that is the only part in this platform where we see complete transparency” IP19

IP19 implied that the live ring provides complete visibility into the buying and selling process. It ensures that primary producers have real-time access to market prices, buyer demand, and competitive bidding. The transparency offered by the live ring reduces price manipulations enabling fair competition and trust within the supply chain. As highlighted by Zhao et al., (2024), transparency allows stakeholders to access key Information, such as pricing, buyer details, and transactional records, promoting fairness.

5.2.27.1.2 Market Position

The IP 19 pointed out Market position as a key resilient capability factor in the SBSC.

“And when I say Scotch beef is a premium product, yes, it's a premium product, but it's also produced to very high standards and some of which are the best in the world” IP19

The IP19's statement highlighted that Scotch beef is positioned as a premium product produced to exceptionally high standards, aligning closely with Petitt et al., (2013), who emphasise that market position including factors like product differentiation, brand equity, and customer loyalty is a key contributor to resilience in supply chains.

By describing Scotch beef as adhering to world-class standards, IP19 implied product differentiation, which distinguishes Scotch beef from competitors through quality assurance, traceability, and sustainability practices. This differentiation strengthens brand equity, enabling the product to command a premium price and maintain consumer trust and loyalty.

The IP19 implied that Scotch beef's premium status, supported by its quality differentiation, brand value, and customer confidence, contributes to the resilience of the SBSC.

5.2.27.1.3 Stakeholder Collaboration

The IP 19 identified stakeholder collaboration as a resilient contributor to SBSC. It was also highlighted by IP7. Scholten and Schilder (2015) concluded that collaboration at the network level enhances resilience within supply chains.

The IP19 implied that the small size of the SBSC is a strength that fosters close collaboration, effective communication, and strong relationships among stakeholders, including primary producers, processors, industry bodies like QMS and SAMW, and the Scottish Government. This tight-knit structure allows for greater awareness of the challenges and needs faced by different parts of the supply chain, enabling coordinated efforts to address issues and implement solutions quickly.

“one of the key strengths of the Scottish beef supply chain is that we are a small industry in the sense that all I've mentioned frequently, that we have a good dialogue with QMS, SAMW, Institute of auctioneers. We're very small industry, which means that everybody is alive to the various and issues that, whether it's a primary producer or the processor, we at the end, the struggles that are going on and I think also because we're a small sector, we have a good dialogue with Scottish Government, which means they take us quite seriously” IP19

IP19 also suggested that the small scale of the industry enhances its visibility and influence with the Scottish Government, leading to policy support and recognition of its importance to the economy. This close dialogue with policymakers strengthens the resilience of the supply chain by enabling it to advocate for resources, shape policies, and respond effectively to emerging challenges.

5.2.27.1.4 Government Support

The role of Government support as a resilience factor for SBSC is also identified by IP5 and IP 6. The IP19 also mentioned the Government support in form of subsidies in achieving the resilience in the SBSC.

The IP19 implied that agricultural policy plays a critical role in providing stability to the livestock sector, which is essential for maintaining the resilience of the SBSC.

“So that's really the role of policy, I would say in creating resilient business that are able to cope with disruptions” IP19

The IP19 discussed the price volatility faced by farmers, particularly in the sale of store cattle, where prices can fluctuate significantly depending on timing and market conditions for instance, a potential 50 pence drop in price between selling in April versus the back end of the year. The IP19 pointed out that agricultural policies act as a buffer against this volatility, helping farmers to sustain profitability and financial stability even during market fluctuations.

“When you stand back and take a look at what the role of agricultural policy is from a Livestock, perspective specifically, it is a bit of stability because when someone sells store cattle in the back end versus if they sold it in April, we could see almost a 50 pence drop in price. So what Ag policy is able to do is continue that stabilization piece throughout the business and without that and I don't think we would have the resilience that we have” IP19

The insights provided by IP19 highlighted key factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC. As per IP 19 transparency plays a critical role in ensuring fair pricing by providing producers with real-time visibility into market prices, buyer demand, and competitive bidding. This openness reduces the risk of price manipulation, builds trust, and promotes fairness within the supply chain. As proposed by IP19 the premium market position of Scotch beef strengthens consumer trust and loyalty, supported by quality assurance and sustainability practices. Lastly the Stakeholder collaboration fosters stronger relationships among the industry stakeholders and Government support provides the financial strength to the livestock farmers to become resilient. These factors collectively seem to enhance the supply chain's resilience to manage challenges.

5.2.27.1.5 Theme Challenges Faced by SBSC

The IP 19 identified various challenges like lack of Succession, Profitability, Labor intensiveness, and Scukler herd efficiency which were also highlighted by other Interview participants as well. The key challenges are elaborated below

5.2.27.1.5.1 Lack of Income Diversification

The IP 19 implied that the lack of diversified income streams in livestock farming poses a significant barrier to building resilience in the SBSC. Unlike conventional businesses that can spread risk by pursuing multiple income sources, livestock farming is inherently time-intensive, labor-intensive, and cost-intensive, leaving farmers with limited capacity to engage in alternative ventures without compromising the core focus of their operations.

“I don't think we would have the resilience that we have and I think also in a in a conventional business sense is that well then you would diversify your business that you have various income streams, et cetera. But farming's maybe not fit for purpose for that. Because it's so time intensive labor intensive cost intensive that you don't have the facilities to diversify as well as run a successful Livestock, business” IP19

5.2.27.1.6 Limited Infrastructure

The P19 is implied that limited infrastructure and resource constraints faced by store producers on the Scottish islands hinder their ability to build resilience within the SBSC. These producers are often price takers, meaning they lack the flexibility to withhold livestock until market conditions improve. Instead,

they are forced to sell cattle as soon as they are ready, regardless of market fluctuations or price volatility. This inability to delay sales due to resource limitations, such as lack of storage, grazing facilities, or feed resources, makes their businesses highly vulnerable to market pressures and economic instability. Unlike larger or mainland producers who may have the capacity to manage inventory and time sales strategically, island producers face structural disadvantages that prevent them from adopting adaptive strategies to weather disruptions.

“a store producer on the islands for example, it doesn't have much choice, but the resource that they have there, once they're they've got that store heifer steer that needs to go, it needs to go and there that creates such high fluctuations both in the in the volume through markets, but also it doesn't give them that opportunity to wait until the market bounces back and that is when we talk about price takers. That's what we mean that their business doesn't have the infrastructure” IP19

5.2.27.1.7 Regulatory Uncertainty.

The IP19 discussed about the uncertain government policies regarding the Livestock Industry.

“Very few LFA farms are profitable without support, so it's not exactly a viable business. And in the in the context of agricultural policy uncertainty, not knowing what else LFASS will look like beyond 2028, not knowing where you're direct support is coming from, and we know that direct support will be reduced, and we've advocated that direct support should still remain 80% of the agricultural budget and there's all these changes that I think uncertainty doesn't help and we know we have an aging agricultural policy” IP19

IP19 implied that agricultural policy uncertainty poses a significant threat to the stability and sustainability of the livestock farming sector, particularly in Less Favoured Areas (LFAs). The statement reflects concerns about the lack of clarity regarding the future of the Less Favoured Areas Support Scheme (LFASS) beyond 2028 and the uncertainty surrounding direct financial support mechanisms for farmers. This ambiguity makes it difficult for farmers to plan long-term investments, implement improvements, or make structural changes to their businesses, leaving them vulnerable to economic instability and market fluctuations. The need for modernized policies that address current economic and environmental challenges is implied as a critical requirement to sustain the sector.

The IP19 highlighted various aspects of the SBSC. The contributing factors of resilience were identified alongside the challenges faced by the SBSC. By mentioning the resilience factors such as transparency, Market position, and Government support, the IP19 pointed out that to sustain this resilience, the supply chain must address the challenges identified. The common challenges the livestock farmers face are the lack of returns, succession and the ageing population. The IP19 mentioned that the uncertainty in the future

support payments, lack of diversification and the limited infrastructure will hinder the resilience of the SBSC.

5.2.28 Policy Manager (Animal Health & Welfare) Farming Organisation Interview Participant 20

The interview Participant is a Policy Manager of Animal health & Welfare at a National Farming Organisation. This position focuses on addressing issues related to livestock health, disease prevention, animal welfare standards, and regulatory compliance, balancing economic viability with ethical considerations. The following nodes were generated after the initial coding of transcript in NVivo. After repetitive watching of the recorded video interview and reviewing the auto generated transcript relevant themes were generated.

Figure 5.29 Interview Coding in NVivo IP20

5.2.28.1 Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC

5.2.28.1.1 Traceability

The IP 20 identified traceability as a contributing factor to SBSC. The IP20 mentioned that the disease monitoring is done by the SCOTEID system. This system enables to monitor that whether the cattle have a negative or positive status. This way the infected cattle can be traced the spread of disease is controlled. Traceability is also identified by IP3, IP7, IP14 and IP15. The importance of traceability as a supply chain resilience contributor is in line with the literature is discussed under the resilience theme of the aforementioned Interview participants.

“We’ve already got on the ScotEID system. It already manages the BVD monitoring scheme that we’ve got, and so it already. And so it links in nicely that you’ve got that traceability in. It already takes that information and looks at whether you’re doing your BVD testing, what animals are positive, what animals are negative, what you’re holding status is, and things like that” IP20

The IP 20 implied that this traceability system also serves as a risk management system wherein the risk of disruption due to a disease outbreak can be identified and mitigated by taking the appropriate measures timely and by reducing any supply disruption due to a spread of disease.

5.2.28.1.2 Risk Management

The IP20 mentioned the preparedness against disease by having a proper risk management approach. As soon as the symptoms are identified at a place the risk assessment and mitigation initiatives are undertaken. The movements are restricted in order to curtail the risk of further spread of disease.

“There are plans there for diseases and that basically just role inter play, and they have the processes there and so they are set up for immediately. They get a report of a of a potential notifiable disease. They’ll get people out there. They’ll get testing done. They’ll shut down the area. Stop moving while they do the testing and then they have the processes that they put in place, including, you know, zones where people can’t move animals, zones where you have to do surveillance, and that that is all there”

The IP20 implied that a risk management framework is in place which reflects the readiness against any notifiable disease and contributes to the resilience of the SBSC.

Although the IP 20 mentioned that the SBSC has a risk management framework which makes it resilient. But it does not have a unlimited capacity and it can be exhausted if the magnitude of the disease outbreak reaches to a stage which is beyond their capacity to cope with.

“It’s all quite well worked out, but it yeah, it does take manpower and you can cope at a certain level, but once you started, you know, if you’re getting 30 disease reports a day and you’ve got to go through that,

have the manpower to go to 30 different holdings and start the process, it starts getting it can get quite difficult”IP20

The IP20 identified traceability and risk management as the key resilience contributors of the SBSC. The traceability and risk management factors both supplement each other. As implied by the IP20 the traceability also helps in the identification of any disease and the risk is mitigated by executing the risk mitigation protocols. However, it is noteworthy that IP20 showed a concern regarding the resource constraints in managing a large disease outbreak.

5.2.28.2 Theme Challenges Faced by the SBSC

The IP20 identified various challenges faced by the SBSC which are also identified by other key stakeholders for instance reducing suckler herd, greenhouse gas emissions, changing consumer preferences, poor infrastructure and trust. The two key challenges are elaborated below

5.2.28.2.1 Poor Infrastructure

The IP 20 mentioned that due to the concentration of the processing sector the animals have to travel to distant places to get the cattle slaughtered. Also mentioned in section 2.3.2 that QMS red meat industry profile 2024 mentioned that in 2023, 75.0% of the total cattle kill occurred in the five largest abattoirs, demonstrating the dominance of large-scale facilities in the industry. In contrast, the five smallest abattoirs account for just 0.7% of the total kill, indicating that smaller facilities play a minimal role in overall processing capacity.

“getting sites with sufficient infrastructure is difficult and we obviously have seen a massive contraction of the industry that that it's really just large plants that are processing large numbers of animals are the only ones that can really make that sums work for it”IP20

The IP 20 also implied that the large processing plants are surviving because they are getting the required throughput.

5.2.28.2.2 Trust

The IP 20 mentioned that there is a lack of trust between the farmers, processors and retailers and this needs to be addressed. The IP 20 implied that this lack of trust has resulted in an unfair supply chain which means that the key stakeholders suspect that they are not getting the large share of the Pie which was also pointed out by IP 3 and IP5.

“we do need to work closer with the retailers and the processors and get these things. Yeah, get things adding up because at the moment, you know it are supply chains aren't fair” IP20

The IP20 provided useful insights regarding the factors contributing to the resilience of SBSC and the challenges which are impacting it.

5.2.29 Overview of the Perspective of Policy Managers (Farming Organisation)

The interviews conducted with the policy managers from livestock and animal health provided valuable insights into the resilience of the SBSC and the challenges it faces. The livestock policy manager (IP19) emphasised the importance of transparency, market positioning, stakeholder collaboration, and government support in strengthening the SBSC. Transparency was identified as a key factor, particularly through the use of live rings, which ensure fair pricing and reduce manipulation by providing real-time visibility into market activities. Market positioning, especially the premium status of Scotch beef, was highlighted as a competitive advantage. The IP 20 mentioned that government support, particularly through subsidies like LFASS, was seen as essential in stabilising incomes and buffering farmers against market volatility.

The IP19 also identified several challenges undermining resilience. The lack of income diversification, labour and cost intensive nature of livestock farming, limits farmers' ability to spread risks or pursue alternative revenue streams. Infrastructure constraints, particularly in remote areas such as the Scottish islands, further exacerbate vulnerabilities by forcing producers to operate as price takers, unable to withhold sales during unfavourable market conditions. Policy uncertainty was another major concern, with the future of support schemes like LFASS beyond 2028 remaining unclear. This uncertainty hampers long-term planning.

The animal health and welfare policy manager (IP20) provided additional perspectives on resilience, focusing on traceability and risk management. Traceability systems, such as SCOTEID, were highlighted as vital tools for disease monitoring and control, enabling rapid identification and containment of outbreaks. This capability supports supply chain stability by reducing the risk of disruption caused by animal health issues. The IP20 also emphasised the role of risk management frameworks in enhancing resilience. Plans for disease outbreaks, including movement restrictions and surveillance zones, were seen as effective in mitigating threats. However, concerns were raised about resource limitations, particularly the ability to handle large-scale outbreaks, which could strain the system's capacity.

The IP20 also identified challenges impacting resilience, including poor infrastructure and lack of trust within the supply chain. The dominance of large processing facilities has resulted in animals needing to travel longer distances, increasing costs and logistical difficulties. Limited infrastructure constrains smaller producers, reducing their ability to compete. Trust issues between farmers, processors, and retailers were also noted, with stakeholders expressing dissatisfaction over the perceived unfair distribution of profits

within the supply chain. Addressing these trust deficits is seen as essential for fostering collaboration and improving supply chain fairness.

In summary, the interviews with the policy managers highlighted key contributors to the resilience of the SBSC, including transparency, market positioning, stakeholder collaboration, government support, traceability, and risk management. At the same time, they revealed significant challenges such as policy uncertainty, ageing demographics, labour intensiveness, income diversification constraints, infrastructure limitations, and trust deficits. These insights emphasise the need for specific policies and investment in infrastructure and promote trust among stakeholders to enhance the resilience of the SBSC in the face of evolving challenges.

5.2.30 Industry Practitioner Traceability Organisation Interview Participant (IP21)

The IP 21 is a General Manager of an Institution that runs a livestock traceability system designed to monitor and record the movements and health statuses of various livestock species, including cattle, sheep, and pigs. The IP21 worked for 30 years as a senior livestock identification regulation movement policy manager for the Scottish Government.

IP 21 described the workings of the traceability system and the developments underway, which are being collaborated on by other institutions. The following figure shows the initial coding done after scrutinising the transcript of the video-recorded interview. The themes were developed after a rigorous analysis of the initial coding, repetitive transcript reading, and watching the interview.

Figure 5.30 Initial Coding of Interview Transcript in NVivo IP21

5.2.30.1 Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC

The key factors identified by the IP 21 were Big Data Analytics, Traceability and Transparency.

5.2.30.1.1 Traceability

The IP21 mentioned that the SBSC's high traceability contributes to its resilience. The IP20 noted that they have different tools for traceability, for instance, Scott Moves+, which captures animal movements. It also records the cattle's BVD (Bovine viral diarrhoea) status. The IP 21 mentioned that the SBSC is in a better position to respond to a disease outbreak, making it more resilient. The system also records the assurance status of the Cattle producer and the veterinary visits, which is visible to the supply chain.

“The high level of traceability that we have. I think we're now in a better position if there is an outbreak, we can control it quicker” IP21

“So we record the assurance status on ScotEID. You also record the vet visit data on ScotEID and that's visible to the supply chain” IP 21

5.2.30.1.2 Big Data Analytics

Ali and Golgeci (2019) mentioned big data analytics as a supply chain resilience driver. IP 20 also mentioned using big data analytics to improve herd performance to ensure a steady cattle supply.

“We're doing analytics through Myherd Statistics for Cattle Keepers, allowing them, you know, on Myherd stats, you don't have to do anything extra. We just take their statutory information that they enter on ScotEid and we provide analytics on their herd performance” IP21

The IP20 mentioned that they can expand the scope of data analytics, but they need government support to execute such a project. Moreover, the IP 21 also noted that the information that livestock farmers capture for submission to the Government is not available to the entire supply chain.

“We could be, you know, if we were funded, we could do more than analytics. You know, I mean the data we've got, you think of things like carbon capture. All these things, you know, Scottish Government's been paying keepers to do, to go and test their soil, do soil sampling and you know that data's sitting on farm, doesn't it Doesn't going anywhere. Well, you try and capture that in some of the Scott Eid and that again builds into that bigger picture”IP21

5.2.30.1.3 Transparency

IP 21 also identified transparency as a contributing factor to resilience. IP15, IP16, and IP 19 also mentioned it as a contributing factor to SBSC's resilience. The IP21 mentioned that the auction marts are vital to the SBSC. The role of the auction marts in ensuring transparency also leads to the resilience of the SBSC

“Markets are really important part of the chain, at least 70 to 80% of animals that are sold moved through markets, and it does get you It does get transparency with pricing, so that's a good thing” IP21

This theme highlighted the insights of the IP21 regarding the resilience of the SBSC. The traceability, transparency and data analytics strengthen the strength of the SBSC by ensuring its readiness against disease to mitigate the risk of supply disruption due to a potential disease outbreak. The traceability also leads to increased consumer confidence and receiving the premium price for the product not only in the domestic market but also in the international markets, as mentioned by the IP21

“Scotch does get a premium, Scott, and you know it gets a premium for export as well”IP21

5.2.30.2 Theme Challenges faced by the SBSC

IP21 identified various challenges identified by other interview participants, such as declining cattle herds, GHG emissions, and negative propagation against livestock farming. However, according to IP21, the biggest challenge is disease outbreaks, highlighted below.

5.2.30.2.1 Disease outbreak

The IP 21 mentioned Disease outbreaks as one of the biggest challenges faced by SBSC. The IP21 Implied that although the level of disease preparedness has increased due to high traceability, the risk of disease outbreaks can still significantly impact the resilience of the SBSC.

“To be honest, I think the biggest threat is disease outbreak. So that that stops the entire chain”

Overall, the IP21 highlighted important resilience aspects of SBSC alongside the challenges it is confronting. The IP21 implied that the traceability of SBSC is very high in terms of its readiness against disease preparation; however, more work needs to be done from the performance monitoring aspect. The IP21 mentioned that they are working on a project with FSS (Food Standards Scotland) so that the data obtained from the Abattoirs regarding Carcass will be made available to inform the farmer how the cattle has ultimately performed. The IP21 also proposed the formulation of Farmer's Cooperatives to make the supply chain fairer, wherein the Cooperatives can safeguard the interest of the livestock farmers. The IP21 specifically mentioned that some farmer Cooperatives are stronger in Europe than the supermarkets. The IP21 implied that the structural imbalance caused by Retailer dominance could be offset by forming the Farmer Cooperatives.

5.2.31 Market Intelligence Manager (Non-Departmental Public Body) Interview Participant (IP) 22

The IP 22 is working as a Market Intelligence Manager at a public institution promoting the red meat sector of Scotland. The IP 22 is responsible for managing datasets and conducting analysis for reports. The IP22 provides information to farmers, processors, and trade bodies to enable them to make informed decisions. The IP22 highlighted various aspects of SBSC. The following figures show the initial coding from the transcript. The interview transcript and video-recorded interview were repeatedly viewed to formulate the themes.

Figure 5.31 Interview Coding in NVivo IP22

5.2.31.1 Theme Factor Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC

The IP22 identified the factors contributing to SBSC's resilience, which other Interview participants also identified. The key contributing factors are mentioned below.

5.2.31.1.1 Inherent Resilience

The IP22 also identified inherent resilience as a contributing factor to resilient SBSC.

“We've got the land, we've got the generations of skills” IP22

“we're thinking of that in Scotland, though we're not going to have major droughts. It doesn't seem like going forward, whereas other parts of the world may have much more volatile, volatile climates, and it's going to restrict their ability to produce silver. Yeah, we're going to be a great place to produce it”IP22

5.2.31.1.2 Government Support

The IP22 also mentioned that Government Support in the form of subsidies has contributed to the resilience of the beef supply chain at the livestock farmers' end.

“Because, yeah, we've we know that cattle farmers, it's always been quite a low margin business and from our enterprise profitability reports over the years, we always found that it was that without agricultural subsidies, the farmers were making a loss” IP22

Market Position

The IP22 also identified Market position as contributing to the supply chain resilience at the demand side.

“we see certainly in Scotland is that consumers are very driven by supporting local supporting Scottish products, so that that's certainly helping at the moment. I don't think there's any prospect of the retailers importing because people really kind of don't want it”IP22

5.2.31.1.3 Traceability

The IP22 also discussed the SBSC's traceability aspect and commented that ScotEID's Myherd Stats is a worthwhile service for herd performance management.

“They have introduced this thing called Myherd Stats. So all farmers can log in and they can see their some of their statistics from their farm, which should in theory help them thinking more about productivity. So I think yeah, that that is kind of worthwhile service”IP22

5.2.31.2 Theme Challenges faced by SBSC

The IP22 identified the key challenges faced by SBSC, including challenges also mentioned by other Interview participants. For Instance, the IP22 identified Critical Mass as a key challenge, highlighted by IP 2, IP4, IP5, IP 6, and IP 8. The IP22 mentioned common challenges, including lack of profitability, labour, succession, and supply-demand imbalance, which other Interview participants have also identified. The interview extracts are shown below, highlighting the challenges

“I guess it's that issue is what we call critical mass” IP22

“it's always been quite a low margin business andfarmers were making a loss” IP22

“Demand is there, supply contracting is going to push the push the farm gate price up” IP22

“You certainly your access to immigrant labor is much from Europe is much lower than it used to be” IP22

“like having a successor to the business, having your some people don't have an identified kid that will definitely take over the reins” IP22

“You can't really do much with the agricultural policy system because there's limitations on the IT system”IP22

Apart from the identification of resilient factors and challenges faced by SBSC, the IP22 mentioned that the Scottish Red Meat Industry does not have a future market for cattle, which can help livestock farmers to hedge the risk of price fluctuations. The IP22 mentioned the limited role of auction marts and implied that the trade routed through livestock is 5%, which is not a significant part of the sector. The IP22 also highlighted the performance data needs to be extended to include the store producer as well because the data to the calve producer is not available, so it is crucial to integrate them in the data link so that it might help them adjust their production systems. The IP22 also mentioned small farmers' lack of risk management due to financial constraints. The IP22 mentioned the knowledge transfer initiatives taken in the industry that deliver positive results, but the scale of operation is quite limited.

Overall, the IP22 provided valuable insights into the SBSC by highlighting its challenges and the factors that make it resilient.

5.2.32 Head of Industry Development (Non-Departmental Public Body) Interview Participant (IP)

23

The IP23 is the head of industry development and is responsible for developing and delivering activities to improve the quality and efficiency of the primary production of red meat and its supply chain in Scotland.

The IP23 discussed various aspects of SBSC alongside the challenges and resilient contributors. The figure below shows the initial coding of the interview transcript in NVivo.

Figure 5.32 Interview Coding in NVivo IP23

5.2.32.1.1 Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of SBSC

The IP 23 identified traceability, supplier relationship and inherent resilience as enabling factors of a resilient SBSC.

5.2.32.1.2 Traceability

IP 23 identified traceability as a contributing factor to SBSC's resilience. The IP23 specifically mentioned that DNA traceability is used in the supply chain to further augment the existing traceability system.

“You know, you get fully comprehensive traceability if you use a DNA sample and trace it right back to where the animal came from. But fundamentally, we're trying to add additional layers of security to the traceability system, which is already pretty robust” IP23

The other interview participants also highlighted the importance of traceability in the SBSC, for instance, the traceability done through the ScotEID by using ScotMove+ and DNA samples used by supermarkets for traceability.

The IP23 also mentioned that DNA can also be used to improve productivity.

“If we use DNA, we can identify these productivity features, make them more readily available, and encourage people to use them. But in the first instance, the real reason we wanted to use the DNA evidence was traceability” IP23

5.2.32.1.3 Supplier Relationship

The IP23 mentioned the supplier relationship in the context of the tier 1 supplier. The store finisher sells the cattle to the finisher, who fattens the cattle and sells it through the auction mart or to the processors.

“So yeah, it was about building that ongoing, excuse me, ongoing relationship with them with the people that bought the stock and trying to make sure that we're providing something that the market wants” IP23

IP 23 implied that the supplier relationship is not solely dependent on uninterrupted cattle supply to the buyer but also on market requirements. The suppliers can use the traceability data to improve their production.

5.2.32.2 Inherent Resilience

The inherent resilience is also identified by other Interview participants, but they described it from the perspective of natural climate and farming skills, whereas the IP23 pointed towards the production cycle as a contributor to inherent resilience.

The IP23 mentioned that the continuous production cycle inherent in livestock farming contributes to the resilience of the SBSC, unlike manufacturing industries, where production can be paused or scaled down in response to market fluctuations or external pressures. Livestock farming operates on a natural, ongoing cycle of breeding and raising animals. This ensures a consistent cattle supply, providing a buffer against sudden disruptions and helping maintain supply chain continuity.

“It's a relatively resilient industry. One of the things that we know is that we sort of remind ourselves is that there is a constant production cycle here. It's not like they can, you know, it's not like a factory where production can cease for a couple of years, or it could be mothballed generally farms have livestock, they produce young stock, so one of the things that that does tend to provide a bit of stability is that there are always that next crop of animals coming through” IP23

The IP23 implied that this ongoing cycle acts as a form of inherent resilience as the constant flow of young stock into the system means that, despite external challenges such as market volatility, environmental pressures, or policy changes, there is a built-in stability due to the biological nature of livestock production.

5.2.32.3 Theme Challenges faced by SBSC

The IP 23 highlighted various challenges, which other interview participants also identified. The IP 23 mentioned the lack of profit margin, rising input costs, changing consumer preferences, price volatility and a demand-supply imbalance. The other key challenges identified by IP23 are as under

5.2.32.3.1 Lack of Risk Management

IP23 is implied that risk management practices adopted by the livestock farmers are often informal and reactive rather than being part of a structured, formalized risk management process. Farmers typically manage risks through practical, day-to-day strategies, such as having backup labour for critical farm tasks or support for administrative work, rather than engaging in comprehensive contingency planning or implementing proactive risk mitigation frameworks.

“I think, yeah, farmers adopting risk management strategies is not necessarily what you would think of as a formalized risk management statute, Process. I suppose the most common way people will do that is by having someone as backup for farm labourer, farm tasks, or someone who can help with administration on a backup basis and not necessarily contingency planning as you would call it. But yeah, I think there's a big role for that and I think it's an industry wide issue that we need to be dealing with” IP23

This perspective suggests that while farmers recognize the need for risk mitigation, their approaches are often improvised and resource-driven, focusing on immediate operational risks rather than broader systemic risks such as disease outbreaks. The IP23 acknowledged that this informal approach may not address the industry's challenges and emphasised the need for the sector to adopt more formalised, industry-wide risk management strategies.

5.2.32.4 Lack of Industry Engagement

The statement by IP23 implied that industry engagement is a significant challenge in the SBSC, particularly in encouraging farmers to adopt innovation and new technologies. Without active participation in

knowledge-sharing and the adoption of modern practices, the industry risks falling behind in responding to emerging challenges such as market volatility, climate change, and sustainability pressures. The implication is that fostering industry-wide engagement through programs like the Monitor Farm initiative is critical for driving sector-wide progress.

“I should say one of the main problems we have is getting the industry engaged into that and the Monitor Farm program is a really effective way of doing that. It allows everybody a forum, allows everybody a chance to come and see the practical benefits of innovation and technology. So yeah, that's the real benefit of the Monitor farm program”IP23

In addition to addressing the challenges and resilience factors within the SBSC, the IP23 also emphasised several critical aspects necessary for strengthening the industry. One of the key points raised was the importance of financial security for the stakeholders to embrace change and adaptability.

“But a big part of that comes from financial security. I think once people have that financial security or able to guarantee that financial security. They will feel more comfortable in making change, so I think that's going to be critical to success moving forward”IP23

Another significant factor discussed by IP23 was the provision of a free flow of valuable and actionable information throughout the supply chain, which is vital for enabling better decision-making. For instance, producers need access to detailed feedback on how their livestock performs after processing, such as kill-out percentages, to make more informed decisions about breeding and management practices. This feedback loop is essential for continuous improvement, allowing producers to align their operations more closely with market demands and processing requirements, ultimately enhancing supply chain efficiency and resilience.

“ I think the best way to improve Cooperation between those different sectors in the supply chain is by having a free flow of information. So information that is useful and is valuable gets all the way back down to the people that are going to make the decisions based on that information. For example, if you're producing Lambs, you want to know how those lambs end up? How they you know how they kill out and what the percentage of kill out is you want to take that back to your own farm and you can make a breeding decision on that basis”IP23

The IP23 also mentioned the importance of empowering livestock farmers within the industry. This empowerment can be achieved through various means, including financial support, access to data, and opportunities for knowledge exchange. By providing these resources, policymakers and industry leaders can enable lives stock farmers to make informed and proactive decisions that drive positive change.

“It is for them to empower people to make positive decisions and that can be through funding, it can be through provision of data, It can be through knowledge exchange but there are ways to empower people to make positive change in Scottish farming and in livestock production” IP23

The interview with IP23, the Head of Industry Development at a non-departmental public body, offered in-depth insights into the resilience and challenges of the SBSC. The IP23 emphasised robust traceability systems, particularly the use of DNA technology. Strong supplier relationships were also highlighted as essential for aligning production with market demands. Furthermore, the continuous livestock production cycle was identified as an inherent resilience factor, providing a steady supply of cattle.

Despite these strengths, IP23 pointed out significant challenges that threaten the sector's resilience. The absence of formalized risk management practices leaves farmers vulnerable to unexpected disruptions, as many rely on informal, reactive approaches rather than structured strategies. Furthermore, limited industry engagement, especially in adopting innovations and new technologies, hinders progress and adaptability. Rising input costs, fluctuating market prices, and shifting consumer preferences exacerbate these challenges, placing further strain on producers. The IP23 stressed that financial security is fundamental for farmers to confidently implement necessary changes and innovations. Additionally, improving the flow of actionable information across the supply chain was identified as vital for informed decision-making and aligning production with processing and market requirements.

To overcome these challenges and strengthen the SBSC's resilience, IP23 advocated for empowering farmers through targeted financial support, access to performance data, and greater opportunities for knowledge exchange.

5.2.33 Public Affairs and Industry Strategy Manager (Non-Departmental Public Organisation) Interview Participant (IP)24

The IP24 is a non-governmental public organisation's Public Affairs and Industry Strategy Manager. The role integrates three key components: industry engagement, public affairs, and policy. This multifaceted responsibility involves fostering stronger connections between the non-departmental public organisations' industry teams, communication teams, policymakers, and local authorities to ensure a cohesive approach to industry representation.

The IP24 is dedicated to championing the Scottish red meat sector by advocating for its vital contributions to Scotland's public health, economic prosperity, and environmental sustainability. The IP24 involves engaging with policymakers and key decision-makers to highlight the industry's role in supporting the national and rural economy and contributing to Scotland's biodiversity and environmental goals. This advocacy ensures the sector is well-positioned to capitalise on emerging opportunities and effectively

respond to macro-environmental risks. The initial coding is done after repeatedly reading the interview transcript, shown in the figure below. After initial coding, the transcript and video were repeatedly viewed to form the theme.

Figure 5.33 Interview Coding in NVivo IP24

5.2.33.1 Theme Factor Contribution to the Resilience of the SBSC

The IP24 identified response against disease preparedness, traceability, government support, and inherent resilience as contributing factors to SBSC. The earlier Interview Participants also determine these factors

5.2.33.1.1 Traceability

The IP24 implied that traceability within the SBSC is highly robust due to systems like ScotEID, which effectively records and tracks the movement of animals across the sector. This system enhances the industry's ability to monitor and manage livestock movement, ensuring that animals can be quickly and accurately traced back to their source if needed.

“Things like ScotEID for the recording of movement of animals and tracking of animals is obviously a lot more proficient and is utilised throughout the sector, and traceability so, ultimately, traceability is a lot more robust. So I do think the industry is quite well, well protected there in terms of being able to monitor situations should they arrive. And track where an animal has been or has come from”IP24

The IP24 implied that ScotEID throughout the sector had prepared the supply chain to handle potential challenges related to biosecurity, disease outbreaks, and food safety incidents. The strong traceability infrastructure allows for rapid responses to disruptions by enabling stakeholders to identify and contain risks associated with animal movement

5.2.33.1.2 Response Against Disease Outbreak

The IP24 identified the response against disease outbreaks as a resilient factor for the SBSC. IP 24 mentioned a recent case of BSE, which was detected and swiftly responded to. BBC News (2024) reported that a mad cow case was reported on a Scottish Farm and was identified, and movement restrictions were applied as per the prescribed procedures. The IP5 has also identified Response against disease outbreaks as a resilience contributor.

“So there was a recent case of BSE in Scotland. But we have very and that was quite a good test, I suppose, in terms of the reporting. Process that was put in place, but I think because of this reporting process and the mechanism that it triggered, it was able to be an isolated incident. That was very quickly responded to ” IP24

5.2.33.1.3 Government Support

The IP24 implied that Government support also contributes to a resilient SBSC. This was also identified by Yuan (2024) mentioned that government support plays an important role in the agricultural supply chain's resilience by allocating resources. The IP5 also mentioned that Government support has enabled the supply chain to survive.

IP24 is implied that investment and strong government policy support are critical factors in enhancing the resilience of the SBSC. The reference to grant programs suggests that targeted financial support enables industry stakeholders to make necessary investments in infrastructure, technology, and operational

improvements. These investments help to strengthen the entire supply chain, making it more capable of withstanding and adapting to challenges.

“ Grant program, and it just helps the industry too, I think investment is key across any industry but you know investment really does help to bolster the whole supply chain and which in turn just makes it more resilient ”IP24

“A lot of it will come from assurances through government policy that the industry is valued and it is going to be supported”IP24

5.2.33.1.4 Inherent Resilience

The IP24 implied that resilience is an inherent characteristic of the farming sector. Farmers constantly face external challenges such as unpredictable weather conditions and the effects of global economic and political events. The reference to the Russia-Ukraine war highlights how global crises can cause widespread disruptions, particularly by driving up input costs for essential resources like energy, animal feed, and fertilizers.

“I think you know farming by nature has to be a resilient Sector. You know, there's so many variables that are out of their control from the weather to the fact that things are so globalized now, you know the Ukraine invasion by Russia had such a ripple effect around the world and massive impacts on input costs. Across the whole sector, from energy to feed and fertiliser. But you know that the sector did manage to pull through, although it went through a very tough time ” IP24

Despite these significant challenges, IP24 emphasised that the farming sector demonstrated its ability to adapt and endure, even under severe pressure, showing the production system's inherent resilience.

5.2.33.2 Theme Challenges Faced by SBSC

The IP24 identified challenges which were familiar to the ones identified by the other Interview participants, for instance, Critical Mass, Lack of Succession, Lack of labour and skills shortages, low-profit Margin, processor consolidation, retailer dominance, ageing farmer population, poor infrastructure, price volatility, declining cattle numbers, propagation against red meat and uncertain government policies.

5.2.33.3 Overview of the IP24's Interview

The IP24 provided valuable insights into the SBSC's resilience and challenges. The IP 24 discussed the importance of collaboration and communication within the industry, highlighting the role of the Scottish Red Meat Resilience group in facilitating a unified voice and proactive approach to addressing challenges. The interview also touched upon key challenges faced by the Scottish beef industry, including structural imbalances, labour shortages, and misinformation about red meat. The IP24 emphasised the importance of

robust traceability systems and the role of digitization in enhancing the industry's ability to respond to potential disruptions.

The IP24 also highlighted the role of exports in the Scottish beef industry, noting the positive development of the export trade to Europe. The IP24 also discussed the role of assurance schemes in meeting high animal welfare standards and facilitating exports.

The interview with IP24 provided a comprehensive overview of the SBSC's resilience, emphasising the importance of traceability, government support, inherent resilience and reactive capabilities.

Figure 5.34 Challenges identified by policy managers

Figure 5.34 Challenges identified by illustrates the key challenges affecting the resilience of the SBSC as identified by industry experts working in animal health and welfare, traceability, industry development, public affairs and strategy, and market intelligence. The challenges are grouped into structural, operational, economic, environmental, and regulatory, and other contextual factors.

5.2.34 Member of Scottish Parliament (MSP) Interview Participant IP (25)

Interview Participant 25 is a Rural Affairs and Islands Committee member in the Scottish Parliament. This committee addresses issues related to rural land use, including forestry, farming, crofting, the food and

drink supply chain, animal welfare, wildlife crime, fisheries, aquaculture, and matters pertinent to Scotland's islands.

The IP25 provided comprehensive insights into the SBSC's current challenges and resilience. The initial coding done from the interview transcript is shown in the figure below. The identified code, interview transcript, and recorded video interview were repeatedly seen to develop and refine the themes and their constituents.

Figure 5.35 Initial Coding of Interview Transcript in NVivo IP25

5.2.34.1 Theme Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC

The IP25 highlighted that adaptability and inherent resilience contribute to a resilient SBSC.

5.2.34.1.1 Adaptability

Stone and Rahimifard (2018) identified adaptability as a core intra-supply chain resilience contributor in the agrifood supply chains. The IP25 also identified adaptability as a contributor to the supply chain resilience of the SBSC. Adaptability is also identified by the IP14 representing the processing sector.

“I think resilience is there because they've had to be resilient. But I think that we're at that kind of moment in time where it's going to go one way or the other way, isn't it? So they've they've weathered Brexit as well as they could. They've been weathering the storm of the cost increases in the pressures. Now they're weathering the storm of new legislation and in new demands that are on them in terms of, you know, how do they become regenerative farmers” IP25

However, IP25 mentioned that the industry's ability to continue adapting is at a critical point, especially with the added demands to transition toward regenerative farming.

5.2.34.1.2 Inherent Resilience

The IP25 implied that the SBSC derives significant strength from the deeply rooted cultural commitment and personal dedication of its farming community. The statement highlights that for Scottish farmers, farming is not merely a profession but a way of life a vocation ingrained in their identity and culture. Their dedication to maintaining livestock farming as a tradition across generations creates a natural buffer against external shocks, ensuring the continuity of production even in difficult circumstances which implies inherent resilience in the SBSC from the livestock farmer's end.

“I think you have a real dedication and a real belief in the farming community about their their their culture. It's it's not just about an occupation, it's a culture. If you're far, if you farm, that's a vocation that's something that's part of you. Your whole, you know being. It's not just a job, so I think in essence there are Hardy bunch of people who work in the sector and I think it's a premium product that the sector offers. So those those two things combined are what help to keep it going” IP25

5.2.34.1.3 Theme Challenges faced by the SBSC

The IP 25 identified various challenges impacting the SBSC's resilience. The common challenges also identified by the other Interview participants included the ageing farming population, the rising cost of inputs, changing consumer preferences, poor infrastructure, lack of Veterinary Services, and skill shortages. One of the key challenges is discussed below, wherein the IP25 implied that the supply chain is not very resilient.

5.2.34.1.4 Lack of Financial Strength

The IP25 implies that the SBSC lacks sufficient financial strength, making the entire sector vulnerable to disruptions. The concern is that financial constraints are not limited to consumers but are widespread across the whole supply chain, from farmers, transporters, and auctioneers to other key stakeholders. This widespread lack of financial resources limits the ability of these actors to invest in improvements, adapt to challenges, or absorb economic shocks.

“I'm not convinced that we have a very resilient you know sector at all. And I don't know how. I don't know how we reinforce in to the supply chain more resilience because people's pockets are not deep and that's not just a consumer That's the entire supply chain. So you know, that's from the farmer right through to those that are hauling it through to, you know to the market, to the auctioneers, to everybody along” IP25

The IP25 implied that the financial constraints restrict the stakeholder's capability to invest in infrastructure and sustainable practices.

5.2.34.1.5 Overview of the IP25's interview

Apart from discussing the challenges and resilience enablers of SBSC, the IP25 also highlighted other aspects of the Scottish beef industry. The IP 25 discussed that the rural affairs and Island's committee ensure that the perspective of all stakeholders of the SBSC is given due consideration while scrutinising the proposed policies and legislations. The IP25 mentioned that the ARIOB (Agricultural Reform Implementation Oversight Board) plays a critical role in shaping and guiding the future of Scottish agriculture. ARIOB serves as a platform where farmer-led groups collaborate with key stakeholders across the industry, including meat processors, abattoir operators, and auctioneers, to oversee how the government implements its broader agricultural vision. This structure ensures that those directly involved in the agricultural sector have a meaningful voice in influencing and monitoring policy decisions that impact their operations. The IP25 also mentioned a lack of collaboration between parliamentary committees. While the Rural and Islands Committee focuses on agriculture-specific legislation, many policies under the jurisdiction of other committees, such as the Net Zero Committee, have direct implications for agriculture and rural communities. The IP25 pointed out that the lack of communication between committees can result in disconnected policymaking, where important cross-sectoral issues such as climate change policies, land reform, and the Good Food Nation Bill are not fully aligned with agricultural policies. By suggesting that committees need to work together more effectively, the IP25 emphasises the importance of a holistic approach to policymaking. The IP 25 proposed that the supermarkets should play their part by funding education and skills development projects to attract young people to join the agricultural sector.

5.3 Main Themes

Two overarching themes emerged from the data analysis as shown in Table 5.7. The first concerns the factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC, which were explored consistently across all stakeholder groups. The second overarching theme relates to the challenges impacting the SBSC and was also discussed extensively by all participants, indicating a shared recognition of the structural, economic, and institutional challenges affecting the supply chain.

Themes	Stakeholder Group										
	Academia (02)	Industry Advisor (01)	Cattle Society Official (01)	Livestock Farmers (07)	Auctioneers (02)	Processors (03)	Retailers (02)	Policy Managers / (04)	Executive Traceability Organisation (01)	Head of Industry Development (01)	Member of Scottish Parliament (01)
Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the SBSC	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Challenges Faced by the SBSC	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Future Resilience	x										
Recent Disruptions	x										
General Issues Related to SBSC		x		x							
Technology Adoption and Digital Transformation				x							
Traceability and Labelling Complexity				x							
Impact of Subsidy Scheme on Efficiency and Profitability				x							
Industry Development			x								
Knowledge Exchange and Efficiency Improvement				x							

Table 5.7 Key themes generated in the dataset

5.3.1 Main Theme 1 Factors Contributing to the Resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

The factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC were identified by the Interview participants and were analysed by the researcher. The capability factors identified by the stakeholders are shown in the table below.

Supply Chain Resilience Capability Factors	Academia (IP1,IP2)	Industry Consultnat (IP3)	Industry Expert Cattle Society (IP4)	Livestock Farmers (IP.5,6,7,8,9,10, 11)	Processors(I P12,13,14)	Auctioneers (IP 15,16)	Retailers (IP17,IP18)	Policy Managers (IP19,20)	Industry Practioner Traceability Organisaiont (IP21)	Market Intelligence Manager (IP22)	Head of Industry dev. IP23	Public Affairs & Ind.Str. (IP24)	Member SNP (IP25)
Traceability (IP3,IP6,IP7,IP10,IP14,IP15,IP16,IP17,IP21,IP22,IP23,IP24)		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Supplier Relationships (IP3,IP13,IP17,IP18,23)		✓			✓		✓				✓		
Supplier Selection (IP8,IP10,IP17)				✓			✓						
Supply base Diversity (IP10,IP13) Sourcing Flex.(IP17)				✓	✓		✓						
Government Support (IP5,IP6,IP9,IP12,IP19,IP22,IP24)				✓	✓			✓				✓	
Inherent Resilience (IP7,IP15) (IP18) (IP22) (IP23) (IP24) (IP25)				✓		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
Transparency (IP15, IP16,IP19,IP21)						✓		✓	✓				
Stakeholder Collaboration (IP7,IP9,19)				✓				✓					
Contingency Planning (IP11) (IP17)				✓			✓						
Risk Mitigation (IP5) -RM Culture (IP14)-RM(IP17)				✓	✓		✓	✓					
Redundancy (IP5,IP8)				✓									
Logistical Capabilities (IP 13,17)					✓		✓						
Brand Strength (IP4,IP7) / Market Position (IP19)(IP22)			✓	✓				✓					
Provenance (IP1,IP17)	✓						✓						
Artificial Insemination (IP4,IP7)			✓	✓									
Reponse Against Disease outbreak (IP5) (IP24)				✓								✓	
Trust (IP5,IP8)				✓									
Information Sharing (IP8)				✓									
Integrated Business Model (IP3)		✓											
Operational Efficiency (IP10)				✓									
Operational Flexibility (IP10,IP13)				✓	✓								
Operational Diversity (IP10)				✓									
Adaptability (IP14) (IP25)					✓								✓
Product Quality (IP4)			✓										
Psychological Resilience (IP5)				✓									
Supplychain Understanding (IP13)					✓								
Supplychain Leadership (IP12)					✓								
Supplychain Intelligence (IP12)					✓								
Income Diversity (IP2)	✓												
Supply Chain Integration (IP18)							✓						
Big Data Analytics (IP21)									✓				
Production Systems (IP1)	✓												
Resilience to Market Volatility (IP1)	✓												

Table 5.8 Supply Chain Resilience Capability factors

The Key capability factors identified by the Interview participants were scrutinized by using the Dynamic Capabilities view and were classified into proactive and reactive capability factors.

Figure 5.36 Key Factors contributing to Scottish Beef Supply Chain Resilience

5.3.1.1 Traceability

The traceability factor is the key resilience capability factor in the SBSC. From livestock farmers to the retailer, a robust traceability system is present. The Scottish Government has provided tools like Myherd Stat, which livestock farmers can use for herd management and recording mandatory movements. The Auction Marts also have a traceability system wherein they record the details of animals which will be presented in the live ring. The Abattoir and processing plants also have traceability systems and label the carcasses for traceability. The retailers also have placed a DNA sampling to ensure the source of their cattle. This traceability throughout the supply chain has protected the supply chain against any food fraud, disease detection and added to increased customer confidence. Along side the digital monitoring of the Cattle the QMS assurance scheme has also added to traceability.

Traceability is best classified as a Proactive Capability under the Readiness Phase. This is because it ensures full supply chain visibility, enabling the early identification and prevention of potential risks such as contamination or disease outbreaks. Interview Participant (IP) 17 emphasised that their vertically integrated supply chain ensures traceability from farm to processing and back to the supplier:

“So ... unique vertically integrated supply.....very good traceability in terms of obviously back to the supply that we purchased it from and got the processing side of which we have sophisticated systems within the factory which allow obviously the carcasses to be traced throughout the whole system back to the kill batch and then obviously back to the supply themselves”

The Institute of Auctioneers and appraisers Executive also mentioned traceability

“Umm, that is probably in terms of the resilience element of this is one of the one of the outside of the trade that for the industry the use of auction markets is probably one of the key areas is actually the traceability element is knowing where animals are and where they have been in that they are properly recorded” IP15

One of the processors also indicated that traceability is strictly observed.

“So we ensure every carcass is obviously traceable. It's got a ticket on it for traceability as soon as that carcass is split into four, it's got a ticket on it, traceable. And then as soon as that's bone out, it's labeled in the Box so each Backpack of meat can be traced back to the animal it was produced from”IP14

This proactive system ensures compliance with safety and quality standards, preventing disruptions and aligning with the readiness phase. Zhao et al., (2022) established the links between traceability as a resilient capability factor in an agrifood supply chain by mitigating supply, demand, and environmental and biological risks IP15 highlighted its importance in the event of a disease outbreak

"Auction markets are actually pretty critical in knowing where animals are and where they've gone, particularly for a disease outbreak” IP15

The supplier relationship is also a capability factor. This factor enables the resilience for the entire supply chain. The livestock farmers, processors and retailers have equally emphasised on the importance of supplier relationships. Supplier Relationships also fall under the Proactive Capability category within the Readiness Phase. Strong relationships foster trust and collaboration, reducing supply risks. IP17 who is retailer mentioned the direct engagement with suppliers:

"We own the direct relationship with our supply base.. the dedicated Scottish team manage that relationship”

The IP13 who is a processor also mentioned their relationship with the supplier

“We've got a a large number of very, very good livestock farms and I've dealt with them for 30 years. My father dealt with their fathers for 30 years and my grandfather dealt with their grandfathers” IP13

“You know, we've got suppliers who have been, they've been farming cattle for the last 30-40 years” IP13

This proactive engagement allows for greater flexibility and adaptability, ensuring supply continuity and supporting proactive risk management. Leat and Giha (2013) identified the importance of supplier relationships in the resilience of pork supply chain in Scotland.

5.3.1.2 Inherent Resilience

Inherent resilience is identified as proactive resilience capability in the SBSC. It is exercised at the livestock farming stage. Participants consistently highlighted Scotland's natural suitability for livestock farming as a key source of this inherent resilience. Umar and Wilson (2024) discussed inherent resilience as the ability of food supply chains to withstand disruptions through pre-existing structures, resources, and relationships. IP7 highlighted the alignment between land use suitability, livestock production practices, and accumulated expertise as sources of inherent resilience.

“We have a land use suited to growing cattle or growing red meat outdoor grazing and things like that and we've had historically have the skills for rearing and they have genetic improvement of our livestock” (IP7).

The role of climate and forage-based feeding systems further reinforces this argument. IP15 explicitly linked Scotland's temperate climate to resilience through reduced dependence on external inputs:

“I think the fact that although we complain about extreme weather, the reality is we still are in our relatively temperate climate We still have a very forage-based diet and for cattle and in Scotland and I think that gives us a good bit of Resilience” IP15

Similarly, IP18 highlighted that Scotland's climate, topography, and geography collectively provide a comparative advantage for livestock production.

“So I think that that's a a strong vein which runs through the industry for Scotland, the climate, the topography, the geography all lend themselves to Livestock raising probably to a larger extent than than arable farming. So I think that's an aspect of it which is also important” IP18

A further dimension of inherent resilience identified in the findings relates to the continuous biological production cycle of livestock farming. IP23 contrasted livestock systems with manufacturing industries

“It's a relatively resilient industry. One of the things that we know is that we sort of remind ourselves is that there is a constant production cycle here. It's not like they can, you know, it's not like a factory where production can cease for a couple of years, or it could be mothballed generally farms have livestock, they produce young stock, so one of the things that that does tend to provide a bit of stability is that there are always that next crop of animals coming through” IP23

In addition to environmental and biological factors, the findings highlight the importance of intergenerational skills and accumulated farming knowledge.

“We've got the land, we've got the generations of skills” IP22

“we're thinking of that in Scotland, though we're not going to have major droughts. It doesn't seem like going forward, whereas other parts of the world may have much more volatile, volatile climates, and it's going to restrict their ability to produce silver. Yeah, we're going to be a great place to produce it” IP22

Cultural commitment also emerged as a significant contributor to inherent resilience. IP25 described farming as a vocation embedded in identity rather than a purely economic activity:

“I think you have a real dedication and a real belief in the farming community about their culture. It's not just about an occupation, it's a culture. If you're far, if you farm, that's a vocation that's something that's part of you. Your whole, you know being. It's not just a job, so I think in essence there are Hardy bunch of people who work in the sector and I think it's a premium product that the sector offers. So those those two things combined are what help to keep it going” IP25

The IP24 implied that resilience is an inherent characteristic of the farming sector. Farmers constantly face external challenges such as unpredictable weather conditions and the effects of global economic and political events. The reference to the Russia-Ukraine war highlights how global crises can cause widespread disruptions, particularly by driving up input costs for essential resources like energy, animal feed, and fertilizers.

“I think you know farming by nature has to be a resilient Sector. You know, there's so many variables that are out of their control from the weather to the fact that things are so globalized now, you know the Ukraine invasion by Russia had such a ripple effect around the world and massive impacts on input costs. Across the whole sector, from energy to feed and fertiliser. But you know that the sector did manage to pull through, although it went through a very tough time” IP24

Overall, the findings demonstrate that inherent resilience in the SBSC operates as a proactive capability embedded within livestock farming systems, shaped by natural conditions, biological continuity, accumulated skills, and cultural commitment.

5.3.1.3 Supplier Selection

Supplier Selection is another capability factor, and it is classified as a proactive supply chain resilience capability factor. This capability factor is also classified as proactive supply chain resilience capability

factor by Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015). In SBSC the livestock finishers, processors and retailers emphasised on supplier selection. Supplier Selection is in the Readiness Phase, ensuring that suppliers meet specific quality and safety standards. IP10 highlighted their strict selection criteria:

"We would never buy cattle from someone who doesn't have farm assurance.. all our cattle are definitely assured" IP10. Another livestock farmer also mentioned the supplier selection criteria for buying cattle.

"On that regard, we sometimes go to the auction, but I would far I would far rather work with a farmer or farm within I can go and see the animals and the system that they're bringing them up and then I can see if those animals are going to suit my system and I get to see the health status, everything like that" IP8

This rigorous supplier vetting helps mitigate potential supply disruptions by having visibility over your supplier system.

5.3.1.4 Supply Base Diversity

Supply Base diversity is also identified as a proactive capability factor. Pettit et al., (2013) identified sourcing in flexibility as a resilience capability factor. Supply Base Diversity also fits within the Readiness Phase as a Proactive Capability. By diversifying sourcing channels, the supply chain reduces dependency on any single supplier. IP10 explained:

"We probably we totallyso 25% from auction markets, 20% from Livestock, agents, so they come straight from a farm farm to farm, but they are sold by an agent and 50 to 60% direct from farm from we have relationships with producers" IP10

One of the retailers also mentioned that they have supply diversity and have initiated a scheme to meet the demands of beef to avoid any interruption in the supply.

"We actually have an integrated beef scheme which we operate. Its called Elite beef scheme. You know, we so this is a sorry, it's a dairy beef scheme that we operate and I think ultimately how we can give longevity to our supply base by utilising it and growing that arm of the business. I think will only help to bolster the supply chain as a whole" IP17

This diversification enhances resilience by minimizing the impact of supply disruptions.

5.3.1.5 Transparency

Transparency is also a capability factor for the SBSC. The Auction Marts in the SBSC enable this factor. Transparency ensures fair pricing in the SBSC. This can be assessed from the retailer's extract that auction marts inform the retailers' pricing decisions.

“So auction marts obviously auction marts will drive pricing in regional areas, which will obviously fluctuate and then inform our purchasing price. Sort of akin to that as well” IP17

Transparency in auction markets was emphasised by IP19 as well

“Live ring is really important.. it's the only platform where we see complete transparency” IP19

This fosters trust and fair market practices but also aids response efforts when disruptions occur. Yuan (2024) transparency as one of supply chain resilience enabler in an agri supply chain.

5.3.1.6 Contingency Planning

Contingency Planning is also identified as a capability factor. It is classified as a reactive capability factor. It is also categorised as a reactive capability factor by Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015). The livestock farmers due to lack of financial resources and sophistication are not engaged in contingency planning. This is highlighted in the below mentioned comment from IP23.

“I think, yeah, farmers adopting risk management strategies is not necessarily what you would think of as a formalized risk management statute, Process .I suppose the most common way people will do that is by having someone as backup for farm labourer, farm tasks, or someone who can help with administration on a backup basis and not necessarily contingency planning as you would call it. But yeah, I think there's a big role for that and I think it's an industry wide issue that we need to be dealing with” IP23

The processors and the retailers have the resources to perform the Contingency planning as highlighted in the comment below

“I think in terms of sudden disruptions, I think because we are, it's not one single abattoir. So because it is one of three, we can work between our full processing plant chain to understand obviously if there are any sudden disruptions we can flatten that out by utilising other processing plants within in food group” IP17

The Contingency Planning done by the Scottish Government against disease outbreak is also important because it provides a standby procedure to follow to respond to a disease outbreak as mentioned by IP11.

“the contingency planning and the structures of that go around that you know I suppose determine your preparedness and I think that you Scotland is quite lucky they've got the EPIC group which is a consortium of institutions and universities with the expertise and not only epidemiology and disease, but in economics as well and that group you'll gives advice to ministers and to the CVO (Chief Veterinary officer) on on your modifying or your thing You're changing the to approach Disease Control could actually model it and and

I suppose to determine its value in cost benefit terms as well. So as well as Disease Control terms. So I think in some ways Scotland is quite well prepared” IP11

5.3.1.7 Risk Mitigation

Risk mitigation also contributes to the resilience of the SBSC again it is not actively exercised by the livestock farmers due to resource constraints but the processors and retailers have the financial resources to exercise it. This is highlighted in the comment below

“What I would also say so for disease preparedness. So, we’ll assess it by processing site basis…… we would put together a site plan for that disease, understand any risk, understand any changes to procedures that need to be made…… then we would change from pre designation status to designated status and then we can operate as normal under those circumstances” IP17

The processor with integrated farming operations also highlighted their risk mitigation approach.

“What I would also say so for disease preparedness. So, we’ll assess it by processing site basis…… we would put together a site plan for that disease, understand any risk, understand any changes to procedures that need to be made…… then we would change from pre designation status to designated status and then we can operate as normal under those circumstances” IP17

Ali, Mahfouz, and Arisha (2017) mentioned risk avoidance, containment, and risk control/transfer/share under situation awareness and categorised them as proactive capability factors. This research also classified risk mitigation as a proactive capability factor based on its preparedness against a disruption.

5.3.1.8 Market Position

Pettit et al., (2013) identified Market position as a supply chain resilience capability factor. For the SBSC, it is also recognised as a proactive capability factor, and it tends to avoid supplier and customer-related disruptions. This capability factor also contributes to the SBSC's resilience.

“Scotch beef is a premium product, produced to very high standards, some of which are the best in the world” IP19

“Scotland is seen to be synonymous with a quality aspect in beef worldwide” IP4

“But it's just a great brand worldwide. Like that's if any. If you ask anyone in the world, you know Scott. What Scotland, famous for its famous for probably its beef and its Whiskey so” IP14

“But essentially, and the resilience of supply chain I, I suppose it's historic reputation and strength of the brand” IP7

Therefore, Market Position acts as a Proactive Capability in the Readiness Phase. This market differentiation builds brand strength and customer loyalty, preventing demand-side disruptions.

5.3.1.9 Logistical Capabilities

Logistical Capabilities are considered Reactive Capabilities during the Response Phase. They ensure supply continuity during disruptions by adapting transportation and distribution strategies. It is also evident that the processors and retailers have the financial means to build the logistical capabilities. The following extracts indicate the logistical capabilities of the processors and retailers.

“We do outsource deliveries to Shetland, we take a pallet to Aberdeen and then check the transport, take it on to Shetland” IP13

“But in terms of getting product to market, we have sufficient spare vehicles, all the struggle for drivers, but we've got sufficient vehicles to cover our delivery network with reserves and vehicles back at Depot for loading up for the next day” IP13

Ponomarov & Holcomb (2009) proposed that integrated logistical capabilities lead to a resilient supply chain.

“So we have our fleet of transport, so we have our own livestock haulage vehicles and so we don't see ripple effects from any transport problems or any strikes, etcetera, So I think that's probably all of the disruptions sort of in a nutshell, I'd say”. IP17

5.3.1.10 Redundancy

Redundancy falls under the Recovery Phase as a Reactive Capability. Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015) also classified it as a reactive capability. The IP5 explained how embryo preservation supports recovery after significant disruptions:

“We have put a lot of embryos into long-term storage. If we get an outbreak of disease, it won't take us long to rebuild the same genetic basis we have now” IP5

Another participant discussed about the buffer stock to respond to any supply disruptions.

“And so regards like disruption in the supply chain, like you know, fertilizer 2 years ago went from 250 pounds a ton to 750 pounds a ton. You know, to a certain extent we'll forward by fertilizer six months in advance of when we actually need it. So we'll take home. We'll be bringing home fertiliser, probably in September” IP8

5.3.1.11 Government Support

Government support is classified as a reactive capability factor in the response and recovery phase. The Scottish Government's financial support, such as the Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme (SSBSS), helps farmers recover from financial losses. The interview extract shows that the government support in the form of subsidies and grants adds to the resilience of the SBSC.

“The EU and the way the support payments were made were was covering up a lot of inefficiency. IP5

The Suckler Support Scheme get a payment for the calve certainly helped in recent years to keep cow number high up in the would have been otherwise” IP6

“we always found that it was that without agricultural subsidies, the farmers were making a loss” IP22

“Grant program and it just helps the industry to I think investment is key across any industry but you know investment really does help to bolster the whole supply chain and which in turn just makes it more resilient rather than just hanging on in there from” IP24

5.3.2 Application of DCV in the exploration of capability factors

Teece et al., (1997) proposed that the processes and position of a firm are a composition of its competencies and capabilities. They further elaborated that the competitive advantage of a firm is due to its managerial and organisational processes, which are shaped by its coordination / integration, its asset position and the paths available to it.

Table 5.9 shows the application of DCV in the exploration of capability factors for the resilience of the SBSC.

Resilience Capability Factor	Primary SBSC Actors	Processes / Routines	Positions / Assets	Paths
Inherent Resilience	Farmers	Adapting production to natural landscapes; utilizing generational farming knowledge.	Complementary Assets : Scottish temperate climate/topography. Generational expertise.	Evolutionary: Long-term historical adaptation to the Scottish environment.

Traceability	Farmers, Auction Marts, Processors, Retailers	Mandatory digital recording and reporting of cattle movements via web portals.	Institutional: ScotEID portal. Technological: Tracking software and DNA sampling.	Regulatory: A mandatory compliance path set by the government.
Supplier Relationship	Farmers, Processors, Retailers	Long-term trust-building and horizontal/vertical collaboration.	Reputational: Farm/Brand standing. Intangible: Social capital and trust.	Evolutionary: Developing stable, long-standing partnership routes.
Supplier Selection	Farmers, Processors, Retailers	Systematic evaluation routines based on quality, suitability, and accreditation.	Structural: Established supply networks. Reputational: Accreditation status.	Evolutionary: Selecting partners based on historical performance.
Supply Base Diversity	Retailers, Farmers	Multi-channel procurement routines (Dairy-beef, auction markets, agents).	Financial: Capital reserves. Structural: Access to diverse sourcing hubs.	Evolutionary: Strategic shift toward procurement flexibility.
Transparency	Auction Marts	Real-time price discovery and data disclosure during public sales.	Structural: The physical auction platform. Intangible: Market openness and trust.	Equifinality: Achieving transparency via different actor roles and starting points.
Risk Mitigation	Processors, Retailers	Iterative identification and buffering against market/disease shocks.	Financial & Technological: Modern infrastructure and financial reserves.	Evolutionary: Adaptive refinement of tactics from past crises.
Market Position	Retailers, Processors, Farmers	Premium branding and rigorous quality assurance routines.	Reputational: "Scotch Beef" brand equity.	Evolutionary: Maintaining a high-value niche market path.
Contingency Planning	Farmers, Processors, Retailers	"What-if" modeling and the preservation of genetic assets (embryos).	Structural: Embryo storage. Technological: Data backups.	Evolutionary: Learning from historical disruptions to refine readiness.

Logistical Capabilities	Processors, Retailers	Asset orchestration for the efficient movement of livestock and meat.	Financial: In-house transport fleets. Institutional: Public infrastructure.	Evolutionary: Continuous optimization of transport and load routes.
Government Support	Farmers	Administrative management of state aid and policy compliance.	Institutional: Agricultural subsidies (SSBSS, LFASS) and grants.	Evolutionary: Dependency on evolving post-Brexit policy landscapes.
Redundancy	Farmers, Processors	Managing intentional "slack" and physical capacity buffers.	Financial & Structural: Capital assets and excess capacity.	Evolutionary: Deliberate path of safety buffers over "lean" models.

Table 5.9 Application of DCV

Inherent resilience is a capability factor, and the process and routines are the use of the natural landscape for the cattle production and rearing and the use of generational farming knowledge in cattle production. The assets are the Scottish temperate climate and topography suitable for cattle farming. Tacit knowledge is also an asset (Vidic, 2022).

Traceability is contributed by the key SBSC players farmers, auction marts, processors and retailers. The traceability processes and routines comprise of the mandatory digital reporting and recording of cattle movements via web portals. The assets used are the institutional assets for instance the ScotEID portal. The other assets used are the technological and financial assets of the supply chain players. Livestock keepers, marts and abattoirs can check, record and refine the information for all their livestock on the system, using their own secure log-in details (ScotEID, 2025). All farm holdings, marts and abattoirs have an individual CPH (County Parish Holding) number. The identity of each animal being moved from one CPH to another, or through a mart or to an abattoir, is recorded into the ScotMoves+ system (The Scottish Government, 2025). The retailers are using DNA sampling to trace the origin of the meat back to each individual farm and the animal (M&S, 2024).

Supplier relationship as a capability factor is contributed by all key SBSC players. The processes and routines are the long-term trust building and collaboration. The assets used are the reputational assets of the farm / brand and Intangible relational asset of trust and the financial assets for supplier development. ALDI pledged a £3 billion investment into the domestic beef industry over five years to strengthen supply chain stability. This initiative includes a £260 million partnership with Kepak specifically to expand and enhance

their premium Aberdeen Angus beef range (ALDI, 2024). The path adopted is evolutionary which is aimed to develop stable long term partnership routes.

Supplier selection is contributed by the farmers, processors and retailers. The processes and routines are systematic evaluation routines based on quality, suitability and accreditation. The assets are established supply networks and the reputational assets in the form of QMS assurance scheme in procurement decisions. The QMS has introduced whole chain assurance schemes to ensure highest standards of production, animal welfare and wellbeing and to deliver a quality eating experience (QMS, 2025).

Supply Base diversity is a capability factor contributed by the farmers, retailers and processors. The processes and routines are the multi-channel procurement sources such as dairy beef markets, direct farm sourcing, use of livestock agents/marts to avoid dependence on a single source. The retailers are relying on the integrated beef schemes from dairy herds (Gamechanger, 2023). The assets are financial and structural, and the path taken is evolutionary showing a strategic shift towards procurement flexibility.

Eisenhardt and Martin (2000) advanced the DCV by proposing equifinality which means that the capability development can have any starting point and can take unique paths. This is evident from table 5.9 that transparency in the SBSC is introduced by the auction marts and the auction marts are not the origin of the SBSC. The process and routines are the real time price discovery and data disclosure during the public sales. The assets are structural and Intangible openness and trust. The Institute of Auctioneers and Appraisers in Scotland (IAAS) advocates for the livestock auction system as the premier transparent mechanism for achieving optimal pricing and ensuring financial security for all participants within the rural economy (IAAS, 2025).

Risk mitigation as a capability factor is primarily driven by processors and retailers. The processes and routines involve iterative identification and buffering against market and disease-related shocks. These mitigation actions are notably uneven across the supply chain, as farm-level mitigation is frequently limited by financial constraints. The assets utilized are financial and technological, encompassing modern infrastructure and capital reserves. The adopted path is evolutionary, characterized by the adaptive refinement of tactics derived from learning from past crises. By learning from the catastrophic 2001 Foot and Mouth outbreak which cost the public and private sectors over £8 billion due to inefficient paper-based systems the SBSC has modernized through the ScotEID initiative ScotEID (2025).

The following interview extract from a retailer shows their financial strength to engage in risk management and contingency planning.

“What I would also say so for disease preparedness. So, we'll assess it by processing site basis..... we would put together a site plan for that disease, understand any risk, understand any changes to procedures that need to be made..... then we would change from pre designation status to designated status and then we can operate as normal under those circumstances” IP17.

These practices have been refined through learning from past crises, reinforcing the evolutionary and experience-based nature of resilience capability development.

Market position is a capability factor contributed by farmers, processors, and retailers. The processes and routines centre on premium branding and the implementation of rigorous quality assurance protocols. Scotch Beef is distinguished by its Geographical Indication (GI) status, which serves as an official assurance of superior quality. This designation confirms that the products strictly adhere to rigorous standards, certifying an authentic connection between the unique natural environment and the traditional agricultural heritage of their specific country of origin (Scotch Beef, 2025). The primary asset is the reputational "Scotch Beef" brand equity, which serves as a critical intangible asset in the marketplace. This follows an evolutionary path aimed at maintaining a high-value niche market trajectory.

Contingency planning involves contributions from farmers, processors, and retailers. The processes and routines are multi-faceted, including the preservation of genetic assets, such as embryos, to safeguard future production. One farmer (IP5) noted regarding the sensing and subsequent transformation of genetic assets as *“We have put a lot of embryos into long-term storage. If we get an outbreak of disease, it won't take us long to rebuild the same genetic basis we have now”*. Other routines include maintaining multiple processing sites and adhering to government-mandated contingency plans against disease outbreaks. The assets utilized are diverse, spanning financial, structural, technological, and institutional categories. The paths taken are both evolutionary, through learning from historical disruptions, and regulatory, particularly regarding mandatory movement restrictions.

Logistical capabilities are established as a resilience factor by processors and retailers. The processes and routines consist of operational practices that enable the efficient movement and coordination of livestock and finished meat products. These are supported by financial assets, such as in-house transport fleets, and institutional assets like public infrastructure. One processor (IP17) highlighted the value of this asset position: *“So we have our fleet of transport..... so we don't see ripple effects from any transport problems or any strikes”*. Another (IP13) reinforced this, noting they have *“sufficient spare vehicles.... to cover our delivery network with reserves”*. The evolutionary path involves the continuous optimization of transport and load routes.

Government support is a capability factor specifically relevant to farmers. The processes and routines which involve the administrative management of, and compliance with, institutional support mechanisms such as subsidies and policy-linked grants. Essential financial assistance is delivered to farmers through the Less Favoured Areas Support Scheme (LFASS) and the Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme (SSBSS) (Hall, 2024). The assets are institutional, primarily agricultural subsidies like the SSBSS and LFASS. The path is characterized as both evolutionary, due to dependency on the changing post-Brexit policy landscape, and regulatory, concerning mandatory compliance for support eligibility.

Redundancy is a capability factor maintained by farmers and processors. The processes and routines involve maintaining buffers or alternative operational methods to absorb the impact of disruptions. The interview extract reflects the use of buffer stock. A livestock farmer mentioned that *“and so regards like disruption in the supply chain, like you know, fertilizer 2 years ago went from 250 pounds a ton to 750 pounds a ton. You know, to a certain extent we'll forward buy fertilizer six months in advance of when we need it. So we'll take home. We'll be bringing home fertiliser, probably in September. That won't be used until next spring, purely as a way I can have just hedge in a little bit”* IP8

The assets are both financial and structural, including capital assets and excess operational capacity. This resilience factor follows an evolutionary path, as it is built over time through strategic investment decisions and deliberate operational design.

The application of the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV) is evident from the table 5.9 and it shows how the key players in the SBSC utilize the Processes, Positions, and Paths to contribute to the resilience of the SBSC. The ability to integrate external competences can be witnessed by the SBSC players to utilize the government's institutional assets, specifically the ScotEID portal, to coordinate movements. The ability to build internal competences is evidenced by Inherent Resilience, where generational expertise and landscape adaptation are cultivated over time to form a foundational asset. Finally, the ability to reconfigure is demonstrated through the flexible procurement routines and physical capacity buffers to absorb disruption impacts and sustain operations.

5.4 Main Theme 2 Challenges faced by the SBSC

The second main theme, Challenges faced by the SBSC, was developed by identifying areas of convergence across all stakeholder groups. Following the initial coding of each interview, similar challenge-related codes repeatedly emerged. These recurring codes were examined comparatively and grouped around a central organising concept. The codes were then clustered into categories based on their conceptual similarity, resulting in six analytically distinct dimensions: economic, structural, operational, technological, environmental and regulatory, and other contextual challenges.

Figure 5.37 Challenges face by SBSC

Figure 5.38 Challenges faced by the SBSC

The key challenge faced by the SBSC is the economic challenge specifically the lack of financial returns. The livestock farmers are the most affected by this challenge. This challenge impacts the resilience of livestock farmers by limiting their ability to prepare against disease outbreaks and their ability to diversify their income stream to enhance their recovery capability against potential disruption. The interview participants highlighted this challenge as

“the biggest threat we have is lack of financial return” IP3

“And so that long term unprofitability is probably the main challenge” IP2

“there's a number of reasons that they are dispersing, the first thing is simply they don't believe the economics are adding up for what return they're getting from the market. It's not equating to what costs are involved” IP3

“What's happening in Scotland is the returns and in supply chain there's a lot of folk getting out, but actually commissioned at work with QMS, which we're just going to hopefully be into discussions with in the next week” IP5

“one of the biggest issues I see in the industry is the lack of returns, lack of margin” IP5

Apart from the livestock farmers, the processors are also facing the challenge of lack of returns. Only the big processors have the financial resilience to survive as part of big groups.

“processes themselves operate on very thin margins and obviously price fluctuates and often if farmers are getting good price for their cattle, it means processes probably aren't making much money and vice versa” IP24

“I think farmers would like to think that they always uh are the ones that have the hardest deal but you know and it's hard to you know. But in reality abattoir the the abattoir sector is often under extraordinary economic pressure” IP11

“So for instance, some of the biggest abattoirs in Scotland are Irish owned. They've got, you know, processing here in Scotland, processing elsewhere in the UK, processing facilities in Ireland and some sometimes and other places in the world, so that gives them a degree of financial resilience and they're they also have resilience in the sense of that they've got that expertise from being part of a bigger group” IP12

Due to the lack of return, the supply chain resilience is impacted because the small abattoirs are not surviving.

“So it's more abattoirs haven't got more of a chance of surviving. We've lost most of them, but you don't want to lose anymore” IP11

The retail sector is not suffering from the lack of returns as mentioned by the Interview Participant.

But ultimately the big retailers can dictate the price. And they are always making a profit IP24

The key structural challenge faced by the SBSC is poor infrastructure which is impacting the resilience of the SBSC. For stance, this challenge restricts the responding capability of a supply chain in case of a disruption caused by a disease outbreak and the movement restriction is introduced and you do not have a abattoir in your local area.

“However, there's always an argument that if we ever got foot and mouth again, it's good to have local, so you don't have to travel too far” IP3

“I think in terms of infrastructure; I think that is under threat. You know auction marts are closing. Small processes have been closing” IP24

“processing facilities is a real problem for us, you know, and generally, yes, that infrastructure that we have that we need and yeah, we need more abattoirs ideally, but unfortunately you know a lot of the regulations that abattoirs have to abide by, bring a lot of extra costs and they are not popular in local areas” IP20

Another component of structural imbalance is retailer dominance which is impacting the SBSC. The retailers are the strongest players in the market, and they dictate the market prices. The transparency exercised through auction marts is limited because most cattle is not traded through the auction markets. Therefore the farmers and processors have to negotiate for a price with the retailer which is rather dictated by the Super market. This dominance of the retailers squeeze the profit margin and that leads to lack of financial strength to better prepare, respond and recover from disruptions.

“then you've got the Supermarket that they'll be in probably quite severe with some of the negotiations, so the the farmer really is very vulnerable” IP6

“without a doubt, first thing that pops to mind is supermarket pressure.OK.Supermarkets dictate umm price.They dictate where they get their products from”IP1

“But ultimately the big retailers can dictate the price. And they are always making a profit” IP24

“So we always forget about the supermarkets, but they've got a role to play here as well, right Because they've got deep pockets” IP25

The Key operational challenge faced by SBSC is Critical Mass. The declining cattle herd is impacting the whole supply chain. The importance of critical mass is reflected in the below mentioned interview extracts.

“because you need a critical mass in order to sustain the whole supply chain because it is so, so inextricably linked from upstream to downstream” IP24

“We don't have the critical capacity, the critical mass in the future on that and so we are under extreme pressure at the moment, extreme pressure”IP3

“And you know those each of the processing plants in the country rely on a certain number of animals per day going through that line to cover the costs.And there's not, you know, that's put the processing sector does operate on very thin margins”IP4

“I can see Scotland losing an abattoir in the next five years if we can't stop the cow numbers going down” IP4

“Again, we often the Union talk about critical mass. There are certain number of livestock units to support an auction market to support a feed farm to support haulage companies ”IP5

You know, if you want to maintain the size of industry, you need to maintain Livestock, numbers. IP12

“I think some of the big buyers realize that they need critical mass to keep these abattoirs going. These abattoirs need fed. They're really hungry. They need a lot of sheep and cattle through everyday and the critical mass. Is really. Is really critical You know well, it's the most important factor. If you can have an abattoir, you need to be able to fill it five days a week, 52 weeks of the year, to employ your staff and your oh, you've no business” IP16

From the above comments, the critical mass has a ripple effect because if livestock farmers are not producing enough cattle, the abattoirs may close as mentioned in the comment of IP4. Moreover, the auction marts and the haulage companies also need cattle for the survival of their businesses. Lack of critical mass is resulting into closure of abattoirs, reducing the profit margins and consequently impacting the supply chain resilience by not having the financial strength to adopt proactive measures for risk management.

The key regulatory challenge is slow government response which is impacting the resilience of the SBSC. The slow government response in shaping new policies is restricting the preparedness capability of the livestock farmers. As mentioned, the Government support is an enabling factor for resilience in the SBSC.

“As government and being very slow to come to the table to develop a policy, they say they're going in the right direction where it might be slow and we're saying, well, the farmers haven't got that time for you to be slow” IP3

“the government policy is has a huge impact on what farmers decide to do and one of the main changes I think we've seen since we came out of the EU is the loss of that long term sort of strategy and the long term policy and at the moment, without that certainty, farmers don't know what's coming around the corner, really”

“I think in terms of the cattle industry that works on a sort of multi year cycle, you know farmers are already planning five years ahead at least. So having sort of one year assurances isn't enough and I don't and I think that's leading to a loss of confidence in the sector and farmers themselves not wanting to invest in a new cattle shed or well, at the moment, it's unpredictable in terms of what the Scottish Government's policy is going to be on agricultural support, obviously they're going through reform right now, post Brexit replacing the CAP” IP24

The Key environmental challenge impacting the SBSC is the Scottish Government initiative of net zero emissions from the livestock sector by 2045. This sparked confusion among livestock farmers, and negative media propagation associated with livestock farming is impacting their mental health too.

“And government has announced the the the net 0 targets and what they wanted the carbon emissions reduction to be from agriculture, but actually they didn't have a clue how they were going to do it” IP15

“The current government policies of reducing numbers and putting too much of an emphasis on environmental issues that are not applicable to Scotland”IP16

“And the idea of buying land airlines buying land that's already there.To then offset their carbon.I think it's just all wrong because they're not actually doing anything to reduce their carbon, they're just offsetting to trees and such like” IP14

“I know that fifficulty that has been and huge annoyance to myself as how the media have portrayed farmers how they they seem to have played with the figure.They take global figures for emissions of Livestock, where the cattle has been fed on produce that's been grown under irrigated conditions. The cattle would be far less productive than the cattle in Scotland and I, the Scottish figure, are amongst the lowest in the world” IP6

This research has uncovered various challenges which the SBSC is facing. However, the key issues are discussed which seem to have a higher impact on the resilience of the SBSC. The challenges are interdependent and if one is addressed, the other will be addressed. For instance, if the financial returns are improved this means the livestock farmers can have financial means to be proactive instead of being reactive. Likewise, if the decline in Suckler cow number is addressed this means that the operational challenge of Critical Mass will be addressed. The supply chain will be able to meet the supply with the demand and the abattoirs will have the required throughput for efficient performance. If fair pricing is by promoting the sale through Auction Marts the Retailer dominance will be curtailed. Likewise, the challenges of lack of Veterinary services are addressed it will reduce the challenge of under preparedness for a disease outbreak due to its chances of being undetected due to lack of Vet services. If the returns are improved, it may lead to the farmers' successors joining the industry and the challenge of lack of succession will be addressed.

5.5 Cross-Stakeholder Perspectives on Supply Chain Resilience in the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

This section explores how resilience within the SBSC is understood, experienced, and interpreted by different stakeholder groups, including livestock farmers, processors, retailers, policymakers, industry bodies, and support organisations. Drawing on cross-stakeholder interview data, the analysis identifies

areas of both convergence and divergence in perceptions of the key issues shaping resilience outcomes across the supply chain.

5.5.1 Propagation against the Livestock Farmers

A strong and consistent pattern of convergence is evident across multiple stakeholder groups regarding the perception that livestock farmers and beef production are subject to widespread misinformation, reputational harm, and unfair public narratives. This concern is articulated not only by farmers themselves but also by processors, institutional actors, traceability organisations, policymaker and industry development manager.

IP12 highlights the prevalence of distorted narratives, stating, *“we’ve got to deal with a lot of misinformation that’s out there about beef, beef production”*, framing misinformation as an external and persistent threat to sector legitimacy. This is reinforced by IP6, who strongly contests dominant public discourse by asserting, *“livestock production is not the problem and we are part of the solution... the farmer has been demonized”*. The use of the term “demonized” is significant, as it indicates not merely criticism but moral stigmatisation, suggesting that farmers perceive themselves as being unfairly portrayed as environmentally harmful.

This pattern is further reinforced by IP21, who notes, *“cattle get a lot of, you know, negative comments about methane”*, highlighting how simplified environmental messaging circulates widely without sufficient contextualisation. IP24 extends this concern into the public health domain, arguing that, *“misinformation is a big threat to the industry in terms of fake news”* and that red meat is often positioned as the cause of disease without acknowledging confounding lifestyle factors. The statement that the sector can become *“a bit of a scapegoat”* is analytically important, as it implies that beef production is being symbolically burdened with wider societal health and environmental anxieties.

At the policy level, IP25 similarly identifies a *“reputational issue with really hard working farmers”* and argues that current narratives fail to provide a *“balanced picture”*, particularly in relation to carbon sequestration and on-farm environmental contributions. The observation that sequestration is *“not counted effectively”* and therefore does not give a *“clear picture of what the carbon output is from a farm”* indicates that misrepresentation is not only discursive but also embedded in measurement frameworks. This reinforces the perception that farmers are structurally disadvantaged in how their environmental performance is assessed and communicated.

Taken together, these extracts demonstrate a high degree of convergence across stakeholder groups regarding misinformation, stigmatisation, and reputational vulnerability.

5.5.2 Structural Imbalances

A clear convergence is evident across interview participants regarding retailer dominance, structural concentration and the erosion of fairness within the Scottish Beef Supply Chain. IP13 states that *“the big supermarkets have too much control and they do”*, establishing retailer power as a structural condition rather than a situational issue. This is reinforced by IP20, who links the contraction of processing infrastructure to power imbalance, noting that *“it’s really just large plants that are processing large numbers of animals... the only ones that can really make that sums work”* and concluding that *“at the moment... our supply chains aren’t fair”*. IP8 further aligns with this view by describing how pressure from supermarket contracts is transferred through processors to farmers, stating that *“they’re trying to put a real squeeze on what they were paying farmers”*. IP8 also highlights the structural risk created by declining suckler herds, warning that *“you end up losing players out of the marketplace... and then the market becomes far too controlled”*. Together, these accounts demonstrate a shared perception across stakeholders that retailer power, processing concentration and declining livestock numbers are interlinked dynamics that restrict competition, weaken bargaining positions upstream and undermine fairness across the supply chain.

5.5.3 Supply Demand Imbalances

A strong convergence emerges across participants regarding the structural consequences of the declining suckler herd and the resulting pressure on supply, pricing, and processor viability within the SBSC. Participants consistently identify the reduction in cattle numbers as a central issue, with IP10 stating that *“cattle gets shorter and there are less and less suckler cows in Scotland... it’s a declining number, so we’re having to probably pay more for cattle if they get scarce”* This perception of scarcity is echoed by IP13, who notes that *“as the national herd gets smaller and smaller, we’re all fighting for the same animals, which means ultimately we’ll all be paying more for them,”* and by IP18, who similarly observes that *“there are times when you know cattle are scarce and everyone is fighting for the same number”* These extracts demonstrate a shared recognition across stakeholder groups that contraction of the herd is intensifying competition for cattle.

Participants also converge on the view that this scarcity is currently being offset by strong demand and retailer commitment, but that this balance is fragile. IP11 explains that *“major retailers are committed to having Scottish label product on their shelves... therefore all sizes of producers are being held up by that and there is real pressure on all the abattoirs... to actually compete quite strongly for cattle,”* while IP22

reinforces this by stating that *“demand is there, supply contracting is going to push the farm gate price up”* However, this is not seen as a stable condition. IP18 cautions that *“if consumer demand is on the floor, then the abattoirs will cut back their kill and the farmers will suffer;”* highlighting a shared awareness of vulnerability that current market conditions are fragile and highly contingent on sustained consumer demand.

There is also convergence around the structural risks facing processors and abattoirs. IP6 explicitly links cattle scarcity to the viability of processing infrastructure, warning that *“one of the processors in Scotland may go out of business because they can’t get the raw material to go through the plant... and I fear that we might lose another sizeable abattoir in the future which just gives the ones that’s left more power”* This reflects a common concern that declining throughput will lead to further consolidation and increased market power among remaining processors.

In addition, several participants acknowledge the role of dairy-beef in compensating for the decline in suckler production. IP10 notes that *“a lot of meat is now coming out of the dairy industry, which makes up the shortfall in suckler produced beef;”* and IP6 similarly states that *“the dairy beef has sort of filled the gap that’s been created by cows disappearance”* However, this is accompanied by a shared reservation regarding quality, with IP6 arguing that *“the quality of it’s not so good as suckler beef;”* indicating convergence not only on the structural role of dairy-beef but also on its perceived limitations.

5.5.4 Lack of Financial Returns

A very strong convergence emerges across participants regarding financial unsustainability and low returns as the most critical threat to the SBSC, outweighing concerns such as disease or technical risk. This is articulated explicitly by IP10, who states that *“the biggest threat we have is lack of financial return... our biggest worry is finance, it is not disease;”* establishing profitability as the dominant concern. This position is reinforced across multiple stakeholder groups. IP2 similarly emphasises that *“the long term unprofitability is probably the main challenge;”* noting that only a small proportion of beef farms are profitable before subsidy. IP18 extends this view, explaining that *“historically for some time now it’s been very difficult to see a profitability in the red meat industry at the farming end... if they didn’t have the subsidies, there’s no way they would be... making often the subsidies and diversification of the farm could bring them up to getting some kind of living out of it”* This highlights a shared recognition that farm-level viability is structurally dependent on external support.

The convergence deepens when participants describe how low returns are driving attrition, exit from farming, and declining cattle numbers. IP11 expresses concern about *“the rate of attrition... the number of*

farmers who are walking away from cattle or walking away from farming,” linking this to cost pressures, regulatory pressures, and high capital costs. IP5 confirms this pattern, stating *“the returns aren’t there... there’s a lot of folk getting out”* and *“consistently cattle numbers are falling and it’s exactly the same reasons as here – the returns aren’t there”*. IP6 mentioned that *“poor profitability... and the fact that you don’t have much time off... the younger generation are not too keen to come back”* reinforcing the link between financial pressure and succession failure.

There is also strong convergence on the idea that financial pressure is not confined to farmers but is distributed across the entire chain. IP3 captures this systemic squeeze, stating that *“everybody’s feeling squeezed,”* and elaborating that *“the producers are finding that their costs are too much compared to the return... the processors feel that they’re paying too much money for what the retailers prepared to pay them... and the retailer feels that if he puts the price up... the consumer will move to chicken or pork”* This chain-wide pressure is reinforced by IP18, who notes that even when farm prices improve, *“it’s not a particularly profitable industry... the processing industry... has suffered from low profitability and therefore low investment”* IP19 also reiterated that *“businesses operate at a loss... it’s not a lucrative business to be in”* Cash flow instability is another area of convergence. IP8 highlights that *“cash flow is a big issue in livestock farming”* and that during tight periods farmers are *“flying by the seat of your pants,”* while IP24 confirms that *“cash flow is a real issue... it’s a very cyclical sector... there’s not a consistent cash flow throughout the whole year”* These extracts collectively show that participants across roles share a common understanding of financial fragility as structural rather than incidental.

5.5.5 Traceability

There is strong convergence across participants that traceability is a foundational capability underpinning the resilience of the SBSC, particularly in relation to food safety, regulatory compliance, disease control, and market credibility. At farm level, IP10 emphasised that procurement is restricted to assured sources, stating that *“we would never buy cattle from someone who doesn’t have farm assurance... all our cattle are definitely assured,”* and that detailed pedigree information is required, including *“the name of the bull.”*

Across auction marts, traceability was consistently described as procedural and automated. IP15 detailed how *“the auction markets do all the movement documentation”* and that this *“takes a big burden off the farmer,”* while also explaining the barcode-based system linking ear tags, parental history, breed, sex, and movement records. Similarly, IP16 outlined the end-to-end process from cattle arrival with passports, pre-sale data upload, real-time display of animal details in the ring, and post-sale documentation, indicating

that traceability is integrated into the commercial transaction process itself. These accounts converge in showing that auction marts function as critical traceability hubs, rather than merely trading points.

From the processing perspective, IP14 highlighted that *“every carcass is obviously traceable... as soon as that carcass is split into four, it's got a ticket on it,”* and that even after boning, *“each backpack of meat can be traced back to the animal it was produced from”* This is reinforced by IP17, who described the use of *“sophisticated systems within the factory”* enabling traceability *“throughout the whole system back to the kill batch and then back to the supply”* The emphasis on internal tracking systems, ID numbers, and batch controls demonstrates convergence on the view that traceability is technically embedded within processing operations.

At system and governance level, participants converged strongly on the centrality of ScotEID as the backbone of national traceability. IP20 noted that the system already manages BVD monitoring and links testing status to animal records, while IP21 explained that their role is to *“make sure that we can track and trace animals at the event of a disease outbreak”* and that *“the high level of traceability that we have... means we can control it quicker”*. IP24 similarly stated that *“things like ScotEID... is utilised throughout the sector”* and that *“traceability is a lot more robust,”* indicating sector-wide reliance on this infrastructure. These consistent accounts point to institutional convergence around ScotEID as a resilience-enabling asset.

There is also convergence on the view that traceability directly supports disease control and crisis response. IP15 explicitly stated that auction markets are *“pretty critical... particularly for a disease outbreak because you want to be able to press a button and go right, we know where all the animals are”* This aligns with IP21's reference to tracking and tracing in outbreak scenarios and IP24's assertion that robust traceability allows the industry to *“monitor situations should they arrive”* These views collectively demonstrate agreement that traceability is not only a regulatory function but a core resilience mechanism.

Finally, participants converge on the idea that traceability underpins reputation, provenance, and future resilience. IP14 described traceability as *“a massive part of our story to our customers,”* linking it directly to brand narrative and consumer trust. IP17 stated that *“unless you can prove that you do have very good traceability, there will be an issue of resilience in the future,”* explicitly connecting traceability to long-term system stability. IP23 further noted that while DNA is being explored for productivity, *“the real reason we wanted to use the DNA evidence was for traceability first and foremost,”*

Overall, these extracts demonstrate a high degree of convergence across stakeholder groups that traceability is embedded at every stage of the SBSC.

5.5.6 Government Support

While participants broadly acknowledged the importance of government support to the survival of the Scottish beef sector, there were clear divergences in how subsidies and public intervention were interpreted in relation to efficiency. A number of participants were critical of historical support mechanisms, arguing that they have masked structural weaknesses and delayed necessary adaptation. IP5 stated that *“the EU and the way the support payments were made were covering up a lot of inefficiency,”* suggesting that subsidy regimes enabled underperformance to persist. This view was reinforced by IP3, who argued that *“taking off subsidies actually encouraged efficiency. Similarly, IP2 captured this tension by observing that “subsidies can increase inefficiencies,”* even while recognising that *“if there’s no investment, there’ll be no moving forward”* These accounts frame subsidies as potentially distorting incentives and reinforcing path dependency rather than building adaptive capacity.

In contrast, other participants emphasised the essential stabilising and enabling role of subsidies and grants, particularly in a sector characterised by chronic low margins. IP18 noted that *“if they didn’t have the subsidies, there’s no way they would have... made a living,”* while IP22 similarly observed that *“without agricultural subsidies, the farmers were making a loss”* IP10 described beef production as *“always... a marginal business”* that was previously sustained by government support, highlighting structural vulnerability rather than inefficiency. From this perspective, subsidies are not seen as distorting, but as necessary to sustain production and prevent sectoral collapse.

5.5.7 Retailer Dominance

Participants demonstrated strong convergence in their views regarding the dominant power of supermarkets and large retailers within the SBSC. Across multiple interviews, retailers were consistently positioned as the primary actors with the ability to dictate prices, shape market structures, and influence the viability of domestic production. IP1 explicitly stated that *“supermarkets dictate price. They dictate where they get their products from,”* highlighting the asymmetry of power between producers and retailers. This was reinforced by IP 24, who argued that *“ultimately the big retailers can dictate the price... they are always making a profit,”*

There was also clear convergence around the view that retailer power has directly contributed to the erosion of local and regional processing infrastructure. IP16 provided a detailed account of how supermarket expansion has displaced local abattoirs and butcher shops, noting that *“before there was an abattoir in Kelso, one in Hawick, one in Galashiels. The animals never left the county... now one was Somerset and one was Southern Ireland for the beef”* This reflects a broader structural shift away from localised supply

chains towards centralised, retailer-driven sourcing models. Similarly, IP1 observed that *“the supermarkets using their muscle and power did away with a product in Scotland,”* referring to the loss of organic processing capacity, which further underscores how retailer strategies can undermine domestic processing capability and regional resilience.

Participants also expressed their concern that retailers prioritise commercial interests over loyalty to domestic producers. IP19 stated plainly that *“retailers do not have a loyalty necessarily to domestically produced food and that is a real shame,”* indicating a perception that origin and national provenance are secondary to cost and margin considerations. This concern was echoed in IP8, who questioned whether Scotland could *“compete against South American beef... American and Canadian beef,”* suggesting that global sourcing options weaken the competitive position of domestic producers.

Another strong area of convergence relates to the downward transmission of pressure through the supply chain, with processors and farmers bearing the brunt of retailer cost control. IP18 mentioned that *“the big retailers... will fight very, very hard to maintain prices and therefore that can push its way back down the chain,”* adding that *“the processors get squeezed more than anybody... but it can blow back then to the farmers as well.”*

IP24 highlighted that retailers are *“putting more and more stipulations on their producers... to align with EU deforestation regulations... carbon credentials,”* while *“they’re always making a profit at the same time”* Interview 25 reinforced this sentiment, stating that *“we always forget about the supermarkets, but they’ve got a role to play here as well... because they’ve got deep pockets”*

The participants expressed that retailer dominance is leading to erode local processing capacity, weaken loyalty to domestic production, and transmit cost and risk upstream to processors and farmers.

5.5.8 Product Quality

There is a clear divergence among participants regarding how quality should be defined, measured, and rewarded within the SBSC, and how this links to resilience. A significant point of divergence centres on the adequacy of the current EUROP grading and payment system. IP1 explicitly stated that *“payment system is a problem. The grading systems problem? Livestock purchasing or procurement is a problem,”* framing the grading structure as a core weakness affecting performance and resilience. This view is echoed by IP2, who argued that payment in Scotland is *“all just about the fat cover”* and shape of the animal, with *“nothing about actual quality,”* and contrasted this with systems in the USA and Australia where *“payment is driven on marbling”* and eating quality. IP14 similarly supported this position, stating that *“QMS could probably*

be pushing more to change the grading system into a more Australia based system where it promotes quality,” indicating dissatisfaction with the current model.

IP3 highlighted lack of uniformity, stating “*we never provide uniformity... how do we standardize it and make sure that we have what we call quality,*” the emphasis here is on measurement difficulty and breed variation, rather than on the grading system itself. This contrasts with IP2’s more structural critique of the payment grid and its misalignment with eating quality, showing divergence between those who see the issue as systemic design failure and those who see it as operational complexity and biological variability.

There is also divergence in how quality is conceptually linked to resilience. IP1 proposed carcass specification as a KPI for resilience, stating that it should be used to assess whether “*the product meets the requirements of the customer or the retailers,*” framing resilience in market-alignment terms. In contrast, IP4 linked marbling directly to biological resilience, stating “*marbling also links to resilience because that intramuscular fat is the instant energy reserve that the cow can pick on*” This interpretation positions resilience as a physiological attribute of the animal, rather than a market or system outcome. Similarly, IP4 argued that “*the Angus breed lends itself to a more resilient supply chain system because... far reduced labour,*” introducing a breed-based and labour-efficiency perspective on resilience, which diverges from the market-quality and grading-focused views of other participants.

5.5.9 Collaboration

The interview data reveal significant divergence in how collaboration across the SBSC is perceived, experienced, and evaluated by different stakeholders. While some participants describe active cooperation and transparent relationships, others emphasise fragmentation, mistrust, and structural barriers to meaningful collaboration. For example, IP8 described close, transparent relationships with other farmers, stating that “*it’s a very transparent relationship where trust is a big thing... it’s a mutual benefit for both parties for us to work together going forward*” Similarly, IP17 highlighted structured engagement with government, QMS, and SRUC, noting “*we do have active lines of communication with QMS, SRUC... I would say that we do have good communication throughout the Scottish industry network*” These accounts frame collaboration as functional and ongoing within specific networks.

In contrast, IP3 offered a much more critical assessment, stating that “*it’s not integrated*” and that “*everybody’s feeling squeezed*” This perception is reinforced by IP20, who argued that “*we do need to work closer with the retailers and the processors... because at the moment... our supply chains aren’t fair.*” IP5 further questioned whether fairness is even achievable, stating, “*is the supply chain fair? that is going to take a lot of honest talking... and I can’t see that happening,*” attributing this to shareholder pressures on

retailers. These views diverge sharply from the more optimistic portrayals of collaboration offered by IP8 and IP17.

Another point of divergence concerns industry representation and inclusion. IP2 suggested that participation in industry meetings is skewed, stating that *“it’ll quite often be larger producers... I don’t think they’d be able to say that there was full industry representation”* This contrasts with IP9’s description of proactive initiatives to connect store producers, finishers, and processors through workshops, emphasising efforts to *“join up that communication so that people are producing what the market is looking for”* Here, divergence emerges between perceptions of exclusion and dominance by larger players versus structured attempts to improve connectivity and dialogue.

Participants also diverge in their interpretation of the causes of poor collaboration. IP8 framed the issue as excessive separation, stating *“there’s far too much of them and us... there needs to be far more farmer chat between each part of the supply chain”*

There is also divergence regarding whether collaboration is improving or stagnating. IP2 acknowledged that *“there is efforts being made”* despite incomplete representation, and IP9 outlined active development initiatives. However, IP3 maintained that *“that won’t be integrated for a while,”* and IP5 argued that discussions about value distribution *“just don’t take place,”* due to self-interest. It is evident from the participants’ views that collaboration is not experienced uniformly across the supply chain. The cross-stakeholder analysis reveals that resilience within the SBSC is shaped by a complex interplay of shared pressures and contested interpretations across actor groups. Strong convergence is evident around structural vulnerabilities such as declining cattle numbers, financial unsustainability, retailer dominance, misinformation, and the centrality of traceability as a resilience-enabling infrastructure. These shared perceptions indicate that many of the system’s challenges are widely recognised and experienced across positional boundaries, reinforcing their structural rather than situational nature. However, the analysis also exposes clear divergences in how key issues such as subsidies, product quality, collaboration, and efficiency are understood and evaluated. These divergences reflect differing positional interests, power asymmetries, and operational realities across farmers, processors, policymakers, and industry bodies. Crucially, this pattern of simultaneous convergence and divergence demonstrates that resilience in the SBSC cannot be understood through isolated stakeholder perspectives, but must be conceptualised as an emergent, relational property shaped by structural conditions, governance arrangements, and interdependencies across the system. This cross-stakeholder lens therefore provides deeper insight into where alignment exists, where tensions persist, and where strategic intervention may be most necessary to strengthen system-wide resilience.

5.6 Temporal Escalation of Systemic Challenges and Resilience Capability Impacts in the SBSC

Drawing on the data collected, this analysis examines how challenges described by participants evolve over time and have the potential to escalate into acute disruptions. The table 5.10 below presents a structured overview of how persistent systemic challenges within the SBSC evolve over time and are associated with progressively more severe outcomes. Adopting a temporal perspective, the analysis distinguishes between short-term operational effects, medium-term structural pressures, and long-term outcomes that manifest as acute disruptions. The table 5.10 further links these trajectories to the erosion of specific resilience capability factors, highlighting how resilience weakens cumulatively rather than instantaneously.

Systemic Challenge	Short-Term Impact	Medium-Term Impact	Resulting Acute Disruption (Long-Term Outcome)	Resilience Capability Factors Eroded Over Time
Declining Suckler Herd Numbers	Tightening cattle supply and increased competition for livestock, reflecting a sustained decline of over 20% since 1990 (QMS, 2024)	Underutilization of auction marts and abattoirs as throughput falls below efficient operating levels	Structural contraction: Rise in permanent closure of processing facilities, increased concentration, and reduced domestic supply capacity	Supply Base Diversity Logistical Capabilities
Lack of Financial Returns	Cash-flow pressure limits reinvestment in productivity, technology, and preparedness	Accelerated farm exit and further contraction of cattle numbers, reinforcing downward herd trends	Sectoral withdrawal: Widespread exit from beef production and long-term reduction in domestic output	Contingency Planning Risk Mitigation

Lack of Succession and Ageing Population	Reduced entry of new producers and delayed strategic investment at farm level	Increasing retirement without successors and erosion of tacit knowledge	Production discontinuity: Loss of farm enterprises, abandonment or repurposing of land, and irreversible loss of sector-specific expertise	Inherent Resilience Supplier Relationships Supply Base Diversity
Retailer Dominance and Power Imbalance	Margin compression and weakened bargaining power for farmers and processors	Reduced collaboration among the supply chain players	Supply chain instability: Increased reliance on imported beef	Transparency Collaboration
Slow Adoption of Technology	Limited real-time visibility of operational, market, and biosecurity risks	Delayed detection and response to disease and market disruptions	Systemic vulnerability: Escalation of biosecurity or operational shocks due to weakened sensing and monitoring capability	Traceability Risk Mitigation
Infrastructure Decline (Abattoirs / Auction Marts)	Increased transport distances, costs, and lead times as local facilities struggle to remain viable	Reduced flexibility and responsiveness during localized disruptions	Operational disruption: Inability to move livestock efficiently during shocks, increasing welfare, cost, and continuity risks	Logistical Capabilities Flexibility

Table 5.10 Temporal Escalation of Systemic Challenges

Declining suckler herd numbers represent a long-term structural trend, but they also produce immediate practical effects on day-to-day supply chain operations. In the short term, reduced cattle availability increases competition for livestock. As this condition persists, throughput across auction marts and abattoirs falls below efficient operating levels, placing pressure on processing and marketing infrastructure. Over the longer term, this process is associated with permanent facility closures and increased concentration, reducing domestic supply capacity. This trajectory reflects a sequential erosion of resilience capabilities

whereby declining herd numbers initially reduce supply base diversity. As volumes continue to fall, the viability and efficiency of logistics and infrastructure are undermined, weakening logistical capabilities.

Limited financial returns exert sustained pressure across the supply chain. In the short term, constrained cash flow restricts reinvestment in productivity, technology, and preparedness. As financial pressure persists, formal planning and preparedness become increasingly difficult to sustain, contributing to farm exit and further contraction in cattle numbers. In the long term, this trajectory is associated with a reduction in domestic beef output. This reflects a cascading erosion of resilience capabilities driven by sustained financial pressure. Resource constraints initially limit investment in formal contingency planning, as forward-looking preparedness activities are deprioritised under low margins. As financial pressure persists, risk mitigation practices become increasingly informal, reactive, and unevenly applied due to reduced capacity for preventative investment.

Succession constraints and an ageing farming population affect the continuity of primary production. Initially, reduced entry of new producers and delayed strategic investment indicate weakening long-term planning. As retirement occurs without succession, tacit knowledge and accumulated experience are lost, reducing adaptive capacity at farm level. Over the long term, these dynamics result in production discontinuity and a reduction in sector-specific expertise. This sequence reflects erosion beginning with inherent resilience, followed by weakening supplier relationships as long-standing production and trading links are lost, and culminating in reduced supply base diversity as fewer producers remain active within the system.

Retailer dominance and power imbalance influence coordination and value distribution within the SBSC. In the short term, margin compression limits bargaining power for farmers and processors. When sustained, this imbalance reduces incentives for information sharing and long-term domestic investment, weakening coordination across the supply chain. Over time, these dynamics contribute to instability within the domestic supply chain as a result of retailer dominance, which can lead to increased reliance on imported beef. This progressive erosion of transparency restricts information visibility and ultimately weakens collaboration, as trust and shared strategic commitment across the supply chain decline.

Slow adoption of technology primarily affects information availability and system visibility. In the short term, limited digital integration restricts real-time monitoring of operational, market, and biosecurity risks. Continued limitations in data integration are associated with delayed detection of, and response to, disruptions. Over the longer term, this increases exposure to systemic risk due to weakened sensing and

monitoring capabilities. This progression reflects how constraints on traceability limit effective risk mitigation by reducing the system’s capacity to anticipate, detect, and manage shock

Infrastructure decline, particularly the loss of abattoirs and auction marts, has direct implications for operational efficiency. In the short term, increased transport distances and costs affect responsiveness and welfare considerations. As local capacity continues to decline, flexibility during localised disruptions is reduced. In the long term, this constrains the system’s ability to mobilise livestock during shocks, increasing continuity risks. This sequence corresponds with erosion of logistical capabilities, followed by reduced flexibility.

Overall, the analysis shows that resilience in the SBSC is shaped by the cumulative and sequential effects of persistent challenges over time. Short-term operational pressures, if left unresolved, propagate through interconnected resilience capabilities, leading to medium-term structural pressures and long-term acute disruptions. The sequential pathways illustrated in the table 5.10 emphasise that early capability erosion amplifies later vulnerability, underscoring the importance of addressing persistent challenges proactively to prevent long-term degradation of system-wide resilience.

5.7 Resilience Capability Effectiveness in the Scottish Beef Supply Chain

This section explains how the resilience capabilities identified in the SBSC are shaped and constrained by persistent structural, economic, and institutional challenges.

The table 5.11 provides a capability-level analysis that moves beyond identifying the presence of resilience mechanisms to examine how and why their effectiveness is limited in practice. The analysis demonstrates that resilience weaknesses within the SBSC stem not only from the presence or absence of capabilities, but from the structural, economic, and institutional conditions that constrain their effective deployment.

Resilience Capability	Primary Type	Impacting Challenge(s)	Specific Impact on Capability Effectiveness
Traceability	Proactive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of financial returns 	While baseline traceability systems (e.g. ScotEID) exist, high costs and limited digital skills restrict advanced data integration and real-time monitoring. This constrains the system’s sensing

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slow adoption to technology 	capability, limiting early detection of disease risks, market shifts, and performance inefficiencies, particularly at farm level.
Inherent Resilience	Proactive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Aging Population •Lack of Succession 	The exit of experienced farmers without successors erodes tacit knowledge and adaptive skills accumulated over generations. This weakens farm-level adaptability, reducing the system’s capacity to absorb shocks and self-adjust, particularly in extensive suckler systems.
Transparency	Proactive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Retailer Dominance •Processor Dominance 	Power asymmetric and asymmetric information flows limit transparency across the supply chain. Dominant retailers and processors retain control over pricing.
Supplier Selection	Proactive	Lack of KPIs	Supplier selection remains compliance-oriented rather than capability-driven, limiting its contribution to system-wide resilience in the SBSC.
Supply Base Diversity	Proactive	Declining Suckler Herd Numbers	Shrinking herd sizes reduce the critical mass required to sustain diverse supply channels (e.g. local vs. dairy-beef systems)
Logistical Capabilities	Reactive	Infrastructure Decline (Abattoir/Mart Closures)	The loss of local abattoirs and auction marts increases travel distances, costs, and lead times. This weakens response capability during disruptions, reduces agility, and increases exposure to transport-related risks and bottlenecks.

Government Support	Reactive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Regulatory Uncertainty (Post-Brexit) •Slow Government response 	While reactive aid supports short-term recovery, uncertainty prevents transformation of support into long-term resilience investments and discourages forward planning.
Contingency Planning	Reactive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of financial returns 	Persistent low margins limit farmers' ability to formalise contingency plans. As a result, recovery strategies remain informal and reactive rather than structured, funded, and scalable, weakening preparedness for future disruptions.
Risk Mitigation	Proactive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Resource constraints at farm level •Uneven distribution of financial capacity across supply chain tiers 	Risk mitigation contributes to SBSC resilience primarily through disease preparedness and site-level planning; however, its effectiveness is uneven across the supply chain. Livestock farmers are constrained by limited financial and operational resources, restricting active exercise of risk mitigation practices. In contrast, processors and retailers possess the capacity to develop formal disease response plans, conduct site-based risk assessments, and adapt operational procedures. As a result, risk mitigation is concentrated downstream, limiting its effectiveness as a system-wide proactive capability and creating asymmetrical resilience across supply chain tiers.

Table 5.11 Resilience Capability Effectiveness

5.7.1 Proactive Resilience Capabilities

Several capabilities within the SBSC are intended to operate proactively by anticipating disruptions and reducing exposure to risk before shocks occur. However, the findings reveal that their effectiveness is uneven and frequently constrained.

Traceability is a proactive capability supported by baseline systems such as ScotEID. While these systems provide compliance-level traceability, their effectiveness is limited by low financial returns and slow technology adoption. High costs and limited digital skills prevent advanced data integration and real-time monitoring, particularly at farm level. This constrains the supply chain's sensing capability, reducing early detection of disease risks, market shifts, and performance inefficiencies.

Inherent resilience, embedded in experience, skills, and tacit knowledge, is undermined by an ageing farming population and lack of succession. The exit of experienced farmers without successors erodes adaptive capacity accumulated over generations. This weakens farm-level adaptability and reduces the system's capacity to absorb shocks and self-adjust, especially in extensive suckler systems that rely heavily on experiential knowledge rather than formalised processes.

Transparency is also identified as a proactive capability, yet it is constrained by retailer and processor dominance. Power asymmetries and asymmetric information flows limit transparency across the supply chain, as dominant downstream actors retain control over pricing and market information. This reduces visibility for upstream actors, undermines trust, and restricts collaborative decision-making, weakening relational resilience.

The lack of clearly defined and consistently applied Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) limits the effectiveness of supplier selection as a resilience capability in the SBSC by reducing the ability of downstream actors to differentiate suppliers beyond basic compliance criteria.

Supply base diversity is weakened by declining suckler herd numbers, which reduces the critical mass required to sustain multiple supply channels. This contraction increases dependency on a narrower set of suppliers, weakening flexibility and reducing the system's ability to absorb supply-side shocks.

Risk mitigation contributes to SBSC resilience primarily through site-level disease planning and risk assessment, but its effectiveness is uneven across the supply chain. Livestock farmers are constrained by limited financial and operational resources, restricting active exercise of risk mitigation practices. In contrast, processors and retailers possess the capacity to develop formal disease response plans and adapt operational procedures.

5.7.2 Reactive Resilience Capabilities

Reactive capabilities within the SBSC focus on response and recovery once disruptions have occurred. These capabilities are also constrained by structural challenges.

Logistical capabilities are significantly affected by infrastructure decline, particularly the closure of local abattoirs and auction marts. The loss of regional infrastructure increases travel distances, costs, and lead times, reducing agility and weakening response capability during disruptions. This also increases exposure to transport-related risks and bottlenecks.

Government support plays an important role in short-term recovery. However, its effectiveness is constrained by regulatory uncertainty in the post-Brexit context and slow government response. While reactive aid supports continuity the policy uncertainty prevents the transformation of support into long-term resilience investments, discouraging forward planning and structural adaptation.

Contingency planning is constrained by persistently low financial returns, which limit farmers' ability to formalise preparedness and recovery strategies. As a result, contingency planning remains largely informal and reactive rather than structured, funded, and scalable, weakening preparedness for future disruptions.

While many proactive and reactive mechanisms exist in principle, their effectiveness is suppressed by financial pressures, power imbalances, infrastructure decline, and policy uncertainty.

5.8 The Interdependency of Challenges and Resilience Capabilities in the SBSC

A critical finding of this research is that the challenges facing the SBSC exist within a complex web of interdependencies. As detailed in Table 5.12 root challenges act as catalysts for secondary pressures, creating systemic bottlenecks that erode the chain's resilience capabilities.

Core / Root Challenge	Interdependent Challenges Reinforced	How the Interdependence Operates	Challenges Curtailed if Root Issue Is Addressed	Resilience Capabilities Impacted
Lack of financial Returns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Aging population and Succession 2. Decline in Sucker Herd 3. Lack of income diversity 4. Slow adoption to technology 	Persistent low profitability discourages reinvestment, deters younger entrants, and accelerates exit from suckler production.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Succession pressures 2. Technology adoption 3. Herd decline 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Traceability 2. Supply base diversity 3. Contingency Planning
Structural Imbalances	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Retailer Dominance 2. Processor Dominance 	Power asymmetry forces farmers into price-taker roles, limits negotiation, and concentrates risk upstream.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of trust 2. Lack of collaboration 3. Fair value distribution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Supplier relationships 2. Collaboration 3. Flexibility
Decline in Suckler herd	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Critical Mass 2. Supply base fragility 3. Infrastructure underutilization 	Shrinking herd sizes reduce throughput for marts and abattoirs, undermining regional infrastructure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Supply stability 2. Infrastructure viability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Supply base diversity 2. Logistical capabilities

Absence of KPIs and Export Ambition	Global Competition	Lack of carcass-based metrics prevents efficiency improvements and limits competitiveness against global producers.	1. Productivity improvements 2. Better market positioning	Market position
Slow Government response	Uncertain Government policies	Reactive and inconsistent policy reduces planning certainty and prevents the transformation of support into long-term resilience.	1. Market Imbalance 2. Lack of financial returns	Government Support

Table 5.12 The Interdependency of Challenges and Resilience Capabilities in the SBSC

5.8.1 Lack of Financial Returns as the Primary Systemic Constraint

The findings clearly identify lack of financial returns as the most fundamental root challenge affecting resilience in the SBSC. Persistent low profitability at farm level discourages reinvestment, deters younger entrants, and limits the adoption of productivity enhancing technologies. As financial pressure intensifies, farmers increasingly exit suckler production, accelerating herd decline across the sector. Low margins restrict capital availability, which limits technology adoption and income diversification. In turn, this weakens productivity and reinforces financial vulnerability. If financial returns were improved, multiple downstream challenges would be curtailed simultaneously: succession pressures would ease, technology adoption would increase, and the rate of herd decline would slow. Consequently, key resilience capabilities particularly traceability, contingency planning, and supply base diversity would be significantly strengthened.

5.8.2 Structural Imbalances

A second critical root challenge is structural imbalance, driven primarily by retailer and processor dominance. Power asymmetry forces farmers into price-taker roles and limits their ability to negotiate terms. This undermines trust and discourages collaboration, weakening relational resilience across the supply chain. Farmers' limited bargaining power reduces incentives for joint investment, long-term contracting, or collaborative risk-sharing. Addressing structural imbalances through fairer value distribution or stronger collective mechanisms would improve trust and enable stronger collaboration. This would directly reinforce supplier relationships and collaboration.

5.8.3 Decline in the Suckler Herd

The decline in the suckler herd represents both an outcome of earlier root challenges and a reinforcing constraint. Shrinking herd sizes reduce throughput for auction marts and abattoirs, leading to infrastructure underutilisation and increasing per-unit operating costs. This weakens regional infrastructure viability, making the supply chain more fragile to supply disruptions. This interdependence operates through volume dependency. As critical mass declines, infrastructure closures become more likely, increasing transport distances and reducing responsiveness. If herd decline were stabilised, supply stability would improve and regional infrastructure would become more viable. As a result, supply base diversity, and logistical resilience would be strengthened, enhancing both readiness and response capabilities.

5.8.4 Absence of KPIs and Export Ambition

The combined challenge of absence of KPIs and limited export ambition further constrains resilience by exposing the SBSC to global competition without the tools needed to compete effectively. The lack of carcass-based performance metrics prevents systematic efficiency improvements and weakens benchmarking against international producers. Simultaneously, limited export ambition increases dependence on the domestic market, amplifying exposure to retailer power and price volatility.

5.8.5 Slow Government Response and Policy Uncertainty

Slow government response emerges as a root institutional constraint that reinforces uncertainty across the supply chain. Policy uncertainty reinforces market imbalance by weakening farmers' negotiating positions and increasing their dependence on short-term subsidies rather than structural improvements. Without clear, stable policy direction, government support remains focused on short term financial relief rather than addressing underlying economic viability. As a result, challenges such as lack of financial returns persist,

since farmers are unable to plan investment, adopt technology, or commit to long-term production strategies with confidence.

Timely government response and policy certainty would reduce market imbalance by improving confidence across the supply chain and enabling fairer engagement between farmers, processors, and retailers. It would also alleviate financial pressure by allowing government support to shift from reactive compensation towards targeted investment in productivity, infrastructure, and resilience-building measures.

This interdependency of the challenges demonstrates that resilience limitations in the SBSC stem not from a lack of resilience mechanisms, but also from root structural challenges that suppress their effectiveness. Addressing foundational issues particularly financial viability, power imbalance, and policy uncertainty would generate cascading benefits across multiple resilience capabilities.

6 Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter outlines the key contributions made by this study and identifies potential directions for future research. It also synthesises the findings by examining how research objectives been achieved through the empirical analysis.

6.1 Objective 1: To explore the current resilience of the Scottish Beef Supply Chain.

This research explores the resilience of the SBSC through a systematic, theory-guided analytical approach. First, persistent economic, structural, operational, technological, regulatory, and environmental challenges were identified from the empirical data. These challenges were then examined to understand how they can impact the resilience capabilities of the SBSC in short term, medium term and long term.

The analysis subsequently mapped the challenges against the resilience capabilities identified within the supply chain, distinguishing between proactive and reactive capabilities and assessing their effectiveness. Finally, resilience was assessed comparatively across livestock farmers, auction marts, processors, and retailers to identify asymmetries in capability distribution and effectiveness at both actor and system levels.

The findings indicate that the SBSC exhibits moderate resilience at the system level, characterised by strong downstream preparedness and recovery capacity, but significantly weaker upstream resilience.

Livestock Farmers

Livestock farmers represent the most vulnerable component of the SBSC in resilience terms. At the readiness stage, farmers draw on proactive capabilities embedded in Scotland's natural production environment, accumulated tacit knowledge, and long-standing farming skills. These characteristics support inherent resilience enabling farmers to continue operating despite persistent pressures such as low financial returns, volatile input costs, and environmental uncertainty. Traceability systems, supported through national infrastructure, further enhance preparedness by enabling compliance and disease monitoring.

However, these proactive capabilities are increasingly constrained by structural challenges. Declining profitability limits investment in technology, risk mitigation, and formal contingency planning, while an ageing population and lack of succession erode accumulated knowledge over time.

In the response phase, farmers' ability to absorb shocks is constrained by limited financial buffers and operational flexibility. Recovery at farm level is therefore heavily reliant on external support, primarily government intervention through schemes designed to stabilise income and provide disease-related compensation. Without such support, recovery capacity would be significantly weakened.

Auction Marts

Auction marts contribute to SBSC resilience primarily through proactive capabilities associated with readiness, rather than through large-scale response or recovery functions. Their central role in transparency and traceability enhances system-wide preparedness by supporting price discovery, movement recording, and regulatory compliance. These functions improve visibility across the supply chain and reduce uncertainty during periods of disruption. Auction marts possess limited response capability, as they do not control livestock production or volumes entering the supply chain. Their recovery is contingent on upstream production continuity and regulatory clearance. The resilience of auction marts is structurally constrained by declining cattle numbers.

Processors

Processors demonstrate stronger resilience capabilities than upstream actors, reflecting sector concentration, diversified revenue streams, and access to financial and organisational resources. In terms of readiness, processors benefit from formal supplier relationships, demand forecasting through retailer contracts, diversified carcass utilisation. During the response phase, processors exhibit considerable operational flexibility, supported by logistical coordination and the activation of contingency plans, such as reallocation of throughput across multiple facilities and adaptive sourcing strategies. Their exposure to biological risk is lower than at farm level, further strengthening response capacity. In the recovery phase, processors show comparatively high resilience due to access to capital, but this recovery capacity remains contingent on sustained cattle supply.

Retailers

Retailers represent the most resilient actors within the SBSC across all three resilience phases. Strong financial capacity, diversified sourcing options, advanced logistics, and robust traceability systems provide high levels of proactive preparedness. Retailers are well positioned to anticipate disruptions and manage risk through strategic sourcing and contractual control. In the response phase, retailers demonstrate exceptional adaptability, rapidly reconfiguring supply chains and substituting sources to maintain continuity. Recovery is similarly strong, with retailers able to absorb shocks and restore operations quickly.

The analysis shows that the resilience of the SBSC is uneven while downstream actors exhibit high levels of preparedness, response, and recovery, upstream resilience is increasingly constrained by structural challenges. The SBSC therefore demonstrates moderate overall resilience.

6.2 Objective 2: To identify the key factors contributing to the resilience of the SBSC.

The second objective was achieved through a systematic identification, categorisation, and analysis of the full range of resilience capability factors operating within the SBSC. Drawing on interview data across all

major stakeholder groups and guided by the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV), the study identified how resilience is constituted through a combination of proactive and reactive capabilities, and how these are enacted through specific processes, asset positions, and evolutionary or regulatory pathways.

Proactive resilience capabilities supporting the readiness phase were identified across all stages of the supply chain. Inherent resilience was found to operate primarily at the farm level, embedded in Scotland's natural suitability for livestock production, biological continuity of cattle systems, and accumulated intergenerational knowledge. This capability provides a structural foundation for resilience by enabling ongoing production despite environmental and market volatility. Traceability emerged as a system-wide proactive capability, supported by institutional and technological assets such as ScotEID, mandatory movement recording, auction mart systems, processing-level carcass tracking, and retailer DNA verification. This capability enhances preparedness by enabling early detection of disease risks, safeguarding food integrity, and supporting rapid containment in the event of disruption.

Supplier relationships and supplier selection were identified as distinct but complementary proactive capabilities. Supplier selection routines based on assurance schemes and suitability criteria reduce exposure to quality and compliance risks. Supply base diversity, achieved through multi-channel sourcing strategies including direct farm supply, auction marts, livestock agents, and dairy-beef integration, further enhances readiness by reducing dependency on any single supply source. Transparency, primarily enabled through auction marts, supports readiness by facilitating open price discovery and information visibility, thereby reducing informational asymmetries and supporting market stability.

Risk mitigation is exercised predominantly by processors and retailers through formal disease preparedness plans, site-level risk assessments, and procedural adjustments, reflecting uneven distribution of financial and operational resources across the supply chain. Market position, underpinned by the Scotch Beef brand, GI status, and quality assurance schemes, functions as a demand-side resilience mechanism by strengthening consumer confidence, stabilising demand, and reducing vulnerability to market shocks.

Reactive resilience capabilities supporting the response and recovery phases were also comprehensively identified and analysed. Contingency planning was evident in different forms such as formalised multi-site operational planning among processors and retailers, as well as government-led disease outbreak response frameworks. Logistical capabilities, including in-house transport fleets, routing flexibility, and distribution capacity, were concentrated downstream and enable rapid response to disruptions by maintaining product flow under constrained conditions. Redundancy, such as buffer stocks, genetic preservation, and excess operational capacity, supports recovery by allowing the system to absorb shocks and re-establish functionality over time. Government support, delivered through subsidies, grants, and regulatory

frameworks, functions as a critical reactive capability by stabilising farm-level viability and enabling recovery following financial or disease-related disruptions, albeit constrained by policy uncertainty and slow responsiveness.

By mapping all identified capabilities onto the DCV dimensions of processes/routines, asset positions, and evolutionary or regulatory paths, the study demonstrates how resilience in the SBSC stems from the interaction of multiple capabilities.

6.3 Objective 3: To explore the key challenges impacting the resilience of the SBSC.

The third objective was achieved through a comprehensive analysis of the challenges affecting the SBSC, their interconnectedness, and their impact on resilience capability effectiveness.

The findings identify lack of financial returns as the primary systemic constraint affecting resilience across the supply chain. Financial pressure limits reinvestment, accelerates farm exit, undermines succession, and restricts the formalisation of contingency planning and risk mitigation. This economic challenge is closely interconnected with declining suckler herd numbers, which reduce critical mass and undermine infrastructure viability, thereby weakening logistical capabilities and supply base diversity.

Structural imbalances, particularly retailer dominance and processing concentration, further constrain resilience by compressing margins upstream, limiting transparency beyond auction markets, and discouraging collaboration. Operational challenges, including an ageing farming population and labour shortages, progressively erode inherent resilience by disrupting the transmission of tacit knowledge and limiting the effective application of adaptive farming practices. Technological challenges restrict real-time sensing and monitoring, while environmental and regulatory uncertainty particularly post-Brexit policy reform and net-zero targets undermines planning confidence and investment.

Crucially, the study demonstrates that these challenges do not act independently but interact cumulatively over time, leading to progressive erosion of resilience capabilities and, ultimately, acute disruptions such as infrastructure closure, sectoral exit, and increased import dependence. By explicitly linking challenges to the degradation of specific proactive and reactive capabilities, the research provides a robust basis for evaluating how resilience is constrained within the SBSC.

6.4 Empirical Contribution to Supply Chain Resilience Literature

The current study has contributed to the supply chain resilience literature in the context of the SBSC. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, the only study (Leat and Revoredo Ghia, 2013) that captured the supply chain resilience of Scottish Livestock farming was on the Pork Supply Chain of ASDA. This is the first research done by taking a holistic view of the entire SBSC. In this study 25 semi structured interviews

were conducted to explore the supply chain resilience of the SBSC and the challenges which it is confronting. The participants comprised of Academic Experts (02), Industry Advisor (01), Official Cattle Society Representative (01), Livestock Farmers (07), Industry Representative Processors (01), Processors (02), Industry Representative Auction Marts (01), Auction Mart (01), Retailer (01), Retail Industry Expert (01), Policy Managers Livestock & Animal welfare (02), Executive Traceability Organisation (01), Market Intelligence Manager (01), Head of Industry Development (01), Public Affairs and Industry Strategy Manager (01), and Member of Scottish Parliament, Rural Affairs Committee Member (01). This diversified participant sample has enriched the findings and implications of the research.

The only comprehensive definition of AFSC resilience was proposed by Stone and Rahimifard (2018) based on a systematic literature review and is not empirically grounded. This thesis has proposed amendments to the definition and has contributed to the literature on agri-food supply chain resilience by providing an empirically grounded definition.

“The collective ability of AFSC stakeholders to ensure acceptable, sufficient and stable food supplies, at the required times and locations, via accurate anticipation of disruptions and the use of strategies which delay impact, aid rapid recovery and allow cumulative learning post-disruption” Stone and Rahimifard (2018, p.232).

The amendments proposed in the original definition of agri-food supply chain (AFSC) resilience enhance its scope and applicability, addressing critical gaps that limit its comprehensiveness. The widely accepted definition of AFSC resilience by Stone and Rahimifard (2018) focused on the collective ability of stakeholders to ensure acceptable, sufficient, and stable food supplies by anticipating disruptions and deploying strategies to delay impact, recover quickly, and enable cumulative learning, providing a solid foundation. However, it primarily emphasises system-level collaboration and response to disruptions without fully accounting for individual stakeholder roles, systemic challenges, and modern priorities such as traceability. The proposed definition by this thesis grounded in empirical data broadens this scope, making it more inclusive and aligned with the complexities of contemporary supply chains.

While the widely accepted definition highlights the importance of collective action, it overlooks individual stakeholders' critical role in achieving resilience. For example, a livestock farmer's ability to be prepared for a disease outbreak, the processor's capacity to respond to supply disruptions, and the retailers' capability to be ready for logistical disruptions are essential components of resilience at the system level. Recognizing these individual contributions complements the collective effort, emphasising that resilience is a shared responsibility where both system-wide and individual actions matter.

Another key amendment is the integration of systemic challenges alongside disruptions. The original definition focuses solely on disruptions, which are often acute and temporary, such as disease outbreaks or extreme weather. However, ongoing challenges like low profitability, climate change, and structural issues such as retailer dominance and declining herd sizes create persistent vulnerabilities that undermine the ability to respond to disruptions effectively. By including the need to "overcome challenges," the proposed definition indicates that the supply chain can navigate through disruptions but also long-term pressures.

The proposed definition also introduces traceable food supplies as a crucial outcome, reflecting the growing importance of transparency and accountability in modern supply chains. The original definition emphasises the delivery of acceptable, sufficient, and stable food supplies but does not address the increasing demand for traceability, which is critical for food safety, consumer trust, and regulatory compliance. In an era where consumers and regulators prioritise ethical and sustainable practices, traceability has become a cornerstone of resilience. Including it in the definition ensures that resilience strategies align with these contemporary expectations.

The definition proposed by this thesis is "AFSC resilience is the collective and individual ability of stakeholders to prepare, respond, and recover from disruptions, overcome challenges, to ensure acceptable, sufficient, stable, and traceable food supplies through strategies that anticipate disruptions, delay impact, aid rapid recovery, and foster cumulative learning post-disruption".

The amendments to the original definition are justified as they address its limitations and align it with the evolving demands of the agri-food sector. By integrating collective and individual abilities, accounting for systemic challenges, and emphasising traceability, the proposed definition offers a more comprehensive and practical understanding of AFSC resilience.

This thesis advances the agri-food supply chain resilience literature by identifying resilience capability factors for SBSC and comparing the resilience capability with those reported in prior studies across different national contexts. Through this comparative lens, the research demonstrates that while certain resilience capabilities recur across agri-food supply chains, their relevance, configuration, and effectiveness are highly context dependent. Zhong et al., (2024) identified fifteen resilience capability factors for the Chinese agri-food supply chain, highlighting leadership as the most influential capability. While this study confirms the importance of several commonly identified factors such as redundancy, government support, visibility (particularly through traceability), and flexibility (expressed as sourcing and supply base diversity) it does not identify leadership as a dominant capability in the SBSC. This absence is itself a meaningful empirical insight, reflecting the contextual realities of limited collaboration and perceived supply chain unfairness within the SBSC. Zhao et al. (2024) identified resilience capability factors through interviews conducted

in Argentina and France, identifying fourteen factors for Argentina and sixteen for France. The SBSC shares some commonalities with these contexts, particularly in relation to long-term relationships (captured in this study as supplier relationships), government support, traceability, and transparency. Zhao et al. (2023) examined agri food supply chain resilience capability factors across preparedness, response, recovery, and adaptation phases for China and Spain. Common factors identified in that study, such as government support and backup suppliers, align with this thesis's findings, where backup suppliers are conceptualized as supply base diversity.

The most distinctive empirical contribution of this thesis is the identification of twelve resilience capability factors specific to the SBSC and their classification into proactive and reactive capabilities operating across the readiness, response, and recovery phases. This study goes beyond identifying capabilities by explicitly examining how persistent structural, economic, and institutional challenges undermine or constrain these capabilities.

6.5 Theoretical Contribution

The Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV) was first introduced by Teece et al., (1997) focuses on how firms sustain competitive advantage in dynamic environments. This framework extended the Resource-Based View (RBV) of Barney (1991) by emphasising a firm's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competencies to adapt to changing conditions. DCV highlights the role of organisational routines, path dependencies, and firm-specific assets in driving innovation and strategic change.

Teece et al., (2007) further refined the DCV by formalizing it into three stages: sensing, seizing, and transforming. Sensing involves identifying opportunities and threats in the environment. Seizing focuses on mobilizing resources to capture opportunities and mitigate risks. Transforming entails the continuous renewal and reconfiguration of assets and capabilities to maintain competitiveness.

Hendry et al., (2019) applied the DCV framework using the stages of sensing, seizing, and transforming to analyse the resilience of local food supply chains in response to the constitutional change brought about by Brexit. Their research specifically focused on how supply chain actors anticipated the impacts of Brexit (sensing), adapted by implementing strategic changes (seizing), and reconfigured their operations to enhance resilience (transforming). However, their application of DCV was tailored to a singular, well-defined disruption of constitutional change, limiting its broader applicability to other complex and multifaceted supply chain disruptions.

Applying the DCV framework as developed by Teece et al., (2007) to the entire SBSC presented several limitations. The framework was originally designed to analyse firm-specific strategic capabilities rather than the collective dynamics of a decentralized supply chain. The Scottish beef industry comprises diverse,

independent actors: livestock farmers, processors, auctioneers, and retailers each with distinct priorities and capabilities. The firm-centric focus of the DCV does not fully capture the interdependencies, collaborative networks, and governance structures critical for managing resilience across an entire supply chain. Moreover, the linear progression of sensing, seizing, and transforming may not reflect the iterative and concurrent processes involved in supply chain resilience, where proactive and reactive measures often co-occur for instance, the preservation of embryos can be a proactive measure used as reactive capability as a Contingency against a disease outbreak to recover by having the same genetics.

This research makes a primary theoretical contribution by advancing the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV) beyond the traditional assumption of sequentially, particularly within decentralized agri-food supply chain. This thesis demonstrates that in a continuous sectoral context, SBSC operates through fragmented routines where independent actors occupy different stages of the DCV cycle simultaneously.

The empirical evidence from the SBSC suggests that the micro foundations of dynamic capabilities do not follow a structured, chronological path for all actors. Instead, sensing, seizing, and transforming are enacted independently based on localized risks and the specific operational environment of each player. This fragmentation is often compounded by the lack of centralized data as highlighted in this interview extract *“No, no, there's not one common database that they can all access to get all that information” (IP3).*

In SBSC the livestock Farmers are in a continuous "sensing" phase regarding biological security, highlighted by sudden disruptions such as the detection of Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE) in Dumfries (BBC News, 2024). They respond with transformative readiness routines by preserving embryos *“We have put a lot of embryos into long-term storage. If we get an outbreak of disease, it won't take us long to rebuild the same genetic basis we have now”IP5.* This transformation of the resource base occurs proactively before a formal recovery phase is even triggered.

While farmers sense biological threats, retailers are in a "seizing" phase to mitigate the strategic risk of a decreasing national herd. One retailer explained their proactive response through integrated supply models *“We actually have an integrated beef scheme which we operate. I think ultimately how we can give longevity to our supply base by utilising it and growing that arm of the business will only help to bolster the supply chain as a whole”IP17.*

The processors were transforming their resources for logistical capabilities simultaneously to avoid driver shortages as reflected in this comment *“But in terms of getting product to market, we have sufficient spare vehicles, all the struggle for drivers, but we've got sufficient vehicles to cover our delivery network with reserves and vehicles back at Depot for loading up for the next day”IP13.*

On the contrary the retailers do not foresee logistical issues as a disruption as shown in the interview extract.

“So we have our fleet of transport, so we have our own livestock haulage vehicles and so we don't see ripple effects from any transport problems or any strikes, etcetera, So I think that's probably all of the disruptions sort of in a nutshell, I'd say”IP17.

The comparative analysis in Table 6.1 highlights a fundamental shift from the traditional, sequential application of the DCV to the non-sequential reality of the SBSC. In the case of a one-off disruption like Brexit, Hendry et al., (2019) observed that supply chain actors moved in a synchronized, sequential manner, where sensing, seizing, and transforming acted as a unified progression across all tiers.

In contrast, the SBSC demonstrated a fragmented enactment of these capabilities, where different players occupy different stages of the DCV cycle simultaneously based on localized risks.

DCV Phase	Hendry et al., (2019) Sequential application	Scottish Beef Supply Chain-Non-Sequential application
Sensing	Unified and collective sensing across supply chain tiers. Actors simultaneously identified Brexit-related threats (e.g. labour shortages, subsidy uncertainty) to anticipate a defined constitutional deadline.	Fragmented and actor-specific sensing. Farmers primarily sense biological and disease-related risks while retailers sense long-term supply risks arising from declining herd numbers.
Seizing	Coordinated seizing behaviour, with supply chain actors reacting as a unit by developing new local market channels to capitalise on increased demand for domestic food.	Actor-specific seizing. Retailers seize opportunities through integrated beef and long-term supplier schemes to secure future supply, while other actors remain in sensing or reactive modes.
Transforming	Transformation treated as a final, downstream stage, where resources and relationships were collectively reconfigured after sensing and seizing were completed	Processors transform logistical assets to bypass strikes while farmers transform genetics proactively.

Execution	The whole chain moves through steps together in response to a one-off event.	Non sequential transformation. Processors reconfigure logistical assets to bypass transport disruptions and strikes. while farmers simultaneously transform herd genetics through embryo preservation as both a proactive and recovery strategy
-----------	--	---

Table 6.1 DCV Application Sequential vs Non sequential path

In this research, the DCV framework was elaborated by integrating both proactive and reactive capability factors of the resilience of the SBSC as conceptualised by Chaudhry and Quddus (2016). This adaptation categorises resilience capabilities into proactive and reactive strategies. Proactive capabilities include preparedness measures and reactive capabilities involve adaptive responses to disruptions.

This adaptation aligns with Ketokivi and Choi’s (2014) guidance on theory elaboration by refining an existing theory (DCV) through empirical insights rather than generating new theoretical models from scratch. The elaboration acknowledges that resilience is not solely a function of firm-specific capabilities but also emerges from the collective dynamics and interdependencies across supply chain actors.

Following Ketokivi and Choi’s (2014) argument for theory elaboration this research contributes to the theoretical elaboration of supply chain resilience by extending the Dynamic Capabilities View beyond firm-level analysis to capture the collective dynamics of an entire supply chain and highlighting its limited application when the unit of analysis is the entire supply chain. Due to the current linear progression by a firm from one stage to another, an amendment is proposed in the DCV to introduce a framework which allows the collective sensing, seizing, and transforming of opportunities and threats at a supply chain level.

6.6 Recommendations

The recommendations proposed in this section are grounded in the empirical findings of the study and reflect the perspectives of multiple stakeholders across the SBSC, including livestock farmers, processors, auctioneers, retailers, industry bodies, and policymakers. While several recommendations require government involvement due to the structural and policy-driven nature of the challenges identified, the findings clearly indicate that supply chain resilience cannot be enhanced through policy intervention alone. Instead, resilience must be co-produced through coordinated actions by all stakeholders who collectively shape the functioning of the SBSC. The recommendations therefore address both stakeholder-specific needs and shared systemic challenges, highlighting areas where collective priorities align.

6.6.1 Reform Agricultural Subsidies to Incentivize Efficiency and Innovation

This recommendation is primarily informed by the perspectives of livestock farmers, policymakers, and industry experts, who consistently identified low financial returns as the most critical vulnerability within the SBSC. Farmers, as the most fragmented and financially exposed actors in the supply chain, experience limited capacity to invest in productivity improvements, innovation, and resilience-building practices. Although existing subsidy schemes provide essential income stability, the findings demonstrate that they are largely designed to offer financial relief rather than incentivise efficiency, innovation, or long-term adaptation.

Reforming agricultural subsidies is therefore crucial to addressing farmers' structural dependence on support payments while simultaneously strengthening their productive and adaptive capacity. Linking subsidies to measurable performance outcomes such as productivity improvements, environmental stewardship, data engagement, and resilience-enhancing practices would directly address farmers' need for sustainable profitability. From a supply chain perspective, improving on-farm efficiency benefits processors and retailers by stabilising supply volumes and quality, thereby addressing a shared need for continuity and predictability across the SBSC.

By aligning subsidies with performance outcomes, this approach would foster a culture of continuous improvement, reducing dependency on government support and strengthening the overall resilience of the SBSC.

6.6.2 Creation of a Centralized and User-Friendly Database

The recommendation for a centralised and user-friendly database reflects a shared concern among farmers, processors, auctioneers, retailers, and industry bodies regarding fragmented data, limited transparency, and weak information flows across the SBSC. Farmers highlighted the administrative burden and limited practical value of existing data systems, while downstream actors emphasised the lack of integrated information to support traceability, forecasting, and risk management.

The creation of a centralised platform is therefore crucial to addressing the collective need for improved transparency, coordination, and decision-making. For farmers, a simplified and automated system would reduce administrative workload and support better herd management and performance monitoring. For processors and retailers, improved data access would enhance supply planning, quality assurance, and traceability, strengthening both operational efficiency and consumer trust. For policymakers and regulators, integrated data would enable more responsive and evidence-based policy interventions.

Importantly, the findings suggest that industry bodies such as Quality Meat Scotland (QMS) and Scotland's Rural College (SRUC) have a critical enabling role in supporting this recommendation. Beyond system development, these organisations can provide training, advisory services, and data interpretation support, ensuring that farmers are not merely data providers but active users of information for resilience-building purposes.

6.6.3 Creation of Future Markets

This recommendation primarily addresses the needs of farmers and processors, who identified price volatility and financial uncertainty as major constraints on resilience. The absence of a domestic futures market in Scotland leaves many stakeholders, particularly smaller farmers, exposed to market shocks and reliant on reactive coping strategies. There are no futures market in Scotland's beef industry, therefore it is important to enhance stakeholders' understanding and use of existing global futures markets for effective price risk management. In the short term, it is recommended that the Scottish Government, in collaboration with industry bodies such as Quality Meat Scotland (QMS) launch targeted awareness and education programs to inform farmers, processors, and retailers about the benefits of futures trading. Additionally, the Scottish Government could explore forming strategic partnerships with established global futures markets like the CME (Chicago Mercantile Exchange) to facilitate easier access for Scottish producers and processors. Such partnerships could involve negotiated agreements that lower participation costs or simplify the process for Scottish businesses to engage with international futures markets. This collaboration would offer immediate risk management solutions while Scotland works towards developing its own futures market infrastructure. By promoting the use of existing futures markets and pursuing strategic partnerships, the SBSC can begin to mitigate price volatility and financial risks, supporting greater stability and long-term sustainability in the sector. This would initiate a risk management culture in the SBSC by integrating the small farmers which lack the financial sophistication to hedge against their risk and are reactive.

6.6.4 Promote Supply Chain Fairness

The recommendation to promote supply chain fairness emerges strongly from farmers' and processors' accounts of power asymmetries, perceived unfair pricing, and a lack of trust within the SBSC. Retailer and processor dominance was repeatedly identified as undermining transparency, collaboration, and long-term relationship-building, all of which are critical drivers of resilience. The SBSC currently faces significant challenges related to fairness and profit distribution among its key stakeholders.

Addressing these imbalances requires fostering open and honest dialogue among all supply chain actors. Facilitated forums for communication between farmers, finishers, processors, and retailers should be established to openly discuss pricing strategies, cost pressures, and market expectations. Quality Meat Scotland (QMS) should adopt more neutral and independent mechanisms for representing the collective interests of the entire supply chain. Introducing independent mediators or creating a stakeholder advisory board could help ensure that all parties have a fair voice in discussions about industry reforms.

In addition to improving communication, there is a need for closer collaboration between processors and retailers. This collaboration could involve exploring fair pricing models and profit-sharing arrangements that distribute risks and rewards more evenly across the supply chain. Transparent agreements on pricing could help alleviate the financial pressures felt by producers and processors without forcing retailers to absorb unsustainable costs. To support these changes, the Scottish Government could implement policies that encourage fair trading practices and promote transparency in pricing throughout the supply chain. These policies should aim to protect producers from disproportionate market pressures while encouraging retailers to engage in practices that sustain the entire industry.

6.6.5 Enhancing Disease Preparedness and Biosecurity Measures

The SBSC is critically underprepared for managing disease outbreaks, posing a significant threat to its resilience and sustainability. This vulnerability was consistently highlighted by industry stakeholders. It is imperative that Scottish Government and industry bodies like Quality Meat Scotland (QMS), should prioritize the development and implementation of comprehensive disease preparedness and biosecurity frameworks. This should include mandatory biosecurity protocols at the farm level, such as routine disinfection practices, regular risk assessments, and biosecurity audits. Additionally, investment in farmer education and training programs focused on disease prevention and response is crucial to fostering a culture of proactive risk management.

6.6.6 Formulation of Long-Term Policies

The resilience of the SBSC is significantly shaped by government policies and the level of long-term support provided to farmers. Various stakeholders along the supply chain have raised concerns regarding the unpredictability and ambiguity of current agricultural policies, which directly affects farmers' confidence and investment choices. Owing to the post-Brexit reform of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), have dissuaded farmers from committing to essential investments in infrastructure and innovation. Without stable and predictable policy frameworks, farmers are reluctant to invest in essential developments like modern cattle facilities or sustainable farming technologies. Moreover, the fragmented nature of

governmental decision-making complicates the agricultural policy landscape further. The lack of collaboration between the Rural and Islands Committee and the Net Zero Committee surfaced in the research findings. This lack of policy coherence leads to inconsistencies in legislative actions, undermining the strategic alignment necessary to effectively support the beef industry. It is recommended that the Scottish Government establish a long-term, transparent, and consistent agricultural policy framework. This should encompass multi-year support programs aligned with sustainability and productivity objectives, empowering farmers to invest in infrastructure, technology, and sustainable practices. Furthermore, government support should be contingent on active agricultural engagement to ensure that subsidies promote meaningful production outcomes. To enhance policy coherence, stronger collaboration between relevant parliamentary committees is essential. Cross-sectoral committees, such as the Rural and Islands Committee and the Net Zero Committee, must work collaboratively to develop integrated policies that reconcile environmental targets with agricultural sustainability. This alignment would ensure that agricultural policies are supportive rather than restrictive, enabling farmers to contribute to climate goals without compromising their economic viability. By fostering policy stability and improving cross-sectoral collaboration, the SBSC can bolster its resilience against economic uncertainties and environmental challenges. This long-term strategic support is crucial for maintaining Scotland's standing as a leading producer of high-quality beef while ensuring the sustainability of its farming communities.

6.7 Stakeholder Implications and Recommendations

The findings of this study demonstrate that enhancing resilience in the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC) requires coordinated action across multiple stakeholders. While several recommendations necessitate government facilitation due to the structural and policy-driven nature of the challenges identified, the empirical evidence clearly indicates that resilience cannot be achieved through government intervention alone. Instead, resilience emerges through the collective and coordinated actions of supply chain actors.

Policymakers can use the study's insights to design agricultural policies that support efficiency, innovation, and fair-trading practices. This includes aligning subsidy mechanisms with productivity and resilience objectives, investing in infrastructure and disease preparedness, and supporting institutional arrangements that promote collaboration and transparency across the supply chain.

Livestock farmers as the most structurally constrained actors within the SBSC, have a central role in strengthening resilience. Beyond policy reform, farmers can enhance resilience through greater collaboration, including engagement in farmer-led cooperatives, peer-to-peer learning networks, and collective marketing initiatives. Improved engagement with data systems, performance benchmarking, and

carcass-based KPIs would support more informed decision-making, improve efficiency, and strengthen farm-level adaptive capacity.

Auction marts can contribute by evolving their role beyond transactional marketplaces to act as hubs for information exchange. By facilitating standardised feedback mechanisms between store producers and finishers, marts can reduce information asymmetries, improve transparency, and support more responsive livestock management decisions upstream.

Processors can strengthen supply chain resilience by improving transparency in carcass specifications, supporting supply forecasting, and engaging in collaborative risk management initiatives with upstream actors. More stable and transparent relationships with producers would help mitigate market volatility, support farm viability, and ensure the long-term continuity of supply upon which processing capacity depends.

Retailers play a significant role in shaping supply chain dynamics through sourcing practices and pricing strategies. The findings suggest that longer-term sourcing relationships, fairer pricing structures, and greater transparency regarding demand forecasting and specification changes would reduce uncertainty upstream and support improved preparedness and coordination across the SBSC.

Consumers can also benefit from the study's findings by gaining a more comprehensive understanding of the Scottish beef industry. The research highlights the value of the industry's traceability systems, quality assurance certifications, and the dedication of farmers to sustainable production practices. This knowledge could strengthen consumer confidence in Scottish beef, promoting its value and supporting the long-term growth of the industry.

6.8 Research Limitations

This research, while providing valuable insights into the resilience of the SBSC, acknowledges limitations that need to be considered when interpreting the findings.

Firstly, the sample size of 25 interviewees, while representative of various stakeholder groups, may not capture the full diversity of perspectives within the industry. The focus on qualitative data, provides rich insights, but limits the generalizability of findings compared to quantitative studies with larger datasets.

Secondly, the research primarily captures current resilience capabilities and challenges, which may evolve over time due to external factors such as climate change, policy reforms, and market shifts.

Thirdly, the research is time-bound, therefore the findings may change over time due to external factors such as policy changes, market shifts, and climate change.

6.9 Recommendations for Future Research

This research has provided a comprehensive insight into the SBSC. While the findings make significant empirical and theoretical contributions, they also open several important avenues for future research that can build upon, test, and extend the insights generated by this work.

A key direction for future research is the use of quantitative methods to complement and extend the qualitative findings of this study. The present research has identified and theoretically grounded a set of resilience capability drivers such as traceability, transparency, redundancy, supplier relationships, and government support and has empirically demonstrated how these capabilities are constrained by persistent structural and systemic challenges, including low profitability, power imbalances, regulatory uncertainty, and limited technological adoption. These findings provide a robust conceptual foundation for future quantitative research by clearly specifying constructs, relationships, and contextual conditions that can now be operationalised and empirically tested at scale.

Future quantitative studies could, for example, develop and validate survey instruments based on the resilience capability framework articulated in this thesis. Such research would allow for the statistical examination of relationships between identified resilience capabilities and performance outcomes such as continuity, recovery speed, adaptability, or financial stability. Quantitative analysis could also assess the relative strength and significance of different resilience drivers across stakeholder groups, thereby confirming, refining, or challenging the patterns identified qualitatively. In this way, quantitative research would not replace the insights of this study, but rather confirm their generalisability, test their robustness, and identify variation across contexts, thereby enriching the overall understanding of resilience in agri-food supply chains.

The recommendation for future research to adopt the firm as a unit of analysis should not be interpreted as contradictory to the holistic, supply chain-level perspective advanced in this thesis. Rather, it represents a complementary and multi-level research strategy. This study has demonstrated that resilience in the SBSC cannot be fully understood by examining isolated firms, as resilience emerges from interdependencies of the supply chain players. However, the findings also reveal that resilience capabilities are unevenly distributed across actors, with farmers, processors, auction marts, and retailers exhibiting different capacities, constraints, and strategic priorities.

Future firm-level research could therefore provide more granular insight into how individual actors develop, deploy, or are constrained in building resilience capabilities within the broader system. For example, firm-level studies could explore how different types of farms e.g. small-scale versus large-scale, operationalise risk management, technology adoption, or collaboration, and how these micro-level practices aggregate or

fail to aggregate into supply chain-level resilience. Such studies would allow researchers to examine how localised capabilities interact with systemic challenges, thereby strengthening, rather than undermining, the holistic perspective advanced in this thesis.

Importantly, this research lays the groundwork for mixed-method and multi-level research designs that explicitly integrate firm-level and supply chain-level analysis. Future studies could adopt sequential or concurrent mixed-method approaches, using quantitative surveys to map patterns across the SBSC. This would enable a deeper exploration of how collective sensing, seizing, and transforming processes proposed in this thesis as an extension of the Dynamic Capabilities View are enacted across decentralised and fragmented supply chains.

While this study focused on the challenges and the capabilities of supply chain resilience within the Scottish Beef Supply Chain (SBSC), it recognises the growing call in the literature to adopt a broader systems view of resilience one that integrates social and ecological dimensions (Wieland and Durach, 2021). The concept of socio-ecological resilience views supply chains as embedded within both human systems (e.g. institutions, communities, governance structures) and ecological systems (e.g. land use, biodiversity, climate impacts). Future research could build on the findings of this study by explicitly adopting a socio-ecological systems framework to examine how interactions between social actors, environmental constraints, and institutional settings influence long-term resilience in agri-food supply chains.

The future research could examine the role of genetic diversity in livestock, particularly the establishment of centralised databases for embryo storage, to strengthen resilience against disease outbreaks.

7 References

- A.K. Stoddart (2025) *Stoddart's: The Best in Beef*. Akstoddart.co.uk. Available at: <https://www.akstoddart.co.uk/> [Accessed 18 Dec. 2025].
- Aberdeen Angus Cattle Society (2024) Sire Verification - Aberdeen-Angus Cattle Society Available at: <https://aberdeen-angus.co.uk/sire-verification> [Accessed 01 November 2024].
- Aboah, J., Wilson, M.M., Rich, K.M. and Lyne, M.C., (2019) Operationalising resilience in tropical agricultural value chains. *Supply Chain Management: an international journal*, 24(2), pp.271-300.
- ABP Food Group. (2023). ABP acquires Scotbeef Sites. Available at: <https://abpfoodgroup.com/news/abp-acquires-scotbeef-sites/> [Accessed 18 October 2024].
- ABP Food Group. (2024). About Us. Available at: <https://abpfoodgroup.com/about-us/> [Accessed 18 October 2024].
- ABSF (2024) ABSF Annual Update 2024 Available at: <https://www.sustainableaustralianbeef.com.au/globalassets/beef-sustainability/documents/absf-annual-update-2024-web.pdf> [Accessed 15 July 2024].
- Adger, W.N., (2000) Social and ecological resilience: are they related? *Progress in human geography*, 24(3), pp.347-364.
- Adobor, H. and McMullen, R.S., (2018) Supply chain resilience: a dynamic and multidimensional approach. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 29(4), pp.1451-1471.
- Adobor, H., (2019) Supply chain resilience: a multi-level framework. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 22(6), pp.533-556.
- AHDB (2023) Beef Carcase classification. Available at: <https://ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/beef-carcase-classification> Beef carcase classification | AHDB [Accessed 01 January 2024].
- AHDB (2024) UN gives pathways towards lower livestock emissions | AHDB. Available at: <https://ahdb.org.uk/news/un-gives-pathways-towards-lower-livestock-emissions> [Accessed 22 December 2024].
- ALDI (2024) *Aldi to invest £3 billion in British beef suppliers*, ALDI UK Press Office. Available at: <https://www.aldipresscentre.co.uk/business-news/aldi-to-invest-3-billion-in-british-beef-suppliers/> [Accessed 21 December 2025].

- ALDI (2024) Best of Scotland | ALDI UK Available at: <https://www.aldi.co.uk/scotland> [Accessed 18 October 2024].
- Ali, A., Mahfouz, A. and Arisha, A., (2017) Analysing supply chain resilience: integrating the constructs in a concept mapping framework via a systematic literature review. *Supply chain management: an international journal*, 22(1), pp.16-39.
- Ali, I. and Gölgeci, I., (2019) Where is supply chain resilience research heading? A systematic and co-occurrence analysis. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 49(8), pp.793-815.
- Ali, I. and Govindan, K., (2023) Extenuating operational risks through digital transformation of agri-food supply chains. *Production Planning & Control*, 34(12), pp.1165-1177.
- Ali, I., Golgeci, I. and Arslan, A., (2021) Achieving resilience through knowledge management practices and risk management culture in agri-food supply chains. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 28(2), pp.284-299.
- Ali, I., Nagalingam, S. and Gurd, B., (2018) A resilience model for cold chain logistics of perishable products. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 29(3), pp.922-941.
- Ali, I., Sadiddin, A. and Cattaneo, A., (2023) Risk and resilience in agri-food supply chain SMEs in the pandemic era: a cross-country study. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 26(11), pp.1602-1620.
- Amaglobeli, D., Benson, T. and Moguees, T., (2024) Agricultural producer subsidies: Navigating challenges and policy considerations. Available at: [https://www.elibrary.imf.org/view/journals/068/2024/002/article-A001-en.xml?ArticleTabs=related%20documentsIssue 002](https://www.elibrary.imf.org/view/journals/068/2024/002/article-A001-en.xml?ArticleTabs=related%20documentsIssue%20002) [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- Ambulkar, S., Blackhurst, J. and Grawe, S., (2015) Firm's resilience to supply chain disruptions: Scale development and empirical examination. *Journal of operations management*, 33, pp.111-122.
- ANM Group (2024) About Us. Available at: <https://www.anmarts.co.uk/about/> [Accessed 18 Oct 2024].
- Bakshi, Swinney, and Tuna (2023) Building supply chain resilience through vertical control. Available at: SSRN 4511024.

- Balfour, S. (2024) *Agribusiness News August 2024 - Management Matters: Auction Marts | Helping farmers in Scotland*. [online]. FAS. Available at: <https://www.fas.scot/article/agribusiness-news-august-2024-management-matters-auction-marts/> [Accessed 18 January 2026].
- Barnett, J., Begen, F., Howes, S., Regan, A., McConnon, A., Marcu, A., Rowntree, S. and Verbeke, W., (2016) Consumers' confidence, reflections and response strategies following the horsemeat incident. *Food Control*, 59, pp.721-730.
- Barney, J., (1991) Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage. *Journal of Management*.
- Barrett, C.B. and Constan, M.A., (2014) Toward a theory of resilience for international development applications. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(40), pp.14625-14630.
- BBC (2023) a Scottish university UWS targeted by cyber attackers Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-scotland-glasgow-west-66327336> [Accessed 20 August 2023].
- BBC (2023) University of Manchester hit by cyber-attack Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-england-manchester-65855002> [Accessed 20 August 2023].
- BBC News (2024) BBC News (2024) Single case of BSE confirmed in cow on Dumfries and Galloway farm [Accessed 07 December 2024].
- Bell, E., Bryman, A. and Harley, B., (2022) *Business research methods*. Oxford university press.
- Blackhurst, J., Dunn, K.S. and Craighead, C.W., (2011) An empirically derived framework of global supply resiliency. *Journal of business logistics*, 32(4), pp.374-391.
- Bode, C., Wagner, S.M., Petersen, K.J. and Ellram, L.M., (2011) Understanding responses to supply chain disruptions: Insights from information processing and resource dependence perspectives. *Academy of Management Journal*, 54(4), pp.833-856.
- Brandon-Jones, E., Squire, B., Autry, C.W. and Petersen, K.J., (2014) A contingent resource-based perspective of supply chain resilience and robustness. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 50(3), pp.55-73.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2022). *Thematic Analysis: a Practical Guide*. London: SAGE.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V., (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), pp.77-101.

- Braun, V. and Clarke, V., (2021) To saturate or not to saturate? Questioning data saturation as a useful concept for thematic analysis and sample-size rationales. *Qualitative research in sport, exercise and health*, 13(2), pp.201-216.
- Brush, T.H. and Artz, K.W., (1999) Toward a contingent resource-based theory: the impact of information asymmetry on the value of capabilities in veterinary medicine. *Strategic Management Journal*, 20(3), pp.223-250.
- Brusset, X. and Teller, C., (2017) Supply chain capabilities, risks, and resilience. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 184, pp.59-68.
- BVA (2024) Single case of atypical BSE confirmed in Scotland Available at: <https://www.bva.co.uk/news-and-blog/news-article/single-case-of-atypical-bse-confirmed-in-scotland/> [Accessed 07 December 2024].
- Cabral, I., Grilo, A. and Cruz-Machado, V., (2012) A decision-making model for lean, agile, resilient and green supply chain management. *International Journal of Production Research*, 50(17), pp.4830-4845.
- Caledonian Marts Ltd (2024) Our History. Available at: <https://www.caledonian-marts.com/Livestock> [Accessed 18 October 2024].
- Carpenter, J. and Lynch, L., (2002) Is There a Critical Mass of Agricultural Land Needed to Sustain an Agricultural Economy? Evidence from Six Mid-Atlantic States. Maryland Center for Agroecology, Inc.
- Carter, N., Bryant-Lukosius, D., DiCenso, A., Blythe, J. and Neville, A.J., (2014) September. The use of triangulation in qualitative research. In *Oncology Nursing Forum* (Vol. 41, No. 5, pp. 545-547).
- Carvalho, H., Cruz-Machado, V. and Tavares, J.G., (2012) A mapping framework for assessing supply chain resilience. *International Journal of Logistics Systems and Management*, 12(3), pp.354-373.
- Casey, C., (2013) *Work, self and society: After industrialism*. Routledge.
- Castillo, C., (2022) Is there a theory of supply chain resilience? A bibliometric analysis of the literature. *International journal of operations & production management*, 43(1), pp.22-47.
- CCC (2022) Progress in reducing emissions in Scotland 2022 Report to Parliament Available at: <https://www.theccc.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Progress-in-reducing-emissions-in-Scotland-2022-Report-to-Parliament.pdf> [Accessed 30 January 2023]
- Choi, T.Y. and Hong, Y., (2002) Unveiling the structure of supply networks: case studies in Honda, Acura, and DaimlerChrysler. *Journal of Operations Management*, 20(5), pp.469-493.

- Choi, T.Y., Dooley, K.J. and Rungtusanatham, M., (2001) Supply networks and complex adaptive systems: control versus emergence. *Journal of operations management*, 19(3), pp.351-366.
- Chopra, S. and Sodhi, M.S., (2004) Managing risk to avoid supply-chain HDdown. *MIT Sloan management review*.
- Chowdhury, M.M.H. and Quaddus, M., (2017) Supply chain resilience: Conceptualization and scale development using dynamic capability theory. *International journal of production economics*, 188, pp.185-204.
- Christopher, M. and Peck, H., (2004) Building the Resilient Supply Chain. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 15(2), pp.1-14.
- Christopher, M. and Rutherford, C., (2004) Creating supply chain resilience through agile six sigma. *Critical eye*, 7(1), pp.24-28.
- CIGAR (2024) Sustainable Livestock Farming Practices for Resilience Available at: <https://alliancebioiversityciat.org/stories/sustainable-livestock-farming-practices-resilience> [Accessed 15 November 2024].
- CMA (2023) *Completed acquisition by Anglo Beef Processors UK of certain assets of Scotbeef Limited Decision on relevant merger situation and substantial lessening of competition*. [online]. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6579cbba095987000d95e03d/ABP_Scotbeef_-_Phase_1_decision_-_non-confidential_for_PUBLICATION_2.pdf. [Accessed 28 December 2025].
- Craighead, C.W., Blackhurst, J., Rungtusanatham, M.J. and Handfield, R.B., (2007) The severity of supply chain disruptions: design characteristics and mitigation capabilities. *Decision sciences*, 38(1), pp.131-156.
- Daily Business (2024) Browns buys Stoddart's stake in expansion drive. Available at: <https://dailybusinessgroup.co.uk/2024/06/browns-buys-stoddarts-stake-in-expansion-drive> [Accessed 25 October 2024].
- Darnhofer, I., Fairweather, J. and Moller, H., (2010) Assessing a farm's sustainability: insights from resilience thinking. *International journal of agricultural sustainability*, 8(3), pp.186-198.
- Day, J.M., (2014) Fostering emergent resilience: the complex adaptive supply network of disaster relief. *International Journal of Production Research*, 52(7), pp.1970-1988.

- DEFRA (2024) *UK Food Security Index 2024*. [online]. GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-food-security-index-2024/uk-food-security-index-2024>. [Accessed 10 January 2026].
- DEFRA (2025) Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs : *A UK government food strategy for England, considering the wider UK Food System*, GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/a-uk-government-food-strategy-for-england/a-uk-government-food-strategy-for-england-considering-the-wider-uk-food-system> [Accessed 17 January 2026].
- Dickinson, G., (2001) Enterprise risk management: Its origins and conceptual foundation. *The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance. Issues and Practice*, 26(3), pp.360-366.
- Diener, E. and Crandall, R., (1978) *Ethics in social and behavioral research*. U Chicago Press.
- Dingwall & Highland Marts Ltd (2024) *Livestock Sales*. Available at: <https://dingwallhighlandmarts.com> [Accessed 18 October 2024].
- Donaldson, L., (2001) *The contingency theory of organizations* Sage Publications. Thousand Oaks, CA, USA.
- Dubey, R., Gunasekaran, A., Childe, S.J., Papadopoulos, T., Blome, C. and Luo, Z., (2017) Antecedents of resilient supply chains: An empirical study. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 66(1), pp.8-19.
- Dunbia (2024) *Our Locations*. Available at: <https://dunbia.com/our-locations/> [Accessed 25 October 2024].
- Durach, C.F., Wieland, A. and Machuca, J.A., (2015) Antecedents and dimensions of supply chain robustness: a systematic literature review. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 45(1/2), pp.118-137.
- Dyer, J.H. and Singh, H., (1998) The relational view: Cooperative strategy and sources of interorganizational competitive advantage. *Academy of management review*, 23(4), pp.660-679.
- Edirisinghe, N.C.P., Bichescu, B. and Shi, X., (2011) Equilibrium analysis of supply chain structures under power imbalance. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 214(3), pp.568-578.
- Eisenhardt, K.M. and Graebner, M.E., (2007) Theory building from cases: Opportunities and challenges. *Academy of management journal*, 50(1), pp.25-32.

EPIC (2014) “What will the Scottish cattle industry look like in 2040 and how resilient will it be to livestock disease?” Available at: <https://www.epicscotland.org/media/pgvjabf4/epic-cattle-industry-scenario-planning-report.pdf> [Accessed 30 November 2024].

Ericksen, P.J., (2008) Conceptualizing food systems for global environmental change research. *Global environmental change*, 18(1), pp.234-245.

Farm Advisory Service (FAS) (2023) Beef finishing systems. [online] Available at: <https://www.fas.scot/publication/beef-finishing-systems/> [Accessed 2 December 2025].

Farmers Weekly (2021) Productive farms being sold to investors for planting trees Available at: <https://www.fwi.co.uk/business/markets-and-trends/land-markets/productive-farms-being-sold-to-investors-for-planting-trees> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

Farmers Weekly (2024) 'Productive farms being sold to investors for planting trees.' Farmers Weekly. Available at: <https://www.fwi.co.uk> [Accessed 22 December 2024].

Farming UK (2020) Aldi announces new way of sourcing Scotch beef - FarmingUK News Available at: https://www.farminguk.com/news/aldi-announces-new-way-of-sourcing-scotch-beef_54962.html [Accessed 18 October 2024].

FAS (2019) New Entrants Guide to Buying and Selling at the Mart Available at: <https://www.fas.scot/downloads/a-guide-to-buying-and-selling-at-the-mart/> [Accessed 2 December 2025].

FAS (2024) Rural Aid Schemes Available at: <https://www.fas.scot/downloads/fmh-june-2024-rural-aid/https://www.ruralpayments.org/publicsite/futures/topics/all-schemes/> [Accessed 22 December 2024].

Fiksel, J. and Fiksel, J., (2015) From risk to resilience (pp. 19-34). Island Press/Center for Resource Economics.

Fisher, D. (2011) “Japan disaster shakes up supply-chain strategies”, *Research and Ideas*, May 31,

Folke, C., Carpenter, S.R., Walker, B., Scheffer, M., Chapin, T. and Rockström, J., (2010) Resilience thinking: integrating resilience, adaptability and transformability. *Ecology and society*, 15(4).

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (2023) Pathways towards lower emissions – A global assessment of the greenhouse gas emissions and mitigation options from livestock agrifood systems. Rome. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc9029en> [Accessed 22 December 2024].

Fraser Hugh (2023) Changes to Livestock Supply chain infrastructure Available at: <https://www.nfus.org.uk/news/blog/changes-to-livestock-supply-chain-infrastructure> [Accessed 01 January 2024].

FSA (2022) FSA takes revised approach to shelf-life safety guidance for chilled fresh beef, lamb and pork following consultation | Food Standards Agency [Accessed 01 January 2024].

Gamechanger (2023) Gamechanging beef initiative gives security to Dairy Farmers, Farmers Weekly. Available at: <https://www.fwi.co.uk/livestock/beef/gamechanging-beef-initiative-gives-security-to-dairy-farmers> [Accessed 21 December 2025].

Ganguly A, Vlajic J. Knowledge sharing, knowledge reciprocity and supply chain resiliency: A conceptual discussion. In EurOMA Conference (2020) Managing Operations for Impact 2020 (pp. 1115-1125).

Garnett, P., Doherty, B. and Heron, T., (2020) Vulnerability of the United Kingdom's food supply chains exposed by COVID-19. *Nature Food*, 1(6), pp.315-318.

Geng, L., Xiao, R. and Xu, X., (2014) Research on MAS-Based Supply Chain Resilience and Its Self-Organized Criticality. *Discrete Dynamics in Nature and Society*, 2014(1), p.621341.

Gibbert, M., Ruigrok, W. and Wicki, B., (2008) What passes as a rigorous case study?. *Strategic management journal*, 29(13), pp.1465-1474.

Gioia, D.A., Corley, K.G. and Hamilton, A.L., (2013) Seeking qualitative rigor in inductive research: Notes on the Gioia methodology. *Organizational research methods*, 16(1), pp.15-31.

Glavee-Geo, R., Engelseth, P. and Buvik, A., (2022) Power imbalance and the dark side of the captive agri-food supplier-buyer relationship. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 178(3), pp.609-628.

Golgeci, I. and Y. Ponomarov, S., (2013) Does firm innovativeness enable effective responses to supply chain disruptions? An empirical study. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 18(6), pp.604-617.

Gov (2014) Beef 2020 Report - A Vision for the Beef Industry in Scotland Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/advice-and-guidance/2014/08/beef-2020-review-report/documents/00457906-pdf/00457906-pdf/govscot%3Adocument/00457906.pdf> [Accessed 01 January 2021].

Gov (2021) Scotland's Third Land Use Strategy 2021-2026

<https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2021/03/scotlands-third-land-use-strategy-2021-2026-getting-best-land/documents/scotlands-third-land-use-strategy-2021-2026-getting-best-land/scotlands-third-land-use-strategy-2021-2026-getting-best-land/govscot%3Adocument/scotlands-third-land-use-strategy-2021-2026-getting-best-land.pdf> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

Gov (2024) UK Food Security Index 2024 - GOV.UK Available at:

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-food-security-index-2024/uk-food-security-index-2024#overall-assessment-of-uk-food-security> [Accessed 15 July 2024].

Greer, A. and Grant, W., (2023) Divergence and continuity after Brexit in agriculture. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 30(11), pp.2326-2348.

Guba, E.G. and Lincoln, Y.S., (1994) Competing paradigms in qualitative research. *Handbook of qualitative research*, 2(163-194), p.105. Gunderson, L.H., 2000. Ecological resilience—in theory and application. *Annual review of ecology and systematics*, 31(1), pp.425-439.

Gunderson, L.H., (2000) Ecological resilience—in theory and application. *Annual review of ecology and systematics*, 31(1), pp.425-439.

Hall, J. (2024) *Less favoured areas – delivering for Scotland*. Available at:

[https://www.nfus.org.uk/userfiles/images/Policy/Support Payments/Less Favoured Areas – Delivering For Scotland v4 - low res.pdf](https://www.nfus.org.uk/userfiles/images/Policy/Support%20Payments/Less%20Favoured%20Areas%20-%20Delivering%20For%20Scotland%20v4%20-%20low%20res.pdf) [Accessed 21 December 2025].

Hamel, G. and Valikangas, L., (2004) The quest for resilience. *icade. Revista de la Facultad de Derecho*, (62), pp.355-358.

Hayes, D., Jacobs, K., Schulz, L. and Crespi, J., (2023) Resilience of US Cattle and Beef Sectors: Lessons from COVID-19. *Journal of Agricultural & Food Industrial Organization*, 21(1), pp.53-67.

Hendrickson, M.K., (2015) Resilience in a concentrated and consolidated food system. *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences*, 5(3), pp.418-431.

Hendry, L.C., Stevenson, M., MacBryde, J., Ball, P., Sayed, M. and Liu, L., (2019) Local food supply chain resilience to constitutional change: the Brexit effect. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 39(3), pp.429-453.

Herbane, B., Elliott, D. and Swartz, E.M., (2004) Business continuity management: time for a strategic role?. *Long range planning*, 37(5), pp.435-457.

- Hohenstein, N.O., Feisel, E., Hartmann, E. and Giunipero, L., (2015) Research on the phenomenon of supply chain resilience: a systematic review and paths for further investigation. *International journal of physical distribution & logistics management*, 45(1/2), pp.90-117.
- Holling, C.S., (1973) Resilience and Stability of Ecological Systems. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, pp.1-23.
- Hwang, D. and Min, H., (2015) Identifying the drivers of enterprise resource planning and assessing its impacts on supply chain performances. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 115(3), pp.541-569.
- IAAS (2025) Institute of Auctioneers and Appraisers in Scotland. Available at: <https://iaas.co.uk/> (Accessed: 21 December 2025).
- IAAS (2025). *Auction Marts | Institute of Auctioneers and Appraisers in Scotland*. Available at: <https://iaas.co.uk/members/category/auction-marts/> [Accessed 27 June 2025].
- Info Security (2024) University of Manchester CISO Speaks Out on Summer Cyber-Attack - Infosecurity Magazine Available at: <https://www.infosecurity-magazine.com/news/uni-manchester-ciso-cyber-attack/> [Accessed 20 August 2023].
- Ivanov, D., (2017) Revealing interfaces of supply chain resilience and sustainability: a simulation study. *International Journal of Production Research*, 56(10), pp.3507-3523.
- Ivanov, D., Dolgui, A. and Sokolov, B. (2019). The impact of digital technology and Industry 4.0 on the ripple effect and supply chain risk analytics. *International Journal of Production Research*, [online]. 57(3), pp.829–846.
- Ivanov, D., Tsipoulanidis, A. and Schönberger, J. (2021). *Global supply chain and operations management : a decision-oriented introduction to the creation of value*. Cham: Springer.
- Jalil, A., (2024) Peer-to-Peer Networks and Agricultural Conservation (Master's thesis, The Ohio State University).
- Jisc (2024) The impacts of a serious cyber incident go far beyond just financial costs . Available at: <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/news/all/the-impacts-of-a-serious-cyber-incident-go-far-beyond-just-financial-costs> [Accessed 20 August 2023].
- John Scott Meat. (2024) History. [online]. Available at: <https://www.johnscottmeat.com/history.html> [Accessed 18 October 2024].

- Johnson, N., Elliott, D. and Drake, P., (2013) Exploring the role of social capital in facilitating supply chain resilience. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 18(3), pp.324-336.
- Jordan, D. and Simpson, E. (2023) 'Food fraud probe into beef falsely labelled as British', *BBC News*, 9 March. Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/business-64904334> [Accessed 22 December 2024].
- Joshi, S. and Sharma, M., (2022) Digital technologies (DT) adoption in agri-food supply chains amidst COVID-19: an approach towards food security concerns in developing countries. *Journal of Global Operations and Strategic Sourcing*, 15(2), pp.262-282.
- Jüttner, U. and Maklan, S., (2011) Supply chain resilience in the global financial crisis: an empirical study. *Supply chain management: An international journal*, 16(4), pp.246-259.
- Kallio, H., Pietilä, A.M., Johnson, M. and Kangasniemi, M., (2016) Systematic methodological review: developing a framework for a qualitative semi-structured interview guide. *Journal of advanced nursing*, 72(12), pp.2954-2965.
- Kamalahmadi, M. and Parast, M.M., (2016) A review of the literature on the principles of enterprise and supply chain resilience: Major findings and directions for future research. *International journal of production economics*, 171, pp.116-133.
- Kamalapur, R., Lyth, D. and Houshyar, A., (2013) Benefits of CPFR and VMI collaboration strategies: a simulation study. *Journal of Operations and Supply Chain Management*, 6(2), pp.59-73.
- Kerslake, E., Kemper, J.A. and Conroy, D., (2022) What's your beef with meat substitutes? Exploring barriers and facilitators for meat substitutes in omnivores, vegetarians, and vegans. *Appetite*, 170, p.105864.
- Kolpakov, V., Ruchay, A., Kosyan, D. and Bukareva, E., (2024) Analysis of Runs of Homozygosity in Aberdeen Angus Cattle. *Animals*, 14(15), p.2153.
- Kumar, A. and Agrawal, S., (2023) Challenges and opportunities for agri-fresh food supply chain management in India. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 212, p.108161.
- Kumar, P. and Kumar Singh, R., (2022) Strategic framework for developing resilience in Agri-Food Supply Chains during COVID 19 pandemic. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 25(11), pp.1401-1424.
- I, M. and Wilson, M.M., (2024) Inherent and adaptive resilience of logistics operations in food supply chains. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 45(1), p.e12362.

Lau, F. and Kuziemsky, C., (2016) Handbook of eHealth evaluation: an evidence-based approach.

Lawrie and Symington Ltd (2024) About Us. Available at: <https://lawrieandsymington.com> [Accessed 18 October 2024].

Leat, P. and Revoredo-Giha, C., (2013) Risk and resilience in agri-food supply chains: The case of the ASDA PorkLink supply chain in Scotland. *Supply chain management: An international journal*, 18(2), pp.219-231.

Leat, P. and Revoredo-Giha, C., (2016) Changes in the market environment and implications for the supply chain: The case of Scottish beef. In *A Stakeholder Approach to Managing Food* (pp. 169-185). Routledge.

LeCompte, M.D. and Goetz, J.P., (1982) Problems of reliability and validity in ethnographic research. *Review of educational research*, 52(1), pp.31-60.

Lidl (2024) Our Scottish Suppliers Available at: <https://www.lidl.co.uk/c/our-scottish-suppliers/s10024805> [Accessed 30 October 2024].

Lidl (2024)a Backing British Farming Available at: <https://www.lidl.co.uk/c/backing-british-farming/s10025121> [Accessed 30 October 2024].

Lidl (2024)b LIDL GB BEEFING UP SUSTAINABILITY WITH £1.5 BILLION INVESTMENT IN BRITISH BEEF PRODUCTION Available at: <https://corporate.lidl.co.uk/media-centre/pressreleases/2024/lidl-gb-investing-1.5-billion-in-british-beef-production> [Accessed 30 October 2024].

M & S (2024) M&S Raises The Stakes With Unrivalled New British Beef Traceability Campaign Available at: <https://corporate.marksandspencer.com/media/press-releases/ms-raises-stakes-unrivalled-new-british-beef-traceability> [Accessed 30 October 2024].

M&S (2024) Our Approach to Animal Welfare2024 Available at: [2024/Our_Approach_to_Animal_Welfare2024%20v3.pdf](https://corporate.marksandspencer.com/media/press-releases/ms-raises-stakes-unrivalled-new-british-beef-traceability) [Accessed 30 October 2024].

Macdonald, I. (2024). Prime cattle numbers show short-term resilience in Scotland despite.... [online]. QMS. Available at: <https://qmscotland.co.uk/news/prime-cattle-numbers-show-short-term-resilience-in-scotland-despite-overall-herd-decline> [Accessed 30 October 2024].

Mackie Gemma (2021) Scottish Government officials accused of planning cull of 300,000 beef cattle Available at: <https://www.pressandjournal.co.uk/fp/business/farming/3079549/scottish-government-officials-accused-of-planning-cull-of-300000-beef-cattle/> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

Mandal, S., Sarathy, R., Korasiga, V.R., Bhattacharya, S. and Dastidar, S.G., (2016) Achieving supply chain resilience: The contribution of logistics and supply chain capabilities. *International Journal of Disaster Resilience in the Built Environment*, 7(5), pp.544-562.

Manuele, F.A., (2005) Risk assessment & hierarchies of control. *Professional safety*, 50(5), pp.33-39.

Marshall, B., Cardon, P., Poddar, A. and Fontenot, R., (2013) Does sample size matter in qualitative research?: A review of qualitative interviews in IS research. *Journal of computer information systems*, 54(1), pp.11-22.

Mascaritolo, J. and Holcomb, M.C., (2008) Moving towards a resilient supply chain. *Journal of Transportation Management*, 19(2), p.7.

Maye, D. and Chan, K.W., (2020) On-farm biosecurity in livestock production: farmer behaviour, cultural identities and practices of care. *Emerging topics in life sciences*, 4(5), pp.521-530.

Meat Management (2022) Meat Management (2022) Princess Royal opens Dunbia Highland Meats plant following £12m upgrade Available at: <https://meatmanagement.com/news/princess-royal-opens-dunbia-highland-meats-plant-following-12m-upgrade/60417.article> [Accessed 25 October 2024].

Millers of Speyside. (2024) About Us. [online]. Available at: <https://millersofspeyside.co.uk/about-us/> [Accessed 18 October 2024].

Montanyà, O. and Amat, O., (2023) The resilience factors of the agri-food supply chain: An integrative review of the literature in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Intangible Capital*, 19(3), pp.379-392.

Morrison (2024) Beef Farmers - Morrisons Farming Available <https://www.morrisons-farming.com/our-farmers/beef/> [Accessed 30 October 2024].

Morrisons (2024)a Turriff Manufacturing locations Available at: <https://www.morrisons.jobs/locations/manufacturing-locations/turriff-site> [Accessed 30 October 2024].

Moses Mwato Dr. (2024) Artificial Insemination in Livestock: Advantages, Procedures, and Considerations Available at: <https://www.bivatec.com/blog/artificial-insemination-in-livestock> [Accessed 12 December 2024].

Nahapiet, J. and Ghoshal, S., (1998) Social capital, intellectual capital, and the organizational advantage. *Academy of management review*, 23(2), pp.242-266.

Nature Scot (2023) Arable farming | NatureScot Available at: <https://www.nature.scot/professional-advice/land-and-sea-management/managing-land/farming-and-crofting/types-farming/arable-farming> [Accessed 31 August 2024].

Neethirajan, S. and Kemp, B., (2021) Digital livestock farming. *Sensing and Bio-Sensing Research*, 32, p.100408.

NFUS (2023) Farming Facts Available at: <https://www.nfus.org.uk/farming-facts/what-we-produce.aspx> [Accessed on 01 April 2024].

NFUS (2024) Future Support Briefing Available at: <https://www.nfus.org.uk/userfiles/documents/0624%20Future%20Support%20Briefing.pdf>

NFUS(2024) Shelfwatch Phase 3 Available at: <https://www.nfus.org.uk/userfiles/documents/1024%20Shelfwatch%20Summary%20Report-Final.pdf> [Accessed 31 December 2024].

Nousaine, A.J. and Jolley, G.J., (2013) Defining a critical mass threshold for agricultural support services. Editorial Team, p.41.

Nye, C., Winter, M. and Lobley, M., (2022) The role of the livestock auction mart in promoting help-seeking behavior change among farmers in the UK. *BMC public health*, 22(1), p.1581.

Paré, G., Trudel, M.C., Jaana, M. and Kitsiou, S., (2015) Synthesizing information systems knowledge: A typology of literature reviews. *Information & management*, 52(2), pp.183-199.

Payne-Gifford, S., Whatford, L., Tak, M., Van Winden, S. and Barling, D., (2022) Conceptualising disruptions in British beef and sheep supply chains during the COVID-19 crisis. *Sustainability*, 14(3), p.1201.

Penrose, E.T. (1958) *The theory of the growth of the firm*. New York: Wiley.

Pereira,Roberta C., Christopher, M. and Lago Da Silva, A., (2014) Achieving supply chain resilience: the role of procurement. *Supply Chain Management: an international journal*, 19(5/6), pp.626-642.

Perrin, A. and Martin, G., (2021) Resilience of French organic dairy cattle farms and supply chains to the Covid-19 pandemic. *Agricultural Systems*, 190, p.103082.

- Pettit, T.J., Croxton, K.L. and Fiksel, J., (2013) Ensuring supply chain resilience: development and implementation of an assessment tool. *Journal of business logistics*, 34(1), pp.46-76.
- Pettit, T.J., Fiksel, J. and Croxton, K.L., (2010) Ensuring supply chain resilience: development of a conceptual framework. *Journal of business logistics*, 31(1), pp.1-21.
- Ponis, S.T. and Koronis, E., (2012) Supply Chain Resilience? Definition of concept and its formative elements. *The journal of applied business research*, 28(5), pp.921-935.
- Ponomarov, S. (2012) Antecedents and Consequences of Supply Chain Resilience: A Dynamic Capabilities Perspective” PhD diss., University of Tennessee-USA.
- Ponomarov, S.Y. & Holcomb, M.C., (2009) Understanding the concept of supply chain resilience. *The international journal of logistics management*, 20(1), pp.124-143.
- Priya Datta, P., Christopher, M. and Allen, P., (2007) Agent-based modelling of complex production/distribution systems to improve resilience. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 10(3), pp.187-203.
- Qazi, A.A., Appolloni, A. and Shaikh, A.R., (2024) Does the stakeholder's relationship affect supply chain resilience and organizational performance? Empirical evidence from the supply chain community of Pakistan. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 19(7), pp.1879-1900
- QMS (2024) a QMS | 2030 Beef Sector Strategy Available at: <https://qmscotland.co.uk/external-affairs/2030-beef-sector-strategy> [Accessed on 30 November 2024].
- QMS (2022) Welcome - QMS Beef Sector Strategy 2030 [Accessed 15 August 2022].
- QMS (2023) QMS_Red_Meat_Economics_Report_Landscape Available at: https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/quality-meat-scotland/documents/Publications/QMS_Red_Meat_Economics_Report_Landscape_A4_2023_s10.pdf [Accessed on 25 July 2023].
- QMS (2024) Available at: QMS-RMIP-2024.pdf [Accessed 30th June 2025].
- QMS (2024) c Quality Assurance Standards Available at: <https://qmscotland.co.uk/integrity-assurance/quality-assurance/standards-schemes/processor-standards> [Accessed 01 November 2024].
- QMS (2024) d Cattle and Sheep Standard Available at: <https://qmscotland.co.uk/integrity-assurance/quality-assurance/standards-schemes/cattle-sheep-standards> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

QMS (2024) e Feed Standards Available at: <https://qmScotland.co.uk/integrity-assurance/quality-assurance/standards-schemes/feeds-standards> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

QMS (2024) f Haulage Standards Available at: <https://qmScotland.co.uk/integrity-assurance/quality-assurance/standards-schemes/haulage-standards> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

QMS (2024) g Processor Standards Available at: <https://qmScotland.co.uk/integrity-assurance/quality-assurance/standards-schemes/processor-standards> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

QMS (2024) h Auction Standards Available at: <https://qmScotland.co.uk/integrity-assurance/quality-assurance/standards-schemes/auction-standards> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

QMS (2024) QMS-RMIP-2024.pdf Available at: <https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/quality-meat-scotland/documents/Publications/QMS-RMIP-2024.pdf>

QMS (2025) *Quality assurance, QMS*. Available at: <https://qmScotland.co.uk/integrity-assurance/quality-assurance> [Accessed 21 December 2025].

QMS(2023) QMS-Red-Meat-Industry-Profile-2023 Available at:<https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/quality-meat-scotland/documents/QMS-Red-Meat-Industry-Profile-2023.pdf>

QMS(2024) QMS Red Meat Industry Profile 2024 Available at: <https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/quality-meat-scotland/documents/Publications/QMS-RMIP-2024.pdf>

QMS(2024) The Scotch Difference Available at: <https://qmScotland.co.uk/marketing-development/marketing/the-scotch-difference>

QMS(2024)b The Scotch Difference Available at: <https://qmScotland.co.uk/marketing-development/marketing/the-scotch-difference> [Accessed 01 January 2024].

QMS(2025) The Scottish Red Meat Industry Profile Available at: https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/quality-meat-scotland/documents/QMS0103517_QMS-RMIP_A5-booklet_online_161025-1.pdf [Accessed 07 November 2025].

Reich, J.W., (2006) Three psychological principles of resilience in natural disasters. *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal*, 15(5), pp.793-798.

Rice, J.B. and Caniato, F., (2003) Building a secure and resilient supply network. *SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT REVIEW*, V. 7, NO. 5 (SEPT./OCT. 2003), P. 22-30: ILL.

Rigby, M. and O'Brien-Smith, F., (2010) Trade union interventions in work-life balance. *Work, employment and society*, 24(2), pp.203-220.

- Ringsberg, H., (2014) Perspectives on food traceability: a systematic literature review. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 19(5/6), pp.558-576
- Rupnik, R., Kukar, M., Vračar, P., Košir, D., Pevec, D. and Bosnić, Z., (2019) AgroDSS: A decision support system for agriculture and farming. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 161, pp.260-271.
- Rural Aid Schemes (2024) Farm Management Handbook - Rural Aid 2024. Updated 28 June 2024. Available at: <https://www.ruralpayments.org/publicsite/futures/topics/all-schemes/> [Accessed 22 December 2024].
- Ryan, G.W. and Bernard, H.R., (2003) Techniques to identify themes. *Field methods*, 15(1), pp.85-109.
- S. A. Melnyk, D. J. Closs, S. E. Griffis, C. W. Zobel, and J. R. Macdonald, "Understanding supply chain resilience," *Supply Chain Manage. Rev.*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 34–41, 2014.
- Sá, M.M.D., Miguel, P.L.D.S., Brito, R.P.D. and Pereira, S.C.F., (2020) Supply chain resilience: the whole is not the sum of the parts. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 40(1), pp.92-115.
- SAMW (2024) Stability vital for Scottish cattle numbers - Scottish Association of Meat Wholesalers Scottish Association of Meat Wholesalers [Accessed 22 December 2024].
- SAOS (2024) Scottish Small Producer Access to Abattoirs Report Available at: <https://saos.coop/assets/media/files/Scottish%20Producer%20Access%20to%20Abattoirs%20Final%20Report%20April%202024.pdf> [Accessed 01 November 2024].
- Sarpong, S., (2014) Traceability and supply chain complexity: confronting the issues and concerns. *European Business Review*, 26(3), pp.271-284.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A., (2009) *Research methods for business students*. Pearson education.
- Scholten, K. and Schilder, S., (2015) The role of collaboration in supply chain resilience. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 20(4), pp.471-484.
- Scholten, K., Sharkey Scott, P. and Fynes, B., (2014) Mitigation processes—antecedents for building supply chain resilience. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 19(2), pp.211-228.
- Scholten, K., Stevenson, M. and van Donk, D.P., (2020) Guest editorial—dealing with the unpredictable: supply chain resilience. *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 40(2), pp.1-10.
- Schwägele, F., (2005) Traceability from a European perspective. *Meat science*, 71(1), pp.164-173.

Scotbeef. (2024). About Us. [online]. Available at: <https://scotbeef.com/welcome-to-scotbeef> [Accessed 18 October 2024].

Scotch Beef (2025) *QMS*. Available at: <https://qmscotland.co.uk/marketing-development/our-brands/scotch-beef> [Accessed 21 December 2025].

ScotEID (2023) MyHerdStats goes live Available at: <https://www.scoteid.com/index.php/node/128> [Accessed 31 August 2024].

ScotEID (2025) *ScotEID - making data work for the Scottish livestock industry*. Available at: https://scoteid.com/Public/Documents/scoteid_booklet.pdf [Accessed 21 December 2025].

ScotEID (2025) *Scottish EID livestock traceability research* (no date) *Home*. Available at: <https://www.scoteid.com/index.php/> [Accessed 21 December 2025].

Scottish Association of Meat Wholesalers. (2025). *See the SAMW Associate Members*. [online]. Available at: <https://samw.org.uk/members-new/> [Accessed 27 June 2025].

Scottish Government (2011) Economic Report on Scottish Agriculture 2011 Edition [Accessed 01 January 2023].

Scottish Government (2015). *Economic Report on Scottish Agriculture 2015*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/economic-report-scottish-agriculture-2015/pages/14/> [Accessed 01 January 2023].

Scottish Government (2016) Economic Report on Scottish Agriculture: 2016 Edition Accessed [01 January 2023].

Scottish Government (2016) Economic Report on Scottish Agriculture: 2016 Edition Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/statistics/2016/06/economic-report-scottish-agriculture-2016/documents/00501417-pdf/00501417-pdf/govscot%3Adocument/00501417.pdf> [Accessed 01 January 2023].

Scottish Government (2018) Foot and mouth disease: how to spot and report the disease Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/foot-and-mouth-disease/> [Accessed 01 January 2023].

Scottish Government (2020) Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018 – 2032 Securing a Green Recovery on a Path to Net Zero Available at <https://www.gov.scot/publications/securing-green-recovery-path-net-zero-update-climate-change-plan-20182032/> [Accessed 01 January 2023].

Scottish Government (2022) Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme (Mainland and Islands) full guidance Available at <https://www.ruralpayments.org/topics/all-schemes/scottish-suckler-beef-support-scheme/scottish-suckler-beef-support-scheme-full-guidance/> [Accessed 01 January 2023].

Scottish Government (2024) Agricultural Reform Route Map Available at: <https://www.ruralpayments.org/topics/agricultural-reform-programme/arp-route-map/> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

Scottish Government (2025) Scottish Suckler Beef Support Scheme (Mainland and Islands) full guidance Available at: <https://www.ruralpayments.org/topics/all-schemes/scottish-suckler-beef-support-scheme/scottish-suckler-beef-support-scheme-full-guidance/> [Accessed 03 January 2025].

Scottish Government (2022) New Entrants and Young Farmers Start-Up Grant Schemes: evaluation Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/new-entrants-young-farmers-start-up-grant-schemes-evaluation/pages/3/> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

Scottish Parliament (2024) FSS Vet shortages Available at: <https://www.parliament.scot/-/media/files/committees/health-social-care-and-sport-committee/correspondence/2024/fss-vet-shortages.pdf> [Accessed [01 November 2024].

Scottish Parliament (2024) Subordinate legislation considered by the Rural Affairs and Islands Committee Available at: <https://bprcdn.parliament.scot/published/RAI/2024/12/3/8e5e7ff9-ce83-4000-aa0c-d6ae6c8c8ba8/RAIS062024R13.pdf> [Accessed 28 November 2024].

SEPA (2024) Sector-specific issues | Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA) Available at: <https://www.sepa.org.uk/regulations/land/agriculture/sector-specific-issues/> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

Sheep Central (2024) NZ farmer co-operative proposes closure of Smithfield Available at: <https://www.sheepcentral.com/nz-farmer-co-operative-proposes-closure-of-smithfield-plant/> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

Sheffi, Y. and Rice Jr, J.B., (2005) A supply chain view of the resilient enterprise. MIT Sloan management review.

Shoomal, A., Jahanbakht, M., Componation, P.J. and Ozay, D., (2024) Enhancing supply chain resilience and efficiency through internet of things integration: Challenges and opportunities. *Internet of Things*, 27, p.101324.

Sleigh John (2023) Scotbeef and ABP deal raises concerns about the balance of power Available at: <https://www.thescottishfarmer.co.uk/news/23605170.scotbeef-abp-deal-raises-concerns-balance-power/> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

smaXtec (2024) Health. Available at: <https://smaxtec.com/en/health/> [Accessed 21 December 2024].

Smith, R., (2004) Operational capabilities for the resilient supply chain. *Supply Chain Practice*, 6, pp.24-35.

SRUC (2018) SRUC Strategic Plan 2018 –2023 Available at: https://www.sruc.ac.uk/media/zwmjdjrog/sruc_strategic_plan_2018_2023.pdf [Accessed 01 January 2024].

Statista (2024) The Biggest Exporters of Beef in the World Available at: <https://www.statista.com/chart/19122/biggest-exporters-of-beef/> [Accessed 15 November 2024].

Stewart, S.M., Polkinghorne, R., Pethick, D.W. and Pannier, L.(2024) Carcass assessment and value in the Australian beef and sheepmeat industry. *Animal Frontiers*, 14(2), pp.5-14.

Stoltz, P.G., (2004) Building resilience for uncertain times. *Leader to Leader*, 2004(31), pp.16-20.

Stone, J. and Rahimifard, S., (2018) Resilience in agri-food supply chains: a critical analysis of the literature and synthesis of a novel framework. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 23(3), pp.207-238.

Sutar, P.S., Kolte, G.C. and Yamini, S., (2025) Food supply chain disruptions and its resilience: a framework and review for resilience strategies in the digital era. *Opsearch*, pp.1-35.

Tadayonrad, Y. and Ndiaye, A.B., (2023) A new key performance indicator model for demand forecasting in inventory management considering supply chain reliability and seasonality. *Supply Chain Analytics*, 3, p.100026.

Tadesse, B., Reda, A.A., Kassaw, N.T. and Tadeg, W., (2022) Success rate of artificial insemination, reproductive performance and economic impact of failure of first service insemination: a retrospective study. *BMC Veterinary Research*, 18(1), p.226.

Teece, D.J., (2007) Explicating dynamic capabilities: the nature and microfoundations of (sustainable) enterprise performance. *Strategic management journal*, 28(13), pp.1319-1350.

Teece, D.J., (2016) A dynamic capabilities-based entrepreneurial theory of the multinational enterprise. In *The Eclectic Paradigm: A Framework for Synthesizing and Comparing Theories of International Business from Different Disciplines or Perspectives* (pp. 224-273). London: Palgrave Macmillan UK.

Teece, D.J., Pisano, G. and Shuen, A., (1997) Dynamic capabilities and strategic management. *Strategic management journal*, 18(7), pp.509-533.

Teixeira, A. and Rodrigues, S., (2019) Meat quality, brands and consumer trends. More than beef, pork and chicken—the production, processing, and quality traits of other sources of meat for human diet, pp.21-29.

Tendall, D.M., Joerin, J., Kopainsky, B., Edwards, P., Shreck, A., Le, Q.B., Krütli, P., Grant, M. and Six, J., (2015) Food system resilience: Defining the concept. *Global food security*, 6, pp.17-23.

Tesco (2024) animal-health-welfare-report Available at:

https://www.tescopl.com/media/omukqkrb/animal-health-welfare-report_221024_v2.pdf [Accessed 30 October 2024].

The Guardian (2013) Tesco sales tumble on horsemeat scandal Available at:

<https://www.theguardian.com/business/2013/jun/05/tesco-sales-fall-horsemeat-scandal> [Accessed 01 Nov 2024].

The Independent (2023) One million NHS patients' data compromised after cyberattack on University of Manchester Available at: <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/health/nhs-patient-data-attack-b2364202.html> [Accessed on 20 August 2023].

The Scottish Government (2025) Livestock identification and traceability: Guidance, Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/livestock-identification-and-traceability-guidance/pages/cattle/> [Accessed 21 December 2025].

The Scottish Government (2025) Total income from farming estimates: 2018-2024. Gov.scot. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/total-income-from-farming-estimates-2018-2024/pages/value-of-output-remains-stable/> [Accessed 6 August 2025].

The Times (2024) 'Town battles forestry firms threatening to change the landscape', *The Times*, 15 November. Available at: <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/town-battles-forestry-firms-threatening-to-change-the-landscape-kb5f2cbsr> [Accessed 22 December 2024].

The Times (2024) Which Supermarket tops the league for Scottish farm goods Available at: <https://www.thetimes.com/uk/scotland/article/which-supermarket-tops-the-league-for-scottish-farm-goods-q7xcbhhkb?> [Accessed 30 October 2024].

Tukamuhabwa, B.R., Stevenson, M., Busby, J. and Zorzini, M., (2015) Supply chain resilience: definition, review and theoretical foundations for further study. *International journal of production research*, 53(18), pp.5592-5623.

UK Parliament (2022) Written Evidence submitted by Quality Meat Scotland (FS0075) Available at: <https://committees.parliament.uk/writtenevidence/111969/pdf/> [Accessed 30 November 2024].

Umar, M. and Wilson, M.M., (2024) Inherent and adaptive resilience of logistics operations in food supply chains. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 45(1), p.e12362.

United Auctions (2024) Company Profile. Available at: <https://uagroup.co.uk/about-us> [Accessed 18 October 2024].

Urciuoli, L., Mohanty, S., Hintsa, J. and Gerine Boekesteijn, E., (2014) The resilience of energy supply chains: a multiple case study approach on oil and gas supply chains to Europe. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 19(1), pp.46-63.

USDA (2024) What do beef grades mean? Available at: <https://ask.usda.gov/s/article/What-do-beef-grades-mean> [Accessed 11 August 2024].

Vidic, F., (2022) Knowledge asset as competitive resource. *SocioEconomic Challenges*, 6(4), pp.8-20.

Vien Courtney L. (2016) How groupthink can damage your organisation Available at: <https://www.journalofaccountancy.com/newsletters/2016/oct/groupthink-damage-organization.html> [Accessed 01 November 2024].

Vishwanath, R., (2003) Artificial insemination: the state of the art. *Theriogenology*, 59(2), pp.571-584.

Wallace, C. and Manning, L., (2020) *Food Provenance: Assuring product integrity and identity*. CABI Reviews.

Wallets Marts Castle Douglas Ltd (2024) Livestock Sales. Available at: <https://walletsmarts.co.uk> [Accessed 18 October 2024].

Wang, J., Huo, Y., Guo, X. and Xu, Y., (2022) The pricing strategy of the agricultural product supply chain with farmer cooperatives as the core enterprise. *Agriculture*, 12(5), p.732.

- Wieland, A. and Durach, C.F., (2021) Two perspectives on supply chain resilience. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 42(3), pp.315-322.
- Wieland, A. and Wallenburg, C.M., (2013) The influence of relational competencies on supply chain resilience: a relational view. *International journal of physical distribution & logistics management*, 43(4), pp.300-320.
- Yadav, V.S., Singh, A.R., Gunasekaran, A., Raut, R.D. and Narkhede, B.E., (2022) A systematic literature review of the agro-food supply chain: Challenges, network design, and performance measurement perspectives. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 29, pp.685-704.
- Yang, C.C. and Hsu, W.L., (2018) Evaluating the impact of security management practices on resilience capability in maritime firms—A relational perspective. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 110, pp.220-233.
- Yarosan, E.V., Breen, L., Hou, J. and Sowter, J., (2021) Advancing the understanding of pharmaceutical supply chain resilience using complex adaptive system (CAS) theory. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 26(3), pp.323-340.
- Yim, H. and Dall’erba, S., (2025) Impact of extreme weather events on the US domestic supply chain of food manufacturing. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 122(41), p.e2424715122.
- Yin, R.K. (2018) *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods*, 6th ed., Sage Publications, Los Angeles, CA
- Yin, R.K., (1994) Discovering the future of the case study. *Method in evaluation research*. *Evaluation practice*, 15(3), pp.283-290.
- Yin, R.K., (2003) *Case Study Research Design and Methods* 3rd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA : Sage Publications
- Yu, W., Jacobs, M.A., Chavez, R. and Yang, J., (2019) Dynamism, disruption orientation, and resilience in the supply chain and the impacts on financial performance: A dynamic capabilities perspective. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 218, pp.352-362.
- Yuan, M., Hu, H., Xue, M. and Li, J., (2024) Framework for resilience strategies in agricultural supply chain: assessment in the era of climate change. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 8, p.1444910.

Zhao, G., Liu, S., Wang, Y., Lopez, C., Zubairu, N., Chen, X., Xie, X. and Zhang, J., (2024) Modelling enablers for building agri-food supply chain resilience: insights from a comparative analysis of Argentina and France. *Production planning & control*, 35(3), pp.283-307.

Zhao, G., Mar Vazquez-Noguerol, Liu, S. and Prado, C. (2023) Agri-food supply chain resilience strategies for preparing, responding, recovering, and adapting in relation to unexpected crisis: A cross-country comparative analysis from the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 45(1)

Zhao, G., Olan, F., Liu, S., Hormazabal, J.H., Lopez, C., Zubairu, N., Zhang, J. and Chen, X., (2022) Links between risk source identification and resilience capability building in agri-food supply chains: a comprehensive analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*.

Zhao, G., Vazquez-Noguerol, M., Liu, S. and Prado-Prado, J.C. (2024) Agri-food supply chain resilience strategies for preparing, responding, recovering, and adapting in relation to unexpected crisis: A cross-country comparative analysis from the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 45(1), p.e12361.

Zheng, Z. (2024) *Enhancing supply chain resilience amid rising global risks*. [online]. UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD). Available at: <https://unctad.org/news/enhancing-supply-chain-resilience-amid-rising-global-risks>. [Accessed 15 August 2025].

Zhong, J., Cheng, H. and Jia, F., (2024) Supply chain resilience capability factors in agri-food supply chains. *Operations Management Research*, pp.1-19.

Zurek, M., Ingram, J., Sanderson Bellamy, A., Goold, C., Lyon, C., Alexander, P., Barnes, A., Bebbler, D.P., Breeze, T.D., Bruce, A. and Collins, L.M., (2022) Food system resilience: concepts, issues, and challenges. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 47(1), pp.511-534.